

Bridging Basic Science, Traditional Medicine, and Environmental Studies for Translational Advancements in Drug Discovery

Conference Proceeding:

International Conference on “Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024)”

Organised By:

Department of Dravyaguna,
Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

Title of Conference Proceeding:

Bridging Basic Science, Traditional Medicine, and Environmental Studies for Translational Advancements in Drug Discovery.

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International Conference on “Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024)

Date of the Event:

21.11.2024 to 23.11.2024

Venue:**Prof. K.N. Udupa Auditorium**

Institute of Medical Sciences

Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India.

PIN Code: 221005 Uttar Pradesh, India

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Prof. Anil Kumar Singh, Professor & Head, Department of Dravyaguna, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221005 Uttar Pradesh, India

Organizing Secretary:

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Organized by:

Department of Dravyaguna, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221005 Uttar Pradesh, India

In Association with:

The National Environmental Science Academy, New Delhi

Chitkara University, Patiala, Punjab

Udai Pratap Autonomous College, Varanasi

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Rajmata Vijayaraje Scindia Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Gwalior, India

Bridging Basic Science, Traditional Medicine, and Environmental Studies for Translational Advancements in Drug Discovery

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Banaras Hindu University is an internationally reputed temple of learning, situated in the holy city of Varanasi. This creative and innovative university was founded by the great nationalist leader, Pandit Madan Mohan Malviya, in 1916.

MESSAGES

सत्यमेव जयते

डॉ. (श्रीमती) एन. कलैसेल्वी

सचिव

वैज्ञानिक और औद्योगिक अनुसंधान विभाग, तथा
महानिदेशक

Dr. (Mrs.) N. Kalaiselvi

Secretary

Department of Scientific & Industrial Research, and
Director General

भारत का नवाचार इंजन
The Innovation Engine of India

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वैज्ञानिक तथा औद्योगिक अनुसंधान परिषद्

वैज्ञानिक और औद्योगिक अनुसंधान विभाग

Government of India

Ministry of Science and Technology

Council of Scientific & Industrial Research

Department of Scientific & Industrial Research

Message

It is my great pleasure to extend warm greetings to all participants of the International Conference on "Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024)," being held from 21st to 23rd November 2024 at Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Varanasi.

This conference serves as a vital platform for scientists, researchers, and practitioners from diverse disciplines to converge, exchange knowledge, and explore innovative approaches in the realms of basic science, environmental studies, and traditional medicine. These domains are pivotal for advancing our understanding of disease mechanisms and developing novel therapeutic strategies. The theme of TMT3D-2024 aligns perfectly with India's rich heritage in traditional medicine and the global need for sustainable and scientifically validated drug discovery and development approaches.

The challenges posed by contemporary health issues necessitate a holistic approach, integrating traditional wisdom with modern science. This conference is an opportunity to foster interdisciplinary collaborations, harnessing the potential of natural products, cutting-edge research, and environmental insights for addressing global health challenges.

I commend the organizers for their efforts in bringing together experts from around the world for this significant event, and I believe that the discussions and deliberations at TMT3D-2024 will inspire new directions for research and innovation.

I extend my best wishes for the success of this conference and hope it leads to fruitful outcomes that contribute to the well-being of humanity.

04 November, 2024
New Delhi

(N.Kalaiselvi)

सत्यमेव जयते

डॉ. राजीव बहल, एमडी, पीएचडी
DR. RAJIV BAHL, MD, PhD

icmr
INDIAN COUNCIL OF
MEDICAL RESEARCH

सचिव, भारत सरकार

स्वास्थ्य अनुसंधान विभाग

स्वास्थ्य एवं परिवार कल्याण मंत्रालय एवं

महानिदेशक

भारतीय आयुर्विज्ञान अनुसंधान परिषद

Secretary, Government of India

Department of Health Research

Ministry of Health & Family Welfare &

Director-General

Indian Council of Medical Research

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my best wishes to the Department of Dravyaguna, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi for organizing jointly with the National Environmental Science Academy, New Delhi. The International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024) on 21-23 November, 2024 at the Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi will be a common platform for the scientists, educationalist and students of diverse field for a common objective to develop new drugs for emerging diseases. The TMT3D-2024 serves as a bridge, connecting minds across disciplines and geographical boundaries to pave the way for ground-breaking discoveries and advancements.

In the realm of scientific inquiry and innovation, this conference serves as a pivotal platform for the exchange of ideas, the dissemination of cutting-edge research, and the fostering of collaborative efforts. With a focus on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine, our collective exploration will undoubtedly contribute to the overarching goal of advancing translational drug discovery and development. The Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University is honoured to host this prestigious gathering, along with all associated institutions. The Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) under Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India is also putting its tremendous efforts to create an innovative research environment for potential research in the country. In this milieu, the theme of the International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024) is the need of the hour.

I wish all success to this international conference, the organizing team, and the Department of Dravyaguna, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi in all its future endeavours. I am sure this would be an excellent platform to engage with multiple stakeholders to embark upon the translational drug discovery using traditional knowledge..

(Rajiv Bahl)

केन्द्रीय आयुर्वेदीय विज्ञान अनुसंधान परिषद्
आयुष मंत्रालय, भारत सरकार
CENTRAL COUNCIL FOR RESEARCH IN AYURVEDIC SCIENCES
Ministry of Ayush, Govt. of India

प्रो (वैद्य) रबिनारायण आचार्य
महानिदेशक
Prof. (Vaidya) Rabinarayan Acharya
Director General

MESSAGE

11th November 2024

Dear Delegates, Scholars, and Participants,

It is my great pleasure to extend a warm welcome to each of you attending the International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024), taking place from November 21st to 23rd, 2024, at the prestigious Prof. K.N. Udapa Auditorium, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

In today's swiftly advancing scientific environment, the synergy between traditional knowledge and modern innovations in basic sciences and environmental studies presents unparalleled potential for novel therapeutic discoveries. This conference offers a valuable opportunity for exchanging ideas, presenting groundbreaking research, and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations that are essential for the growth of translational drug discovery. Over these three days, participants will engage with an extensive array of themes, including Plant Science, Environmental Science, Animal and Veterinary Sciences, Chemical and Physical Sciences, Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, Agriculture and Horticulture, Pharmacology and Medicinal Chemistry, Health and Allied Sciences, Traditional Systems of Medicine (AYUSH), Innovation, Engineering and Technology, and other Allied Interdisciplinary fields. The conference is further enriched by the support of nine other esteemed Indian institutions, whose involvement strengthens this vibrant exchange of knowledge.

At CCRAS, our commitment is to harness India's rich medical heritage to benefit human health worldwide. We recognize the importance of collaborative research for validating traditional knowledge and have launched several initiatives to contribute to evidence-based practices. Such efforts aim to enhance the safety, efficacy, and global acceptance of traditional medicine systems. The goals of this prestigious event align beautifully with CCRAS's vision, with the presence of scientists from various prestigious organizations mentioned above. I am delighted by the potential this conference holds to inspire pioneering research, sustainable health solutions, and lasting contributions to scientific knowledge through collaborative efforts. I am confident that the shared vision between CCRAS and TMT3D-2024 will lead to meaningful outcomes in research and foster innovative, sustainable health solutions that advance our collective understanding and impact on global wellness.

My heartfelt best wishes go to the organizers, speakers, and participants for a successful and impactful conference. I look forward to witnessing the valuable insights, collaborations, and innovations that will emerge from TMT3D-2024, driving us all toward a brighter and healthier future.

Warm regards,

(Prof. Vaidya Rabinarayan Acharya)

डॉ. समिर वी. कामत
Dr. Samir V. Kamat

सचिव, रक्षा अनुसंधान तथा विकास विभाग
एवं
अध्यक्ष, डीआरडीओ
Secretary, Department of Defence R&D
&
Chairman, DRDO

MESSAGE

1. I wish for a successful joint event organized by the Department of Dravyaguna, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi and the National Environmental Science Academy in New Delhi. A common platform for scientists, educators and students from various fields will be provided by the International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024), which will take place from November 21-23, 2024, at the Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.
2. The International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024) is focused on the topic of the urgent need in this environment. The conference's shared goal is to develop new drugs for emerging diseases. By uniting brains from different fields and places, the TMT3D-2024 builds a bridge that opens doors for revolutionary discoveries and breakthroughs.
3. I wish the Department of Dravyaguna, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi and the organising team of this international conference success in their future undertakings.

Samat

(Dr. Samir V. Kamat)

परशोत्तम रूपाला
PARSHOTTAM RUPALA

सत्यमेव जयते

मंत्री
मत्स्यपालन, पशुपालन एवं डेयरी
भारत सरकार
Minister
Fisheries, Animal Husbandry and Dairying
Government of India

D.O. No. 167 MIN(FAH&D)/20.24-25

29 FEB 2024

Message

I am delighted to know that the Department of Dravyaguna, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences, BHU, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh is going to organize an International Conference with the National Environmental Science Academy, New Delhi on 21-23 November 2024, at Institute of Medical Sciences, BHU, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh. It is being organized in association with Chitkara University, Patiala, Punjab, Department of Zoology, Udai Pratap Autonomous College, Varanasi, Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies, Nuzvid, Major S.D.Singh Postgraduate Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Farrukhabad, Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences & Technology of Jammu, Cotton University, Guwahati, Assam, and Rajmata Vijayaraje Scindia Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Gwalior.

The International Conference on "Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024)" has a wide range of themes, which include Plant Science, Environment Science, Animal Science, Veterinary Sciences, Chemical and Physical Sciences, Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, Agriculture and Horticulture, Pharmacology and Medicinal Chemistry, Health and Allied Sciences, Traditional System of Medicine (AYUSH), Innovation, Engineering and Technology, Allied Interdisciplinary and Others.

I convey my best wishes to the Organizer and the participants for success of this event.

(Parshottam Rupala)

National Environmental Science Academy

(Registered Under Society Act XXI of 1860)

206, Raj Tower-I, Alaknanda Community Centre, New Delhi-110 019

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10.11.2024

Message

General Secretary, NESA & Convenor's Message

Dear delegates and friends! Warm greetings!!!

On behalf of NESA and the organizing committee, I would like to cordially welcome you to the International Conference on “Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024) on 21-23 November 2024 to be held at Prof. K.N. Udapa Auditorium, Institute of Medical Sciences, BHU, Varanasi, (Uttar Pradesh). The conference aim is to bring together leading academicians, scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and on all aspects of the environment. The TMT3D-2024 conference will showcase recent advancements in fundamental scientific principles, from elucidating the intricacies of biological pathways to understanding the genetic underpinnings of diseases. Delegates will have the opportunity to engage in discussions on the latest breakthroughs in genetics, biochemistry, and other fundamental sciences, with a keen eye on their implications for translational medicine. Environmental Studies are now more critical than ever, given the escalating challenges posed by climate change, pollution, and the depletion of natural resources. Researchers participating in TMT3D-2024 will explore the intricate relationship between the environment and human health. Discussions will span topics ranging from the impact of environmental factors on disease prevalence to the development of sustainable practices that can mitigate the adverse effects of human activity on the planet. Traditional Medicine, with its rich history spanning centuries and diverse cultures, continues to offer unique insights into holistic approaches to health and healing. At TMT3D-2024, experts in traditional medicine will share their knowledge, presenting research on the efficacy of traditional therapies and their integration into modern healthcare practices.

We are trying our best to ensure that your time and stay at the city of Varanasi during the conference be one of the most memorable one and you go back with rich information and memories. I welcome you, your family and friends again to this wonderful gathering and make the maximum out of it. I thank each and every one of you who are contributing to the success of the conference and looking forward to seeing you all soon. m out of it. I thank each and every one of you who are contributing to the success of the conference and looking forward to seeing you all soon.

JAIHIND

Best wishes

(Prof. Shakeel Ahmad Khan)

General Secretary NESA & Convenor TMT3D-2024

Principal Scientist/Scientist 'G'

Division of Environmental Sciences

ICAR-Indian Agricultural Research Institute (A deemed to be University)

NAAC A+ & NIRF # 1 (Agriculture), New Delhi -110012

Please visit our website : www.nesa-india.org

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12.11.2024

Message

Dear Delegates, Esteemed Colleagues, and Honored Guests,

On behalf of the National Environmental Science Academy, it is my pleasure to welcome each of you to the conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024). This gathering reflects our collective commitment to bridging science, environment, and traditional medicine to unlock transformative advancements in healthcare.

In today's rapidly evolving landscape, interdisciplinary research is the need of the hour for addressing complex global health challenges. This conference offers a platform for scholars, researchers, and practitioners to collaborate, share their insights, and explore innovative approaches that integrate basic science, environmental studies, and traditional medicinal knowledge. Such cross-disciplinary dialogues are essential in creating sustainable and effective solutions for drug discovery and development, aligning with our goal to improve human health while respecting the environment.

Throughout the sessions, we will delve into promising advancements that have the potential to revolutionize medical treatments. We will also discuss how our work in environmental science supports the discovery of bioactive compounds, while preserving biodiversity and fostering respect for natural resources. Furthermore, we aim to celebrate traditional knowledge systems that have provided invaluable insights into the natural world and its medicinal potential.

Thank you all for joining us in this important journey of discovery and innovation. May TMT3D-2024 inspire new partnerships, ideas, and solutions that contribute meaningfully to the future of healthcare, environmental sustainability, and scientific progress.

Wishing you all a fruitful and inspiring conference.

Warm regards,

(ALTAF AHMAD)

President

National Environmental Science Academy

Professor

Department of Botany

Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, U.P.

Please visit our website : www.nesa-india.org

International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024) 21-23 November, 2024

Ref. No.: DG/TMT3D/2023-24/01

Dt. 02.11.2024

MESSAGE FROM THE CONVENER

It is my great pleasure to extend warm greetings to all participants of the **International Conference on "Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024)"**, being held from **21st to 23rd November 2024** at the **Prof. K.N. Udupa Auditorium, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Varanasi**.

This conference serves as a vital platform for scientists, researchers, and practitioners from diverse disciplines to converge, exchange knowledge, and explore innovative approaches in the realms of basic science, environmental studies, and traditional medicine. These domains are pivotal for advancing our understanding of disease mechanisms and developing novel therapeutic strategies. The theme of TMT3D-2024 aligns perfectly with **India's rich heritage in traditional medicine** and the **global need for sustainable and scientifically validated drug discovery and development approaches**.

The challenges posed by contemporary health issues necessitate a holistic approach, integrating traditional wisdom with modern science. This conference offers an opportunity to foster interdisciplinary collaborations, harnessing the potential of natural products, cutting-edge research, and environmental insights to address global health challenges.

I commend the organizers for their efforts in bringing together experts from around the world for this significant event, and I believe that the discussions and deliberations at TMT3D-2024 will inspire new directions for research and innovation.

I extend my best wishes for the success of this conference and hope it leads to fruitful outcomes that contribute to the well-being of humanity.

With best regards,

(Prof. Anil Kumar Singh)
Convener, TMT3D-2024
Head, Dept. of Dravyaguna
FoAy, IMS, BHU, Varanasi

In association with:

Conference Secretariat :

Department of Dravyaguna, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221005, India. E-mail: tmt3d2024@gmail.com; Website: <http://tmt3d2024.nesa-india.org/>

International Conference on Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024) 21-23 November, 2024

Ref. No.: DG/TMT3D/2023-24/01

Dt. 02.11.2024

MESSAGE FROM THE ORGANIZING SECRETARY

Dear Esteemed Delegates,

On behalf of the organizing committee, it is my privilege to welcome you all to the International Conference on "Advancements in Basic Science, Environmental Studies, and Traditional Medicine for Translational Drug Discovery and Development (TMT3D-2024)", being held from 21st to 23rd November 2024 at the Prof. K.N. Udupa Auditorium, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Varanasi. This conference represents a unique opportunity to bring together leading experts, eminent scientists, researchers, and young scholars from across the globe to share their knowledge, exchange ideas, and deliberate on advancing research in basic sciences, environmental studies, and traditional medicine. These fields hold immense potential for addressing global health challenges and for fostering innovative approaches to drug discovery and development.

The theme of TMT3D-2024 reflects a commitment to integrating the wisdom of traditional medicine with the rigor of modern scientific research, leveraging the diversity of nature and the richness of traditional knowledge for sustainable and effective healthcare solutions. This event is designed to inspire thought-provoking discussions and collaborations that will drive transformative advancements in these disciplines.

I extend my heartfelt thanks to the distinguished speakers, panelists, and participants for joining us and contributing to the success of this event. My sincere gratitude also goes to the organizing committee, sponsors, and supporters for their unwavering dedication in bringing this conference to fruition.

I wish you an engaging, enlightening, and memorable experience at TMT3D-2024, and I hope that your participation leads to meaningful connections and new research endeavors that benefit humanity.

With warm regards,

Rajesh Kr. Singh

(Dr. Rajesh Kumar Singh)
Convener, TMT3D-2024
Head, Dept. of Dravyaguna
FoAy, IMS, BHU, Varanasi

In association with:

MAJOR SD SINGH
AYURVEDIC MEDICAL COLLEGE
BEWAR ROAD, FATEHGARH, FARRUKHABAD

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Abstract of Invited Speakers

Engineering Tissues *In Vitro*: Focus on Smart and Sustainable Biomaterials and Technologies

Naresh Kasoju

Biomedical Technology Wing, Sree Chitra Tirunal Institute for Medical Sciences and Technology (An Institution of National Importance, Dept. of Science & Technology, Govt. of India) Thiruvananthapuram - 695012, Kerala, India.
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Abstract

Tissue/organ failure due to injury or disease is a critical health challenge faced by many across the globe. The significant gap between the number of donor transplants available and the number of patients waiting for a transplant further worsens the situation. The concept of tissue engineering which aims to construct human tissue alternatives by combining cells, biochemical cues and biomaterials has provided new hope in the field. In this context, our group at SCTIMST Trivandrum has been working on cornea, skin and other epithelial tissue regeneration projects using a variety of biomaterials, scaffolding technologies and stem cells. This lecture would highlight some of the work done on the development of thermoresponsive polymer for epithelial cell sheet engineering, development of alginate – gelatin based 3D bioprinted skin tissue constructs, development of electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds for co-culture applications, and development of silk fibroin based optically clear films for corneal tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: scaffolding, SCTIMST, nanofibrous, organ failure, 3D bioprinted

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Science and Engineering Research Board (GOI), Department of Science and Technology (GOI) and Sree Chitra Tirunal Institute for Medical Sciences and Technology, Trivandrum for funding the work through various schemes.

Microbial antagonists as environment friendly alternative approach in bio-protecting wheat from biotrophic pathogens

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Abstract

Wheat, a vital global cereal crop, is essential for food security, particularly in India, where it ranks as the second most important cereal and contributes over 50% of daily calories. In 2020-21, India's wheat production reached a record 109.52 million tons. However, due to a growing population, the demand for wheat is expected to exceed 140 million tons by 2050. This makes sustainable wheat productivity crucial, especially as biotic stresses like fungal diseases threaten yields. Wheat diseases, including rusts (stripe, leaf, and stem), powdery mildew, Karnal bunt, and Fusarium head blight, significantly reduce crop yield and grain quality, with biotrophic pathogens like rusts and mildew being particularly damaging.

Traditionally, disease control has relied on resistant cultivars and fungicides. However, long-term fungicide use, especially triazoles, risks creating fungicide-resistant pathogens and contributes to environmental pollution. Furthermore, disease resistance in cultivars can be quickly overcome by evolving pathogens, creating a need for sustainable, non-chemical alternatives. Biological control using beneficial soil microbes offers an eco-friendly option for managing wheat diseases. Certain microbes act as biocontrol agents, suppressing pathogens and promoting sustainable agriculture through integrated pest management.

Among potential biocontrol agents are *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Trichoderma*. *Bacillus* spp., for instance, effectively colonizes the rhizosphere, promoting plant growth and lysing fungal mycelia. Its spore-forming capability makes it resilient in field conditions. *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, another effective biocontrol agent, inhibits fungal pathogens through secondary metabolites like antibiotics and hydrogen cyanide, also supporting plant growth and disease suppression. Numerous strains of these bacteria have demonstrated effectiveness in controlling wheat pathogens like *Blumeria graminis* (powdery mildew) and *Puccinia* spp. (rusts) under laboratory, greenhouse, and field conditions.

Overall, biocontrol agents offer a sustainable and stable approach to wheat disease management, aligning with integrated pest management goals for enhanced yield and environmental safety.

Keywords: Wheat productivity, Biotic stresses, Biological control, Biocontrol agents, Integrated pest management.

Growth of Type II Si and Ge Clathrate Thin Films

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Abstract

Group IV elements such as Si, Ge and Sn can form a cage-like open framework crystalline structure with a guest alkali metal (Na, Cs etc.) atoms inside the cages. These structures are known as clathrate material or clathrate compound. The most common clathrate forms are type I and type II. The type-II structure ($Fd\bar{3}m$) is formed by 16 E_{20} (E= Si/Ge) and 8 E_{28} cages, leading to the general formula of $M_{x=24}E_{136}$ (M= Na/Cs) for fully occupied (by guest atoms) clathrate. The guest atoms induce peculiar characteristics in clathrate material. The clathrate with fully occupied cages by guest atoms shows metallic behavior. However, guest-free clathrate ($x\sim 0$) behaves like as a semiconductor with similar or wider direct band gap. In recent years nearly guest free type II clathrates of Si (Si_{136}) and Ge (Ge_{136}) have attracted attention for their applications in solar photovoltaic due to their unique physical properties such as tunable and direct wide band gap. The predicated theoretical band gap of Type II Si_{136} and Ge_{136} clathrates are 1.74 and 0.81 eV respectively. On the other hand, the experimental studies have reported $E_g = 1.9$ eV for Si_{136} and 0.6 eV for Ge_{136} .

Keywords: Clathrate materials, Type-II clathrates, Group IV elements (Si, Ge, Sn), Tunable band gap, Solar photovoltaic applications.

Novel Biomaterials in Tissue Engineering and Drug Delivery

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Abstract

The advancement of technology has helped produce various types of nanomaterials, including metals, nano-metals, ceramics, polymers, and composites. However, the biomedical applications of these nanomaterials require specific properties, such as suitable biomechanical characteristics, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and minimal foreign body response. To meet these requirements, various types of biomaterials have been designed, developed, and produced for tissue repair, regeneration, and replacement. In this work, we synthesized several types of nanomaterials to produce biomaterials using advanced techniques such as electrophoretic deposition (EPD), electrospinning (ES), and 3D bioprinting (3D) for applications in both hard and soft tissue regeneration. Furthermore, these novel biomaterials were capable of delivering drugs and biomolecules for antibacterial and regenerative purposes.

Keywords: Biomaterials, Tissue engineering, Drug delivery, Electrospinning, 3D bioprinting.

Health Hazards of Synthetic Chemical Insecticides, and Use of Green Insecticides as Alternates

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Abstract

Historically, people secured food through two methods namely hunting and agriculture. Today, the majority of the food required by the ever increasing population of the world is supplied by the food industry based on agriculture produce. Agrochemicals are chemicals used in agriculture to improve quality and mainly quantity of food and include synthetic fertilizers, hormones, growth regulators but, in most cases they stand for 'pesticides' or the 'insecticides'. By their very nature, most insecticides create some risk or harm to non-target insects, humans, animals and of course the environment as a whole. The effects of synthetic chemical insecticides can be divided broadly into two categories: Acute effects, which appear immediately or very soon after exposure and include irritation of the nose, throat, and skin causing burning, stinging and itching as well as rashes and blisters. Nausea, dizziness and diarrhoea are also common. People with Asthma could have serious problems to some insecticides, particularly pyrethrin/pyrethroid, organophosphate and carbamates.

Chronic effects, which may manifest themselves many years later and whose origins are often difficult to trace and include cancer and other tumours; brain and nervous system damage; birth defects; infertility and other reproductive problems; and damage to the liver, kidneys, lungs and other body organs. Chronic effects may not appear for weeks, months or even years after exposure, making it difficult to link health impacts to insecticides.

Plants possess secondary metabolites, which can be an effective source of insecticides. Botanicals could be considered as safe to non-target populations, biodegradable and eco-friendly, safe in handling, cost effective and easily available. Therefore, work to screen several plants belonging to different families for their efficacy against the stored insect pest *Callosobruchus chinensis* Linn. was carried out in the Laboratory of Entomology, Post Graduate Department of Zoology, Govt. Dungar College, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India. A number of plants, their various parts in the form of different formulations and concentrations were employed against the above mentioned insect pest. And from the results obtained, it could be concluded and suggested that searching for bio-rational insecticides by screening naturally occurring compounds in plants-the 'Green insecticides' could be one alternate for sustainability of environment as well as safe guarding the insects.

Keywords: - Green insecticides, pesticides, insecticides, *Callosobruchus chinensis*, Agrochemicals

Reconciling Bioprospection and Conservation Research for the Sustainability of Himalayan Medicinal Plants and Quality Herbal Products Development

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Abstract

The Indian Himalayan Region is well recognized for its plethora of biodiversity, particularly for wide array of medicinal plants. In the IHR around 171 ethnic groups (30 % of the total ethnic group of India) inhabit in remote areas, and they are highly reliant on the medicinal plants for primary health care needs. Owing to the close association with nature, the tribal and local communities of the IHR have developed the traditional knowledge system that incorporates the use of locally available plants and its products for the treatments of several ailments and diseases. But with the impact of urbanization, industrialization, migration from rural to urban areas, rapid loss of natural habitats and changes in life style, the wealth of knowledge on ethnomedicinal plants from many cultures are gradually diminishing. Realizing the dire need of integration of ethnomedicinal plant based traditional medicine into health sector, field based exploration, documentation, bioprospection, and conservation of medicinal plants are highly required. My research group is extensively working on the above research line i.e. exploration, bioprospection and conservation of high altitude medicinal plants of Himalaya. We have identified some unexplored plants from the Himalayan region which can be used for anticancer and antimicrobial molecule production. We have also developed in-vitro techniques for large scale propagation and conservation of threatened medicinal plants, so that, medicinal plants can be sustainably used for quality herbal product development.

Keywords: Bioprospection, Himalaya, Medicinal Plants, Propagation.

Aquatic Angiosperms Growing in Jharkhand Their Utility and Control

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Abstract

Aquatic plants are those species which normally grow in water and grow for at least a part of their life cycle in water. It may also be defined as water as their seed germinate in either the water phase or the substrate of a body of water or which must spend a part of their life cycle in water.

The intensive floristic survey of aquatic and semi-aquatic taxa of Jharkhand during 2014 to 2019 have revealed 272 species, belonging to 157 genera, distributed over 67 families of angiosperms. Out of 272 aquatic taxa 137 are monocotyledons belonging to 80 genera and 23 families whereas 135 taxa are dicotyledons belonging to 77 genera and 44 families. These plants are very much productive than the other crops as because these plants do not require any care, tillage and irrigation. These plants are used as medicinal herb, making compost, human and fish food, fodder, fiber industry, aquarium industries and phytoremediation. Besides these the rapid growth of these plants in the water bodies turned the plants as weed which causes harm to the water bodies as well as the native biodiversity of the plant. Hence there is a need to control these plants in a proper way. In the present communication the details of the aquatic plant species growing in Jharkhand along with the uses and harm of aquatic plants has also been dealt in detail. Control measures of these plants through their utilization are also discussed.

Keywords: Aquatic angiosperms, Weed, Jharkhand, Control, Utilisation.

Integrative Medicine for Military and Civil Applications: Transforming the Narrative

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Abstract

Integrative medicine (IM) is increasingly recognized within military and civilian healthcare systems to enhance patient care through a combination of conventional and complementary therapies. This approach is particularly relevant for addressing complex health issues faced by military personnel, such as chronic pain, traumatic brain injury (TBI), and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Various IM services are offered by scientists and medical practitioners in a calibrated way to deal with such problems. In IM, the concept of holistic "one health" is emphasized, with attention to mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being in addition to physical problems. This is especially helpful for military personnel who face the onslaught of complex health problems brought on by conflict or other occupational stressors. IM complies with patient desires to manage chronic diseases, not just by using pharmaceuticals, but also by incorporating non-drug therapies into treatment modalities. Notwithstanding the many advantages of IM integration in military healthcare, obstacles still need to be overcome. For integrative modalities to be widely accepted and used, perspectives regarding the trustworthiness of IM within the military community must transform. Integrative medicine has great potential to change healthcare delivery in the future, both in military and civilian settings. There is a unique opportunity to develop more robust healthcare frameworks that tackle complicated health issues comprehensively by combining the advantages of both traditional and modern systems. Integrative medicine may become the mainstay of contemporary medical practice in a variety of contexts as research advances and legislative frameworks change. This lecture will trace some steps in this transformative process.

Keywords: Integrative medicine; Complementary therapy; Non-drug therapy; Complex health issues

Breathing Easier: Ethnopharmacology of Himalayan Medicinal Plants against Bronchial hyperreactivity, Congestive and Inflammatory states of Asthma

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Abstract

Himalayan state carries a rich repository of medicinal plants meeting unmet medical needs. *Onosoma bracteatum*, *Hedychium spicatum*, *Pistacia integremma*, *Verbascum thapsus* and *Brugmansia sauveolens* are native to Western Himalayas region including Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand and J&K. Ethnopharmacological evidences recommend traditional uses to get relief against cough, allergy, breathing difficulty, asthma, bronchitis and lung infection. The study aimed to evaluate anti-asthmatic activity of bioactive fraction of selected Himalayan plants using *in-vitro*, *in-vivo*, *ex-vivo*, and *in-silico* methods. The plant part was procured, authenticated and subjected for extraction/fractionation using organic solvents. *In-vitro* antioxidant (H₂O₂, DPPH, and ABTS) and anti-inflammatory assays were performed. An acute toxicity study as per OECD guidelines was done. Cough centre suppressant activity using citric acid model and anti-asthmatic activity using antigen-induced asthma using ovalbumin in Male Guinea pigs were performed. *Ex-vivo* bronchial dilation was performed using tracheal-chain preparation. Phytochemical evaluation of prepared fraction using LC-HRMS, TLC/HPTLC, GC-MS was done. Preliminary phytochemical screening exhibited the presence of phenolics, alkaloids, flavonoids, and glycosides phytochemical constants. Prepared extracts showed a significant increase in latency time and a decrease in cough frequency against citric acid, as compared to the disease group. In the antigen-induced asthma model, plant extracts produced a reversal of ovalbumin-induced hyperreactivity, congestion, and inflammation at 100 and 200 mg/kg in Guinea pigs with marked decrease in total lymphocyte count, TNF-alpha, IL-6 cytokine, oxidative markers, tissue inflammation of mononuclear cells and eosinophils compared with non-treated guinea pigs. GC-MS, TLC/HPTLC and LC-HRMS analysis revealed the presence of potent phytochemical showing a significant binding energy towards 5-LOX, IL-6, and iNOX protein targets under *in-silico* study. The findings from present project revealed that the ethnopharmacology of Himalayan medicinal plants pin points justified use to treat asthma with a view to develop an effective and safe medicines satisfying the pathology of asthma.

Keywords: Asthma, Himalaya, *in-vivo*, *in-vitro*, inflammation.

QSPR Modelling of Molnupiravir Using Several Other Antiviral Drugs for the Treatment of COVID-19 Patients

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Abstract

The global pandemic caused by the novel virus SARS-CoV-2 (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome CoronaVirus 2), also known as COVID-19, is now a serious public health concern that has affected people worldwide. The condition has become worse due to a lack of adequate treatment. To combat the pandemic, several drugs are being investigated. A topological index (or molecular descriptor) is a numerical parameter that correlates the molecular structure of a chemical compound to its various physico-chemical properties and plays a significant role in the development of QSPR/QSAR (quantitative structure-property relationship/quantitative structure-activity relationship) models. In this study, we evaluate the degree-based topological indices (namely, the Nirmala index, first and second inverse Nirmala indices, geometric-quadratic and quadratic-geometric indices) of nine antiviral drugs (namely, Molnupiravir, Remdesivir, Chloroquine, Ritonavir, Theaflavin, Arbidol, Hydroxychloroquine, Thalidomide and Lopinavir) used in the remedy of COVID-19 patients, with the help of their respective M-polynomials. Also, we calculate the neighborhood degree sum-based indices of Molnupiravir by using its neighborhood M-polynomial (that is, NMpolynomial). In addition, we execute the correlation analysis among the topological indices and physico-chemical properties of these antiviral drugs. Furthermore, we demonstrate the QSPR models for strong correlation through the linear, quadratic and cubic regression analysis to appraise the effectiveness of the topological indices. And, the squared correlation coefficients obtained from the performed curvilinear regression models are compared with those acquired in the previous studies. The obtained topological indices and established QSPR models may help predict the pharmacokinetic properties of these antiviral drugs and in the discovery of new drugs related to the medication for the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: - Hydroxychloroquine, M-polynomial, COVID-19, QSPR/QSAR

Translatability of In-Vivo Animal Models For Clinical Drug Development and Novel Strategies to Enhance Their Applicability in Translational Research Based on Traditional Leads

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Abstract

In vivo animal models play a pivotal role in preclinical drug development, but their translatability to human system remains a significant challenge. The complexity of human diseases and interspecies differences often limit the predictive power of these models, leading to high attrition rates in clinical trials. The focus is to discuss the current limitations and potential strategies to improve the predictive power of traditional lead-based in vivo models and to enhance the translatability of vivo animal models for clinical drug development. The Critical evaluation of existing animal models and their limitations is highly relevant to develop novel strategies for enhancing their applicability in translational Research based on Traditional Leads. Inadequate model relevance for complex human diseases, interspecies differences in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics as well as the variability in model design and data interpretation persist as major challenges in this field. Strategies for enhancement of applicability of animal models include exploring novel approaches for improving model relevance, including humanized models and precision medicine approaches. The scope of incorporating advanced imaging and monitoring techniques for enhanced data accuracy and integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning for predictive modeling can be recommended. Incorporating human-relevant biomarkers and clinical endpoints for in-vivo animal models can improve their translatability. By addressing all these challenges and implementing innovative solutions, we can improve the translatability of in vivo animal models, accelerating the development of effective treatments and enhancing the success rate of clinical trials that will lead to accelerated drug development timelines and better patient outcomes.

Keywords: Translational research, in vivo animal models, clinical drug development, preclinical research, precision medicine, biomarkers.

Sirtuin-2 Mediates Neuro-Immune Interaction in COPD Regulating Airway Inflammation and Remodeling

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Abstract

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a progressive respiratory disorder characterized by persistent airway inflammation, tissue remodeling, and systemic effects that extend beyond the lungs, affecting neuro-immune interactions. Sirtuin-2 (SIRT2), a member of the sirtuin family of NAD⁺-dependent deacetylases, has emerged as a key regulator of inflammatory responses and cellular homeostasis in various disease contexts. Recent studies suggest that SIRT2 plays a significant role in modulating neuro-immune interactions contributing to several pathophysiology. However, its specific influence on airway inflammation and structural remodeling in COPD remains underexplored. Hence, the present study aims to elucidate role of SIRT-2 in modulating fibrosis and neurogenic inflammation in cigarette smoke (CS) induced experimental mice model of COPD. The study evaluated lung injury and airway inflammation marked by increased Cortisol, ACTH, COX-2, LDH and cellular recruitment in COPD group and their attenuation by SIRT-2 inhibition. Additionally, CS exposure exhibited neurogenic inflammation represented by activated TPRV1 and TRPM8, elevated neuromediators levels (dopamine, acetylcholine, substanceP, serotonin) and their respective receptors which were mitigated by AK-7. However, targeting fibrotic cascade, enhanced MMP-9, total collagen, hydroxyproline and upregulation of α -smooth muscle actin, MUC5AC, TGF- β , PKA, GATA-3, FOXO3, and STAT-6 were observed in CS exposed group thereby enhancing fibrosis. SIRT-2 inhibition effectively reversed all these factors suppressing fibrosis further supported by downregulated SIRT-2 expression. Histopathological studies also supported findings where collagen deposition and mucus production were also attenuated by AK-7. These results suggest that SIRT2 plays a crucial role in COPD by mediating neuro-immune interactions that exceeds airway inflammation and remodeling. Targeting SIRT2 could therefore represent a promising therapeutic approach to modulate neuro-immune responses, potentially slowing COPD progression and alleviating systemic impacts associated with chronic lung inflammation. Future research should further explore SIRT2 as a target for therapeutic intervention to address both pulmonary and extrapulmonary complications of COPD.

Keywords: Airway inflammation, Sirtuin, COPD, AK-7.

Mitochondrial Complex I (MCI) controls NMJ function and plasticity through distinct pre- and post-synaptic mechanisms.

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Abstract

Neurons require high amounts energy, and mitochondria help to fulfill this requirement. Dysfunctional mitochondria trigger problems in various neuronal tasks. Using the *Drosophila* neuromuscular junction (NMJ) as a model synapse, we previously reported that Mitochondrial Complex I (MCI) subunits were required for maintaining NMJ function and growth. Here we report tissue-specific adaptations at the NMJ when MCI is depleted. In *Drosophila* motor neurons, MCI depletion causes profound cytological defects and increased mitochondrial reactive oxygen species (ROS). But instead of diminishing synapse function, neuronal ROS triggers a homeostatic signaling process that maintains normal NMJ excitation. We identify molecules mediating this compensatory response. MCI depletion in muscles also enhances local ROS. But high levels of muscle ROS cause destructive responses: synapse degeneration, mitochondrial fragmentation, and impaired neurotransmission. In humans, mutations affecting MCI subunits cause severe neurological and neuromuscular diseases. The tissue-level effects that we describe in the *Drosophila* system are potentially relevant to forms of mitochondrial pathogenesis.

Keywords: ROS, NMJ, *Drosophila*, MCI, Dysfunctional, impaired neurotransmission

***Tinospora cordifolia* Silver Nanoparticles Attenuated the Lipopolysaccharide-Induced Testicular Inflammation in Golden Hamster**

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Abstract

Medicinal plants are increasingly used to treat diseases, with inflammation being a common cause of male infertility. Testicular inflammation is one of the primary causes of male infertility. Plant-rich remedies are known to reduce testicular inflammation, but the exact mechanism is not known. *Tinospora cordifolia* (*T. cordifolia*), an Indian ayurvedic medicinal plant, possesses excellent immunomodulatory properties. We, therefore, studied the anti-inflammatory potential(s) of green synthesized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) from *T. cordifolia* (TC-AgNPs) on the testes of golden hamsters. Aqueous extract of *T. cordifolia* was used to synthesize the silver nanoparticles (TC-AgNPs), validated by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography-high-resolution accurate mass spectrometry (UHPLC-HRMS). Physical characterization was done using UV–Vis spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and Fourier transform infrared analysis (FTIR) spectroscopy. Biological parameters were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), western blot analysis, histopathology, photoacoustic, and ultrasound imaging. The UV–Vis surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band at 420 nm confirmed the formation of TC-AgNPs. TEM revealed the semi-spherical morphology of silver nanoparticles with an average diameter of 15 nm. Biological studies with lipopolysaccharide (LPS) challenged male golden hamsters and demonstrated that TC-AgNPs treatment reduced the serum pro-inflammatory cytokine levels (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF α). The testicular photoacoustic and ultrasound imaging significantly improved testicular volume and oxygenation level. Western blot analysis suggests that TC-AgNPs reduced inflammation by downregulating NF- κ B protein expression. Furthermore, TC-AgNPs alleviated LPS-induced testicular damages along with an increase in serum testosterone level. The synthesized TC-AgNPs have shown strong anti-inflammatory effects against LPS-induced testicular inflammation in male golden hamsters.

Keywords: ELISA, NF- κ B, UHPLC-HRMS, *T. cordifolia*, immunomodulatory, SPR

Genetically encoded FRET-based nanosensors for real-time monitoring of metabolites in living cells

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Abstract

Nanobiotechnology is the most revolutionizing area of research that deals with matters of nanoscale dimensions. There are several ongoing and future advancements in nanobiotechnology and nanoscale science with reference to its application in medicine, food, electronics, agriculture, etc. One of the major breakthroughs in this discipline of science was brought about by the development of biosensors or nanobiosensors. The explicit idea of using DNA as nanomaterials to create useful tools for understanding the biological processes is remarkable. The genetically encodable nanobiosensors based on Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) are among the many tools offered by the progressive investigation in nanobiotechnology. Most of these sensors are widely used and are emerging to be invaluable for uncovering the complex biological roles of metabolites in their native environment, reflecting a new perspective on the understanding of systemic biology. These sensors are best suited for their wide application due to the properties like high-specificity, high-sensitivity, non-invasive and non-destructive fluorescence efficacy, and the potentiality of genetic encoding and real-time imaging. Some of the FRET-based genetically encoded nanosensors developed so far are described in this lecture.

Keywords: FRET, nanobiosensors, non-invasive, non-destructive, nanobiotechnology

Molecular Mechanisms of Second Messenger Signaling in Bacteria and Its Implication in Developing Next-Generation Antibiotics

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Abstract

Bacterial pathogens remain a formidable threat to global health and economies. The post-COVID-19 era has accentuated concerns about antimicrobial resistance (AMR), underscoring the pressing need for innovative strategies to combat illnesses caused by bacteria. To effectively confront these challenges, we must gain molecular insights into how bacteria navigate and adapt, particularly in stressful situations like antibiotic exposure and nutrient starvation. Bacteria employ various strategies to respond to environmental changes, most notably by deploying second messengers such as c-di-GMP, (p)ppGpp (alarmone) and c-di-AMP. These second messengers are master modulators of survival pathways across bacterial species, including biofilm formation, stress response, persistence, microbial memory, quorum sensing, and virulence factors. While we recognize the critical importance of second messengers in all aspects of bacterial success and survival, the precise molecular mechanisms underlying their actions remain puzzling. This mystery stems from our inadequate knowledge of the specific targets of the second messengers. In my talk, I will discuss a novel approach that combines capture compounds with mass spectrometry (CCMS) and TPP to discover novel targets of second messengers. I will present data showing structural elucidation, functional characterization and mechanistic insights into how second messengers modulate the functions of these novel targets (CckA, ShkA and SmbA) at atomic resolution. This includes detailed mechanistic insights into how second messengers intervene in signal transduction pathways, effectively rewiring biological processes to favor bacterial growth, survival and adaptation. I will also talk about the physiological and mechanistic implications of cross-talk between second messenger regulatory networks in bacterial growth optimization during the stress of nutrient starvation.

Over time the horizon of my research has widened to encompass translational applications of these fundamental insights. My current and future work aims to identify new therapeutic targets of survival pathways controlled by second messenger and uncover their molecular mechanism that can disrupt those pathways responsible for stress response, antibiotic resistance, persister formation, quorum sensing and biofilm development with high specificity. In my seminar, I will discuss the future perspective of this innovative approach to precisely target pathogenic bacteria while preserving our gut's beneficial microbial communities (microbiome). Crucially, the selectivity of this approach is distinct from the effect of conventional antibiotics, which often disrupt essential pathways indiscriminately. I am confident that this research plan will ultimately pave the way for developing next-generation antibiotics (NGAs) or novel synergistic therapeutic combinations and early diagnosis of chronic infections. These advancements would undoubtedly represent significant milestones in our ongoing battle against antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

Keywords: AMR, CCMS, novel targets, biofilm, c-di-GMP, bacterial growth

Beneficial Effects of Snake venom PLA2 inhibitors from medicinal Plants

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Abstract

Snake envenomation is a severe public health problem that affects tens of thousands of people worldwide, particularly in rural areas of tropical and sub-tropical Asian countries. The cobra, common krait, Russell's viper, and saw-scaled viper are some of India's most dangerous and medically significant species, and they can be found all over the world. With members found in Africa, Europe, Asia, and the Americas, the Viperidae family is the largest of the poisonous snake families. Phospholipase A2 (PLA2), a pharmacologically active enzyme isolated from *Daboia russelii*, causes neurotoxicity, myotoxicity, cardiotoxicity, anticoagulant, hemolytic, and platelet effects. Secretory phospholipases A2, which are significant toxins found in snake venom and are structurally similar to those seen in inflammatory diseases in mammals, such as arthritis and atherosclerosis, can be useful tools for finding novel anti-phospholipase A2 medicines. In the present study 3',5,7-trihydroxy-4'-methoxy flavone-7-rutinoside (Diosmin) from *Oxalis Corniculata*, which was identified using LC-MS/MS, FT-IR, UV-spectrophotometer, and NMR and XRD analysis.

PLA2's were purified from *Daboia russelii* snake venom using a variety of chromatographic purification processes (Sephadex G-75, CM-Sephadex C-25, Sephadex G-50. Compound ability to ability to inhibit biochemical properties of PLA2s, and it was also shown inhibit homolytic activity, phospholipase A2 activity, and procoagulant activity considerably, a circular dichroism investigation revealed a considerable change in secondary structure of PLA2s. compound also found to inhibit cardiotoxicity supported by LDH level. Furthermore, it is also promoting survival time, reduced neuro toxic symptoms, from the histopathological studies it is revealed that considerable reduction in lung haemorrhage and myotoxicity supported by CPK level.

Keywords: LDH, *Daboia russelii*, histopathological, Viperidae, myotoxicity

Engineering Tissues *In Vitro*: Focus on Smart and Sustainable Biomaterials and Technologies

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Abstract

Tissue/organ failure due to injury or disease is a critical health challenge faced by many across the globe. The significant gap between the number of donor transplants available and the number of patients waiting for a transplant further worsens the situation. The concept of tissue engineering which aims to construct human tissue alternatives by combining cells, biochemical cues and biomaterials has provided new hope in the field. In this context, our group at SCTIMST Trivandrum has been working on cornea, skin and other epithelial tissue regeneration projects using a variety of biomaterials, scaffolding technologies and stem cells. This lecture would highlight some of the work done on the development of thermoresponsive polymer for epithelial cell sheet engineering, development of alginate – gelatin based 3D bioprinted skin tissue constructs, development of electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds for co-culture applications, and development of silk fibroin based optically clear films for corneal tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: scaffolding, SCTIMST, nanofibrous, organ failure, 3D bioprinted

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Advancements in Basic Science for Harmonizing Agriculture with Environmental Sustainability: Innovative Biopesticides as a Localized Solution for Global Agricultural Challenges

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Abstract

Advancements in basic science have become essential in addressing the growing environmental concerns associated with conventional agricultural practices, particularly the excessive use of chemical pesticides. This study focuses on developing an innovative biopesticide using *Cassia tora* leaf extract and cow urine, aiming to harmonize agriculture with environmental sustainability. *Cassia tora*, an invasive species in the Saurashtra region of Gujarat, was explored for its potential to be repurposed as a natural pesticide and growth promoter for *Glycine max* (soybean), a major crop in the region. The research sought to create a cost-effective, eco-friendly alternative to synthetic agrochemicals, suitable for local farmers and scalable for broader agricultural applications.

Field experiments, with various treatments combining different concentrations of *Cassia tora* leaf extract, cow urine, and water. Growth parameters such as plant height, branch number, leaf length, pod number, seed size, and overall yield were measured across 10 treatment plots. The T2 treatment, consisting of 15% *Cassia tora* leaf extract, 25% cow urine, and 60% water, demonstrated the highest efficacy, significantly enhancing plant growth, increasing the number of pods, and improving seed size and weight compared to the control (T0) and other treatments. This treatment resulted in a marked improvement in crop health and productivity, underscoring the potential of this biopesticide to replace harmful chemical inputs. The findings reveal that such advancements in basic science can offer practical, sustainable solutions for global agricultural challenges. The localized biopesticide not only reduces dependency on synthetic chemicals but also promotes environmentally responsible farming practices. Furthermore, the study highlights the dual benefits of utilizing an invasive species to create a natural biocontrol agent, thus supporting biodiversity conservation while improving agricultural productivity. This research contributes to a broader understanding of how basic scientific advancements can drive innovative, sustainable agricultural technologies that align with global efforts to mitigate environmental impact.

Keywords: global efforts, *Cassia tora*, *Glycine max*, biopesticide, harmonize

Internationalization of Traditional Indian medicine: Strengthening patent regime, Strategies and Modulation of policy

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Abstract

Traditional Indian medicine (TIM) is currently most influential traditional medical system with the largest number of users worldwide. In recent years, the trend of TIM adoption has increased greatly, but the process of TIM internationalization has suffered from a series of setbacks. Both the Indian government and Indian medicine enterprises are making efforts to promote TIM as it moves into the overseas market. However, several issues associated with TIM, such as its complex composition, various effects of its actions, insufficient systematic studies during its internationalization, etc., hinder the adoption of specific TIM drugs in the internationally recognized pharmaceutical market. To overcome these challenges, current studies depicts strategies to achieve a breakthrough for the obstacles inhibiting the globalization of Traditional Medicine(TM) in India, by modulating legal regulatory networks (Pharmacovigilance), patent policies and standard systematically. Developed countries have implemented trade protectionism such as technical standard barriers, technical regulation barriers, patent technology barriers, green barriers, etc., which makes Ayurveda and herbal products fail to enter in that market or are forced to withdraw from the target market due to shortcomings in technology. My work on framework for comparative strategies on legal regulations (with reference of China, EU and USA) and innovation on international market for TM, will propose solutions that can help facilitate the internationalization of TM of India and strengthening the patent regime for the future.

Keywords: TIM, Pharmacovigilance, internationalization, herbal products, pharmaceutical

Abstract for Oral Presentation

Assessment of children's Developmental Effect on the Mind

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Abstract

Child development refers to the continuous but predictably sequential biological, psychological and emotional changes that occur in human beings between birth and the end of adolescence. Developmental surveillance should be incorporated into every child visit. Parents play an important role in the child's developmental assessment. The primary care physician should educate and encourage parents to use the developmental checklist in the health booklet to monitor their child's development. Further evaluation is necessary when developmental delay is identified. This article aimed to highlight the normal child developmental assessment as well as to provide suggestions for screening tools and questions to be used within the primary care setting. Child development refers to the continuous but predictably sequential biological, psychological and emotional changes that occur in human beings between birth and the end of adolescence. The sequence of development is the same for all children and can be described in terms of developmental milestones. As children develop at different rates, which are determined by a complex interplay of environmental and genetic factors, the age of attainment for each milestone ranges widely. It is essential to not only be aware of the median age of attainment of the milestone (the age at which half of the standard population achieves the milestone) but the limit age as well (the upper age limit at which the particular milestone should have been achieved). This would help to guide the clinician on whether to reassure the parent/caregiver, monitor the child's development closely or refer the child to a specialist for a detailed assessment and further management. It is also essential for the clinician to assess the quality of the skill rather than taking note of the age at which the milestone was achieved. For example, a child may have acquired sufficient language skills to allow him to speak in phrases, but may be unskilled in using language for conversational purposes. The basic architecture of the brain is constructed by an ongoing process that begins before birth and continues into adulthood. Maximum brain development occurs within the first three years of a child's life and is hence called the early developmental phase. It is therefore essential to recommend that parents engage in appropriate stimulation activities with their children, starting from the newborn period.

Keywords: Child developmental, developmental screening tools, primary care, surveillance

Health and traditional system of medicines Indigenous Plants that heal Cancer

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Abstract

Health care, which was a part of the traditional culture of the people, has become a profession in the modern industrial world. Medicinal indigenous plants are the greatest assets of an our environment, have found their utilization in human life and healthcare system since prehistoric times of mankind and have still maintained their importance in modern times by virtue of maintaining their basic therapeutic, curative and other various types of roles. In this research article especially some medicinal plants form the source for large varieties of herbal drugs are used for Cancer treatment in local people. Integrating these natural remedies into our lifestyle can bring numerous health benefits. Medicinal plants contain their curative value to naturally occurring biologically active ingredients in them, i.e. the primary and secondary metabolites which obtained either in pure or combined form with other molecules form a pivotal source of drug lead compounds for Cancer treatment. Such plants includes *Carica papaya*, seeds of Papaya are used to be an antidote for Cancer, *Mimosa pudica*, commonly called Chui-Mui, the whole plant juice makes a good lotion to be applied over Cancerous ulcers, *Allium sativum*, commonly called Garlic, it's bulbs act as a natural antibiotic and prevents Cancer, *Vitis vinifera*, commonly called Grape, it's fruits are used to cure Cancer, *Ficus glomerata* commonly called Cluster Fig, the latex, in combination with Sesamum (Til) oil helps to check Cancer and *Asclepias curassavica* commonly called Tropical milk weed (wild Ipecacuanha), the juice of the plant leaves used for checking growth of the Cancerous cell. Due to presence of various types of active chemical ingredients in the above plant parts make them cancer growth blockers.

Keywords: Cancer, Health care, Indigenous, Medicinal plants, Metabolites (Til)

Driving Climate Solutions: The Role of CSIR-NEIST, Jorhat, Assam in India's Fight against Climate Change

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Abstract

Climate change, predominantly instigated by human activities, is anticipated to raise global temperatures by approximately 2°C between the years 2040 and 2050, thereby exacerbating climate-related challenges on a worldwide scale. The principal repercussions encompass land degradation resulting from escalating sea levels, an increased incidence of natural disasters, agricultural susceptibility, and disturbances to ecosystems. The rise in temperatures is projected to displace populations residing in coastal areas and incur substantial economic costs, while the frequent occurrence of extreme weather events, such as hurricanes and floods, will place considerable strain on disaster management systems. The agricultural sector is confronted with significant threats, as alterations in temperature, deterioration of soil quality, and recurring droughts are likely to diminish crop yields and disrupt food security. Furthermore, the shifts in ecosystems prompted by warming and variations in precipitation jeopardize biodiversity, thereby destabilizing natural habitats and the adaptive capacity of various species.

As the ramifications of climate change become more pronounced, global efforts towards adaptation are gaining significant traction, with societies enhancing their climate resilience, fostering environmental cognizance, and formulating decarbonization strategies. Nations are fortifying their infrastructure and emergency response frameworks, complemented by intensified public awareness campaigns that advocate for sustainable practices. Moreover, both governmental entities and industries are hastening their transitions towards low-carbon alternatives, increasing their dependence on renewable energy sources, and implementing policies aimed at reducing emissions.

In the agricultural domain, although certain regions may experience short-term increases in productivity owing to elevated levels of CO₂ and warmer climatic conditions, the overarching impact remains largely detrimental. Potential advantages, such as prolonged growing seasons and CO₂-induced fertilization, are likely to be counterbalanced by declines in crop quality, soil erosion, and a rise in agricultural calamities. The escalation of temperatures, alongside more frequent occurrences of droughts, floods, and pest infestations, will adversely affect crop productivity, compromise soil health, and lead to the degradation of forest ecosystems, ultimately resulting in a series of cascading ecological consequences.

Climate change also exerts an influence on air and water quality, with the situation being aggravated by pollutants such as carbonaceous aerosols, which affect regional climatic conditions and levels of air pollution. India's National Carbonaceous Aerosol Program (NCAP), established

under the auspices of the Ministry of Environment, Forests, and Climate Change in 2017, represents a pivotal initiative aimed at addressing these pollutants. This program is designed to evaluate aerosol emissions, particularly those originating from coal-based industries in Northeast India, along with their climatic implications. Research conducted under the NCAP indicates that aerosols play a significant role in shaping India's seasonal rainfall patterns, thereby affecting agriculture, water management, and preparedness for disasters by amplifying rainfall in regions such as North India.

CSIR-North East Institute of Science and Technology (NEIST), Jorhat, Assam holds a significant position within India's National Carbonaceous Aerosol Program (NCAP), investigating carbonaceous aerosols, including black carbon and organic carbon, which influence both climate and air quality. NEIST's activities include the sampling of aerosols, source apportionment to differentiate between natural and anthropogenic emissions, and climate modelling to evaluate the effects of aerosols on regional climatic conditions. It assesses the implications for health, agriculture, and ecosystems, and collaborates with international initiatives to standardize data, thereby informing strategies for climate adaptation. NEIST's research bolsters India's climate policy framework and aligns with global climate mitigation endeavours. Additionally, they are at the forefront of research aimed at converting pollutants into high-value products, such as nanodiamonds, for advanced biomedical applications. Furthermore, these entities facilitate climate action by meticulously monitoring national emissions and systematically tracking advancements as documented in reports to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), thereby augmenting transparency and informing updates to emission inventories.

Research and development organizations in India serve a crucial function in the mitigation of climate change. Their endeavours encompass three primary responsibilities: dissemination of knowledge, monitoring, and collaboration with stakeholders. Through initiatives like the National Carbonaceous Aerosol Program (NCAP), the CSIR-NEIST generates essential insights into climate dynamics, particularly regarding the impacts of aerosols on rainfall patterns and agricultural productivity. Collaboration is essential to their mandate, as these entities engage in coordination with governmental agencies, scientific communities, and international collaborators. By promoting discourse and the exchange of knowledge among a diverse array of stakeholders, they propel actionable solutions and advocate for India's trajectory towards a decarbonized future. In conclusion, Indian research and development organizations can play a pivotal role in climate mitigation, providing evidence-based recommendations, comprehensive monitoring, and nurturing partnerships that collectively strengthen resilience and sustainability in the face of a dynamic climate landscape.

Keywords: Climate change, Carbonaceous aerosols, Agriculture, Resilience, Decarbonization

Development of Sustained-Release Attukal Kizhangu L.-PCL Nanofibers for Chronic Periodontitis: In-vitro and Randomized Controlled Clinical Study

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Abstract

Aims: Design of PCL-loaded nanofiber-containing herbal formulation *Attukal Kizhangu L.* in chronic periodontitis: A randomized controlled investigation.

Material & methods: The electro-spinning method was used to create the composite nano-fibers containing herbal formulation, which were then evaluated for various parameters including *in-vitro* and clinical study.

Findings: The electrospinning method was successfully used to fabricate AK-PCL nanofiber (NF) scaffolds. The “Quality by Design” approach followed by the Box-Behnken experimental design was used to optimize the NF. The optimized nanofiber exhibited an interconnected, continuous, and bead-free nanofiber with an average diameter of 150-250 nm. Anti-microbial investigation and CLSM study indicated the remarkable inhibition of periodontal pathogens such as *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonas Gingivitis*, *Fusobacter spp.*, and *Prevotella Intermedia* by optimized nanofiber and *in-vitro* drug release study also demonstrated the controlled release of composite nanofiber for over 220 hours. Additionally, the MTT assay and *in-vitro* scratch assay indicated the composite NF had no cytotoxicity to the fibroblast cell line. Also, the clinical study suggested the therapeutic effectiveness of composite NF in patients by substantially reducing ($p < 0.05$) clinical parameters such as plaque index, gingival index, clinical attachment loss, and probing pocket depth.

Conclusion: The fabricated NF is a potential option for chronic periodontitis treatment since it expedited anti-bacterial, cytotoxic, and sustained-release medications.

Keywords: *Attukal Kizhangu L.*, Nanofiber scaffolds, Characterization, *In-vitro* study, Clinical study

Microbial Antagonists as Environment Friendly Alternative Approach in Bio-Protecting Wheat From Biotrophic Pathogens

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Abstract

Wheat is one of the most predominant cereal crops of global economic significance. It is a staple food crops provides daily nourishment to millions of people globally. In India, wheat is the second most important cereal crops, play a pivotal role in food & nutrition security and provide >50% of the food calories to the population. In 2020-21, India attained a record production of 109.52 mt from an area of 31.45 mha and productivity of 3.51 t/ha. In view of the increasing food requirement due to burgeoning population, India alone will need >140 mt of wheat by 2050 to feed an estimated population of 1.73 billion. Sustainable productivity of wheat is of supreme importance in the context of several biotic stresses that limit its production.

Wheat crop suffers from many biotic and abiotic stresses in all stages of growth that limit its production. Many biotic stresses interfere with normal functioning of physiological processes of plants and cause different foliar, seed, soil and air borne diseases. The fungal diseases of wheat viz., rusts (stripe, leaf & stem), powdery mildew, Karnal bunt, spot blotch, *Fusarium* head blight, Septoria blotches, tan spot, take-all, *Rhizoctonia* root rot and wheat blast are the known to be most potentially damaging because they cause substantial reduction in yield as well as deterioration in quality of grain. Among these the wheat biotrophic pathogens (all the three rusts and powdery mildew) are considered as a serious constraint inflecting high economic yield losses in most of the wheat growing areas of the world. Control of these wheat diseases has mainly relied on a combined approach of growing resistant cultivars and applying fungicides. However, the potential risk of the pathogen becoming resistant to fungicides has been increasing because triazole compounds as fungicides, especially triadimefon, have been widely used for a long period of time. Meanwhile, the widespread use of fungicide can cause environmental pollution. Resistance of cultivars to diseases could be easily overcome by new virulence of pathogens. Therefore, it is better to develop a non-chemical alternative approach to manage diseases. Use of beneficial microbes may provide an environmentally friendly option for control of diseases and reduce the potential risk of fungicide-resistant strains in the fungal population. There are various naturally occurring soil microbes that aggressively attack on plant pathogens and benefit plants by disease suppression and hence referred to as biocontrol agents. It has the potential to be more stable and long lasting than other controls and is comparative with the concepts and goals of integrated pest management and sustainable agriculture. Biological control, offers an additional strategy and can be used as part of an integrated management of wheat diseases for a greater level of protection with sustained yield.

Among the micro-organisms with high potential for the development of biocontrol agents, using *in vitro* production systems, are bacteria and fungi. In combating plant diseases, microbial antagonists belong to the genus *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas* and *Trichoderma* are among the most widely used bacteria and fungus respectively, and a good candidate for biological control. The

Bacillus spp. is among the highly potent bacterial biocontrol agents used for controlling principally rhizosphere and to a lesser extent foliar diseases of plants. These bacteria are germ-positive, aerobic, and found to colonize the root surface which increase the plant growth and cause the lysis of fungal mycelia. The capacity of *Bacilli* to produce spores which are extremely resistant to high temperatures, unfavorable pH, and lack of nutrients or water are a very good feature required for field application. The pseudomonads are common gram-negative, rods-shaped bacteria, has simple nutritional requirements and grows well in mineral salts media supplemented with any of a large number of carbon sources. Certain members of the *Pseudomonas fluorescens* have been shown to be potential agents for the biocontrol which suppress plant diseases by protecting the seeds and roots from fungal infection. They are known to enhance plant growth promotion and reduce severity of many fungal diseases through the production of a number of secondary metabolites including antibiotics, siderophores and hydrogen cyanide. A number of antagonistic bacteria belongs to pseudomonads, possess antifungal and growth promoting activities, and widely associated with wheat rhizosphere have been found effective against various wheat diseases under *in vitro*, greenhouse and the field conditions.

As several bacterial antagonists belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas* and *Streptomyces* have been found to inhibit mycelial growth of wheat biotrophs, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici* (Powdery mildew), while a few of them also inhibit growth of other fungal pathogens like *Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici* (stripe rust), *Puccinia recondite* f.sp. *tritici* (leaf rust). Laboratory studies also revealed that a large number of bacterial and fungal antagonists possess the ability to bio-protect wheat plants from rusts and powdery mildew.

Keywords: Wheat, Biotic stresses, Fungal diseases, Biocontrol agents, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, Integrated pest management

Aldehyde-Mediated Open-Air Stereoselective β -Glycosylation of Glycals: An Expeditious Route towards Glycosyl-Ester Synthesis

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Abstract

The study introduces a method for achieving a selective synthesis of β -glycosyl esters through the reaction of glycals with carboxylic acids. This process is characterized by stereoselectivity, operating under mild reaction conditions and in an open-air environment mediated by an aldehyde. Detailed investigations and control experiments indicate the significance of benzaldehyde in conjunction with atmospheric air in facilitating this transformation. The method's versatility is evident in its broad substrate scope, accommodating various carboxylic acid derivatives with electron-releasing and electron-neutral functional groups. The practical applicability of the protocol is demonstrated by successfully esterifying different drugs, including indomethacin, tolmetin, and stearic acid, resulting in the production of novel compounds with excellent yields. Mechanistic studies, supported by controlled experiments, highlight the formation of glycal epoxide as an intermediate in the reactions.

- Open air
- Mild conditions and good yields
- β -selective
- Synthetic utility

Think Locally Act Globally With Reference to Bioprospection of Ethnomedicinal Plants of India

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Abstract

Ethnomedicines have played tremendous role in discovery of novel life saving drugs to combat chronic diseases. Several novel lead compounds like morphine, cocaine, codein, digitoxin and quinine have been discovered from the ethnomedicinal plants to combat pain, fever, alzheimers, malaria and to boost intellect as well as immunity. Ethnomedicinal wisdom , which is still a key player in achieving sustainable health management by maintaining health security as well as well being, is currently facing different challenges such as biopiracy, standardization, clinical trials as well as collection and quality assurance of raw materials . Every nation has sovereign right over its biodiversity which is frequently violated by the act of biopiracy or gene robbing. There are many examples of exploitation of traditionally used medicinal plants by the biotechnologically rich but biodiversity poor countries. *Pentadiplandra brazzeana* from tropical Africa, *Vinca rosea* from Madagascar, *Curcuma longa*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Withania somnifera* from India are some classical examples of biopiracy. Due to recent developments in gene technologies, many biotechnologically rich but biodiversity poor countries are involved in the act of biopiracy by illegally patenting the traditional knowledge of other countries. Hence, bioprospection would help the native countries in legal exploitation of the bioresources by preventing the act of biopiracy. Hence, bioprospection is a burning issue for biodiversity-rich countries like India, China, and tropical African nations to document their bioresources as well as to identify their useful plants, related phytochemicals and genes controlling them. Incorporation of modern technologies along with digitalization of traditional knowledge and their bioprospection may overcome the associated challenges.

Keywords- Ethnomedicines, Biopiracy, Biodiversity, Bioprospection, Traditional knowledge, Phytochemicals

Diabetes and its Pathological Complications Ameliorate Through Tradition Systems of Medicine

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is characterized by elevated glucose levels due to either abnormalities in insulin production or insulin resistance. Chronic hyperglycemia contributes to several major complications, including nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, and both macrovascular and microvascular damage. Diabetic retinopathy accounts for an estimated 5% of all cases of blindness worldwide, while nearly 50% of patients undergoing renal replacement therapy have diabetic nephropathy. Additionally, diabetic peripheral neuropathy is associated with significant morbidity, mortality, and diminished quality of life, affecting up to 50% of individuals with diabetes. Clinical trials have shown that achieving normal glycemia can significantly reduce the incidence of these complications. However, in practice, reaching target blood glucose levels is challenging, with almost 50% of individuals unable to achieve the recommended HbA1c of less than 7%. Antioxidant defenses and cellular redox status play crucial roles in the pathophysiology of diabetes and its complications, and combining antioxidant treatments with other therapies is likely to be effective in alleviating these issues. Traditional systems of medicine, such as Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese Medicine, along with herbal remedies, offer holistic approaches that may help mitigate these complications. Numerous herbs are believed to assist in lowering blood glucose levels, making the prospect of better glycemic control and reduced dependence on insulin through herbal medicine particularly appealing. However, the selection of herbs depends on several factors, including the stage of diabetes, existing comorbidities, and considerations of availability, affordability, and safety. Preclinical studies have advanced to patient care, with recent clinical research demonstrating that medicinal plants such as *Bruguiera cylindrica*, *Ageratina adenophora*, *Aerva sanguinolenta*, and *Basella alba* possess significant antidiabetic potential. Moreover, evidence suggests that integrating traditional practices with conventional treatments can enhance glycemic control and improve overall patient outcomes. Therefore, explanatory and pragmatic clinical studies are essential for acquiring reliable preclinical data. Implementing these criteria in research will help restore credibility to pharmacological studies involving natural products in the context of diabetic complications. This abstract explores the potential benefits of traditional medicine in managing diabetes and its associated complications, highlighting the importance of a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach to care.

Keywords- Diabetes mellitus, hyperglycemia, diabetic complications, antioxidant treatments, herbal remedies, traditional medicine.

Ethical Concerns in Preclinical Research

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Abstract

Many important scientific therapeutic advances in human and veterinary have been achieved through the conduct of preclinical research and understanding of the science behind the development of novel drug molecules. Animals in research have contributed enormously to the development in medical science that had benefited both humans and animals. We can follow the ethical and regulatory rules approved by the competent authority. By doing so we can make scientific advances that will improve the quality of humans and animals and at same time reducing the number of animals used in research and providing better refinement conditions for the animals that continue to be used.

Wherever possible by adopting ethics and regulatory guidelines the 5R's Principles [Replacement, Reduction, Refinement, Reuse and Rehabilitation] can be followed in biomedical research involving the animals. Apart from the 5R's Principles, we should also consider 5F's Principles – 1) Freedom from Hunger & Thirst, 2) Freedom from Fear and Discomfort, 3) Freedom from Pain, Injury and Diseases, 4) Freedom for expressing normal behavior and 5) Freedom from Discomfort while conducting the research. The selection of suitable animal model should be done meticulously considering the resemblance of some of the important anatomical, physiological and pathophysiological aspect between human and animals due to various life processes limitations.

Animal models have not only played important roles in drug development, safety, efficacy, pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics and toxicity studies of a drug, but also have provided the base for clinical trials in humans. Small laboratory animal models are more cost-effective, have short life span, resemblance of some of the physiological functions and agreeable to high throughput testing as compared to large animal models.

Alternatives methods to animals in research such as genetic engineering, artificial intelligence, Advanced *in vitro* models (3D human tissue cultures, Spheroids, Organoids, Microfluidic or specific Organs On-chip systems), mathematical models, bioprinting of organs, and advanced machine learning technologies can also be used as some of the new strategies in research activities.

Keywords: - Preclinical research, animal models, 5R's Principles, 5F's Principles, drug development, advanced *in vitro* models,

Unravelling the Mechanisms Underlying Zinc Biosorption and Tolerance in a Heterocytous Cyanobacterium *Anabaena sphaerica*

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Abstract

Cyanobacteria, a group of prokaryotic photoautotrophs, adopt a variety of changes at their physiological, morphological, metabolic and molecular levels to survive under toxic environmental conditions including heavy metal stress. So far, a large number of studies related to the evaluation of impact of heavy metals like Cr, Cu, Cd, As, Pb, Hg on cyanobacteria have been performed and the strategies employed by these organisms to tolerate such heavy metals have also been explored. However, the impacts of zinc stress on cyanobacteria are poorly known. In our previous study, we meticulously explored the zinc stress impacts on the cyanobacteria using *Anabaena sphaerica* as experimental organism, but the zinc tolerance mechanisms of cyanobacteria are still unknown. In this context, the present study was designed to assess zinc stress induced changes in the proteome of *Anabaena sphaerica* to understand the molecular mechanisms of its zinc tolerance. The study revealed three different aspects that were associated with the zinc tolerance in *A. sphaerica*: (i) the reduced expression of photosynthesis, nitrogen fixation, energy metabolism, respiratory, and transcriptional/translational proteins probably to conserve energy and utilizing it to sustain growth; (ii) the enhanced expression of metallothionein and ferritin domain protein All 3940 to chelate free zinc ions whereas upregulation of antioxidative proteins for detoxifying reactive oxygen species; and (iii) the expression of large numbers of hypothetical proteins to maintain the important cellular functions. Furthermore, over expressions of sulfate adenylyl transferase and cystathionine beta synthase along with the increased synthesis of peptidases and thiolated antioxidant proteins were also noticed which denoted cysteine synthesis under sulfur deprivation possibly by mobilizing the sulfur from dead cells and its channelization towards the production of thiolated antioxidants. Beside tolerating excess amount of zinc, *A. sphaerica* exhibited high zinc biosorption efficiency (pseudo second order kinetics) which indicated its possible zinc bioremediation applications.

Keywords: Zinc stress; Bioremediation; *Anabaena sphaerica*; Proteomics; Metallothionein; Ferritin domain protein.

Resolving Severe Man-Animal Conflicts - Safe Translocating Blackbuck Using a Novel Method of Capturing Technology

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Abstract

The Indian Blackbuck (*Antelope cervicapra*), a vulnerable species protected under the Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972, has adapted well, to the dry, scrubby environments of Andhra Pradesh. Kurnool district, in particular, has seen a rise in Blackbuck populations due to the absence of natural predators and habitat changes caused by agricultural expansion. As a result, conflicts have emerged between farmers and the Blackbuck, especially during drought years, when the animals concentrate their foraging on limited cultivated areas. This has led to significant crop damage, frustrating local communities. The rapid increase in Blackbuck numbers, exacerbated by strict wildlife protection laws, has left farmers unable to manage the crop damage effectively. In response, a series of capture and translocation efforts were initiated to mitigate the conflict. Two primary techniques were employed: the “Lure Crop Method”, where crops favoured by Blackbuck were used to attract and trap them for relocation, and the “Light and Sound Method”, which involved capturing Blackbucks at night using lights and sounds to immobilize them. A total of 6000+ Blackbuck were captured and relocated safely to Sirigiripadu Beat in the V.P. South range of the ‘Nagarjunasagar Srisailam Tiger Reserve’ (NSTR). Post-release monitoring was conducted to assess the long-term adaptation of the animals, track demographic and ecological changes, investigate mortalities, and engage the local communities through education and awareness programs. Initial results suggest that the translocated Blackbucks are adapting well to their new environment. The study highlights the importance of continuous monitoring to ensure successful long-term integration and the need for ongoing public education to foster coexistence between humans and wildlife.

In conclusion, while the translocation of Blackbuck has helped reduce immediate human-wildlife conflicts, the success of this strategy depends on sustained efforts in habitat management, species monitoring, and community involvement. This initiative demonstrates the potential of adaptive management in resolving wildlife conflicts in agricultural regions.

Keywords: Indian Blackbuck, Wildlife Protection, Human-Wildlife Conflict, Crop Damage, Translocation, Lure Crop Method, Light and Sound Method, Nagarjunasagar Srisailam Tiger Reserve, Habitat Management, Community Engagement, Conservation, Adaptive Management.

Entomotherapy, Health Benefit and Nutritional composition of Certain edible insects of North Eastern India

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Abstract

Edible insects are excellent sources of high-quality nutrients and are gaining attention as alternative nutrient sources to alleviate global food insecurity. In the north-eastern region of India, where numerous ethnic communities reside, entomophagy emerges as the most effective means of supplying the increasing need for nutrients. The present study has been designed to evaluate proximate composition, antioxidant and antinutritional properties; amino acids, fatty acids and minerals of certain commonly consumed edible insects both in their fresh and processed forms in different stages of development, viz., adult, pupae and larvae. The protein content was significantly higher in fresh samples (7.87 ± 1.18 mg/g) compared to fried (3.38 ± 0.98 mg/g) and roasted (2.89 ± 1.26 mg/g) forms. Significant differences were observed across different developmental stages, with fresh *S. cynthia ricini* larvae having the highest protein content (9.21 ± 0.53 mg/g). Lipid content increased upon frying and roasting, with roasted *P. barthelemyi* adults showing the highest lipid concentration (5.51 ± 0.07 mg/g). Carbohydrate content also varied, highest in fried *Cossus* sp. (12.17 ± 3.78 mg/g). Phenol content was highest in roasted *S. cynthia ricini* larvae (10.4 ± 1.1 mg/g), and total antioxidant concentrations were maximized in fried *H. cashmirensis* (13.47 ± 0.05 mg/g L-ascorbic acid equivalent). The study also examined the amino acid profiles, noting significant variation among species and preparation methods. Essential amino acids such as leucine, lysine, and valine were found in higher concentrations in *P. barthelemyi* larvae. Non-essential amino acids, including alanine and glycine, were particularly abundant in wood larvae. Additionally, the fatty acid profile indicated the presence of myristic, palmitic, linoleic, oleic, and stearic acids, with oleic acid being highest in *Cossus* sp. larvae with 61.61%. Thus, the nutritional value of insects is significantly affected by their developmental stage and preparation method. Fresh forms generally retain higher protein content, while frying and roasting increase lipid and carbohydrate concentrations. The presence of essential and non-essential amino acids and a diverse fatty acid profile further highlights the potential of insects as a valuable food source. The authors advocate for large-scale production of nutrient-rich edible insects and focuses on the traditional usage of insects as a sustainable and alternative protein food source in the region

Keywords: Entomotherapy, Health nutrition Amino acid, Antioxidant, Protein, Northeast India.

Sustainable Synthesis and Computational Antidiabetic Evaluation of benzothiazoles

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a serious and pressing worldwide health concern that makes the search for better antidiabetic drugs imperative. Benzothiazole derivatives have emerged as pivotal therapeutic agents for T2DM management.

Aim of the study: The present study introduces an efficient synthesis method for the production of benzothiazole compounds and subsequently, their evaluation as potential T2DM agents.

Methodology: An environmentally benign synthetic protocol is developed for the synthesis of a wide range of benzothiazole compounds. In order to understand the mechanics of ligand-protein interaction, ADME/Toxicity, and drug-likeness aspects, in silico studies were incorporated.

Results: An efficient and easy method for synthesis of benzothiazole compounds has been devised. Thorough evaluation of the produced compounds' biological activity, particularly in the context of T2DM, has been carried out.

Conclusion: A thorough computational evaluation of the synthesized heterocyclic compounds' biological activity has been carried out thereby displaying their significant promise as prospective antidiabetic drugs. The findings demonstrate the benzothiazole compounds' applicability in the continuous search for innovative and novel T2DM treatment strategies.

Keywords: Benzothiazole, Antidiabetic agents, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Sustainable, in-silico,

Assessing the Therapeutic Efficacy of Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka in Cerebral Palsy: A HRAMS Study"

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Abstract

Background: Cerebral palsy (CP) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by motor impairment, muscle tone abnormalities, and cognitive deficits.

Objective: To evaluate the bioactive compounds present in Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka and its therapeutic potential in CP patients using High resolution accurate mass spectrometry (HRAMS).

Methodology: 1. HRAMS analysis of Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka's phytochemical composition. 2. Non Randomized controlled clinical trial in 60 CP patients. 3. Interventional group patients received Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka for 1 year.

Results: 1. The HRAMS of Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka data reveals presence of certain bioactive substances that has neuroprotective, antioxidant, enhance cognitive function, therapeutic role in neurodegenerative diseases, anti-inflammatory characteristics. 2. Significant improvements in motor function, muscle tone and cognitive performance noted. Reducing the increased muscle tone, improving muscle power and ability to hold objects manually.

Conclusion: Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka demonstrates therapeutic potential in CP, with HRAMS analysis providing valuable insights into its phytochemical composition and biochemical effects. These findings reveals presence of certain bioactive substances that has neuroprotective, antioxidant, and improving blood flow in ischemic and hypoxic state of brain.

Keywords: Ashwagandhadi Ksheerpaka, cerebral palsy, HRAMS, Ayurveda, europrotection, motor function.

Pharmacognostical and physicochemical analysis root of Sarapunkha (Tephrosia purpurea (Linn.) Pers.)

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Abstract

Introduction: *Sarapunkha* [Tephrosia purpurea (Linn.)Pers.] commonly known as "Wild Indigo" is a leguminous plant widely used in traditional medicine for its reported hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. Evaluating the properties of the plant through pharmacognostical and physicochemical parameters is essential for determining its authenticity, chemical stability, purity, and suitability for use in pharmaceutical formulations. According to P. V. Sharma, it is renowned as pleehasatru because of its potential to act upon spleen and liver.

Materials and methods: The roots of Sarapunkha were collected from Jaipur District, Rajasthan, cleaned, shade-dried and were powdered. Macroscopic examination for anatomical features was carried out. Microscopic examination and physicochemical parameters such as moisture content were conducted in accordance with API guidelines.

Results: The root of Sarapunkha is cylindrical, light brown, fibrous, and has a rough surface with longitudinal ridges. Microscopic examination of the transverse section shows 8 cork layers made up of rectangular cells, a wide cortex rich in starch grains, and multiple patches of sclerenchyma cells. The solid xylem contains wide vessels, tracheid, and xylem parenchyma filled with starch, with biseriate medullary rays present between the xylem vessels. Physicochemical analysis revealed aqueous soluble extract value (10.56%), alcohol soluble extract value(4.97%), petroleum ether soluble extract value (0.82%), moisture content (5.11%) and pH value is 4.25.

Conclusion: The pharmacognostic and physicochemical analysis of Sarapunkha root provides essential data for its identification and quality control. These findings contribute to ensuring the authenticity, purity, and standardization of the raw material for medicinal use.

Keywords: Sarapunkha, Pharmacognosy, physicochemical, biseriate, pleehasatru

Impact of Climatic Effect on Diarrheal Diseases

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Abstract

Diarrhoeal diseases depend on several climatic factors, including temperature, rainfall, sunspots, and humidity. During the study period, a total of 3987 diarrhea patients were enrolled at Infectious Diseases Hospital (IDH) in the diarrhoeal diseases surveillance system, and a total of 9235 patients attended the Diarrhoea Treatment Unit (DTU) in B.C. Roy Children Hospital. *V. cholerae* isolations were 11.05% of cases. All *V. cholerae* strains were susceptible to ofloxacin, azithromycin, norfloxacin, and gentamicin, while *Shigella* strains were susceptible to only ceftriaxone. In the present study, a logistic bi-variant regression was undertaken to ascertain the risk factors of gender, age, income, source of drinking water, practices of storage of drinking water, hand washing, and covered stores of drinking water on the severe/some dehydration of diarrhoea. The results revealed that dehydration was significantly correlate with age, hand washing source of drinking water. Moreover, it suddenly occurred corona, which also indicated us to see the impacts of it on diarrhoeal diseases. The initial observation of climatic data temperature, rainfall, and humidity has a good correlation with the number of diarrhea cases.

Keywords: Diarrhoea, climate, *V. cholera*, *Shigella*, antimicrobial therapy. Diarrhoea, *Shigella* strains

Study on Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (MRSA) Carriage in Medical Students before and after Exposure to Hospital Environment

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Abstract

Introduction: Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is a strain of *S. aureus* that has developed resistance to methicillin and other beta lactam antibiotics as well as cephalosporins and monobactams. It harbours a gene, *mecA*, coding for altered penicillin binding protein (PBP 2a). Exposure to hospital environments is known for MRSA carriage. Health care workers (HCW) have often been implicated in outbreaks of MRSA associated hospital acquired infections due to MRSA carriage in their anterior nares, hands, axillae etc.

Aim of the study:

- I. To evaluate the prevalence of MRSA carriage in among the medical students.
- II. To assess the impact of hospital environment on the colonization by MRSA in students with no previous exposure to the organism.

Methodology: It was a cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary care centre. A total of 86 students were involved in the study. Nasal swabs were taken before exposure to the hospital, 6 months and 1 year after the exposure to the hospital environment. Swabs were cultured on to mannitol salt agar and blood agar. Standard microbiological methods were followed to identify *S. aureus* and methicillin resistance was checked for, using cefoxitin discs. Data were recorded and analysed using Microsoft Excel.

Results: No MRSA carriage was seen before hospital exposure. At the end of 6 months, 2 students (2.3%) were colonized with MRSA and 3 students (3.48%) were colonized at the end of 1 year. The male: female ratio at the end of 1 year was 2:1.

Conclusion: Increasing rate of colonization with MRSA was seen with increase in duration of exposure to the hospital environment. Since MRSA is one of the major causes of Hospital acquired infections (HAI) and HCW are considered the source of the infection, periodic screening and treatment of the carriers will go a long way in controlling HAIs caused by MRSA.

Keywords: *S. aureus*, infection, MRSA, *mecA*, Cephalosporins and hospital environment

Studies on the interaction of an insecticide nitenpyram with 1-hexyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium bromide for the effective enhancement of the wettability

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Abstract

Effective pesticide utilization is extremely significant in agriculture but is typically neglected owing to a lack of knowledge and the overuse of pesticides, leading to high pesticide residues in crops. Pesticide solution tends to drift away from crops owing to the hydrophobic surface of leaves. Thus, considering the enhancement in wettability and surface activity of pesticides, adjuvants are added to the spray solution even though these are detrimental to the environment. In this study, the effect of a pyrrolidinium based ionic liquid (IL), 1-hexyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium bromide $[\text{PyrC}_6]\text{Br}^-$ was studied on the wettability of the pesticide Nitenpyram (NTP). The critical micellar concentration (cmc) for the IL and IL-NTP systems was found using the surface tension method, UV-visible and fluorescence spectroscopy. Various thermodynamic parameters were calculated through surface tension and cmc values. It was observed that adsorption was favored over micellization for the NTP-IL system which also exhibited higher surface activity as compared to the IL, and increased with temperature. The stability of the NTP-IL system was determined by dynamic light scattering and zeta potential measurements at various concentrations of IL. The wettability of IL-NTP system on different crop leaves like guava, lemon, chilli, spinach and okra was examined using static contact angle measurements. The higher stability of IL-NTP system was also supported through density functional theory calculations. The results demonstrated an enhanced wettability of the IL-NTP system as compared to NTP alone, exhibiting maximum influence at the cmc value of the IL.

Keywords: Ionic liquid, surface tension, contact angle, wettability, density functional theory.

Integrating Geospatial and Analytical Hierarchy Process Techniques for Identification of Potential Rainwater Harvesting Sites in Lower Shivaliks of Punjab

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Abstract

Water is one of the most vital natural resources on the earth, without which life is not possible. In the contemporary times, population explosion coupled with industrial advancement and upsurge in agricultural activities has put a tremendous pressure on freshwater resources leading to water crises. In order to deal with this prevailing scenario, rainwater harvesting at potential sites is emerging as an ecofriendly strategy for sufficing the agricultural and other domestic requirements. In this perspective, it is imperative to identify the potential sites for storing the excess rainwater which otherwise flows as a surface runoff. In the present study, suitable sites for rainwater harvesting have been identified in block Balachaur of District SBS Nagar Punjab using GIS and multi-criteria decision making techniques. The analytical hierarchy process (AHP) technique has been used to determine the most suitable sites for rainwater harvesting. Eight criterion layers including runoff depth, soil type, slope, stream order, drainage density, geology, LULC and distance to road have been used. The runoff was estimated using SCS-CN method. The site suitability map reveals that the about 5.35% (17.41 km²) of the total area is extremely suitable for RWH in this region. About 61.8 (200.78 km²) and 26.1 (84.78 km²) is highly and moderately suitable for RWH. However, 6.75 (21.93 km²) of the area is not suitable for RWH. The storage structures like earthen dams may be constructed across the *choes* (seasonal channels/rivulets) while as percolation tanks and farm ponds may be constructed in lower lying areas of the region. Therefore, it is concluded that the integration of GIS and AHP is the cost-effective technique to determine the suitable sites for rainwater harvesting.

Keywords: Rainwater harvesting, GIS, AHP, Runoff, Suitable sites, earthen dams, choes.

Study of Infection of Helminth Parasites in *Silonia silondia*

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Abstract

Introduction: *Silonia silondia* is a common edible fish in Saran district after “Labeo rohita” and infection in fish with helminth adversely affect the production in pisciculture.

Aim of the Study: The present study aim to evaluate and identify the common infection of helminth in *Silonia silondia*.

Methodology: To find the helminth infection of *silonia silondia* dissection of freshly collected fish (N=150) was performed and microscopically examined the gills, liver, intestinal smear and other organs. The helminth were identified using microscopic analysis and reference to standard parasitology keys.

Results: A low prevalence of helminth infection was observed with various species. A very low prevalence of parasite were found in intestine and liver.

Conclusion: The study concluded that *silonia silondia* is less or no susceptible to various helminth parasite.

It shows that the fish collected from Saryu river Saran district were free from parasite or less affected.

Keywords: Helminth, Parasite, *Silonia silondia*, Fish, Saryu river, intestinal smear.

Assessing the Consequences of Drought Stress on Maize Productivity in Mizoram: Integrating Growth, Physiological, and Antioxidant Defense Mechanisms

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Abstract

Drought frequency and severity are rising globally, driven by declining rainfall and altered precipitation patterns. This poses significant threats to agricultural productivity and food security. This study explores the impact of drought stress on the growth, physiology, antioxidant defense mechanisms, and yield performance of two local maize landraces from Mizoram, India - Puakzo (MZM-17, IC 638846) and Mimban (MZM-8, IC 640946). The study employed two irrigation regimes: 100% field capacity (control) and 35% field capacity (drought simulation) at three developmental stages (35, 70, and 105 days after germination). Drought stress reduced growth parameters (leaf number, plant height, stem diameter) and physiological parameters (net assimilation rate, internal CO₂ concentration, transpiration rate, stomatal conductance, chlorophyll fluorescence) in both landraces. MZM-8 exhibited greater reductions as compared to MZM-17. The study identified landrace-specific responses regarding reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, membrane damage, chlorophyll pigments, and antioxidant activity under drought stress. Specifically, MZM-8 demonstrated a significant upregulation of enzymatic antioxidants, whereas MZM-17 showed notable rise in non-enzymatic antioxidants. *In vivo* histochemical localization of ROS indicated higher levels of superoxide radicals ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in MZM-8, suggesting a greater sensitivity to drought stress than MZM-17. All yield parameters, including cob weight plant⁻¹, kernel row number, kernel count plant⁻¹, kernel weight plant⁻¹, and 1000-kernel weight (test weight), were significantly reduced under drought conditions in both landraces. The seed yield (kernel weight plant⁻¹) decreased by 35.6% in MZM-8 and 25.9% in MZM-17. These results offer valuable insights for farmers seeking to enhance crop productivity with limited water resources and highlight the genetic potential of maize landraces for drought tolerance breeding, informing strategies to address global food insecurity.

Keywords: Drought stress, Maize, growth, physiology, antioxidants, yield, MZM-17.

Evaluation of Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation (*Stress WIN*) on DOCA-salt-induced hypertensive rats

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Abstract:

Hypertension is a chronic condition that occurs when the force of blood pushing against artery walls is constantly too high. It's a saviour condition that can increase the risk of heart, brain, kidney, and other diseases.

In this condition pro-inflammatory cytokines and cholesterol is high and may cause chronic inflammation through thrombogenesis and fibrosis. This chronic inflammation producing excess ROS through pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-I β and TNF- α) causes endothelial dysfunction. However, the nitric oxide (NO₂⁻) and malonaldehyde (MDA) is also become high and facilitate the oxidative stress that damage the liver to produce SGOT, SGPT, and glomerulus filtration of the kidney. In this research work, a novel polyherbal formulation (*Stress WIN*) showed a potent therapeutic drug for the treatment of DOCA-salt-induced hypertensive rats. Three well-known herbs used in Ayurvedic medicine (*Stress WIN*) are *Ashwagandha* (*Withania somnifera* (L.) Dunal), *Pushkarmoola* (*Inula racemosa* Hook. f.), and *Jatamansi* (*Nardostachya jatamansi* (D.Don) DC. Here, *Stress-WIN* significantly reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-I β and TNF- α) and the level of ROS, nitric oxide, malonaldehyde, SGOT, and SGPT in the serum of DOCA-salt-induced hypertensive rat. A part from this, *Stress-WIN* reduces glutathione concentration and decreases the cholesterol level also. Histological analysis showed that *Stress-WIN* A treatment (500 mg/kg and 1000 mg/kg) reversed the infiltration. Furthermore, *Stress-WIN* B (1000 mg/kg) administration attenuated DOCA-salt-mediated morphological changes in the kidney and the heart. In this study, the importance of Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation (*Stress WIN*) is highlighted as an alternative source of hypertension to control the stress condition in vitro.

Keywords: Cholesterol, β -Sitosterol, Apigenin, Piperine, Salicylic Acid, Hypertension,

Cardioprotective efficacy of Carvacrol against Isoproterenol induced cardiotoxicity in rats

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Abstract

Background: Heart is the most active and incumbent organ of the body, which maintains blood flow, but due to various pathological reasons, several acute and chronic cardiac complications arise out of which myocardial infarction is one of the teething problems. Isoproterenol imitates the adrenergic stimulation and manifests the main index of the pathogenesis of maladaptive myocardial hypertrophy. Isoproterenol induced cardiotoxicity is a well-established model to study cardiac damage. Carvacrol is a phenolic monoterpenoid abundantly present in the essential oils of oregano and thyme and is well-known for exerting multiple pharmacological effects such as antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, anti-angiogenic, and anti-tumor activity. The present study was undertaken to understand the protective effect of carvacrol on isoproterenol induced cardiac damage in rats.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in Swiss Albino rats. Rats were divided into four groups: control, isoproterenol, carvacrol alone and carvacrol+isoproterenol. Isoproterenol (150 mg/kg b.w.t.) was injected intraperitoneally to induce myocardial injury to rats. Carvacrol (10 mg/kg b.w.t.) was supplemented orally for 14 days to assess its beneficial effect.

Results: Isoproterenol induced cardiotoxicity was evident by abnormal ECG parameters, hemodynamic parameters, lipid profile, increase in lipid peroxidation (malondialdehyde levels) and decrease in cellular antioxidants (superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione S transferase, vitamin E, vitamin C and vitamin A). Histopathological analysis of cardiac tissue further confirmed the cardiac damage induced by isoproterenol. Carvacrol treatment significantly reversed all the above abnormalities induced by isoproterenol.

Conclusion: The results of our present investigation reveals that the mechanism behind the cardioprotective effect of carvacrol could be reducing oxidative stress and enhancing cellular antioxidant levels.

Keywords: Isoproterenol, cardiac damage, carvacrol, oxidative stress, lipid profile; antioxidants

Assessment of Culturable Bacterial Bioaerosol Variability in Fields Growing Aromatic and Medicinal Plants

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Abstract

The decline in air quality due to rapid urbanization and industrialization in developing countries is an increasingly pressing issue, particularly with the rise in bioaerosols—airborne particles of biological origin. These bioaerosols pose significant threats to public health and the environment. As a result, there is growing interest in exploring natural remedies. Understanding microbial diversity in natural environments, particularly in plants with antimicrobial properties, could offer valuable insights into combating bioaerosols. In this context, aromatic and medicinal plants emitting volatile compounds with known antimicrobial activity may be especially worth investigating.

This study aimed to examine the variability in the bacterial communities present in bioaerosols collected from fields planted with aromatic and medicinal plants. Two species of *Ocimum*—*Ocimum sanctum* and *Ocimum basilicum* were selected for the aromatic plants and medicinal, while *Andrographis paniculata* represented the non-aromatic and medicinal category. The results showed no significant difference in the concentration of particulate matter (PM₁₀) across the three sites. The average PM₁₀ concentrations were 221.78 µg/m³ at Site 1 (*Ocimum sanctum*), 232.76 µg/m³ at Site 2 (*Ocimum basilicum*), and 239.31 µg/m³ at Site 3 (*Andrographis paniculata*). However, when comparing the total culturable bacterial units in the bioaerosols, the lowest bacterial concentration was observed at the *Ocimum sanctum* site, followed by the *Ocimum basilicum* site, with the highest bacterial concentration recorded at the control (*Andrographis paniculata*) site. Bioaerosols collected from the control site (*Andrographis paniculata*) were dominated by bacterial species such as *Bacillus* sp., *Pantoea* sp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* AB18, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain ASR-39. In contrast, these bacteria were found in much lower concentrations in the bioaerosols from the *Ocimum sanctum* and *Ocimum basilicum* sites. This study highlights a distinct pattern in the bacterial communities of bioaerosols across fields of aromatic and non-aromatic plants. These findings deepen our understanding of bacterial aerosols in fields of aromatic plants and also suggest potential interactions between aromatic plant species and bioaerosols.

Keywords: Bioaerosol; Bacterial composition; *Ocimum*; Aromatic; *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; bioaerosols.

The Integration of Modern and Conventional System of Medicine for Holistic Patient Care

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Abstract

An Amalgamation of conventional medication systems of India is known as Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy (AYUSH), with coincident medicine (like allopathic medicine, biomedicine, mainstream medicine, orthodox medicine, western medicine) is the developing sector of engrossment in medical management.

The amalgamation of coincident medicine and AYUSH come up with a unique synergy, saddle the strengths of both approaches to deliver personalized comprehensive and holistic care. There are numerous potential superiorities of AYUSH, but faces a lot of difficulty in amalgamation, which is challenging our caregiver, health care provider and primary care provider (PCP) to acquire conventional medication treatments into their practices due to insufficient scientific data on their efficacy as well as not proper education system which teaches and train health care professional for use of conventional medication system. Consequently, there are very limited access to conventional medical practitioners instructed in AYUSH makes challenging to receive treatment. However, this system can treat a wide range of diversified medical difficulties including, cancer treatment, post chemotherapy care. In rural area cultural assumptions restricts and creates some misconceptions regarding the conventional medical practitioner and amalgamation. Therefore, the health care organization and government should take some protective role in removing the barriers and impediments to amalgamation. To completely understand the advantages and restrictions as well as to create successful promotional technique for integrative practices, more research is required.

In this paper, we have analyzed various problems and explored more potential areas to integrate both systems. We concluded with the suggestions to improve the existing system with a lot of positive attitudes with patient-oriented workout.

Keywords: AYUSH, Amalgamation, Conventional medication system, evidence-based research, Holistic care, Coincident medicine, Allopathic medicine, Biomedicine

Coating Seeds with Biochar and Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria Enhanced Heavy Metal Stress Tolerance in *Zea Mays*

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Abstract

The rapid pace of industrialization and urbanization in developing countries has led to severe environmental challenges, including the accumulation of heavy metals in soils. This contamination, largely driven by human activities, degrades soil fertility, reduces crop yields, and poses serious risks to human and animal health by entering the food chain. In recent years, seed coating along with biochar and plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) has emerged as a pioneering, eco-friendly solution for enhancing agricultural productivity across a range of soil conditions, from conventional to highly challenging environments. By improving nutrient availability, strengthening plant defences, and fostering a healthier soil ecosystem, seed coating along with biochar and PGPRs represents a revolutionary approach to sustainable agriculture, paving the way for more robust and adaptable crop production in an era of changing environmental conditions. The present study aimed to assess the effect of seed-coating with PGPR, biochar and binders on the survival efficiency of inoculated PGPR and thus plant growth and physiological response in multi-metal contaminated soils. The wood chips biochar (WCB) was selected for this study based on its plant growth promotion potential and its physicochemical parameters. This study investigated individual and combined effects of WCB and PGPR *Bacillus cereus* (Zn01) and *Bacillus subtilis* (Zn11) coated seeds on *Zea mays* growth, physiology, and their impact on antioxidant enzyme activity under multi-metal stress. It was observed that even under multi-metal stress, *Z. mays* growth, pigment contents, proteins, phenolics, relative water and antioxidant enzyme activity were increased in response to WCB, biochar and PGPR-treatment. Hence, the results highlight that seed coating with WCB and PGPR provides a conducive environment which in turn enhances plant growth and physiological responses by producing various plant growth-promoting metabolites. Therefore, seed coating with WCB and PGPR could be exploited as an effective strategy for eco-restoration and phytoremediation for improving plant growth, removal of metal contents and establishing the survival of plants under multi-metal stress conditions.

Keywords: Biochar, Heavy metals, PGPR, *Zea mays*, phytoremediation, *Bacillus subtilis*.

Impact of Blood Transfusions on Climate Change and mitigation strategies

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Abstract

Background: Modern Medicine Healthcare activities significantly contributing in single use plastic waste and Green House Gas emissions. Healthcare carbon footprint is responsible for 4-5% of global carbon emissions. Blood Transfusions is among one of the top five overused interventions of Modern Medicine. Blood Transfusions are energy intensive process which involves transport, collection, processing in heavy electrical equipment, refrigeration and transfusion. Blood Bags are made up of PVC with DEHP plasticizer. Its manufacturing, use and incineration impacts climate change and it contaminates environment from carcinogenic vinyl chloride monomer, bio accumulative toxins dioxins, furans and mercury contamination of waterways and micro plastics.

Aims and Objectives: Our primary aim is to assess the extent of inappropriate transfusions and secondary objective is to assess the burden of PVC waste generated due to inappropriate transfusions

Material and Methods: In a cross-sectional study from Rajasthan state, data of transfusion practices collected from transfusion request forms from 10 blood centres. The sample size was calculated to be 5650 transfusion request forms, catering to 7350 transfusions at a rate of 1.3 units issued per transfusion request.

Results: Out of 3803 blood units transfused in the medical and medical super speciality branches, 1669 transfusions (43.89%) of them were transfused without any documentation for the indication for transfusion or a haemoglobin value, which is considered as inappropriate practices. In India the annual collection accounts for 12-15 million units, 40% of which is utilized in correcting nutritional anaemia/iron deficiency anaemia Each unit of blood collected generates 381 gm of plastic waste (PVC with DEHP). Considering 50% of inappropriate transfusions annually generates approx. 3 lakhs tons of plastic waste for incineration. NHS Blood and Transplant, UK in one of their study calculated 15000 tonnes of carbon dioxide emission in 2019, most of which were attributable to blood donation and testing and the manufacture, storage, and distribution of blood components.

Conclusion: Bio-Medical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2016 states phase out use of chlorinated plastic bags, gloves and blood bags within two years from the date of notification of these rules. Since there is no alternative for blood bags reduction and rational utilization is the only solution Environment pollutants and micro plastics generated from incineration of PVC blood bags. Plasticizer DEHP is an endocrine disrupter and cause ADHD, asthma, breast cancer, obesity and type 2 diabetes.

Keywords: Transfusions, PVC, DEHP, Climate change, carcinogens, endocrine disrupter.

Mitochondrial-Targeted Drug Delivery: Harnessing Triphenylphosphonium-Pluronic F127 Conjugate for Effective Oxidative Stress Treatment

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Abstract

Oxidative stress is a pathological condition characterized by an imbalance between the excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the body's endogenous antioxidant defence mechanism, which can precipitate a range of metabolic disorders, including hyperglycaemia. Elevated blood glucose levels amplify ROS production in pancreatic β -cells, primarily through mitochondrial pathways, leading to increased oxidative damage and triggering mitochondrial fission, a process where mitochondria undergo fragmentation, which not only disrupts energy production but also contributes to the pathogenesis of various metabolic disorders, including type 2 diabetes mellitus. Triphenylphosphonium (TPP) is commonly employed in delocalized lipophilic cations, typically covalently attached to nanocarriers to achieve mitochondrial targeting. On the other hand, Pluronic F127 (PF127), a triblock copolymer known for its high hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value, demonstrates limited affinity for cellular membrane interactions. However, the conjugation of TPP with PF127 alters the physicochemical properties of the resulting polymeric micelles, reducing the HLB value and enhancing the interaction with cellular membranes. This modification enables the formation of micelles capable of co-delivering lipophilic drugs specifically to mitochondria, thereby significantly improving their bioavailability and therapeutic index. This study aims to formulate, evaluate, and optimize drug-loaded polymeric micelles in conjugation with TPP using the thin film hydration technique. As per the results, polymeric micelles exhibited particle sizes ranging from 133.46 nm to 288.5 nm and zeta potential ranging from -14.1 mV to 13.4 mV. DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) and Lipid peroxidation (LPO) radical cation assay which were adopted as *In vitro* models to study the antioxidant activity of formulated polymeric micelles, yielded IC_{50} values of $6.29 \pm 0.43 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $6.09 \pm 0.37 \mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively, indicating a potent antioxidant activity of the formulated micelles. Moreover, confocal microscopy studies provided visual confirmation of successful mitochondrial targeting by the polymeric micelles. The co-localization of the fluorescently labeled micelles with mitochondrial markers in treated cells demonstrated the efficacy of TPP conjugation in directing the drug-loaded micelles to mitochondria.

Keywords: Triphenylphosphonium, Pluronic F127, Mitochondrial Targeting, Polymeric Micelles, cellular membrane.

Divergent Antioxidant Responses and Growth Dynamics in Ozone-Sensitive and Ozone-Tolerant Wheat Cultivars Under Elevated CO₂ and O₃: Implications for Food Security in a Changing Climate

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Abstract

Crop plants are increasingly vulnerable to the complex stress of tropospheric ozone (O₃), which underscores the urgency for food security-oriented management strategies. While extensive research has examined the detrimental effects of O₃, this study uniquely investigates the combined impacts of elevated ozone (eO₃) and elevated carbon dioxide (eCO₂) on wheat cultivars. Specifically, it contrasts the responses of the O₃-sensitive cultivar PBW-550 with the O₃-resistant cultivar HUW-55, assessing the effects of eO₃ and eCO₂ both separately and in combination. The findings demonstrate that eCO₂ exerts a beneficial influence on wheat cultivars exposed to eO₃ stress, with more pronounced effects observed in the O₃-sensitive PBW-550 compared to the O₃-resistant HUW-55. This differential response is attributed to mechanistic differences in enzyme activities within the Halliwell-Asada pathway (AsA-GSH cycle) and the ascorbate and glutathione pools. Notably, eCO₂ did not enhance the regeneration of the glutathione pool in HUW-55; however, PBW-550 exhibited a favorable response under similar eO₃ conditions. The study's results underscore the mechanistic variations in antioxidant responses, revealing a more favorable yield outcome in PBW-550 under the combined ECO treatment. These insights can guide agricultural strategies, advocating the use of O₃-sensitive cultivars to maintain productivity in future environments characterized by elevated O₃ and CO₂ levels.

Keywords: Ascorbate- glutathione, elevated O₃, carbon dioxide, antioxidants, PBW-550

Exploring the therapeutic potential of *Momordica charantia* in the mitigation of liver function in the letrozole-induced PCOS like conditions in mice

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Abstract

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a hormonal disorder affecting approximately 6-12% of women of reproductive age. The onset of PCOS is accompanied by a spectrum of metabolic disturbances, including insulin resistance, obesity, dyslipidemia, cardiovascular problems, and type 2 diabetes mellitus. These metabolic derangements contribute significantly to an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD). The liver, as a central organ in metabolic regulation, is profoundly affected by these metabolic abnormalities, highlighting the importance of liver health in the management of PCOS. In recent years, healthcare systems have increasingly acknowledged the value of food-based, alternative, and complementary medicines. This trend may stem from a better understanding of the potential toxicity associated with conventional allopathic treatments or their higher costs. Phytochemicals found in herbal remedies and medicinal plants offer therapeutic benefits for conditions like PCOS. *M. charantia*, commonly known as bitter melon or bitter gourd, has been traditionally used in various cultures for its medicinal properties, particularly its anti-diabetic and hepatoprotective effects. The bioactive compounds in *M. charantia*, such as charantin, quercetin, polypeptide-p, and vicine, have been shown to exhibit insulin-mimetic and lipid-lowering effects, which could be beneficial in managing PCOS-related metabolic complications. Based on this, we sought to study the hepatoprotective effect of *M. charantia* in the mitigation of liver function in the PCOS mice. The aqueous methanolic extract of *M. charantia* on biochemical, lipid profile, and histopathological study elucidated its potential hepatoprotective and metabolic regulatory roles in PCOS mice. The *M. charantia* treatment causes improvement in lipid profile, along with normalization of hormonal enzymes. Therefore, understanding these effects could provide insights into novel therapeutic strategies for managing liver health in PCOS patients, potentially improving their overall metabolic profile and quality of life.

Keywords: PCOS, liver function, Ovarian function, lifestyle modification, phytochemicals, *M. charantia*,

Spiders of Andhra Pradesh: A Comprehensive Checklist and Taxonomic Study

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Abstract

Background: The variety of spiders is important for maintaining the correct balance of ecosystems and combating pests. This work aims to establish the spider fauna of Andhra Pradesh, India, emphasizing species abundance and availability in different ecosystems and periods.

Methods: In tropical moist deciduous forests, dry deciduous forests, mangrove swamps, grasslands, and agricultural areas, field surveys were done through hand collection, pitfall traps, beating sheets, sweep nets, and sifting of the leaf litter. The species were identified using keys to taxonomy while specimens were collected for future use.

Results: The total of the recorded species was 215 belonging to 30 families with the most representation of *Araneidae*, *Salticidae*, and *Lycosidae*. The Shannon-Wiener Index showed the highest diversity in tropical moist deciduous forests ($H' = 3.45$) and the least diversity in agricultural landscapes ($H' = 2.31$). The study showed that the diversity was higher post-monsoon ($H' = 3.65$) than pre-monsoon ($H' = 3.20$).

Conclusion: The study reveals the diverse spider fauna in the region and the critical role of habitat structure and temporal variation in structuring spider assemblages in the area. In this context, this research provides important data for conservation and management plans and further arachnological research.

Keywords: Tropical, Deciduous, Grasslands, Mangrove, Diversity and Conservations.

Systematic Surveillance of Antimicrobial Resistance from Different Food Sources

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Abstract

Human exposure to antimicrobial resistance (AMR) through food is now very imperfectly understood, creating a significant gap in the design of interventions. The interchange of AMR genes and the transfer of AMR bacteria from animals to humans through the food chain necessitate comprehensive methods for risk reduction. With a focus on AMR in bacterial species isolated from food products, foods (of both animal and non-animal origin), and ambient samples, the current meta-analysis gathered up-to-date information on the epidemiology of AMR in the animal-source food chain. As a result, the combined prevalence of AMR across the various food sources was calculated. From the 18,784 food samples obtained as a result of selected publications, 7,676 (40.9%) samples were contaminated, including 4343 (56.6%) and 3363 (43.4%) samples from Taiwan and India, respectively. Meat (chicken, pork, and beef), fish, and milk all have moderate to medium potential for AMR exposure to both Gram-positive and Gram-negative foodborne pathogens such as *S. aureus*, *Clostridium*, *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, etc. Antibiotic resistance to β -lactam, fluoroquinolone, carbapenem, etc. is present in the majority of food samples. The results of this study emphasize the persistent danger of antimicrobial residue in animal-derived foods in Taiwan, India, and other nations with comparable customs.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR), Antibiotics, Surveillance, Food sources, β -lactam

Discovery and characterization of a novel Fpn1 isoform involved in iron homeostasis

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Abstract

Ferroportin (Fpn1), a vital iron transporter, plays a critical role in maintaining iron homeostasis by facilitating iron release from within cells. Its activity is precisely controlled by Heparin, a peptide hormone produced in the liver, which binds to Fpn1, inducing its internalization and degradation. This regulation is essential for balanced iron levels in the body, safeguarding against both iron overload and deficiency. Insight into the Ferroportin-Heparin pathway is crucial for designing treatments for iron-related disorders and infections. Iron export not only supports iron recycling but also restricts iron availability to intracellular pathogens, serving as an important host defence mechanism.

Alternative splicing is a finely regulated process enabling a single gene to generate multiple mRNA isoforms, greatly enhancing proteome complexity. This post-transcriptional mechanism is pivotal for cellular function, development, and adaptation by shaping gene expression patterns. Dysregulated alternative splicing is associated with numerous diseases, including cancer, neurodegenerative disorders, and metabolic conditions.

We have identified and validated a novel alternatively spliced isoform of human Ferroportin 1 (Fpn1), distinguished by a variation in the C-terminal domain. Using in-silico analysis and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, we characterized the structure of this isoform, offering insights into its potential functional roles. These findings enhance our understanding of Fpn1 isoform diversity and its possible contributions to iron homeostasis and disease, underscoring the role of alternative splicing in regulating protein function.

Keywords: Ferroportin, New isoform, Iron regulation, Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, Protein functionality, Alternative splicing, Structural analysis.

Lifecycle and Morphological Traits of *Drosophila melanogaster*: A Study In Lab Culturing

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Abstract

Drosophila melanogaster, commonly known as the fruit fly, has been widely studied and used as a model organism in biomedical research for over a century due to its genetic similarity to humans and its requirement for a variety of proteins, lipids, and fats similar to those in human physiology. This study provides a detailed examination of the lifecycle and morphological traits of *D. melanogaster*, from egg to adult, as observed under controlled lab conditions. Emphasis is placed on the four key stages egg, larva, pupa, and adult highlighting significant morphological changes during development.

The research aims to optimize culturing protocols that promote high survivability and health across generations, ensuring reproducibility in experimental results. By analyzing the general morphology at each stage, this study reinforces the importance of *Drosophila*'s role in genetic, developmental, and toxicological studies. Additionally, the influence of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and food medium on the lifecycle and morphological development is discussed.

Keywords: *Drosophila melanogaster*, Lifecycle, Morphological traits, Developmental stages, Model organism.

Evaluating the Hepatoprotective Activity of *Yakinaran* (*Atalantia ceylanica* (Arn.) Oliv) Leaves in Paracetamol-Induced Hepatotoxicity Models.

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Abstract

Atalantia ceylanica (Arn.) Oliv., also known as *Yakinaran* in Sinhala is a perennial woody shrub from the Rutaceae family and natively distributed across Sri Lanka, India and Vietnam. It is extensively used in Sri Lankan traditional medicine, particularly herbal porridge made with fresh juice of this leaves in liver diseases. The hepatoprotective activity and anti-oxidant activity of the *A. ceylanica* leaves has been previously demonstrated through in-vitro study. Hence, this study aimed to validate the traditional claim of *A. ceylanica* leaves as a hepatoprotective drug with a confirmed safety profile through in-vivo experimental model. An acute toxicity study was conducted following OECD guideline 425, wherein ten female Wistar albino rats were administered a single oral dose of dry leaf powder at 2000 mg/kg body weight. The hepatoprotective activity of *A. ceylanica* leaves was investigated using a paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity model in Wistar albino rats after obtaining the IAEC approval. Ponderable changes, biochemical parameters, including liver-specific biomarkers of animals and histopathology of livers were used to determine the hepatoprotective activity of the drug. The administration of *A. ceylanica* dry leaf powder at a single oral dose of 2000 mg/kg did not result in any mortality or observable toxic signs in female albino rats. The potential hepatoprotective effect of *A. ceylanica* was evidenced by observable changes in the animals and was notably confirmed by biochemical parameters, including total bilirubin, direct bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, and IL-1 β , a liver-specific biomarker and by the cytoarchitectural findings of the liver. The non-significant positive effects on total cholesterol, uric acid, creatinine, SGPT, SGOT, GGT, and GLDH further support the consideration of *A. ceylanica* leaves for their hepatoprotective activity. These findings validate the traditional claim with safety aspect and encourage further research to explore its full therapeutic potential.

Keywords: *Yakinaran*, *Atalantia ceylanica* (Arn.) Oliv., hepatoprotective activity, acute toxicity, Sri Lankan traditional medicine

Genetic Enhancement of Grain Yield and its Attributing Traits in Bread Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Based on Combining Ability Analysis and Gene Action

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Abstract

The estimation of combining ability is useful for assessing the performance of genotypes in any cross and elucidating the nature and magnitude of gene actions involved. The investigation was undertaken to study the combining ability for grain yield and its contributing traits in bread wheat. The experimental material consisted of twelve parents (8 lines and 4 testers) and 32 F₁'s produced from line x tester mating design. It was evaluated in randomized block design via utilizing three replications for grain yield and its attributing traits. The analysis of variance for combining ability revealed that Specific combining ability effects (SCA) variances were higher than their respective general combining ability effects GCA variances for all the characters confirming the preponderance of non-additive gene action for most of the traits emphasizing the utility of the hybrid breeding approach to exploit existing heterosis in breeding. The parents *viz.*, AKAW4927, MP3382, DDW88, GW496, and RAJ4328 exhibited good general combining ability effects whereas based on Specific combining ability effects, the top three hybrids *viz.*, AKAW4927 x GW496, MP3288 x GW499 and DDW88 x RAJ4328 were found to offer best possibilities of their further exploitation for developing high yielding varieties of bread wheat. The study provides valuable insights for wheat breeding programs aimed at enhancing global nutrition security via genetic enhancement of grain yield of bread wheat.

Keywords: Combining ability, general combining ability and specific combining ability effects, gene action, line x tester analysis, bread wheat.

Sustainable Cultivation of Medicinal Plants through Organic Farming: Scope, Challenges, and Solutions.

Binay Sen

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Abstract

Background: The chemical fertilizers and pesticides used in contemporary agriculture has many negative impacts on health of soils, humans, livestock and environment. Organic farming is a method that focuses on growing crops and raising livestock without the use of synthetic chemicals, fertilizers, or genetically modified organisms. The principles involve natural soil fertility, preservation of biodiversity, use of natural fertilizers and pest controls, etc.

Aim of the Study: To emphasize on the principles, processes, mechanisms, ingredients, available techniques, scope, challenges, and possible solution for economic, ecofriendly and sustainable medicinal plant cultivations.

Methodology: Adopted to review *Vrikshayurveda* literatures and current research related to organic farming which can be used in the cultivation of medicinal plants for achieving sustainable development goals.

Observation and Results: Crop rotation, intercroops, cover cropping, etc. are often practiced in organic farming techniques. It has a positive impact on the soil, the environment and ecosystem, quality products lead to organic brands having economic benefits. Increased demand for organic remedies and herbal products due to health consciousness creates a robust market for medicinal plants. Pharmaceutical products with high quality organic brands are in market demand both for plant products and medicinal formulations. Good health and wellbeing (SDG-3) is one of the SDGs declared by the UN in the year 2015 that is to be achieved by 2030. Organic farming is a sector which plays cross-sectorial roles in clean water, economic growth, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water and life below land under 17 SDGs. There are certain challenges that hinder the adoption of organic farming in the medicinal plant sector, like certification cost, market access, cost of organic manure and pest and weed management. Partnership collaboration, research and development, policy implementation and government support, holistic integration of traditional techniques described in *Vrikshayurveda*, etc. will open the bottleneck solution.

Conclusion: Organic farming of medicinal plants can thrive, contributing to both economic and environmental sustainability. It is a sustainable alternative to conventional agriculture, with multi component ecological benefits and market opportunities make a better choice for many farmers and consumers.

Keywords: Organic farming, Sustainable Development Goals, Intercrops, Vrikshayurveda.

Unlocking the potential of peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.) yield and quality through Induced Mutagenesis

Akancha Gupta^{1,2}, Nashra Aftab^{1,2}, Priyanka Prasad^{1,2}, Himanshu Kumar Kushwaha^{1,2}, Puja Kumari^{1,3}, Ram Kishor^{1,2}, Vagmi Singh^{1,2}, Shivani Chandra¹, Anju Kumari Yadav^{2,4}, Birendra Kumar^{1,2*}

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Abstract

Mentha piperita L., commonly known as peppermint, is valued for its essential oil, which is rich in menthol and has various applications. However, challenges such as low oil yield and poor oil quality have limited the potential of peppermint cultivation. This study aimed to develop a noble mutant of *Mentha piperita* that complements US-type peppermint oil, characterized by higher oil yield and improved oil quality, specifically targeting a menthol content of 36-46% and less than 5% menthofuran. Induced mutagenesis was achieved through gamma radiation, with seeds from a menthofuran-rich variety CIM-Indus of *Mentha piperita* subjected to varying doses (10 Gy, 20 Gy, 30 Gy, 40 Gy, 50 Gy, 70 Gy, 90 Gy, and 110 Gy). A broad range of diversity was observed among the resulting mutants, leading to the selection of improved lines. Notably, CIM-I452 exhibited the highest oil yield along with substantial herb yield, followed by CIM-I332 and CIM-I324. Lines CIM-I43, CIM-I44, CIM-I451, CIM-I32, CIM-I34, CIM-I332, and CIM-I452 were identified as menthol-rich, while CIM-I311 and CIM-I431 were menthofuran-rich. Additionally, CIM-I322 and CIM-I331 were recognized as limonene-rich lines. The mutants CIM-I452, CIM-I332, and CIM-I324 demonstrated high menthol content with low menthofuran levels, making them globally accepted. Based on essential oil quality, oil yield, and herb yield, the selected mutants CIM-I452, CIM-I332, and CIM-I324 show promise as parental lines for future recombinant breeding or hybridization efforts.

Keywords: *Mentha piperita*, Genetic diversity, Menthol, Menthofuran, Induced mutagenesis

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Niroshani BADT*, Panara KB, Nariya MB

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²Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh – 362 001, Gujarat, India.
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Abstract

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Binay Sen

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Abstract

Background: The chemical fertilizers and pesticides used in contemporary agriculture has many negative impacts on health of soils, humans, livestock and environment. Organic farming is a method that focuses on growing crops and raising livestock without the use of synthetic chemicals, fertilizers, or genetically modified organisms. The principles involve natural soil fertility, preservation of biodiversity, use of natural fertilizers and pest controls, etc.

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Keywords: Organic farming, Sustainable Development Goals, Intercrops, Vrikshayurveda.

Unlocking the potential of peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.) yield and quality through Induced Mutagenesis

Akancha Gupta^{1,2}, Nashra Aftab^{1,2}, Priyanka Prasad^{1,2}, Himanshu Kumar Kushwaha^{1,2}, Puja Kumari^{1,3}, Ram Kishor^{1,2}, Vagmi Singh^{1,2}, Shivani Chandra¹, Anju Kumari Yadav^{2,4}, Birendra Kumar^{1,2*}

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Abstract

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Keywords: *Mentha piperita*, Genetic diversity, Menthol, Menthofuran, Induced mutagenesis

Effect of Correlation and Path Analysis in Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.)

Akhil Kumar Chaudhary*, Gulab Chand Yadav, D. K. Upadhyay*, Rajat Kumar Maurya, Suman Poonia, Nimit Singh
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Abstract

The present investigation was carried out in thirty-two genotypes of brinjal with a view to estimate the extent of variability, analysis of variance and genetic divergence. The experiment was conducted in Randomized Block Design with three replications at Department of Vegetable Science, Acharya Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Kumarganj, Ayodhya (U.P.), during Kharif, 2020-21. Each treatment consisted of twelve plants in two rows, having spacing of 60 cm x 50 cm with net plot size of 1.2 m x 3.00 m². The magnitudes of genotypic correlation were higher than the phenotypic correlation coefficients for all the character combinations. The most important trait, total fruit yield per plant had exhibited highly significant and positive phenotypic correlation with average fruit weight (0.747), number of fruits per plant (0.672) and fruit circumference (0.468) at both phenotypic and genotypic levels. Positive direct effect on total fruit yield was exerted by total sugars (0.474), average fruit weight (0.396), fruit circumference (0.358), number of fruits per plant (0.254), plant height (0.242), fruit polar length (0.194) and day to 50 % flowering (0.168). The higher magnitude of positive direct effect on total fruit yield was exerted by total sugars (0.474), average fruit weight (0.396), fruit circumference (0.358), number of fruits per plant (0.254), plant height (0.242), fruit polar length (0.194), day to 50 % flowering (0.168). High heritability coupled with high genetic advance were recorded for the traits viz. total fruit yield per plant, marketable fruit yield per plant, average fruit weight and number of primary branches, fruit length and fruit circumference. Thus, there exists ample genetic variability and as consequence scope of improvement in the available germplasm of brinjal.

Keyword: Brinjal, Genetic variability, Genetic Correlation and Path, Germplasm

Nutritional and Therapeutic Analysis of Sethura Laddu for Postpartum women

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Abstract

Background: Sethura laddu, a traditional Indian sweet consumed by postpartum women, particularly in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. A well- balanced nutrition is essential for a child's development which is starting from conception and extending through lactation, where maternal nourishment plays a significant role.

Aim of the study: This analysis aims to verify its role in supporting newly delivered mothers through nutritional and therapeutic perspectives.

Methodology: Sethura laddu is traditionally prepared recipe for recovery of postpartum, using a specific mixture of ingredients, including ginger powder, desiccated coconut, tikhur powder, deshi ghee, almonds, gond katira, cashews, raisins, sugar, moong dal powder, makhana, turmeric powder, chironji, and poppy seeds. A detailed nutritional analysis was performed to assess the nutritional composition which is beneficial for postpartum women. The study also included a review of the nutritional benefits.

Results: Nutritionally, the laddu provides a balanced combination of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates, contributing to its role in enhancing milk production, reducing back pain, and providing sustained energy. The iron content was quantified as 3.30 mg/100g through analysis. Key ingredients such as dry ginger, moong dal powder, tikhur powder, almonds, and deshi ghee are known for their beneficial effects on digestion, cardiovascular health, lactation, and overall postpartum recovery.

Conclusion: Sethura laddu is a nutrient-dense recipe with significant benefits for postpartum women. Its traditional formulation, supported by both historical usage and nutritional analysis, aids in lactation, energy provision, and ease postpartum discomfort. This study highlights the laddu's value as a dietary supplement for new mothers, combining traditional wisdom with nutritional science to support postpartum health and recovery.

Keywords: Nutrition, lactation, postpartum health, Sethura Laddu, traditional foods, maternal health, ayurvedic medicine.

Senna: An Excellent Laxative Herbal Medicine - Cultivation and Storage Strategies

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Abstract

Background: It is evident from the literature that 80% of the world's population depends on herbal drugs. Now-a-days, the herbs and herbal medicines are much effective for the treatment of varied disorders as they have minimal side effects as compared to the allopathic medicines. Nowadays, constipation is a common complaint and challenge for older and adults. Senna (*Cassia augustifolia*) is an ayurvedic herb more popularly known as *swarnapatri* in Sanskrit, widely used for its numerous benefits. The plant is mainly valued for its cathartic properties and is especially useful in habitual constipation. The pods and leaves contain anthraquinone glycosides that have a big laxative effect, besides its use as mild laxative, senna's other benefits include in the treatment of jaundice, hepatitis, herpes simplex, cracking of the skin, migraine headache, hair loss, and for relaxing muscle tension.

Aim: To cultivate and store Senna more and more due to its numerous Health Benefits.

Methodology: Cultivation of senna doesn't require much expense on irrigation, manuring, pesticides, protection and other pre- and post-harvesting care. About 20 Kg seeds are required to cover one hectare of land. This makes the plant a perfect crop for arid regions where water provision, wasteland development, desertification control, dune stabilization are the main challenges such as in Rajasthan.

Results: This prophetic herb is very beneficial for numerous health issues. The plant has been investigated for its various chemical constituents and pharmacological properties.

Conclusion: Given the profound health benefits and economic feasibility of *Cassia augustifolia*, there is a strong need to promote the cultivation and use of senna on a large scale. This will not only support the healthcare system but also provide environmentally sustainable crop options for areas facing agricultural challenges.

Keywords: Senna, Prophetic medicine, Anthraquinone glycosides, Laxative, Cultivation, Storage

Effects of Cadmium Exposure on the Morphology and Behaviour of Fresh Water Snakehead Fish, *Channa punctatus*

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Abstract

The presence of heavy metals in freshwater systems is a critical concern due to their toxic effects, persistence, and potential for bioaccumulation. This study examines the toxicity of cadmium in the freshwater fish species *Channa punctatus*. Common heavy metal pollutants include cadmium, nickel, arsenic, chromium, copper, mercury, zinc, and lead, all of which can severely harm various aquatic organisms. Cadmium naturally occurs in the Earth's crust alongside lead, copper, zinc, and nickel. It is also utilized in batteries, fertilizers, pesticides, coatings, and alloys. Cadmium can easily enter the atmosphere, bind to small particles, and contaminate soil or water, impacting fish, animals, and plants. This study aims to explore the relationship between mortality rates and the abnormal behavioral and morphological changes seen in *Channa punctatus* exposed to cadmium chloride.

The primary behavioral reactions noted during the experiment included erratic swimming, gulping air at the surface, loss of balance, lethargy, and fish lying on the water's surface before death. Additionally, morphological changes such as skin discoloration, pigmented patches on the body, scale shedding, chemical sedimentation, and increased mucus secretion were recorded in the exposed fish. The data indicated that *C. punctatus* is an effective bio-indicator for heavy metal contamination in freshwater environments. The accumulation of cadmium in fish can also lead to bioaccumulation in humans, potentially entering the food chain and destabilizing ecosystems. The results suggest that *Channa punctatus* can act as an effective bioindicator for heavy metal pollution in freshwater environments.

Keywords: Cadmium, toxicity, *Channa punctatus*, morphology, behavioural, ecosystems,

Antioxidant analysis and characterization of bioactive compounds from *Leptadenia pyrotechnica* Forssk. Decne

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Abstract

Background: *Leptadenia pyrotechnica* Forssk. Decne (LP) is a medicinal herb from the Asclepiadaceae family with many advantageous properties.

Aim of the study: The goal of this research is to identify, quantify, evaluate the antioxidant potential, and characterize the bioactive compounds from LP to validate its remarkable therapeutic advantages.

Methodology: Different LP extracts (hot Soxhlet extraction) were evaluated physiochemically to check their impurity, purity, and quality; qualitatively to detect different phytochemicals; and quantitatively for phenol, saponin, tannin, flavonoid, and alkaloid contents. Then, the *in vitro* antioxidant potential was estimated by DPPH, NO, H₂O₂ scavenging assays, and MC and FRAP assays. The most prevalent phytochemicals of LP were then analysed by AAS, FT-IR, UV-visible, and GC-MS techniques. The extraction methods (soxhlation or ultrasonication) were optimized by utilizing response surface methodology (RSM) to determine the impacts of multiple parameters.

Results and conclusions: A higher extractive yield was shown by LPSE and LPRE (7.37 ± 0.11 and 5.70 ± 0.02). The LP stem showed better physicochemical and qualitative results than the root. The findings of the quantitative analyses showed that, maximal quantity of TPC, TTC, and TAC were observed in the LPSE extract (996.24 ± 66.81 $\mu\text{g GA}/50\text{g dried extract}$; 997.11 ± 31.76 $\mu\text{g TA}/50\text{g dried extract}$, and 966.48 ± 24.51 $\mu\text{g TA}/50\text{g dried extract}$); TFC in LPSEA extract (791.43 ± 3.53 $\mu\text{g RUT}/50\text{g dried extract}$) of LP stem; and TSC was observed highest in the LPREA extract (846.24 ± 119.33 $\mu\text{g QJ}/50\text{g dried extract}$) of LP root respectively. The findings of the *in vitro* antioxidant activities showed that maximal antioxidant potential of DPPH ($170.4 + 19.67$ $\mu\text{g/ml}$), NO (70.9 ± 9.91 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), H₂O₂ ($89.87 + 50.41$ $\mu\text{g/ml}$), and MC (86.06 ± 42.67 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were observed in LPSE extract, whereas FRAP (59.36 ± 0.02 $\mu\text{MFe(II)}/\text{g}$) in LPSCH extract. The quantitative and *in vitro* antioxidant results indicated maximal phenols, tannins, and alkaloid contents in LPSE extract, which was further confirmed by UV-visible, FT-IR, and GC-MS results. Ultrasonication was selected over the hot Soxhlet extraction method via RSM. The study concluded that the plant has remarkable therapeutic advantages to promote additional clinical investigations and the mechanisms of its action.

Keywords: Antioxidants, FT-IR, GC-MS, *Leptadenia pyrotechnica*, UV-Visible, Soxhlet

Efficacy and Safety of Herbal Remedies in AYUSH: A Scientific Review

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Abstract

The efficacy and safety of herbal remedies in the AYUSH system (Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy) are gaining attention as these traditional practices become more integrated into modern healthcare. This review examines the scientific validation of herbal treatments, highlighting their therapeutic benefits and potential risks. Through an analysis of recent clinical studies and systematic reviews, we aim to illustrate the effectiveness of key herbal remedies in managing various health conditions, including diabetes, arthritis, and mental health issues. Additionally, the review addresses safety concerns, such as common side effects, contraindications, and the regulatory frameworks governing herbal medicine use. By synthesizing findings from pharmacological research and clinical applications, this study provides a comprehensive perspective on the role of herbal remedies in AYUSH. Ultimately, it underscores the need for ongoing research to enhance understanding and promote the safe integration of these remedies into contemporary medical practice, supporting holistic health and well-being.

Keywords: AYUSH, Herbal remedies, Pharmacological research, Therapeutic benefits, gaining attention

The Genetics of Obesity and its Management by Ayurveda

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Abstract

Obesity is a complex clinical challenge and a significant public health concern, driven by a mix of genetic, environmental, and multifactorial factors. Genetic stability plays a vital role in understanding metabolic disorders, including obesity. Physiological variations can affect gene structure and function, disrupting metabolic pathways and leading to obesity, a prevalent nutritional disease. Excess adipose tissue produces triglycerides in both essential and non-essential forms, with overweight status defined by excess body weight relative to height. This condition is linked to increased morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing nations, and is associated with co-morbidities such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, certain cancers, and premature death.

Monogenic obesity, resulting from rare genetic mutations, has been linked to over 150 cases involving 11 genes across 50 loci that follow Mendelian inheritance patterns. Key genes such as leptin (LEP), leptin receptor (LEPR), proopiomelanocortin (POMC), and melanocortin-4 receptor (MC4R) have been identified as significant contributors to this disorder.

While modern medical approaches have been explored for obesity management, they often fall short due to complications and varying efficacy. Conversely, Ayurvedic medicine offers a range of herbal treatments, including Agnimantha, Amalaki, Apamarga, Brahati, Chitraka, Daruharidra, Devadaru, Eranda, Gokshura, Guduchi, Guggulu and Hingu which have been utilized for their therapeutic potential. active set prediction of protein targets has been done. The Key genes such as leptin (LEP), leptin receptor (LEPR), proopiomelanocortin (POMC), and melanocortin-4 receptor (MC4R) has been run by the different in network pharmacology programs and found the key ingredients of these drugs having good docking score for giving highest medicinal value This study employs in silico methods and network pharmacology to evaluate the efficacy of these Ayurvedic plants in managing obesity. The findings suggest that these herbal remedies may provide significant benefits in addressing obesity, highlighting their potential as adjunct therapies in contemporary obesity management.

Keywords: Obesity, Adipose cell, Genomic stability, Ayurveda, Ayurvedic plants, proopiomelanocortin

Standardization of *Apamarga* (*Achyranthes aspera* Linn.) *Ksharodaka*

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Abstract

Apāmārga (*Achyranthes aspera* Linn.) is an important medicinal plant in Ayurveda, revered for its versatile therapeutic properties. This study aimed to standardize Apāmārga Kṣārodaka through modern analytical techniques to establish its safety, efficacy, and quality. The research included detailed phytochemical analyses, stability testing, and an in vivo excision wound model using male Wistar rats. Analytical methods comprised pH measurement, TLC, FTIR, XRD, UV spectroscopy, HRMS, and microbial studies to assess the composition, purity, and stability of Kṣārodaka. The results revealed that Apāmārga Kṣārodaka has a high pH (12.75) and contains essential minerals like calcium, magnesium, and iron, indicating its suitability for wound healing. It demonstrated significant antimicrobial activity, especially against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and showed no toxic heavy metals within safe limits. In vivo studies confirmed its efficacy, with improved wound contraction and faster epithelialization compared to controls. Histopathological assessments indicated no adverse effects, confirming its safety. In-silico molecular docking identified homovanillic acid and biochanin A as bioactive components, binding effectively with proteins linked to wound healing. The shelf-life study indicated that Apāmārga Kṣārodaka remains stable for up to 9 months under accelerated conditions. These findings validate the Ayurvedic principles behind Apāmārga Kṣārodaka and support its potential for use in modern wound care, highlighting the need for continued research and application.

Keywords: Apāmārga Kṣārodaka, standardization, wound healing, phytochemical analysis, epithelialization

Synergistic effect of N-substituted pyrrolidinium based-ionic liquids on nisin: Strategy to combat bacterial resistance

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Abstract

Antibiotic resistance is one of the biggest threats to global health, food security, and development today. Antibiotic resistance occurs naturally, but misuse of antibiotics in humans and animals is accelerating the process. Antibiotic resistance leads to longer hospital stays, higher medical costs, and increased mortality. Considerable attention has been directed towards finding new alternative antibiotics to counter bacterial resistance, leading to longer hospital stays, higher medical costs, and increased mortality. A suitable solution for these problems is found by using ionic liquids (ILs). ILs have gained considerable global attention due to their diverse applications in various fields of chemical sciences. Since the past few decades, they have attracted significant attention from researchers owing to their unique physicochemical properties such as low vapour pressure, recyclability, non-volatility, and non-combustibility. Though the toxicity of ILs is the most debated topic in their applications as therapeutic agent; several efforts are being made to afford ILs with a balance between their toxicity and application. Therefore, the present study involves the synthesis of novel antimicrobial pyrrolidinium-based-ILs with varied hydrophobicity that are less toxic than imidazolium and pyridinium-based-ILs. The present study involves the non-covalent coupling of Nisin (Nis), an antimicrobial peptide with a series of synthesized less toxic pyrrolidinium-based ionic liquids (ILs) for which an MTT assay was performed. The antibacterial results of conjugates showed remarkable improvement in the MIC value as compared to MEL and ILs alone against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. In addition, hemocompatibility results suggested good selectivity of the non-covalent conjugate as a potential antibiotic agent.

Keywords: antibiotics, MTT assay, resistance, ionic liquid, peptide, non-combustibility

Pharmacognostical and physicochemical evaluation of leaves of *Lajjalu* (*Mimosa pudica* Linn.)

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Abstract

Introduction: Lajjalu, (*Mimosa pudica* Linn.) belonging to the family Mimosaceae commonly known as the "sensitive plant" or "touch-me-not," is a herbaceous plant widely recognized for its unique response to physical stimuli. Traditionally, it has been utilized in various medicinal practices due to its reputed therapeutic properties, including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects. Additionally, investigating the physicochemical properties of the plant provides insight into its chemical composition, stability, and potential applications in pharmaceutical formulations.

Materials and methods: Lajjalu leaves were collected from Thrissur District, Kerala, thoroughly cleaned, and shade-dried. Once fully dried, they were powdered using machinery. Macroscopical and microscopical analysis, along with physicochemical analysis were carried out in accordance with API guidelines.

Results: The leaves of Lajjalu are green, bipinnate, sensitive to touch, and fold when disturbed. Microscopic examination of the transverse section of Lajjalu (*Mimosa pudica*) leaves revealed calcium crystals in the central midrib. A single layer of upper and lower epidermis was observed, with some cells showing enlargement. Small vascular bundles were present at the center, surrounded by a sclerenchymatous layer. The lamina region exhibited a single layer of palisade cells extending into the midrib area, while the spongy cells in the lower lamina were loosely arranged. Physicochemical analysis showed moisture content of 10.88%, water-soluble extractive value of 5.62%, alcohol-soluble extractive value of 5.16%, petroleum ether-soluble extractive value of 0.88%, and a pH of 5.57.

Conclusion: The pharmacognostic and physicochemical screening of Lajjalu(*Mimosa pudica*) will offer reference information to ensure the quality, purity, and identification of the plant.

Keywords: Lajjalu, Microscopy, Pharmacognostic, Physicochemical analysis, sclerenchymatous

Effect of Mantra Therapy on Feto-maternal Well-Being

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Abstract

Introduction: Mantra therapy, an ancient Vedic practice, involves the repetitive chanting or listening to sacred sounds, believed to harmonize mind, body, and spirit. This review examines the available literature on mantra therapy's physiological and psychological effects during pregnancy.

Materials and Methods: A systematic review of peer-reviewed articles, clinical trials, and traditional Ayurvedic texts was conducted using PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases. Studies focusing on mantra therapy's effect on maternal mental health, pregnancy outcomes, and fetal development were included.

Results: Evidence suggests that mantra therapy reduces maternal stress, anxiety, and depression through its calming effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and enhancement of parasympathetic nervous system activity. Improved maternal physiological parameters, such as heart rate and blood pressure, were commonly reported. Studies also indicate better fetal heart rate variability (FHRV), higher birth weights, and improved neonatal APGAR scores in mothers practicing mantra therapy.

Conclusion: The therapeutic effects of mantra therapy are likely mediated through neurophysiological mechanisms involving relaxation and stress reduction. Mantra therapy shows potential as a culturally integrated, non-invasive intervention for enhancing feto-maternal well-being.

Keywords: Mantra therapy, Feto-maternal well-being, Prenatal care, Maternal stress, Fetal development.

Evaluating the Hepatoprotective Activity of *Yakinaran* (*Atalantia ceylanica* (Arn.) Oliv) Leaves in Paracetamol-Induced Hepatotoxicity Models.

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Abstract

Atalantia ceylanica (Arn.) Oliv., also known as *Yakinaran* in Sinhala is a perennial woody shrub from the Rutaceae family and natively distributed across Sri Lanka, India and Vietnam. It is extensively used in Sri Lankan traditional medicine, particularly herbal porridge made with fresh juice of this leaves in liver diseases. The hepatoprotective activity and anti-oxidant activity of the *A. ceylanica* leaves has been previously demonstrated through in-vitro study. Hence, this study aimed to validate the traditional claim of *A. ceylanica* leaves as a hepatoprotective drug with a confirmed safety profile through in-vivo experimental model. An acute toxicity study was conducted following OECD guideline 425, wherein ten female Wistar albino rats were administered a single oral dose of dry leaf powder at 2000 mg/kg body weight. The hepatoprotective activity of *A. ceylanica* leaves was investigated using a paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity model in Wistar albino rats after obtaining the IAEC approval. Ponderable changes, biochemical parameters, including liver-specific biomarkers of animals and histopathology of livers were used to determine the hepatoprotective activity of the drug. The administration of *A. ceylanica* dry leaf powder at a single oral dose of 2000 mg/kg did not result in any mortality or observable toxic signs in female albino rats. The potential hepatoprotective effect of *A. ceylanica* was evidenced by observable changes in the animals and was notably confirmed by biochemical parameters, including total bilirubin, direct bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, and IL-1 β , a liver-specific biomarker and by the cytoarchitectural findings of the liver. The non-significant positive effects on total cholesterol, uric acid, creatinine, SGPT, SGOT, GGT, and GLDH further support the consideration of *A. ceylanica* leaves for their hepatoprotective activity. These findings validate the traditional claim with safety aspect and encourage further research to explore its full therapeutic potential.

Keywords: *Yakinaran*, *Atalantia ceylanica* (Arn.) Oliv., hepatoprotective activity, acute toxicity, Sri Lankan traditional medicine

Genetic Enhancement of Grain Yield and its Attributing Traits in Bread Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Based on Combining Ability Analysis and Gene Action

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Abstract

The estimation of combining ability is useful for assessing the performance of genotypes in any cross and elucidating the nature and magnitude of gene actions involved. The investigation was undertaken to study the combining ability for grain yield and its contributing traits in bread wheat. The experimental material consisted of twelve parents (8 lines and 4 testers) and 32 F₁'s produced from line x tester mating design. It was evaluated in randomized block design via utilizing three replications for grain yield and its attributing traits. The analysis of variance for combining ability revealed that Specific combining ability effects (SCA) variances were higher than their respective general combining ability effects GCA variances for all the characters confirming the preponderance of non-additive gene action for most of the traits emphasizing the utility of the hybrid breeding approach to exploit existing heterosis in breeding. The parents *viz.*, AKAW4927, MP3382, DDW88, GW496, and RAJ4328 exhibited good general combining ability effects whereas based on Specific combining ability effects, the top three hybrids *viz.*, AKAW4927 x GW496, MP3288 x GW499 and DDW88 x RAJ4328 were found to offer best possibilities of their further exploitation for developing high yielding varieties of bread wheat. The study provides valuable insights for wheat breeding programs aimed at enhancing global nutrition security via genetic enhancement of grain yield of bread wheat.

Keywords: Combining ability, general combining ability and specific combining ability effects, gene action, line x tester analysis, bread wheat.

Sustainable Cultivation of Medicinal Plants through Organic Farming: Scope, Challenges, and Solutions.

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Abstract

Background: The chemical fertilizers and pesticides used in contemporary agriculture has many negative impacts on health of soils, humans, livestock and environment. Organic farming is a method that focuses on growing crops and raising livestock without the use of synthetic chemicals, fertilizers, or genetically modified organisms. The principles involve natural soil fertility, preservation of biodiversity, use of natural fertilizers and pest controls, etc.

Aim of the Study: To emphasize on the principles, processes, mechanisms, ingredients, available techniques, scope, challenges, and possible solution for economic, ecofriendly and sustainable medicinal plant cultivations.

Methodology: Adopted to review *Vrikshayurveda* literatures and current research related to organic farming which can be used in the cultivation of medicinal plants for achieving sustainable development goals.

Observation and Results: Crop rotation, intercrops, cover cropping, etc. are often practiced in organic farming techniques. It has a positive impact on the soil, the environment and ecosystem, quality products lead to organic brands having economic benefits. Increased demand for organic remedies and herbal products due to health consciousness creates a robust market for medicinal plants. Pharmaceutical products with high quality organic brands are in market demand both for plant products and medicinal formulations. Good health and wellbeing (SDG-3) is one of the SDGs declared by the UN in the year 2015 that is to be achieved by 2030. Organic farming is a sector which plays cross-sectorial roles in clean water, economic growth, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water and life below land under 17 SDGs. There are certain challenges that hinder the adoption of organic farming in the medicinal plant sector, like certification cost, market access, cost of organic manure and pest and weed management. Partnership collaboration, research and development, policy implementation and government support, holistic integration of traditional techniques described in *Vrikshayurveda*, etc. will open the bottleneck solution.

Conclusion: Organic farming of medicinal plants can thrive, contributing to both economic and environmental sustainability. It is a sustainable alternative to conventional agriculture, with multi component ecological benefits and market opportunities make a better choice for many farmers and consumers.

Keywords: Organic farming, Sustainable Development Goals, Intercrops, Vrikshayurveda.

Unlocking the potential of peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.) yield and quality through Induced Mutagenesis

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Abstract

Mentha piperita L., commonly known as peppermint, is valued for its essential oil, which is rich in menthol and has various applications. However, challenges such as low oil yield and poor oil quality have limited the potential of peppermint cultivation. This study aimed to develop a noble mutant of *Mentha piperita* that complements US-type peppermint oil, characterized by higher oil yield and improved oil quality, specifically targeting a menthol content of 36-46% and less than 5% menthofuran. Induced mutagenesis was achieved through gamma radiation, with seeds from a menthofuran-rich variety CIM-Indus of *Mentha piperita* subjected to varying doses (10 Gy, 20 Gy, 30 Gy, 40 Gy, 50 Gy, 70 Gy, 90 Gy, and 110 Gy). A broad range of diversity was observed among the resulting mutants, leading to the selection of improved lines. Notably, CIM-I452 exhibited the highest oil yield along with substantial herb yield, followed by CIM-I332 and CIM-I324. Lines CIM-I43, CIM-I44, CIM-I451, CIM-I32, CIM-I34, CIM-I332, and CIM-I452 were identified as menthol-rich, while CIM-I311 and CIM-I431 were menthofuran-rich. Additionally, CIM-I322 and CIM-I331 were recognized as limonene-rich lines. The mutants CIM-I452, CIM-I332, and CIM-I324 demonstrated high menthol content with low menthofuran levels, making them globally accepted. Based on essential oil quality, oil yield, and herb yield, the selected mutants CIM-I452, CIM-I332, and CIM-I324 show promise as parental lines for future recombinant breeding or hybridization efforts.

Keywords: *Mentha piperita*, Genetic diversity, Menthol, Menthofuran, Induced mutagenesis

Unlocking the potential of peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.) yield and quality through Induced Mutagenesis

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Abstract

Mentha piperita L., commonly known as peppermint, is valued for its essential oil, which is rich in menthol and has various applications. However, challenges such as low oil yield and poor oil quality have limited the potential of peppermint cultivation. This study aimed to develop a noble mutant of *Mentha piperita* that complements US-type peppermint oil, characterized by higher oil yield and improved oil quality, specifically targeting a menthol content of 36-46% and less than 5% menthofuran. Induced mutagenesis was achieved through gamma radiation, with seeds from a menthofuran-rich variety CIM-Indus of *Mentha piperita* subjected to varying doses (10 Gy, 20 Gy, 30 Gy, 40 Gy, 50 Gy, 70 Gy, 90 Gy, and 110 Gy). A broad range of diversity was observed among the resulting mutants, leading to the selection of improved lines. Notably, CIM-I452 exhibited the highest oil yield along with substantial herb yield, followed by CIM-I332 and CIM-I324. Lines CIM-I43, CIM-I44, CIM-I451, CIM-I32, CIM-I34, CIM-I332, and CIM-I452 were identified as menthol-rich, while CIM-I311 and CIM-I431 were menthofuran-rich. Additionally, CIM-I322 and CIM-I331 were recognized as limonene-rich lines. The mutants CIM-I452, CIM-I332, and CIM-I324 demonstrated high menthol content with low menthofuran levels, making them globally accepted. Based on essential oil quality, oil yield, and herb yield, the selected mutants CIM-I452, CIM-I332, and CIM-I324 show promise as parental lines for future recombinant breeding or hybridization efforts.

Keywords: *Mentha piperita*, Genetic diversity, Menthol, Menthofuran, Induced mutagenesis

Effect of Correlation and Path Analysis in Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.)

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Abstract

The present investigation was carried out in thirty-two genotypes of brinjal with a view to estimate the extent of variability, analysis of variance and genetic divergence. The experiment was conducted in Randomized Block Design with three replications at Department of Vegetable Science, Acharya Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Kumarganj, Ayodhya (U.P.), during Kharif, 2020-21. Each treatment consisted of twelve plants in two rows, having spacing of 60 cm x 50 cm with net plot size of 1.2 m x 3.00 m². The magnitudes of genotypic correlation were higher than the phenotypic correlation coefficients for all the character combinations. The most important trait, total fruit yield per plant had exhibited highly significant and positive phenotypic correlation with average fruit weight (0.747), number of fruits per plant (0.672) and fruit circumference (0.468) at both phenotypic and genotypic levels. Positive direct effect on total fruit yield was exerted by total sugars (0.474), average fruit weight (0.396), fruit circumference (0.358), number of fruits per plant (0.254), plant height (0.242), fruit polar length (0.194) and day to 50 % flowering (0.168). The higher magnitude of positive direct effect on total fruit yield was exerted by total sugars (0.474), average fruit weight (0.396), fruit circumference (0.358), number of fruits per plant (0.254), plant height (0.242), fruit polar length (0.194), day to 50 % flowering (0.168). High heritability coupled with high genetic advance were recorded for the traits viz. total fruit yield per plant, marketable fruit yield per plant, average fruit weight and number of primary branches, fruit length and fruit circumference. Thus, there exists ample genetic variability and as consequence scope of improvement in the available germplasm of brinjal.

Keyword: Brinjal, Genetic variability, Genetic Correlation and Path, Germplasm

Nutritional and Therapeutic Analysis of Sethura Laddu for Postpartum women

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Abstract

Background: Sethura laddu, a traditional Indian sweet consumed by postpartum women, particularly in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. A well-balanced nutrition is essential for a child's development which is starting from conception and extending through lactation, where maternal nourishment plays a significant role.

Aim of the study: This analysis aims to verify its role in supporting newly delivered mothers through nutritional and therapeutic perspectives.

Methodology: Sethura laddu is traditionally prepared recipe for recovery of postpartum, using a specific mixture of ingredients, including ginger powder, desiccated coconut, tikhur powder, deshi ghee, almonds, gond katira, cashews, raisins, sugar, moong dal powder, makhana, turmeric powder, chironji, and poppy seeds. A detailed nutritional analysis was performed to assess the nutritional composition which is beneficial for postpartum women. The study also included a review of the nutritional benefits.

Results: Nutritionally, the laddu provides a balanced combination of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates, contributing to its role in enhancing milk production, reducing back pain, and providing sustained energy. The iron content was quantified as 3.30 mg/100g through analysis. Key ingredients such as dry ginger, moong dal powder, tikhur powder, almonds, and deshi ghee are known for their beneficial effects on digestion, cardiovascular health, lactation, and overall postpartum recovery.

Conclusion: Sethura laddu is a nutrient-dense recipe with significant benefits for postpartum women. Its traditional formulation, supported by both historical usage and nutritional analysis, aids in lactation, energy provision, and ease postpartum discomfort. This study highlights the laddu's value as a dietary supplement for new mothers, combining traditional wisdom with nutritional science to support postpartum health and recovery.

Keywords: Nutrition, lactation, postpartum health, Sethura Laddu, traditional foods, maternal health, ayurvedic medicine.

Senna: An Excellent Laxative Herbal Medicine - Cultivation and Storage Strategies

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Abstract

Background: It is evident from the literature that 80% of the world's population depends on herbal drugs. Now-a-days, the herbs and herbal medicines are much effective for the treatment of varied disorders as they have minimal side effects as compared to the allopathic medicines. Nowadays, constipation is a common complaint and challenge for older and adults. Senna (*Cassia augustifolia*) is an ayurvedic herb more popularly known as *swarnapatri* in Sanskrit, widely used for its numerous benefits. The plant is mainly valued for its cathartic properties and is especially useful in habitual constipation. The pods and leaves contain anthraquinone glycosides that have a big laxative effect, besides its use as mild laxative, senna's other benefits include in the treatment of jaundice, hepatitis, herpes simplex, cracking of the skin, migraine headache, hair loss, and for relaxing muscle tension.

Aim: To cultivate and store Senna more and more due to its numerous Health Benefits.

Methodology: Cultivation of senna doesn't require much expense on irrigation, manuring, pesticides, protection and other pre- and post-harvesting care. About 20 Kg seeds are required to cover one hectare of land. This makes the plant a perfect crop for arid regions where water provision, wasteland development, desertification control, dune stabilization are the main challenges such as in Rajasthan.

Results: This prophetic herb is very beneficial for numerous health issues. The plant has been investigated for its various chemical constituents and pharmacological properties.

Conclusion: Given the profound health benefits and economic feasibility of *Cassia augustifolia*, there is a strong need to promote the cultivation and use of senna on a large scale. This will not only support the healthcare system but also provide environmentally sustainable crop options for areas facing agricultural challenges.

Keywords: Senna, Prophetic medicine, Anthraquinone glycosides, Laxative, Cultivation, Storage

Effects of Cadmium Exposure on the Morphology and Behaviour of Fresh Water Snakehead Fish, *Channa punctatus*

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Abstract

The presence of heavy metals in freshwater systems is a critical concern due to their toxic effects, persistence, and potential for bioaccumulation. This study examines the toxicity of cadmium in the freshwater fish species *Channa punctatus*. Common heavy metal pollutants include cadmium, nickel, arsenic, chromium, copper, mercury, zinc, and lead, all of which can severely harm various aquatic organisms. Cadmium naturally occurs in the Earth's crust alongside lead, copper, zinc, and nickel. It is also utilized in batteries, fertilizers, pesticides, coatings, and alloys. Cadmium can easily enter the atmosphere, bind to small particles, and contaminate soil or water, impacting fish, animals, and plants. This study aims to explore the relationship between mortality rates and the abnormal behavioral and morphological changes seen in *Channa punctatus* exposed to cadmium chloride.

The primary behavioral reactions noted during the experiment included erratic swimming, gulping air at the surface, loss of balance, lethargy, and fish lying on the water's surface before death. Additionally, morphological changes such as skin discoloration, pigmented patches on the body, scale shedding, chemical sedimentation, and increased mucus secretion were recorded in the exposed fish. The data indicated that *C. punctatus* is an effective bio-indicator for heavy metal contamination in freshwater environments. The accumulation of cadmium in fish can also lead to bioaccumulation in humans, potentially entering the food chain and destabilizing ecosystems. The results suggest that *Channa punctatus* can act as an effective bioindicator for heavy metal pollution in freshwater environments.

Keywords: Cadmium, toxicity, *Channa punctatus*, morphology, behavioural, ecosystems,

Antioxidant analysis and characterization of bioactive compounds from *Leptadenia pyrotechnica* Forssk. Decne

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Abstract

Background: *Leptadenia pyrotechnica* Forssk. Decne (LP) is a medicinal herb from the Asclepiadaceae family with many advantageous properties.

Aim of the study: The goal of this research is to identify, quantify, evaluate the antioxidant potential, and characterize the bioactive compounds from LP to validate its remarkable therapeutic advantages.

Methodology: Different LP extracts (hot Soxhlet extraction) were evaluated physiochemically to check their impurity, purity, and quality; qualitatively to detect different phytochemicals; and quantitatively for phenol, saponin, tannin, flavonoid, and alkaloid contents. Then, the *in vitro* antioxidant potential was estimated by DPPH, NO, H₂O₂ scavenging assays, and MC and FRAP assays. The most prevalent phytochemicals of LP were then analysed by AAS, FT-IR, UV-visible, and GC-MS techniques. The extraction methods (soxhlation or ultrasonication) were optimized by utilizing response surface methodology (RSM) to determine the impacts of multiple parameters.

Results and conclusions: A higher extractive yield was shown by LPSE and LPRE (7.37 ± 0.11 and 5.70 ± 0.02). The LP stem showed better physicochemical and qualitative results than the root. The findings of the quantitative analyses showed that, maximal quantity of TPC, TTC, and TAC were observed in the LPSE extract (996.24 ± 66.81 µg GA/50g dried extract; 997.11 ± 31.76 µg TA/50g dried extract, and 966.48 ± 24.51 µg TA/50g dried extract); TFC in LPSEA extract (791.43 ± 3.53 µg RUT/50g dried extract) of LP stem; and TSC was observed highest in the LPREA extract (846.24 ± 119.33 µg QJ/50g dried extract) of LP root respectively. The findings of the *in vitro* antioxidant activities showed that maximal antioxidant potential of DPPH (170.4 + 19.67 µg/ml), NO (70.9 ± 9.91 µg/ml), H₂O₂ (89.87 + 50.41 µg/ml), and MC (86.06 ± 42.67 µg/ml) were observed in LPSE extract, whereas FRAP (59.36 ± 0.02 µMFe(II)/g) in LPSCHE extract. The quantitative and *in vitro* antioxidant results indicated maximal phenols, tannins, and alkaloid contents in LPSE extract, which was further confirmed by UV-visible, FT-IR, and GC-MS results. Ultrasonication was selected over the hot Soxhlet extraction method via RSM. The study concluded that the plant has remarkable therapeutic advantages to promote additional clinical investigations and the mechanisms of its action.

Keywords: Antioxidants, FT-IR, GC-MS, *Leptadenia pyrotechnica*, UV-Visible, Soxhlet

Efficacy and Safety of Herbal Remedies in AYUSH: A Scientific Review

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Abstract

The efficacy and safety of herbal remedies in the AYUSH system (Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy) are gaining attention as these traditional practices become more integrated into modern healthcare. This review examines the scientific validation of herbal treatments, highlighting their therapeutic benefits and potential risks. Through an analysis of recent clinical studies and systematic reviews, we aim to illustrate the effectiveness of key herbal remedies in managing various health conditions, including diabetes, arthritis, and mental health issues. Additionally, the review addresses safety concerns, such as common side effects, contraindications, and the regulatory frameworks governing herbal medicine use. By synthesizing findings from pharmacological research and clinical applications, this study provides a comprehensive perspective on the role of herbal remedies in AYUSH. Ultimately, it underscores the need for ongoing research to enhance understanding and promote the safe integration of these remedies into contemporary medical practice, supporting holistic health and well-being.

Keywords: AYUSH, Herbal remedies, Pharmacological research, Therapeutic benefits, gaining attention

The Genetics of Obesity and its Management by Ayurveda

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Abstract

Obesity is a complex clinical challenge and a significant public health concern, driven by a mix of genetic, environmental, and multifactorial factors. Genetic stability plays a vital role in understanding metabolic disorders, including obesity. Physiological variations can affect gene structure and function, disrupting metabolic pathways and leading to obesity, a prevalent nutritional disease. Excess adipose tissue produces triglycerides in both essential and non-essential forms, with overweight status defined by excess body weight relative to height. This condition is linked to increased morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing nations, and is associated with co-morbidities such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, certain cancers, and premature death.

Monogenic obesity, resulting from rare genetic mutations, has been linked to over 150 cases involving 11 genes across 50 loci that follow Mendelian inheritance patterns. Key genes such as leptin (LEP), leptin receptor (LEPR), proopiomelanocortin (POMC), and melanocortin-4 receptor (MC4R) have been identified as significant contributors to this disorder.

While modern medical approaches have been explored for obesity management, they often fall short due to complications and varying efficacy. Conversely, Ayurvedic medicine offers a range of herbal treatments, including Agnimantha, Amalaki, Apamarga, Brahati, Chitraka, Daruharidra, Devadaru, Eranda, Gokshura, Guduchi, Guggulu and Hingu which have been utilized for their therapeutic potential. active set prediction of protein targets has been done. The Key genes such as leptin (LEP), leptin receptor (LEPR), proopiomelanocortin (POMC), and melanocortin-4 receptor (MC4R) has been run by the different in network pharmacology programs and found the key ingredients of these drugs having good docking score for giving highest medicinal value This study employs in silico methods and network pharmacology to evaluate the efficacy of these Ayurvedic plants in managing obesity. The findings suggest that these herbal remedies may provide significant benefits in addressing obesity, highlighting their potential as adjunct therapies in contemporary obesity management.

Keywords: Obesity, Adipose cell, Genomic stability, Ayurveda, Ayurvedic plants, proopiomelanocortin

Standardization of *Apamarga (Achyranthes aspera Linn.) Ksharodaka*

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Abstract

Apāmārga (*Achyranthes aspera* Linn.) is an important medicinal plant in Ayurveda, revered for its versatile therapeutic properties. This study aimed to standardize Apāmārga Kṣārodaka through modern analytical techniques to establish its safety, efficacy, and quality. The research included detailed phytochemical analyses, stability testing, and an in vivo excision wound model using male Wistar rats. Analytical methods comprised pH measurement, TLC, FTIR, XRD, UV spectroscopy, HRMS, and microbial studies to assess the composition, purity, and stability of Kṣārodaka. The results revealed that Apāmārga Kṣārodaka has a high pH (12.75) and contains essential minerals like calcium, magnesium, and iron, indicating its suitability for wound healing. It demonstrated significant antimicrobial activity, especially against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and showed no toxic heavy metals within safe limits. In vivo studies confirmed its efficacy, with improved wound contraction and faster epithelialization compared to controls. Histopathological assessments indicated no adverse effects, confirming its safety. In-silico molecular docking identified homovanillic acid and biochanin A as bioactive components, binding effectively with proteins linked to wound healing. The shelf-life study indicated that Apāmārga Kṣārodaka remains stable for up to 9 months under accelerated conditions. These findings validate the Ayurvedic principles behind Apāmārga Kṣārodaka and support its potential for use in modern wound care, highlighting the need for continued research and application.

Keywords: Apāmārga Kṣārodaka, standardization, wound healing, phytochemical analysis, epithelialization

Synergistic effect of N-substituted pyrrolidinium based-ionic liquids on nisin: Strategy to combat bacterial resistance

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Abstract

Antibiotic resistance is one of the biggest threats to global health, food security, and development today. Antibiotic resistance occurs naturally, but misuse of antibiotics in humans and animals is accelerating the process. Antibiotic resistance leads to longer hospital stays, higher medical costs, and increased mortality. Considerable attention has been directed towards finding new alternative antibiotics to counter bacterial resistance, leading to longer hospital stays, higher medical costs, and increased mortality. A suitable solution for these problems is found by using ionic liquids (ILs). ILs have gained considerable global attention due to their diverse applications in various fields of chemical sciences. Since the past few decades, they have attracted significant attention from researchers owing to their unique physicochemical properties such as low vapour pressure, recyclability, non-volatility, and non-combustibility. Though the toxicity of ILs is the most debated topic in their applications as therapeutic agent; several efforts are being made to afford ILs with a balance between their toxicity and application. Therefore, the present study involves the synthesis of novel antimicrobial pyrrolidinium-based-ILs with varied hydrophobicity that are less toxic than imidazolium and pyridinium-based-ILs. The present study involves the non-covalent coupling of Nisin (Nis), an antimicrobial peptide with a series of synthesized less toxic pyrrolidinium-based ionic liquids (ILs) for which an MTT assay was performed. The antibacterial results of conjugates showed remarkable improvement in the MIC value as compared to MEL and ILs alone against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. In addition, hemocompatibility results suggested good selectivity of the non-covalent conjugate as a potential antibiotic agent.

Keywords: antibiotics, MTT assay, resistance, ionic liquid, peptide, non-combustibility

Pharmacognostical and physicochemical evaluation of leaves of *Lajjalu* (*Mimosa pudica* Linn.)

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Abstract

Introduction: Lajjalu, (*Mimosa pudica* Linn.) belonging to the family Mimosaceae commonly known as the "sensitive plant" or "touch-me-not," is a herbaceous plant widely recognized for its unique response to physical stimuli. Traditionally, it has been utilized in various medicinal practices due to its reputed therapeutic properties, including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects. Additionally, investigating the physicochemical properties of the plant provides insight into its chemical composition, stability, and potential applications in pharmaceutical formulations.

Materials and methods: Lajjalu leaves were collected from Thrissur District, Kerala, thoroughly cleaned, and shade-dried. Once fully dried, they were powdered using machinery. Macroscopical and microscopical analysis, along with physicochemical analysis were carried out in accordance with API guidelines.

Results: The leaves of Lajjalu are green, bipinnate, sensitive to touch, and fold when disturbed. Microscopic examination of the transverse section of Lajjalu (*Mimosa pudica*) leaves revealed calcium crystals in the central midrib. A single layer of upper and lower epidermis was observed, with some cells showing enlargement. Small vascular bundles were present at the center, surrounded by a sclerenchymatous layer. The lamina region exhibited a single layer of palisade cells extending into the midrib area, while the spongy cells in the lower lamina were loosely arranged. Physicochemical analysis showed moisture content of 10.88%, water-soluble extractive value of 5.62%, alcohol-soluble extractive value of 5.16%, petroleum ether-soluble extractive value of 0.88%, and a pH of 5.57.

Conclusion: The pharmacognostic and physicochemical screening of Lajjalu(*Mimosa pudica*) will offer reference information to ensure the quality, purity, and identification of the plant.

Keywords: Lajjalu, Microscopy, Pharmacognostic, Physicochemical analysis, sclerenchymatous

Effect of Mantra Therapy on Feto-maternal Well-Being

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Abstract

Introduction: Mantra therapy, an ancient Vedic practice, involves the repetitive chanting or listening to sacred sounds, believed to harmonize mind, body, and spirit. This review examines the available literature on mantra therapy's physiological and psychological effects during pregnancy.

Materials and Methods: A systematic review of peer-reviewed articles, clinical trials, and traditional Ayurvedic texts was conducted using PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases. Studies focusing on mantra therapy's effect on maternal mental health, pregnancy outcomes, and fetal development were included.

Results: Evidence suggests that mantra therapy reduces maternal stress, anxiety, and depression through its calming effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and enhancement of parasympathetic nervous system activity. Improved maternal physiological parameters, such as heart rate and blood pressure, were commonly reported. Studies also indicate better fetal heart rate variability (FHRV), higher birth weights, and improved neonatal APGAR scores in mothers practicing mantra therapy.

Conclusion: The therapeutic effects of mantra therapy are likely mediated through neurophysiological mechanisms involving relaxation and stress reduction. Mantra therapy shows potential as a culturally integrated, non-invasive intervention for enhancing feto-maternal well-being.

Keywords: Mantra therapy, Feto-maternal well-being, Prenatal care, Maternal stress, Fetal development.

A Comprehensive Review of Sal Tree (*Shorea Robusta* Gaertn.)

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Abstract

The Sal tree (*Shorea robusta* Gaertn), known as Shala, Indian Dammer, and Holy tree, holds significant cultural and medicinal importance in Ayurvedic medicine. This comprehensive review explores the various therapeutic applications, botany, phytochemical constituents and traditional uses of the Sala tree within the framework of Ayurveda. Through an extensive analysis of ancient texts and modern scientific literature, the review highlights the tree's rich pharmacological profile, including its analgesic, anticancer, anticonvulsant, anti-diabetic, anti-hyperlipidemic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antipyretic, antiulcer, immunomodulatory, wound healing activity, etc. In Ayurveda, bark resin and leaves of *S. robusta* were used to cure itching, leprosy, gonorrhoea, wounds and stomach ulcers, disease of the vagina, cough, pain in ear and head. It is used as an anthelmintic, alexeteric, enriching the blood, preventing sweating, improving the complexion etc. The phytochemical studies have shown the presence of many secondary metabolites belonging to terpenoids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, lignans, phenols and sterols. The present review is, therefore, an effort to give a detailed survey of the literature on its traditional, pharmacognosy, phytochemistry and pharmacological uses. The outcome of these studies will further expand the existing therapeutic potential of *S. robusta* and provide convincing support for its future clinical use in modern medicine.

Keywords: Shala, Ayurvedic medicine, secondary metabolites, phytochemistry.

Tracking Malaria: Surveillance, Identification, and Vector Mapping of Anopheles Mosquitoes in Muzaffarpur

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Abstract

Aim: The *Anopheles sub pictus* species complex is an important malaria vector across several regions, including India. Accurate identification and characterization of its members are essential for effective vector surveillance and malaria control. This study aims to investigate the Morphologically different species within the *Anopheles* complex to improve species-level identification, particularly in the context of vector surveillance for malaria control programs.

Methods: The study employed Entomological Key Based Morphological identification and molecular techniques, including DNA barcoding and PCR amplification of specific genetic markers, to distinguish between cryptic species within the complex. The cytological analysis involved polytene chromosome banding patterns to identify species-specific traits. Field samples of *Anopheles subpictus* were collected from high-malaria-risk regions, and morphological characteristics were cross-referenced with molecular and cytological data for confirmation.

Results: The molecular analysis successfully differentiated multiple cryptic species within the *Anopheles subpictus* complex, some of which were previously misidentified through traditional morphological methods. Cytological studies further confirmed the presence of chromosomal variations that corresponded with molecular findings. The study identified specific species as primary malaria vectors in the region, highlighting the need for targeted vector control strategies.

Conclusion: This study underscores the importance of integrating molecular and cytological approaches in the surveillance of malaria vectors, particularly cryptic species like *Anopheles* vectors. The findings provide a better understanding of the distribution and vector potential of each member of the *Anopheles subpictus* complex, aiding in designing more efficient malaria prevention programs.

Keywords: Malaria, *Anopheles*, Entomology, Chromosomes, Vector Control.

Understanding the shade-stress tolerance in *Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek, under agroforestry systems for higher production and developing food-based medications

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Abstract

Green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) is an important pulse in India, known for its easily digestible, high-quality proteins (20–32%), total carbohydrates (53.3–67.1%), lipids (0.71–1.85%), dietary fibres, several minerals and bioactive compounds. Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, phenols, glycosides, and bioactive peptides possess a range of important pharmaceutical properties, including anti-inflammatory, antinociceptive, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, lipid metabolism regulation, antihypertensive, antiallergic, and antitumor effects. Due to its high nutritional content and various phytochemicals and antioxidants, it thrusts the further research into its medicinal properties and potential use as an effective food additive for various dietary supplements or food-based medications discovery and development. It's a high preferred legume crop by farmers as it's a drought tolerant and short duration crop suitable for cultivation during *kharif*, *rabi* and *summer* seasons either as sole crop, intercrop or under agroforestry. Although, agroforestry is currently a most viable and potential solution available for restoration and resilience of cropland ecosystems and sustainable crop productivity by keeping all the climatic challenges in mind. However, the canopy of perennial trees directly limits the light interception to understory crops, resulting in the poor light availability or shade stress which certainly restrict the growth and productivity. Understanding the mechanisms of shade stress tolerance is essential for breeding tolerant biofortified cultivars for higher secondary metabolite production. Recent next generation sequencing and omics-based molecular interventions particularly transcriptomics and metabolomics and transgenics would certainly elucidate the underlying physiological mechanisms, molecular pathways and candidate gene sequences for improving shade-stress adaption and biofortification in green gram for developing the shade tolerant and bioactive compound and antioxidant rich cultivars in the future for enhancing its area and production under agroforestry and developing food-based medications.

Keywords: Green gram, Shade-stress, Agroforestry, Transcriptomics, Metabolomics, Food-based medications

Mainstreaming the Biodiversity in to health sector

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Abstract

Biodiversity provides important resources for traditional and modern drug discovery. Traditional medicine continues to play an essential role in health care, and estimated to be used by 60% of world's population. Many modern synthetic drugs have their origin in bio-actives from natural products. 67% of chemotherapy drugs have a natural origin.

Modern drugs are mostly derived from wild species and as of now one million plant and animal species are threatened with extinction because of climate change, habitat loss, farming, poaching, pollution, invasive species etc., Biodiversity loss also means that we are losing, before discovery of many nature's chemicals and genes, of kind that have already provided humankind with enormous health benefits.

Biodiversity and human-health are linked in many ways and CBD/WHO has identified six biodiversity and health topics: water; food and nutrition; diseases; medicines; physical, mental and cultural dimensions of health; adaptation to climate-change. Health is fundamental human-right and key indicator of sustainable development, and has central place in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) agenda, with Goal-3 calling on all stakeholders to “ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all at all ages”. Over last decade, multiplicity and complexity of linkages between biodiversity and human-health have been increasingly recognized.

Biodiversity loss and ecosystem change can increase risk of emergence or spread of infectious diseases in animals, plants and humans, including economically important livestock diseases, zoonotic outbreaks and global pandemics. COVID-19 pandemic highlights urgency of addressing biodiversity crisis and need for transformative change.

Conclusion: Biodiversity is the foundation for human health and continuing loss of biodiversity on a global scale represents direct threat to human health. By strengthening collaboration with health sector and mainstreaming biodiversity and health linkages into national strategies policies, programmes, we can improve our understanding of the complex linkages between biodiversity, ecosystem services and human-health and promote co-benefits through more integrated policies and implementation activities.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Human Health, Pandemics, Mainstreaming, SDGs

Role of *Suvarnaprashana* (Gold Electuary) in Children with Cerebral Palsy: An overview

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Abstract

Background: Cerebral palsy (CP) is defined as a nonprogressive neuromotor disorder of cerebral origin caused by insult or injury to developing brain during its early stage of development. CP is an umbrella term encompassing a group of nonprogressive, noncontagious condition that causes motor impairment by abnormalities in movement, posture, and tone. It can be caused by any of prenatal, natal, and postnatal factors and eventual pathology is any type of injury to the developing brain. CP is a lifelong physical disability as a consequence of upper motor neuron impairment, and it affects 1.5–2.5 children per 1000 live births with an estimated prevalence of 17 million people globally. *Suvarnaprashana* (oral administration of gold as electuary) is a unique practice documented in Ayurveda for child healthcare. Kashyapa Samhita, an authoritative textbook of Ayurvedic pediatrics, describes *Suvarnaprashana* (SP) under the context of *Lehana* (electuaries). For SP, gold *Bhasma* is triturated along with honey and *ghrita* (clarified *butter*) and the mixture is licked to the child.

Aim of the study: This review documents and evaluates the potential of SP in the management of CP with a special focus on its mechanisms of action in regulating different domains of problems in these children.

Methodology: The evidence of multidimensional functions of this ayurvedic electuary is drawn from published studies that have used in vitro and in vivo experimental methods and clinical studies.

Conclusion: This review proposes that the benefits of SP can be achieved at multiple levels as a general health promoter and in specific to enhancement of intelligence, digestion, metabolism, immunity and physical strength wsr to CP. SP improves the *agni* (digestion and metabolism), *medha* (cognition) and *bala* (Strength and immune status). It possesses subtle effects through multiple mechanisms and bio chemical targets, collectively leading to substantial health benefits in CP children. The study indicates that SP has potential for management of CP children and can thereby improves the quality of life by multidimensional benefits.

Keywords: Ayurveda, gold preparation, immunomodulator, *Swarnaprashana*, ayurvedic electuary

Bringing Nature to Indian Cities to Harness Nature-Based Solutions (Nbss) Amid Changing Climate: Insights on Bridging the Policy-Practice Gap

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Abstract

The process of urban transformation and changing climate is posing a substantial threat to human life and the entire human-urban system. Climate induced extreme-events have made India the 7th most climate change affected country in the world. The large urban demography including the vast majority of vulnerable and marginalized communities living in cities makes the country even more vulnerable to climate impacts. Among the many solutions (e.g. technological, social, etc.) for climate impact mitigation and adaptation, nature-based solutions (NBS) have been found to be one of the innovative solutions to build resilience against changing climate by offering a wide range of ecosystem services. However, this urban nature is severely threatened due to land-use change and hence, instead of harnessing the potential of urban nature in building resilience, cities are losing these natural components and becoming more vulnerable. Against this backdrop, this study aims to investigate the challenges of realising the potential of nature-based solutions (NbSs) in Indian cities and to provide recommendations to bridge the policy-practice gap for using nature-based solutions (NBS) for urban sustainability. The study found that urban nature can mitigate the effects of heat stress and Indian cities are gradually realizing its importance. However, urban nature is threatened during land transformation and is still a vulnerable land use category. Indian urban policies and plans are yet to strategically integrate nature as critical infrastructure and NBS to build climate resilience. This study advocates the strategic integration of nature-based solutions (NBS) into urban policies and planning in India, as there is an urgent need to build climate resilience.

Keywords: nature-based solutions (NbSs); climate change; adaptation; resiliency; Indian cities.

A Novel Sulforaphane Analog Inhibits PI3K/Akt Mediated GSK3 β and NRF-2 Signalling and Triggers ROS-Mediated Caspase-Independent Apoptosis in Human Cancer Cells

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Abstract

In today's era of remarkable technological advancements and social progress, cancer remains one of the most prevalent diseases and is the second leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. While chemotherapy, radiation, and immunotherapy are considered the gold standards for cancer treatment, they often come with significant toxicity. Therefore, there is a pressing need to develop alternative therapeutic strategies, particularly through the chemical modification of compounds derived from natural sources or by conjugating various compounds via pharmacophores, with the ultimate goal of enhancing efficacy while minimizing toxicity.

Sulforaphane, a naturally occurring isothiocyanate, has garnered attention for its impressive anticancer properties. In light of this, a series of sulforaphane analogs were designed, synthesized, and evaluated for their cytotoxic effects against various murine and human cancer cell lines. Among these, compound **4a** emerged as the most potent, demonstrating high cytotoxicity against cancer cells while exhibiting low toxicity toward normal cell lines.

Our study established that the lead compound induces reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated mitochondrial dysfunction and promotes apoptosis. The inhibition of cell proliferation was associated with evidence of G2/M phase arrest, and the Bax/Bcl-2 ratio indicated mitochondrial dysfunction. Additionally, the compound was found to interact with IGFR1, effectively blocking the PI3K/Akt pathway. Molecular docking and western blot analyses provided further insights into these mechanisms. Notably, compound **4a** suppressed NRF-2 protein expression, resulting in an increase in ROS levels within tumor cells. Moreover, compound **4a** induced ROS-mediated caspase-independent apoptosis as confirmed by western blot analysis.

Moreover, compound **4a** induced ROS-mediated, caspase-independent apoptosis, as confirmed by western blot analysis. The efficacy of this lead compound was further validated in a 4T1-injected Balb/C syngeneic tumor model, where it demonstrated significant inhibitory effects.

This study elucidates the mechanistic pathways through which compound **4a** exerts its cytotoxic effects in cancer cells. As a novel sulforaphane analog, compound **4a** acts as an antagonist of the IGFR1 receptor, inhibits the PI3K/Akt and NRF-2 pathways, and promotes apoptosis via ROS generation in a caspase-independent manner.

Keywords: Sulforaphane, ROS, apoptosis, Nrf-2, IGF R1, PI3K/Akt, Caspase.

Antipyrine Derivatives and its Biological Evaluation

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Abstract

Antipyrine, also pyrazolone is a five membered heterocyclic ring which consist of two nitrogen atoms and a ketonic group. A number of researchers evident that this molecule has several biological actions like anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidepressant, antitubercular, analgesic, anticonvulsant, anthelmintic, antioxidant, cytotoxic and antiviral activities. Among the pyrazolone derivatives, 4-aminoantipyrine is capable to gives diverse types of Schiff-bases with carbonyl compounds with specific aldehydes or ketones. These compounds are considered as bioactive compounds having good potential in pharmacological, biological, clinical and analytical applications.

In our lab, we synthesized several prototypes of 4-aminoantipyrine derivatives and its metal complexes. These derivatives have been characterised by Mass, NMR, and IR spectroscopy. 4-AAP derivative and its complexes have been biologically evaluated for anti-diabetic activity. They have shown a significant role for anti-diabetic activity. Most of them have shown moderate to good potential. Prototypes of synthesized compounds and its metal complexes are shown below.

Keywords- 4-aminoantipyrine, anti-diabetic, researchers evident, pyrazolone, anthelmintic

Characterization of pearl millet germplasm for morpho-biochemical traits

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Abstract

Pearl millet is a resilient crop cultivated in arid regions, offering food security and nutritional benefits. This study assessed the diversity among 30 pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) germplasm, cultivated during the Kharif season of 2023–2024, for agronomic and biochemical traits under drought and heat stress conditions. Morphological evaluation revealed a significant range in grain yield (2.14 to 4.44 kg/net plot), dry fodder yield (5.00 to 11.50 kg/net plot), days to 50% flowering (34 to 48 days), and plant height (177 to 280 cm). Biochemical analysis showed variations in protein content (9.2% to 11.5%), total soluble sugars (1.4 to 2.6 g/100 g), total phenolic content (20.14 to 34.78 mg/100 g), and DPPH radical scavenging activity (44.18% to 54.89%). Germplasm such as HHB 299 and Dhanshakti exhibited superior performance in yield, drought tolerance, and enhanced nutritional properties, including higher protein and antioxidant content. The observed genetic diversity underscores the potential of these germplasm in breeding programs aimed at developing climate-resilient and nutritionally fortified pearl millet cultivars. These efforts are crucial for improving food security and public health in drought-prone regions.

Key words: Pearl millet; Drought tolerance; Heat stress; Biochemical analysis; Morphological evaluation

Evaluation of *Trichoderma viride* for control of fusarium wilt and growth promotion in tomato plants

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Abstract

Trichoderma spp. are widely recognized as eco-friendly bioagents, offering dual benefits of disease suppression and plant growth promotion. Their role as biopesticides and biostimulants has been well-established in managing plant diseases caused by both biotic and abiotic stresses. Fusarium wilt, caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL), leads to significant yield losses in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) crops. Biological control using antagonistic strains of *Trichoderma* offers a sustainable alternative to chemical pesticides for combating soil-borne pathogens. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *Trichoderma viride* in controlling fusarium wilt and explore the relationship between disease incidence and plant growth-promoting properties of this bioagent. Tomato seedlings treated with different concentrations of *Trichoderma viride*, applied as a seedling dip, were compared to untreated, FOL-inoculated controls. The application of *Trichoderma viride* at 10 g/liter water resulted in the lowest disease incidence, enhanced physiological activity, increased biochemical and antioxidant levels, improved phosphate solubilization, and superior root and shoot growth, leading to higher yields. These findings suggest that *Trichoderma viride* can be a valuable antifungal bioagent for controlling fusarium wilt while enhancing plant growth and yield in commercial tomato production.

Keywords: Biological control, biopesticide, fusarium wilt, growth promotion, *Trichoderma viride*,

Hempseed (*cannabis sativa*) Based Therapeutics Against Experimental Hypercholesterolemia and Inflammatory Pathologies

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Abstract

Hypercholesterolemia (HC), i.e., elevated cholesterol or lipid levels in the body, is one of the key risk factors in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), besides other metabolic and inflammatory conditions. A myriad of genetic, environmental, and nutritional factors contribute to the hypercholesterolemia-associated pathological effects due to the exacerbation of ROS-mediated oxidative stress and inflammation culminating in chronic inflammatory conditions like atherosclerosis. Thus, preventive/therapeutic strategies aimed to combat these inflammatory pathways in a redox-regulatory manner might be effective against pathophysiological conditions associated with HC. A Plethora of management strategies, such as lifestyle and dietary modifications, as well as the use of drugs such as statins, NSAIDs etc, are recommended. However, scientific evidence indicating associated side effects and toxicity with the use of these drugs limits their use. It warrants the exploration of better management strategies against HC-associated physiological insults. In this context, omega-3 fatty acids have demonstrated favorable effects against cardiovascular inflammation, arrhythmias, thrombosis, and elevated blood pressure. The major dietary sources of these omega-3 fatty acids are seafood and plant oils such as canola, soybean, and hempseeds. Hempseeds, as a rich source of all the essential amino acids and gamma-linolenic acid, demonstrate significant health benefits and pharmacological activities. Therefore, the current study is designed to screen hempseed and hempseed-based nanoparticles for their therapeutic potential in experimental cholesterol-rich High-fat diet (HFD)-induced model of HC as well as DNBS-induced experimental colitis models. In both the models, hempseed lipid extract (HEMP) and hempseed-based nanoparticles demonstrated potential *in vitro* and *in vivo* redox modulatory activities. There was a significant decrease in LDL/HDL ratio, Triglycerides, and cholesterol levels. Further anti-inflammatory, anti-hypercholesterolemic, and cardio-protective properties of HEMP were also shown and validated using morphological and histopathological examinations of the tissues. Finally, the expression profiles of pro and anti-inflammatory factors indicated the molecular mechanism being regulated by hempseed responsible for its pro-resolution effects. Although the current study demonstrates the therapeutic potential of green pharmaceuticals against various pathological conditions, detailed studies are warranted to gain insight into the modulatory effects of such phytochemicals, including hemp seed.

Keywords: Hempseed, Hypercholesterolemia, Colitis, nanoparticles, Inflammation, oxidative stress

Urban wastewater quality assessment for its sustainable management

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Abstract

Urban wastewater generation is increasing with extensive urbanization and led to affect the water quality of receiving water bodies including river, lake and marine ecosystem. Most of the rivers of India are getting polluted due to continuous discharge of untreated or partially treated urban sewage and deteriorate the quality of rivers. Urban sewage with high biological oxygen demand (BOD) and high concentration of nutrients (N&P) changes water quality of receiving aquatic environment by reducing the dissolved oxygen and promoting the overgrowth of aquatic weeds which further deteriorate the wastewater quality. Therefore, assessment of wastewater quality of urban sewage including the organic load and concentration of nitrate and phosphate is essential to categorize the wastewater into highly and moderately polluted to opt appropriate option for sustainable treatment and reuse for health and environmental safety. Using efficient aquatic plants could be a sustainable option for nutrient recovery and reducing organic load from urban sewage having high organic load and nutrients (N&P) through different phyto-techniques for safe disposal and waste management. However, urban sewage having moderate organic load and nutrients concentration may be recommended for reuse for irrigation purposes.

Keywords: Sewage, Nutrients, Phytoremediation, Recycle, Algal bloom, Water treatment

Targeting Dephospho Coenzyme A Kinase (DPCK) in *Leishmania donovani*: Discovery and Validation of steroidal alkaloids as Potent Anti-Leishmanial drugs

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Abstract

Leishmaniasis, commonly known as "kala-azar," remains a critical health challenge in India, indicated by rising drug resistance among parasites. In our research, we targeted the Dephosphocoenzyme A kinase (LdDPCK) of *Leishmania donovani* to inhibit Coenzyme A synthesis, aiming to eliminate the parasite. Using molecular docking and simulations, Veratramine and Hupehenine were screened from a natural products database, which was demonstrated by strong binding affinities for LdDPCK. These *in-silico* findings were further verified by *in-vitro* assays, which revealed that IC₅₀ of Hupehenine and Veratramine as $7.34 \pm 0.37 \mu\text{M}$ and $12.46 \pm 2.28 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. Through a series of *in-vivo* validations, we confirmed that the inhibitory effects of Hupehenine and Veratramine are primarily mediated through the induction of autophagy, a cellular process where cells degrade and recycle their components. Unlike other drugs, which show typical cell death by apoptosis, evidence indicates cell death involving autophagy, which was further assisted using CYTO-ID staining. This study shows the potential of Veratramine and Hupehenine as effective anti-leishmanial agents and attributes the importance of DPCK as a drug target against Visceral Leishmaniasis. Our conclusions are supported by flow cytometry, which confirmed the absence of apoptosis markers; ultrastructural imaging, which provided visual evidence of toxicity; and fluorescence imaging, which highlighted the visual evidence of autophagic vacuole formation. Furthermore, the upregulation of ATG genes, revealed by real-time PCR, provides molecular confirmation of autophagy induction. This study identifies steroidal alkaloids, Veratramine and Hupehenine as potent inhibitors of the LdDPCK enzyme, providing a new mechanistic insight into their action through autophagy-mediated cell death. These findings pave the way for developing novel therapeutic strategies against Visceral Leishmaniasis, particularly in overcoming the challenge of drug resistance in *Leishmania* parasites.

Keywords: *Leishmania donovani*, Visceral Leishmaniasis, Dephospho-coenzyme A kinase, Hupehenine, Veratramine, Autophagy

Synthesis, Antimycotic and Antileishmanial Potential of Some New Derivatives 1,3,4-Oxadiazole and 1,2,4-Triazole

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Abstract

Methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate on reaction with 2-methylbenzyl chloride resulted in 4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) benzoate which on hydrazinolysis gave 4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) benzoyl hydrazine. Benzoyl hydrazine on reaction with potassium isopropyl xanthate in isopropyl alcohol resulted in 5-(4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol. Benzoyl hydrazine when treated with phenylisothiocyanate, gave 1-(4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) benzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide which underwent cyclization in the presence of sodium hydroxide to give 5-(4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) phenyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol. Both oxadiazole and triazole on reaction with amines in the presence of formaldehyde, substituted aralkyl halides and aroyl halides gave N-aminomethylated, S-alkylated and s-arylated oxadiazoles and triazoles. The structures of the compounds have been elucidated with help of elemental and spectral (IR, NMR and Mass) analysis. Compounds have been evaluated for their antimycotic potential against human pathogenic fungi and *Leishmania donovani* causal organism of Leishmaniasis.

Keywords: oxadiazole, triazole, antimycotic potential, antileishmanial potential, aroyl halides

"Integrating Ancient and Modern Approaches in Soil Remediation: A Comparative Analysis"

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Abstract

Introduction: Soil contamination is a significant environmental concern, worsened by industrial waste, heavy metals, and agricultural chemicals. Both ancient Ayurvedic practices and modern scientific methods offer solutions for soil detoxification. This study evaluates the effectiveness, benefits, and limitations of traditional soil purification methods in comparison to modern approaches, including physical, chemical, and bioremediation techniques.

Methods: A detailed review of Vedic and Ayurvedic texts was conducted to explore natural remedies, for soil detoxification. These were compared with modern remediation techniques, including soil washing, chemical oxidation, and bioremediation. The study evaluates the environmental impact, cost-effectiveness, flexibility, and long-term sustainability of both approaches.

Results: Ancient methods, such as the use of natural remedies are eco-friendly, inexpensive, and align with natural soil processes. However, these techniques are often slow and less effective for heavily polluted soils. Modern methods, such as soil washing and chemical oxidation, offer quicker results and can handle severe contamination but are resource-intensive, expensive, and may introduce secondary pollutants into the environment.

Discussion: Traditional remedies emphasize sustainability and harmony with natural systems, making them suitable for long-term, low-impact remediation. However, their slow effectiveness and limited ability to address large-scale contamination pose significant challenges. Modern techniques, while efficient and scalable, can be costly and potentially harmful due to their reliance on chemicals and machinery. Integrating both approaches could provide a balanced strategy, using Ayurvedic methods for long-term maintenance and modern techniques for initial intensive detoxification.

Conclusion: Traditional soil remediation techniques offer sustainable, low-cost solutions, but modern methods provide the efficiency required for severe contamination. A combined approach could optimize soil health restoration, ensuring environmental safety and sustainability.

Keywords: Ayurveda, soil remediation, phytoremediation, chemical oxidation, sustainable agriculture.

A Survey on Traditional Medicines Used By Different Tribal Communities of Sonbhadra District of Uttar Pradesh for Various Diseases Related to Digestive System

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Abstract

Introduction: Sonbhadra is the second largest district of Uttar Pradesh by area. It is the only district in India which borders four states namely MP, Chhattisgarh, Bihar and Jharkhand. This district has eight blocks- Babhani, Chatra, Chopan, Duddhi, Ghorawal, Myorpur, Nagwan and Robertsganj. About 83.12% population of this district lives in rural areas. Nature is integrated part of their life. These tribes having distinct culture, values and practices hold on their traditional knowledge which is transmitted only to people belonging to their clan. The present study is designed to explore the traditional medicine used for various diseases related to digestive system by different tribal communities of Sonbhadra district of Uttar Pradesh.

Objectives: To find out the ethnobotanical knowledge of different tribal communities of Myorpur and Chopan block of Sonbhadra district of Uttar Pradesh; related to cure of various diseases related to digestive system like anorexia, dyspepsia, constipation, jaundice, piles, fissure, fistula, gastric ulcer, diarrhoea, dysentery, abdominal colic etc. . 2. Collection of medicinal plants used by tribes for various digestive disorders and their botanical identification in lab.

Methodology: It is a survey study in which primary and secondary data has been collected. Primary data was collected by interview of participants; collection of medicinal plants used by tribes for the treatment of various diseases related to digestive system like anorexia, dyspepsia, constipation, jaundice, piles, fissure, fistula, gastric ulcer, diarrhoea, dysentery, abdominal colic etc. and their botanical identification in lab. Audio and visual aids (camera and mobile) was used to take photographs and videos related to the present study. Secondary data was collected by related books and previous researches.

Result: Many of the plants used by different tribal communities of Sonbhadra for the treatment of diseases related to digestive system like anorexia, dyspepsia, diarrhoea, dysentery, jaundice and many other related conditions. There are many plants which are known by different vernacular names by different tribal communities. Some of the plants used by them are –GhÍkuÉwÁra (*Aloe barbadensis* miller.), JaÉgalÍ PiyÁja (*Urginea indica* Kunth), Àmla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn.), Harre (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), BaheÕÁ (*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb.), Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.), CitÁ (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.), KaÉÓkarejÍ (*Caesalpinia bonducella* (L.) Roxb.), SÁkhu (*Shorea robusta* Gaertn.), SÁnana (*Ougenia oogeinensis* (Roxb.), JÁmuna (*Syzygium cumini* Linn. Skeels), KantelÍ / ChaulÁÍ (*Amaranthus spinosus* Linn.), LunÕiÁrÁ (*Bigonia picta* Sm.), LasoÕÁ (*Cordia dichotoma* forst.f.), Salai (*Boswellia serrata* Roxb.Ex Colebr), KoilÁra (*Bauhinia purpurea* Linn.), KaÕhmahulÍ / KachnÁla (*Bauhinia racemosa* Lamk.), HardÍ (*Dalbergia lanceolaria* Linn.f.), BijaysÁla (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.), Sihora (*Streblus asper* Lour.) etc.

Conclusion: Tribal communities of Sonbhadra have Unique life style and culture. Their Knowledge about herbs related to cure of digestive system diseases like anorexia, dyspepsia, diarrhoea, dysentery, jaundice and many other related conditions are very effective and unique. There is need to explore their knowledge globally and to establish it on scientific basis.

Keywords: Ethnobotanical, Digestive disorders, medicinal plants, anorexia

Pharmacognostical and physicochemical evaluation of leaves of *Lajjalu* (*Mimosa pudica* Linn.)

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Abstract

Introduction: Lajjalu, (*Mimosa pudica* Linn.) belonging to the family Mimosaceae commonly known as the "sensitive plant" or "touch-me-not," is a herbaceous plant widely recognized for its unique response to physical stimuli. Traditionally, it has been utilized in various medicinal practices due to its reputed therapeutic properties, including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects. Additionally, investigating the physicochemical properties of the plant provides insight into its chemical composition, stability, and potential applications in pharmaceutical formulations.

Materials and methods: Lajjalu leaves were collected from Thrissur District, Kerala, thoroughly cleaned, and shade-dried. Once fully dried, they were powdered using machinery. Macroscopical and microscopical analysis, along with physicochemical analysis were carried out in accordance with API guidelines.

Results: The leaves of Lajjalu are green, bipinnate, sensitive to touch, and fold when disturbed. Microscopic examination of the transverse section of Lajjalu (*Mimosa pudica*) leaves revealed calcium crystals in the central midrib. A single layer of upper and lower epidermis was observed, with some cells showing enlargement. Small vascular bundles were present at the center, surrounded by a sclerenchymatous layer. The lamina region exhibited a single layer of palisade cells extending into the midrib area, while the spongy cells in the lower lamina were loosely arranged. Physicochemical analysis showed moisture content of 10.88%, water-soluble extractive value of 5.62%, alcohol-soluble extractive value of 5.16%, petroleum ether-soluble extractive value of 0.88%, and a pH of 5.57.

Conclusion: The pharmacognostic and physicochemical screening of Lajjalu(*Mimosa pudica*) will offer reference information to ensure the quality, purity, and identification of the plant.

Keywords: Lajjalu, Microscopy, Pharmacognostic, Physicochemical analysis.

The therapeutic qualities, Culinary uses and health benefits of Black Rice – An overview

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Abstract

Oryza sativa L. indica (Black Rice), also known as luck rice, purple rice, forbidden rice, heaven rice, imperial rice, king's rice and prized rice. Black rice is a panacea of many diseases so it is believed that people consuming black rice would live longer. The dark purple colour of black rice is due to the presence of Anthocyanins. Approximately 95% of rice is cultivated in Asia in which China is the highest cultivator of black rice followed by Sri Lanka, Indonesia, India, the Philippines, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Thailand, and Myanmar. Black rice is a whole grain, super nutritious type of rice that is high in fibre, anthocyanin, antioxidants, iron, copper, zinc, carotene, 18 amino acids, and a number of vital vitamins. Black rice has a high concentration of minerals including calcium and iron (21.38 mg/100g). All samples have low sodium, with the exception of black rice (10.19 mg/100g). It has high levels of potassium and magnesium (106.21 mg/100g and 186.54 mg/100g, respectively). Black rice had the greatest concentration of total saturated and unsaturated fatty acids (5.89%). Oleic and linoleic acid is highest in Black rice as compare to other rice. Black rice contains 8.17 ± 0.07 % SDF and 14.49 ± 0.07 % IDF. It has many health benefits like anti diabetic effect, antioxidant effect, anti- inflammatory effect and also helps in controlling weight. Consumption of Black rice reduces the risk of cardio vascular diseases. Its high anthocyanin content protects against the negative effects of free radicals, reduces inflammation throughout the body, maintains HDL and LDL cholesterol levels, and has anticancer properties. Black rice is free of gluten which helps in improving digestion and rich in iron content prevents anaemia. There are several culinary uses like used as sauce, condiment, or garnish for a variety of sweet dishes. Total phenolic compounds were higher in black rice wine made from raw black rice grains. In terms of both area and output, rice is the most important crop in the Northeastern states of India. It also greatly enhances food security, and there is a great deal of potential for rice crop development in this region.

Keywords: Anthocyanins, SDF, IDF, inflammation, HDL and LDL.

TCF7L2 Gene Variations are Associated with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in the North Indian Population

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 diabetes is a metabolic disorder that is caused by insulin resistance, insulin deficiency & hyperglycemia. Transcription factor 7-like 2 is a member of the T-cell factor/lymphoid enhancer binding factor family, a group of transcription factors binding to DNA through a high-mobility group domain. TCF7L2 gene plays an important role in the WNT Signaling pathway, which plays a very important role in β -cell development. TCF7L2 is located on chromosome 10q25.2-q25.3. Polymorphism in TCF7L2 is strongly related to type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Aim: TCF7L2 gene variations are associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus in the north Indian population.

Methodology: Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) are genotyped through ARMS-PCR. Firstly DNA isolation is followed by the amplification of target gene-associated polymorphic sites by ARMS-PCR and statistical study will be performed using SPSS software.

Results: As per Hardy Weinberg Equation TCF7L2 rs4506565 (A/T) and rs11196205 (C/G) SNPs are in higher frequency in the control patient group and highly significant. The carrier group was found to have mutant heterozygous AT, and the diabetic patient group was found to have TT mutant homozygous and AA homozygous in the control group, Similarly, the rs11196205 carrier group was found to have mutant heterozygous CC, and the diabetic patient group was found to have CG mutant homozygous and GG homozygous in the control group.

Conclusion: This study assesses the relationship between the rs4506565 (A/T) and rs11196205 (C/G) genotypes of TCF7L2 gene and type 2 diabetes in the North Indian population by using dominant, recessive, and codominant models. This polymorphism was associated with an increased risk for diabetes in the North Indian population so we can say that these variants cause pathophysiological that affect the risk of T2DM.

Keywords: ARMS-PCR; TCF7L2; Insulin Deficiency; Type 2 Diabetes; WNT Signaling.

Design of PCL-Loaded Nanofiber-Containing Herbal Formulation *Attukal Kizhangu L.* in Chronic Periodontitis: A Randomized Controlled Investigation.

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Abstract

Aims: Design of PCL-loaded nanofiber-containing herbal formulation *Attukal Kizhangu L.* in chronic periodontitis: A randomized controlled investigation.

Material & methods: The electro-spinning method was used to create the composite nano-fibers containing herbal formulation, which were then evaluated for various parameters including *in-vitro* and clinical study.

Findings: The electrospinning method was successfully used to fabricate AK-PCL nanofiber (NF) scaffolds. The “Quality by Design” approach followed by the Box-Behnken experimental design was used to optimize the NF. The optimized nanofiber exhibited an interconnected, continuous, and bead-free nanofiber with an average diameter of 150-250 nm. Anti-microbial investigation and CLSM study indicated the remarkable inhibition of periodontal pathogens such as *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonas Gingivitis*, *Fusobacter spp*, and *Prevotella Intermedia* by optimized nanofiber and *in-vitro* drug release study also demonstrated the controlled release of composite nanofiber for over 220 hours. Additionally, the MTT assay and *in-vitro* scratch assay indicated the composite NF had no cytotoxicity to the fibroblast cell line. Also, the clinical study suggested the therapeutic effectiveness of composite NF in patients by substantially reducing ($p < 0.05$) clinical parameters such as plaque index, gingival index, clinical attachment loss, and probing pocket depth.

Conclusion: The fabricated NF is a potential option for chronic periodontitis treatment since it expedited anti-bacterial, cytotoxic, and sustained-release medications.

Keywords: *Attukal Kizhangu L.*, Nanofiber scaffolds, Characterization, *In-vitro* study, Clinical study

Carbon Capture for Wellness: Turning CO₂ into high value Nutraceuticals

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Abstract

With the maturity of gas fermentation technologies, there is a relatively new approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from different industries by biotransformation of waste gases into liquid biofuels via an acetic acid intermediate. This acetate can be used as energy carrier for producing any bio-based commodity by adding another reactor along with acetate producing gas fermenting reactors, thus eliminating the need to feed costly sugars in the heterotrophic cultivation systems. Building upon this concept, we established a novel two stage close loop continuous chemo-heterotrophic process for co-production of high value Omega3-fatty acids (i.e DHA, Docosahexaenoic acids) along with biodiesel using acetate as a carbon source produced by CO₂ utilization. We successfully integrated two process anaerobic and aerobic fermentations at bench scale (2L to 10L) in such a way that in one reactor anaerobic bacteria produce acetate 3% acetic acid by using CO₂ as the sole carbon source that is then consumed as carbon and energy source by our inhouse developed marine oleaginous microalgae in second fermenter at the same time giving biomass productivity (80g_L-1d⁻¹), DHA production (25 g_L-1d⁻¹) and lipids production (40% of CDW) at commercially competitive production scale with continuous biomass separation from broth thus effectively recycling the residual liquid in the process with zero liquid discharge. Therefore, given the use of cheapest and easiest carbon source available and producing high value co products make this process a potentially viable at industrial scale.

Keywords: Gas fermentation, CO₂ utilization, Acetate-based biofuel production, Omega-3 fatty acids (DHA) co-production, Continuous chemo-heterotrophic process.

***In-Silico* Analysis of Polyherbal Formulation ‘Trayushnadi-Vati’ Extract for Determination of Potential Inhibitor of Nitric Oxide Synthase**

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Abstract

Type 2 Diabetes mellitus, a metabolic syndrome characterized by high level of serum glucose that could result either from inadequate insulin synthesis and secretion, or insulin resistance, or over-secretion of glucagon. In diabetes, abnormal metabolic processes lead to superoxide (ROS and RNS) production in mitochondria and further increases oxidative stress. **Nitric Oxide Synthase (NOS) (PDB: 4NOS)** is an anti-oxidant enzyme that catalyses the production of nitric oxide (NO). Inhibition of NOS ameliorates oxidative stress in body. Ayurvedic drug ‘Trayushnadi-Vati’ contains several phytochemical compounds that exhibits medicinal properties *viz.* anti-hyperglycemic, anti-oxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-hypertensive and anti-inflammatory.

‘Trayushnadi-Vati’ powder was prepared and its phytochemicals were extracted in ethylacetate by ‘maceration cold extraction’ method. GCMS (untargeted analysis) of ethylacetate extract was done at Metabolome Division, NIPGR which led to detection of seven major compounds. By utilizing PubChem database, the PubChem SDF files and CID number of these compounds were retrieved. Then, these seven compounds were screened through *in-silico* mode for possible toxicity, mutagenicity and carcinogenicity using TOPKAT software of BIOVIA DS 2019. The most potential inhibitor of 4NOS was screened out of non-toxic, non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic compounds, using Discovery Studio 2019 computer-aided virtual screening technique. Libdock was used for virtual screening and scoring of S-ethylisothiourea (control ligand for 4NOS), as well as for candidate inhibitor compounds, and CDOCKER module was utilized for molecular docking analysis.

Two out of seven compounds (CID: 64860 and 5317320) were screened out as toxic by TOPKAT screening while other compounds were screened out as non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic. Based on **Libdock score**, **-CDOCKER Energy**, **-CDOCKER Interaction Energy** of S-ethylisothiourea and candidate phytochemicals compounds, **CID: 12314028** was screened out as most potential inhibitor of 4NOS, as they yielded scores greater than the scores of the ‘control ligand’ of target enzyme.

Keywords: Diabetes; Polyherbal; Computational study; Molecular docking; Diabetes mellitus; Reactive Nitrogen Species.

Development of Nanomaterials for Fire Extinguishing Agents

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Abstract

The development of nanomaterials for fire extinguishing agents is an emerging area of research that addresses limitations in traditional fire suppression systems. Conventional fire extinguishers often involve halons and other chemicals, which, while effective, have notable drawbacks, including high environmental toxicity, potential respiratory hazards, and significant contributions to ozone layer depletion. Nanotechnology offers innovative solutions, leveraging unique properties at the nanoscale to enhance extinguishing efficiency, reduce environmental impacts, and provide safer alternatives. Nanomaterials such as metal oxides, carbon-based nanostructures, and nanofluids have shown promise in fire suppression applications. For example, metal oxide nanoparticles like magnesium oxide (MgO) and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) exhibit high thermal stability and can act as effective heat absorbers, preventing flame propagation. These nanoparticles, when dispersed in a liquid or as part of a gel, can disrupt combustion reactions by scavenging free radicals, significantly slowing the fire spread. Carbon-based nanomaterials, such as carbon nanotubes and graphene oxide, have demonstrated high specific surface areas, which enhance their capacity to adsorb flammable gases and potentially reduce the release of toxic byproducts. Nanofluids, which are suspensions of nanoparticles within a fluid medium, provide advantages for rapid fire suppression. Their enhanced heat transfer capabilities, driven by the high thermal conductivity of nanoparticles, allow them to cool surfaces quickly, extinguishing flames more efficiently than traditional water-based systems. Our research explores nanoparticle-based additives in foams and dry powders, improving coverage and performance across various fire classes. We are optimizing the size, stability, and reactivity of nanoparticles to ensure safety and environmental sustainability. The nanomaterial-based fire extinguishing agents represent a promising advance toward more effective, sustainable, and versatile fire suppression technologies.

Keywords: Nanomaterials, Fire Extinguishing Agents, Toxicity, Flame propagation, Dry powders

Chalcones as Potential Antileishmanial Agents: Synthesis and Biological Evaluation

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Abstract

Leishmaniasis is a disease transmitted by the bite of *Leishmania*-infected female sandflies. This disease has been recognized as an increasing health problem worldwide by WHO; an estimated 700000 to 1 million new cases occur annually. The discovery of new lead compounds for this disease is a pressing concern for global health programs. Chalcones with various structural features were synthesized and evaluated for their *in vitro* antileishmanial activity. Several of these compounds were active *in vitro* screening; a few were further evaluated for *in vivo* antileishmanial efficacy in the *L. donovani*/hamster model. The *in vivo* antileishmanial activity was determined in golden hamsters infected with the MHOM/IN/80/Dd8 strain of *L. donovani*. Golden hamsters of both sexes were infected intracardially with 1×10^7 amastigotes per animal. The intensity of infection in treated and untreated animals and the initial parasite count in treated animals were compared, and the efficacy was expressed in percentage inhibition. Many compounds exhibited potent *in vitro* activity (IC_{50} range from 1.70 to 8 μ M) against extracellular promastigotes and intracellular amastigotes form of *L. donovani*. A few promising compounds were tested *in vivo* in a hamster model and showed exceptional parasite inhibition at 50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg doses. A series of chalcone analogs with various structural features, such as chromenochalcones and *O*-prenyl/geranyl/farnesyl/aminoalkyl groups containing chalcones, were prepared based on natural product lead and tested for their antileishmanial activity. Few derivatives were significantly more active than the standard antileishmanial drugs in *in vitro* evaluation. The *in vivo* studies of promising compounds were performed in the *L. donovani*/hamster model, in which one compound showed good antileishmanial activity (83.32% parasite inhibition at the dose of 50 mg/kg x 10 days and 75.89% parasite inhibition at 100 mg/kg x 5 days by IP route).

Keywords: Chromenochalcones, Chromenodihydrochalcones, Antileishmanial, *Leishmania donovani*, Hamster model

Efficiency of Developed Phosphorus Enriched Organo-Mineral Fertilizer on green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) and on Some Chemical Properties of Soil

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Abstract

Background: Phosphorus is a very important plant nutrient for the development of plants and its production is not unlimited in the world. In addition, excessive use can lead to soil and water pollution. In this respect, phosphorus should be used effectively in plant production, especially in degraded soils.

Aim of the study: An experiment was carried out to develop p-enriched organomineral fertilizers (p-OMF) using organic substrate i.e., rice straw, mineral waste i.e., low-grade rock phosphate (RP), and phosphate-solubilizing microorganism (*Aspergillus sp.*). Thereafter the study was carried out to determine the effects of p-OMF on some chemical properties of a degraded soil.

Methodology: In this study, four doses of developed p-OMF (D₁: 10, D₂: 20, D₃:30, and D₄: 40 t ha⁻¹) were applied excluding control.

Results: According to the research findings, p-OMFs increased the soil organic matter (SOM), salinity, total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) by 65.1%, 16.9%, 26.1%, 138%, and 14.8%, respectively. According to the results of the study, the highest change in exchangeable Ca and Na content in soils was obtained from p-OMF applications by D₄ and D₃ respectively. They also decreased soil pH by 5%. As a result, it was determined that the most effective p-OMF dose that maintains soil properties at appropriate levels in sandy soils is D₃ (30 t ha⁻¹ OMF). Thereafter a field experiment was conducted to determine the effect of fertilizer on the growth of green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.). Growth parameters of percentage emergence, plant height, leaf area, number of leaves per plant and branch/plant were collected and subjected into statistical analysis, using ANOVA and Fisher's L.S.D. at 5 % probability level. The results showed that growth parameters i.e., germination percentage (100%), plant height (13.8 cm), leaf area (21.87cm²), number of leaves (9.21), branch/plant (5.63) were found to be significantly highest with p-OMF @30 t ha⁻¹ OMF soil and least was found in the control.

Conclusion: The study thus revealed that crop residue could be converted into a value-added product through composting technology using low-grade rock phosphate along with phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms.

Keywords: P deficiency, P rich Organomineral fertilizer, soil properties, green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

Ameliorative Role of Isolated Andrographolide on Chromium-Induced Oxidative Stress Linked Cytokines, Pro-Apoptotic and Anti-Apoptotic Markers in Rat Lymphocytes

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Abstract

Potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$), a Cr (VI) compound, is the most toxic form of chromium and has been demonstrated to induce toxicity associated with oxidative stress in humans and animals. Reactive oxygen species are the molecules and ions containing unpaired valence shell electrons and being a free radical, it is highly active and shows an important role in cell signalling regulation, leading to oxidative cell damage and ultimately cell death. Therefore, the aim of this present investigation was an attempt to reduce the effects of Cr-induced cytotoxicity by using the most potent isolated Andrographolide (ANDRO) from *Andrographis paniculata* in the intracellular ROS generation, expression of certain cytokines and apoptotic signalling pathway in rat lymphocytes. In this investigation, a group of male Wistar rats (80-100 g) were induced by intraperitoneal injection of vehicle (0.9% NaCl), $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (0.8 mg / 100 g body weight / day), $K_2Cr_2O_7$ plus ANDRO (20mg/kg/day) for the period of 28 days. It was found that the increased intracellular ROS and pro-inflammatory responses that stimulate the cell death process were confirmed by PI staining and estimation of pro-apoptotic and anti-apoptotic markers. Our result demonstrated that pro-apoptotic markers were increased in the chromium-treated groups. It was found that chromium significantly induced cell death generated by ROS which induced TNF- α which serves as an important function in cell death by suppressing pAKT followed by caspase-8 and caspase-3. ANDRO may be used as potential therapeutic natural herbal product for amelioration of chromium-mediated dysfunction and effectively protected the lymphocytes from chromium-induced cytotoxicity.

Keywords: Chromium, Andrographolide, Lymphocytes, Cytokines and Apoptotic markers.

Effect of Salicylic Acid Elicitation on Morphological, Biochemical and Physiological Parameters of *Plumbago zeylanica*

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Abstract

Elicitation is used in agriculture as a method of crop protection or a means to enhance nutraceutically or pharmaceutically important metabolites with the help of chemical stimuli known as elicitors. Salicylic acid is a phytohormone, known to regulate various developmental and defense related processes in plants. Exogenous application of this molecule has revealed its elicitor potential by modulating growth and metabolic changes in several plant species. Therefore, the present experiment was conducted to analyze morphological, biochemical and physiological response of an important medicinal plant, *Plumbago zeylanica* towards salicylic acid treatment. Salicylic acid of various concentrations (1–0.01 mg/ml) were applied on the plant through soil treatment and observed for changes. It was found that soil treatment increased growth parameters and enhanced abiotic stress tolerance in *P. zeylanica*. Biological activities; antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal were also found to be elevated after the treatment. Metabolite profile of the samples were studied by analysing UHPLC-HRMS data. A change in the ion intensity peak of the important naphthoquinones of *P. zeylanica*, including plumbagin, as well as various phenolic acids, polyphenols, flavonoids and fatty acids were observed.

Keywords: Elicitation; Salicylic acid; *Plumbago zeylanica*; metabolites; Abiotic stress

Spatial Distribution and Composition of Microplastic Pollution in Phalgu River in Gaya District of Bihar, India

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Abstract

Microplastic (MP) contamination is a global environmental challenge, impacting both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Despite rivers playing a key role in transporting MPs to marine environments, studies on MP loads in Indian freshwater systems remain scarce. This study assessed MP contamination in water and sediments from the Phalgu Rivers, tributaries of the River Ganga in Gaya, Bihar, India. Samples were collected from 4 locations, analyzing MP size, shape, polymer types, and color abundances, alongside physicochemical parameters. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy identified the polymer composition, revealing MP concentrations of 120–380 items/L in water and 400–760 items/kg in sediments. Polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) were the most common polymers. In water samples, fibers/threads constituted 41% of MPs, while fragments (38%) were dominant in sediments, with white and black MPs being most abundant in both. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) indicated that urban runoff and sewage mixing are significant contributors to MP pollution in these rivers. Sources of MPs included illegal dumping of urban solid waste in catchment areas, encroachment near riverbanks, and direct disposal of sewage and industrial effluents into rivers. These findings underline the critical role of these Phalgu River in transporting MPs into the River Ganga, emphasizing the need for improved urban waste management and sewage control to mitigate MP contamination. Addressing these pollution sources is essential to reduce MP levels in the rivers, helping to safeguard the health of freshwater ecosystems and downstream marine environments.

Keywords: Microplastic contamination, Freshwater ecosystems, Polymers, Urban runoff and sewage, Phalgu River, ATR-FTIR analysis

Food Colours and Health: Pink Sweet (Cotton Candy) Sets Off Alarm Bells in India

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Abstract

Food colour is habitually used for inclusively imagination to colorful parcels like flavours, taste, sensitive rates and numerous further ways. But synthetic grounded food colorings or colours may beget several dangerous goods directly to mortal health especially in children. Utmost of food colours are not admissible in food artificial according to the regulations of each country. The system of medication of different food colorings are now entering larger attention because of their safety suggestions and use of green natural grounded food colorings are set to open a new period or pathway to overcome the present situation. This perspective focus on to give a current background on food colorings and health relationship especially in India through a literature quantitative exploration analysis way. The southern state of Tamil Nadu in India enforced the ban after tests verified the presence of some cancer- causing substances like Rhodamine- B, in specific samples as tested in laboratory. Before some reports also suggest the fact that the union home of Puducherry in India banned the sweet treat while other countries have begun testing samples of it. Cotton delicacy or candy, also notorious as buddi- ka- baal (old woman's hair) in India for its special appearance, is popular substantially in children the world over. It's an institution in numerous children's exertion centre like recreation premises, expositions and other places of entertainment as kiddies like it because of its sticky, melt- in- the- mouth texture. But some of officials say that the sweet is more minatory than it seems the contaminations in sweet could lead to direct affects all organs of the body as result could lead to cancer. The chemical composition imparts a fluorescent pink tinge and is used substantially for color fabrics, cosmetics and inks. Studies have also shown the fact that the chemical compositions can effectively enhance the threat of cancer. Some of foreign countries like Europe and California have made its use as a food be paint illegal. Under the Food Safety and norms Act, 2006, not only dealing cotton candy but direct use of Rhodamine- B in the field of packaging g, import, trade of food or serving food containing it at marriages and other public events would be punishable in Tamil Nadu.

Keywords: Cotton Candy, Rhodamine B, Health Safety, Environmental, Synthetic food colour.

The Storm of Natural and Health Hazard Due to Climate Change

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Abstract

Natural hazard due to climate change is the nature's subtle way of reminding us who's boss. In most of the cases natural disaster can cause the health impacts even life-threatening in humans. It is a global threat that put stress on various sectors. This study investigates the intersection of climate change and natural hazard and how climate fluctuation is got worsen and how it effects to the sustainability of diverse sectors worldwide (specially health sector). Vulnerability and resilience specially for those regions in world who are economically weaker, also provide some suggestions to mitigate the natural hazard and climate change. Climatic changes lead to food and waterborne and parasitic diseases, and a recent example is a coronavirus pandemic. Climate change also accelerates the mystery of antimicrobial resistance, one more threat to human health due to the increasing incidence of antibiotic resistant. The methodology is to scrutinize the systematic review of literatures, case study, statical data analysis, and conducted the surveys and interview to better understand the problem. The study found that Climate change making worst existing vulnerabilities, particularly in low-income regions. Our policy framework highlights the need for collaboration across governments, civil society, and the private sector to protect vulnerable communities and promote sustainable development. Urgent climate change mitigation and adaptation measures are necessary to reduce the risks associated with natural hazards. Effective policy responses require integrated approaches, community engagement, and inclusive decision-making.

Keywords: climate change, natural hazards, vulnerability, resilience, policy framework, adaptation, mitigation.

Integrated alliance of the 2 AIs: Artificial Intelligence & Ancient Ideology

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Abstract

The study delves into the ancient system, knowledge, practices and beliefs which are inherited awards contributing to the world today, influencing the technological field which is giving us impeccable outcomes in all desired industries, be it medicine, architecture, education, commerce, transport, communication, security, finance and also the mental health, which is also the major subject of the following analysis. The modern technological innovations indicating how it is shaped with the ancestry of primeval practices is demonstrated by the ancient books, prehistoric sculptures, temple layouts and aged practices which power up the technological applications of the contemporary period. The phrases which came into trend nowadays such as, mental well-being, depression, anxiety, panic attacks, therapeutic practices etc. are assessed and resolved through ancient rituals and customs since the dawn of time, which are now used and enacted with the advancements of technology and computational intelligence. Definitely, when the 2 AIs i.e., Artificial Intelligence and Ancient Ideology are integrated together then the results will be absolutely miraculous with respect to the mental care, which should be addressed, keeping in mind the present scenario and for the vitality of the future generation chiefly, along with all the age groups as mental health doesn't discriminate between ages or financial and economical variability. This research reveals the positive impact of digital development associated with the principles of ancient knowledge on the mental health, coupled with enthralling ancient methods employed in today's technological advancements.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, computational intelligence, Therapeutic practices, economical variability

In-Silico Pharmacokinetic Study of JM Herbal Formulation for Screening of Potential Inhibitors of Aldose Reductase

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease defined by elevated blood sugar levels that are directly caused by insulin resistance, insufficient insulin production, or excessive glucagon secretion. The JM herbal drug is made from a blend of two plants which are shown to have anti-hyperglycemic and anti-oxidant effects.

Human aldose reductase (AKR1B1) (EC 1.1.1.21), is an enzyme encoded by the AKR1B1 gene. It catalyzes the initial step of polyol pathway of glucose metabolism i.e. conversion of glucose to sorbitol. Polyol pathway is an important source of diabetes-induced oxidative stress. LDT is a known inhibitor of AKR1B1 (PDB: 1US0).

JM herbal formulation was prepared by mixing powder of dried leaves of *Moringa oleifera* and *Lagerstroemia speciosa* in 1:1 ratio. Its phytochemicals were extracted by 'maceration' method in 70% ethanol (1:20 w/v). LC-MS/MS (untargeted analysis) hydroalcoholic extract was performed at Central Discovery Centre- Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, where 1173 compounds were detected. Using PubChem database, the PubChem CID number and of these compounds were retrieved. Thereafter, compounds were screened for drug-likeness using Lipinski and Veber Filter. The 3D SDF files of the compounds which passed through Lipinski and Veber filter were retrieved. Using TOPKAT software, these compounds were subjected to *in-silico* screening for any possible toxicity, mutagenicity and carcinogenicity. The compounds screened out as non-toxic, non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic were tested for ADME parameters using SWISS ADME. The compounds which passed SWISS ADME test were subjected to *in-silico* screening for finding potential inhibitors of AKR1B1, using Discovery Studio 2021 computer-aided virtual screening technique. LibDock was used for virtual screening and scoring of LDT and candidate inhibitor compounds, and CDOCKER module was utilized for molecular docking analysis.

Out of 1173 compounds, only 173 compounds were able to pass Lipinski's & Veber Filter, TOPKAT toxicity and SWISS ADME test. Out of these 173 compounds, 12 compounds yielded LibDock score, -CDOCKER Energy and -CDOCKER Interaction Energy higher than that of the scores of LDT (Control for 1US0). Based on these scores, CID No. 60957, 134601 and 152198 were screened out as most potential inhibitor of AKR1B1.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, herbal formulation, anti-hyperglycemic, computational study, molecular docking.

Encapsulation of *Foeniculum vulgare* Essential Oil in Chitosan Nanomatrix: A Green and Eco-Friendly Approach for Aflatoxin B₁ Inhibition in Stored Herbal Raw Materials

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Abstract

Background: Herbal raw materials are integral parts of the medicinal system due to presence of different bioactive compounds. The traditional herbal medicines act as a proxy to modern allopathic system with different side effects. However, herbal raw materials are being contaminated in storage conditions by *Aspergillus flavus* along with the carcinogenic aflatoxin B₁. Various synthetic fungicides have been used to control aflatoxin B₁ contamination, but the negative impact on human health and environment limit their practical applications. Essential oils are green chemicals and commonly used to inhibit fungal and aflatoxin contamination in stored herbal raw materials.

Aim: The aim of the study was to encapsulate *Foeniculum vulgare* L. essential oil (FVEO) in chitosan nanopolymer and assess the efficacy against *A. flavus* and aflatoxin B₁ contamination in stored *Withania somnifera* root samples.

Methodology: Encapsulation of FVEO into chitosan was done through ionic gelation and evaluated for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus* with mechanism of action through ergosterol assessment, ions leakage and methylglyoxal production. The molecular and *in-situ* study along with biodegradation of withanolides was performed in *Withania somnifera* root samples over 1 year of storage.

Results: The nanoencapsulated FVEO inhibited the *A. flavus* growth at 1.2 µL/mL and aflatoxin B₁ synthesis at 1.0 µL/mL. The inhibition of ergosterol, leakage of ions and methylglyoxal production in *Aspergillus flavus* cells was observed at 1.2 µL/mL of nanoencapsulated FVEO. During *in-situ* conditions, the nanoencapsulated FVEO mitigated the lipid peroxidation and biodegradation of withanolides without altering the organoleptic qualities along with high mammalian safety profile.

Conclusion: The nanoencapsulated *Foeniculum vulgare* essential oil showed promising preservative potentiality and *in situ* antifungal and anti-aflatoxigenic activity in stored herbal raw materials which extends its practical potentiality as green and nano-smart preservative in pharmaceutical and agricultural industries.

Keywords: Essential oil; Nanoencapsulation; Smart preservative, Aflatoxin B₁, Antifungal

The Impact of Cinnamon on Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) Patients

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Abstract

Background: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) is characterized by fat accumulation in the liver in individuals who consume minimal or no alcohol. NAFLD varies in severity from simple steatosis (fat accumulation) to more advanced forms like Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis (NASH), which includes liver inflammation and damage. Untreated NAFLD can progress to liver fibrosis, cirrhosis, or liver cancer. While the cause of NAFLD is not fully understood, it is commonly linked to obesity, insulin resistance, type 2 diabetes, and metabolic syndrome. Treatment primarily involves lifestyle changes such as diet and exercise, although medication may be necessary in some cases. Recently, the use of herbal remedies for NAFLD has gained considerable attention.

Aim of the study: The Cinnamon popularly known as Dalchini (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), belongs to the Family Lauraceae. To evaluate the effects of cinnamon supplementation on insulin resistance, abnormal lipid profiles and liver enzymes, and the condition of high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) in patients with NAFLD.

Methodology: The study was designed as a case-controlled trial with two parallel groups. Animal model (mouse) in the treatment group received would be provided with 750mg of cinnamon at a time and twice in a day, and the control group would not receive any supplement other than their diet for 12 weeks.

Result: Cinnamon has been linked to improvements in hepatic enzymes, specifically Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST), indicating decreased liver injury and inflammation. It may also positively affect the insulin resistance index, fasting blood glucose (FBS), and lipid profile levels.

Conclusion: Cinnamon supplementation of 1.5 g daily for 12 weeks would improve NAFLD characteristics by positively affecting blood parameters and lipid profiles, making it a potential adjunctive therapy for the condition.

Keywords: NAFLD (Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease), Cinnamon, ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase), AST (Aspartate Aminotransferase)

Climate change and the rise of infectious diseases :Implication for Global Health

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Abstract

This study explores the significant impact of climate change on the emergence and spread of infectious diseases, particularly vector –borne illnesses. With rising global temperatures and shifting weather patterns, the environmental factors influencing diseases outbreak are increasingly complex .the research focus on how climate change affects diseases vectors , especially mosquitoes , and the regions most susceptible to these shifts . warming temperatures expand the range of mosquito species such as *Aedes aegypti* and *Anopheles gambiae* ,enabling them to thrive in areas previously unsuitable for their survival . Additionally , increased rainfall and altered precipitation patterns provide ideal breeding conditions for mosquito populations, thus intensifying disease transmission risks . climate –induced changes in human behavior , including urbanization and increased travel ,also contribute to the spread of diseases. This study highlights the potential rise in prevalence of malaria ,dengue ,chikungunya , zika virus and COVID-19 (highlights the urgency of understanding climate’s role in pandemics, as environmental changes may support new and re-emerging diseases) particularly in tropical and sub-tropical areas , as mosquito population flourish due to warmer temperature and new water sources from melting glaciers. According to world health organization (WHO) the dengue has grown dramatically around the world in recent decades , with cases increasing from 505430 in 2000 to 5.2 million in 2019. The highest number of dengue cases was recorded in 2023, affecting over 80 countries. The tally of dengue cases continue to rise , highlighting the persistent challenges posed by this infectious diseases. Health authorities are grappling with the situation as outbreaks escalate , necessitating urgent public health responses and preventive measures. The ongoing vigilance is essential to mitigate the impact and protect vulnerable population from this widespread arboviral threat.

KEYWORDS: Climate change ,infectious diseases ,vector borne illness, mosquito proliferation , arboviral threats.

Alteration in Temperature Modulates Leucocyte Immune Responses in Freshwater Snakehead Teleost, *Channa punctatus*

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Abstract

Temperature fluctuations act as a multifaceted stressor, influencing various biological processes such as growth, physiology, reproductive and immunological functions in fish. The changes in temperature often interact with other abiotic stressors such as oxygen levels, salinity, or pollutants, intensifying their combined effects on aquatic organisms. This study aimed to explore the influence of temperature on the immunity of a teleost *Channa punctatus*. The leucocytes were isolated from whole blood and cultured at three different temperatures (20°C, 25°C and 30°C respectively) and immune parameters were evaluated. Respiratory burst, nitrite release, lymphocyte proliferation and phagocytic activity of leucocytes were assessed. The results showed that there was significant elevation in respiratory burst activity of leucocytes when temperature increases. In addition, the significant increase was seen in nitrite release with the rise in temperature. Similarly, Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), Concanavalin A (Con A) and Phytohemagglutinin (PHA) stimulated lymphocyte proliferation was increased in cultures maintained at higher temperature. Leucocyte phagocytosis also showed an elevation trend with increase in temperature. These findings suggest that temperature plays a crucial role in modulating the immune responses of teleost fish. Understanding the impact of temperature on leucocyte immunity in teleost is essential for assessing their overall health and susceptibility to diseases in changing environmental conditions. Further research is warranted to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and implications of temperature-induced immune responses in teleost.

Keywords: Temperature, teleost, immunity, peripheral blood leucocytes, mitogens.

Role of fractionation pattern of toxic metals in atmospheric particulate in subcellular distribution and chemical forms in *Andrographis paniculata*

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and arsenic (As) fractionation patterns in aerosols on their subcellular distribution and chemical form accumulated in the *A. paniculata* taken up from the soil. The experiment was performed at two differently polluted sites i.e. agricultural area and a traffic junction, using both un-contaminated and Pb, Cd, and As-contaminated soils. Simultaneously, a closed chamber experiment was also performed to avoid any atmospheric deposition. The concentration of PM₁₀, dry deposition on leaf surfaces, the bioavailability of Pb, Cd, and As in PM₁₀ and soil, and their subcellular distribution and chemical forms in plant tissues were examined. Results demonstrated that atmospheric dust directly contributed to the accumulation of these metals in leaf tissues, but no translocation from leaf tissue to stems and roots was found. The atmospheric deposition altered the subcellular sequestration pattern of Pb, Cd, and As from the cell wall and soluble fraction to the nucleus, chloroplast, mitochondria, and soluble fraction in plants. The exposure to atmospheric deposition increased the proportions of extractable forms of metals (Et-OH and H₂O). The emission sources of Pb, Cd, and As contribute a major role in the bioavailability of these metals, which directly influence direct or indirect uptake and their distribution in plants. The atmospheric metal enhanced their content in the nucleus, chloroplast, and mitochondrial fractions. The atmospheric Pb²⁺\Cd²⁺ being more bioavailable increased concentrations of EtOH and H₂O-extractable Pb²⁺\Cd²⁺ in leaves in plants exposed to only atmospheric deposition. However, the dominance of oxidizable and residual fractions in PM₁₀ increased oxalate complexes and residual forms of Pb and insoluble-phosphate complexes and residual forms of Cd in leaves. The *A. paniculata* exposed to the atmospheric deposition also increased these three metals content in the nucleus, chloroplast, and mitochondria with increasing EtOH and NaCl extractable chemical form for Pb and Cd and HAc and HCl for As in the root tissues by enhancing their bioavailability in the soil.

Keywords: Atmospheric deposition; Potentially toxic metals; Subcellular distribution; Chemical forms

Air Quality in Cuttack During Bali Jatra- A Case Study

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Abstract

Now a days Ambient Air Quality (AAQ) with Air Quality Index (AQI) is an important parameter for enhancing public health and improving quality of life. It effects on respiratory, cardiovascular, neurological, cancer, overall mortality, reproductive and developmental systems. In Odisha on full moon day of Kartika (considered highly auspicious) people celebrate Bali unique festival in the memory of ancient maritime linkages with Bali. A big fair popularly known as Bali Jatra is held with tiny boats made of either paper or bark of banana tree are lit with clay lamps and floated at the fort area of Cuttack on the banks of the Mahanadi on this occasion. In the present case study, we analyzed and compared the three successive year Air pollutants data like SO₂ NO₂ PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} collected from RO, SPCB Cuttack during the Bali Jatra. It was observed that AQI standard was moderate and reaching to poor near by future. Comparative tables and bar graphs were plotted and discussed the various parameters. However, State Pollution Control Board Bhubaneswar, Govt. of Odisha already initiated many steps to control the Air Quality Index during this Bali Jatra season for good health and environment.

Keywords: Air pollutants, Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂), Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), Particulate Matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) Air Quality Index, Cuttack Bali Jatra and Human Health.

Metabolic profiling of serum to uncover potential biomarkers of Lymphatic Filariasis

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Abstract

Background: Lymphatic filariasis, or elephantiasis, is an infection caused by three closely related parasitic nematodes: *Wuchereria bancrofti*, *Brugia malayi*, and *Brugia timori*. It is one of the most debilitating neglected tropical diseases transmitted by mosquito vectors. Hydrocele and lymphedema are major pathologies associated with LF infection. All the diagnostic tests for LF have limitations, therefore new methods are needed for improved diagnosis and prognosis of the disease. In this study, we compared serum profiles of LF-infected individuals against healthy individuals to identify novel metabolic biomarkers that can be used as therapeutic targets.

Aim of the study: The present study aimed to identify metabolite biomarkers that can be used to understand the disease's pathophysiology and progression better. By characterizing these metabolic alterations, we can better diagnose, treat, and understand the molecular pathways underlying lymphatic filariasis.

Methodology: Serum samples of LF-infected and healthy volunteers living in the endemic regions of Eastern Uttar Pradesh were collected. The serum samples were processed, and the serum metabolites were extracted and identified using untargeted mass spectrometry. Metabolomic data analysis was performed via the default parameters of the "Compound Discoverer 3.2.0.421" software combined with Metaboanalyst 5.0. A multi-network was constructed using Cytoscape 3.10.0 software.

Results: Analytical techniques and statistical analysis revealed LF-specific metabolic biomarkers and impacted pathways. A rough difference between LF-infected and Healthy subjects was seen in PCA score plots. Metabolites such as Hexadecanoic acid, Octadecanoic acid, and Taurine associated with their respective pathways demonstrated statistical significance. Network analysis revealed metabolites that play important clinical roles.

Conclusion: Overall our findings have important implications for advancing the understanding of Lymphatic Filariasis pathophysiology, uncovering new pathways, and developing effective therapeutic targets for future clinical diagnosis of LF.

Keywords: Lymphatic filariasis, metabolomics, pathology, diagnosis, Octadecanoic acid

Bio-medical Waste: A Serious Threat to The Environment

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Abstract

Background: Bio-medical waste (BMW) refers to any waste, which is generated during the diagnosis, treatment or immunisation of human beings or animals or research activities pertaining thereto or in the production or testing of biological or in health camps. There has been a continuous rise in BMW generation in India from 484 Tonnes/day of BMW in 2013 to about 705 tonnes/day of BMW generated during the year 2022 as per Central Pollution Control Board, New Delhi. Improper disposal and undertreatment of BMW before disposal are serious threats to sustainable healthy environment.

Aim of the study

1. To study the trend in biomedical waste generation and its disposal.
2. To study factors affecting biomedical waste generation and its disposal.
3. To study about availability of BMW treatment facilities

Methodology: This study was conducted in a tertiary care centre. Data on biomedical waste generation and its management provided by Central Pollution Control Board, New Delhi and State Pollution Control Boards (SPCBs)/ Pollution Control Committees (PCCs) in the respective States/Union Territories (UTs) which are available in public domain were studied. Data were collected from various sources like websites, social networking sites, newspapers, magazines, books, academic journals, government publications, etc. Data were recorded and analysed using Microsoft Excel.

Results: Result of the study showed that there has been a continuous rise in generation of BMW across the country. During the year 2020 & 2021, a substantial increase in quantity of BMW generated was seen owing to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2022, total quantity of BMW generated was the lowest (0.5 tons/day) in Arunachal Pradesh and highest in Uttar Pradesh (89 tons/day).

Conclusion: The quantity of BMW generated per day is going up every year. In future, with the increase in number of health care centres, the BMW generation is going to escalate. Improper disposal of BMW will be a serious threat not only to the human health but also to the health of animals. We need to increase awareness among people about BMW and its management. At the same time, we will have to increase the number of Common Bio-medical Waste Treatment Facilities (CBWTFs) for proper treatment and disposal of biomedical wastes throughout the country.

Keywords: Bio-medical waste (BMW), Pollution, Environment, Public health, CBWTFs

Optimization of Level of Basil Essential Oil in Chhana Batter Stored at Refrigeration Temperature Under Aerobic Packaging Condition

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Abstract

Milk nuggets are ready to eat value added milk products with good source of milk nutrients. To enhance functionality and shelf life of milk nuggets the present study was designed. The developed fibre fortified chhana batter was then explored for optimizing level of basil essential oil. The incorporation of basil essential oil in chhana batter did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) affect the pH of batter among groups throughout storage except that on 12th day. Though, pH value varied significant ($P < 0.05$) during storage in all groups. The titratable acidity values varied significantly ($P < 0.05$) on 3rd and 9th days of storage among groups. However, TA values decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) during storage. Total phenolic content, DPPH and ABTS activity of all basil oil treated groups increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) with the level of basil oil incorporation. These values decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) among all groups throughout study. Lipid oxidative attributes PV, TBARS and FFA values were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in chhana batter prepared with addition of basil oils. However, these values decreased considerably among the all sample across storage. Standard plate counts, psychrophilic counts and yeast moulds count were significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower in cinnamon oil added groups and control throughout storage. Though, coliform counts were not detected among all groups during entire storage. The colour and appearance, and flavour score were maintained comparatively better for basil oil treated chhana batter than control throughout storage. However, both colour and appearance as well as flavour attributes varied significantly ($P < 0.05$) among all samples during storage. Therefore, on the basis of findings T2 sample was recommended for product development.

Keywords: Essential oil, TA value, DPPH activity, ABTS activity, yeast moulds

Harnessing the potential of PGPRs for modulating growth and quality traits in peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.)

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Abstract

Peppermint (*Mentha piperita* L.; Fam.; Lamiaceae) is a well-known herb having medicinal and aromatic properties with various commercial and therapeutic aims. Despite being extensively used in the pharmaceutical, cosmetics, and confectionary industries, peppermint is less favored by growers and farmers due to its relatively lower profitability, induced by its lower herb and oil yield, compared to other mint species. Although, various agro-technologies and breeding techniques are employed to achieve yield enhancement in this vegetatively propagated crop. The administration of closely associated rhizobacterial communities confers a sustainable and promising alternative to enhance growth and quality attributes in peppermint. A total of three plant-beneficial rhizobacterial isolates R9K-1, R9K-3, and R9K-4 isolated from peppermint genotype MPS-3637 were analyzed for their nucleotide homology with the genomic sequences available in the NCBI database. Where R9K-1 was found to show maximum similarity (99.82%) to *Agrobacterium chroococcom*, R9K-3 was similar (98.22%) to *Bacillus safensis*, and R9K-4 was showing its nucleotide similarity (98.79%) with *Agrobacterium salinitolerance*. Further, a pot experiment in CRD was conducted by implementing these plant growth-promoting bacterial strains with a varieties/genotype CIM-I452 of peppermint in a triplicate manner. The surface sterilized runners of the peppermint genotype CIM-I452, without any administration of PGPRs were potted as the control. However, surface sterilized runners of the same genotype with the amendment of rhizobacterial isolates R9K-1, R9K-3, and R9K-4 were considered as T1, T2, and T3 respectively, and potted separately in a triplicate manner. The results of the study revealed that the maximum improvement in oil content (188.57%) and menthol content (49.74%) was depicted by T1 followed by T2 which improved the oil content (%) by 71.43% and menthofuran content (%) up to more than seven times whereas the menthol content (%) was decreased by 65.72%, over the control. T3 has increased the oil content (%) by 17.14% and menthofuran content (%) by more than four times whereas the menthol content (%) was decreased by 16.87%, over the control. After analyzing the results, runners of CIM-I452 amended with *Agrobacterium chroococcom* (T1) were found to significantly improve the growth of peppermint genotype CIM-I452 while ameliorating its essential oil quality up to the mark of globally accepted quality of peppermint oil.

Keywords: *Agrobacterium* spp., Growth-promoting rhizobacteria, *Mentha* spp., Menthol, Menthofuran, Sustainable agriculture

Holistic Approaches for PCOS through Ayurveda

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Abstract

Introduction: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a complex condition characterized by elevated androgen levels, menstrual irregularities, and the presence of small cysts on one or both ovaries. It can present morphologically as polycystic ovaries or biochemically with hyperandrogenemia. The disorder affects approximately 5 to 10% of women aged 18 to 44 in the U.S., making it the most prevalent endocrine disorder among reproductive-age women. In Ayurveda, diseases are explained through the lens of Dosha (functional energies), Dushya (affected tissues), and Srotasa (channels in the body). Health disorders, including PCOS, are considered to be a result of Dosha Vaishamyata (imbalance in Doshas), where symptoms (Lakshanas) directly reflect the dominant Dosha imbalance. This holistic understanding provides alternative avenues to explore PCOS management beyond modern medicine.

Methods: Exploration of classical Ayurvedic texts to understand how disorders like PCOS align with Dosha Vaishamyata and specific Lakshanas. Identification of patterns in PCOS symptoms corresponding to Vata, Pitta, and Kapha Dosha imbalances, with emphasis on Srotasa (channels affected) and Dushya involvement.

Results: PCOS can be understood through the lens of Vata, Pitta, and Kapha imbalances, with Vata and Kapha often being the predominant factors in symptom manifestation. Symptoms such as anovulation and menstrual changes correspond to Vata-Pitta Vaishamyata, while cyst formation aligns with Kapha Dushti (disturbance). Ayurvedic texts suggest that an imbalance in reproductive Srotasa may explain the disruption in ovarian function.

Discussion: Managing PCOS may benefit from a multidisciplinary approach, incorporating hormone regulation alongside Ayurvedic practices targeting Dosha balance. Future research could explore clinical trials using Ayurvedic therapies alongside biomedical treatment to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Polycystic ovary syndrome, PCOS, Ayurveda, Dosh Vaishmayata.

Impact of Drought stress on Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) genotypes

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Abstract

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most important and dependable food crops in the world. In Asia, more than two billion people get 60–70% of their daily calories from rice and products manufactured from it. 90 million tons of rice are produced annually on an average of 44 million hectares of land in India. Drought is the largest hazard to agriculture on a national and worldwidescale. Drought is one of the primary causes of damage in arid and semi-arid parts of the world. Drought stress lowers rice output and can potentially be lethal in severe situations. Rice is somewhat vulnerable to field dryness, just like almost every other crop species. The present study revealed the effects of drought stress on two rice genotypes at seedling stage. Variations were perceptible in different parameters including Root length, Relative Water Content and Electrolyte leakage. In the present study, drought stress cause increase in Root length, Electrolyte leakage while Relative Water Content was decreased in both rice genotypes. The study suggested that drought stress cause negative impact on rice genotypes at seedling stage.

Keywords: Rice, Drought, RWC, Root, Electrolyte

Assessing Runoff Dynamics and Water Security in the Baspa Basin: Impacts of Climate Change on Himalayan Glaciers

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Abstract

Himalayan glaciers are vital freshwater sources for millions in South Asia, supporting river systems that are essential for agriculture, drinking water, and hydropower. As climate change accelerates the melting of snow and glaciers, the dynamics of runoff from these sources are becoming increasingly intricate. Initially, the increase in meltwater can boost river flows, improving water availability. However, sustained melting leads to reduced glacier mass, ultimately threatening long-term water resources. Factors such as rising temperatures, changing monsoon patterns, and glacier dynamics contribute to this variability in runoff. Moreover, glacial lakes formed from melting ice present risks of outburst floods, endangering downstream communities. To effectively manage these resources, it is crucial to balance immediate water needs with sustainable usage, taking into account both ecological and socio-economic impacts of changing runoff patterns. Monitoring programs aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals emphasize the importance of water assessments in high-altitude regions. This study focuses on the Baspa basin, which feeds a 300 MW hydropower plant, to evaluate runoff patterns. Our analysis reveals a strong correlation between observed and modelled runoff using machine learning algorithms integrated with the SWAT model. From January 2000 to December 2024, total discharge in the basin was estimated at 17,000 m³/s, with average discharge rates reaching 470-650 m³/s during the ablation season from May to September. Overall, the annual discharge trend shows a slight increase over the observation period. These findings indicate potential water security challenges for local communities in the near future, underscoring the need for effective water management practices to safeguard the livelihoods of those living in these villages.

Keywords: Himalayan glaciers, Freshwater resources, Climate change, Runoff dynamics, Water security, Baspa basin, Hydropower, Machine learning, SWAT model, Glacial lakes, Flood risks, Sustainable water management, Ecological impacts, Socio-economic implications

Molasses Mix Replacement of Unworthy Calcium Liquid Sold in India

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Abstract

Cane molasses has several important roles in livestock feeding, due to the nutritive, appetizing and physical properties of its sugar content. An experiment was conducted to assess the lactation performance and Body growth of lactating crossbred dairy cows fed with molasses mix trace mineral oral liquid supplement (M group) with dose of 100 gm/400 kg body weight in compare with oral liquid calcium with 100 gm/400 kg body weight. A total of fifteen lactating cows were divided into three groups (C, M & Ca) with five cows in each group following completely randomized design on the basis of body weight and milk production. Cows were fed concentrate mixture, green fodder and wheat straw to meet the nutrient requirement. The control group (C) was fed basal diet without molasses mix trace mineral oral liquid supplement, whereas treatment group (M) was fed molasses mix trace mineral oral liquid supplement @ 100 gm/400 kg body weight & last group (Ca) was fed with traditional oral liquid calcium. The result showed increase in water intake, body condition score & milk production in molasses mix trace mineral oral liquid supplement group in comparison with the group which fed with traditional oral liquid calcium.

Keywords: Molasses, Calcium, Trace mineral, oral liquid, lactating crossbred

Importance, Challenges and Future Prospects of AYUSH Systems of Medicine

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Abstract

India is the only country that officially recognizes a variety of medical systems, including allopathy, Ayurveda, Yoga and naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, homeopathy, and Sowa Rigpa. Many Indians prefer traditional methods of treating their disease conditions, and this preference increases with wealth and education. Recently people from several developed and developing countries have been attracted toward traditional Indian herbal medicines. A large number of modern medicines are derived from the plants used in AYUSH traditional medical systems. Indian traditional medicines have sound scientific background of effectiveness and also acknowledged by the recent researches. Traditional herbal medicines of AYUSH systems are capable of addressing some modern unmet medical needs, and can provide the basis for developing potential medicines. However, lack of drug standardization information, quality control, and strict monitoring are the primary lacunae in the promotion of traditional Indian herbal products. Several regulatory and promotional steps have been undertaken in India to promote such medicines and to integrate them into clinical practice. Evidence based incorporation of Indian traditional medicine in clinical practice will help to provide quality healthcare to all.

Keywords: Ayurveda, AYUSH, Herbal medicines, Traditional herbal, primary lacunae

Effect on Antioxidant Status and Cellular Damage Indicators in Kidney of Wistar Rats Following Oral Exposure of Arsenic and Diallyl Disulfide

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Abstract

Arsenic is a potent environmental contaminant known to have potent health hazards in human and animals. Diallyl disulfide (DADS), an organosulfur metabolite of allicin from the herb garlic having numerous health benefits. The present study aims to determine the effect on antioxidant status and cellular damage indicators in kidney of Wistar rats following oral exposure of Arsenic and DADS. Forty-two adult Wistar rats were randomly allocated in seven groups with six rats in each. Group I served as control whereas in group II animals were administered with corn oil. Group III was given sodium arsenite (4.1 mg/kg b. wt. oral gavage). The rats in group IV and V were given DADS at a dose of 50 and 100 mg/kg b. wt. orally, respectively. Group VI and VII were administered sodium arsenite along with DADS at the rate of 50 mg/kg b. wt. and 100 mg/kg b. wt., respectively. Administrations of DADS produce dose dependent increases ($p < 0.05$) in the levels of plasma renal biomarkers (BUN, Cr, UA, Plasma Proteins) indicating renal damage. Levels of total antioxidant status (TAS), total thiols (TTH) and reduced glutathione (GSH) were significantly decrease ($p < 0.05$) the in renal tissue. Altered activities of hepatic antioxidant enzymes *viz.* SOD, CAT, GPx, GST, GR and increased cellular damage indicators (MDA, AOPP) along with histomorphology of kidney indicated nephrotoxicity in dose dependent manner in exposed rats. Simultaneous administration with arsenic and DADS significantly reduced these plasma and renal tissue biomarkers along-with histopathological changes. Observations of present study indicated arsenic produces antagonizing effects on nephrotoxicity induced by DADS in Wistar rats.

Keywords: DADS, sodium arsenite, glutathione, nephrotoxicity, Wistar rats, organosulfur

Assessment of children's Developmental Effect on the Mind

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Abstract

Child development refers to the continuous but predictably sequential biological, psychological and emotional changes that occur in human beings between birth and the end of adolescence. Developmental surveillance should be incorporated into every child visit. Parents play an important role in the child's developmental assessment. The primary care physician should educate and encourage parents to use the developmental checklist in the health booklet to monitor their child's development. Further evaluation is necessary when developmental delay is identified. This article aimed to highlight the normal child developmental assessment as well as to provide suggestions for screening tools and questions to be used within the primary care setting. Child development refers to the continuous but predictably sequential biological, psychological and emotional changes that occur in human beings between birth and the end of adolescence. The sequence of development is the same for all children and can be described in terms of developmental milestones. As children develop at different rates, which are determined by a complex interplay of environmental and genetic factors, the age of attainment for each milestone ranges widely. It is essential to not only be aware of the median age of attainment of the milestone (the age at which half of the standard population achieves the milestone) but the limit age as well (the upper age limit at which the particular milestone should have been achieved). This would help to guide the clinician on whether to reassure the parent/caregiver, monitor the child's development closely or refer the child to a specialist for a detailed assessment and further management. It is also essential for the clinician to assess the quality of the skill rather than taking note of the age at which the milestone was achieved. For example, a child may have acquired sufficient language skills to allow him to speak in phrases, but may be unskilled in using language for conversational purposes. The basic architecture of the brain is constructed by an ongoing process that begins before birth and continues into adulthood. Maximum brain development occurs within the first three years of a child's life and is hence called the early developmental phase. It is therefore essential to recommend that parents engage in appropriate stimulation activities with their children, starting from the newborn period.

Keywords: Child developmental, developmental screening tools, primary care, surveillance

In-Silico Pharmacokinetic Study of JM Herbal Formulation for screening of potential inhibitors of Aldose Reductase

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease defined by elevated blood sugar levels that are directly caused by insulin resistance, insufficient insulin production, or excessive glucagon secretion. The JM herbal drug is made from a blend of two plants which are shown to have anti-hyperglycemic and anti-oxidant effects. Human aldose reductase (AKR1B1) (EC 1.1.1.21), is an enzyme encoded by the AKR1B1 gene. It catalyzes the initial step of polyol pathway of glucose metabolism i.e. conversion of glucose to sorbitol. Polyol pathway is an important source of diabetes-induced oxidative stress. LDT is a known inhibitor of AKR1B1 (PDB: 1US0).

JM herbal formulation was prepared by mixing powder of dried leaves of *Moringa oleifera* and *Lagerstroemia speciosa* in 1:1 ratio. Its phytochemicals were extracted by 'maceration' method in 70% ethanol (1:20 w/v). LC-MS/MS (untargeted analysis) hydroalcoholic extract was performed at Central Discovery Centre- Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, where 1173 compounds were detected. Using PubChem database, the PubChem CID number and of these compounds were retrieved. Thereafter, compounds were screened for drug-likeness using Lipinski and Veber Filter. The 3D SDF files of the compounds which passed through Lipinski and Veber filter were retrieved. Using TOPKAT software, these compounds were subjected to *in-silico* screening for any possible toxicity, mutagenicity and carcinogenicity. The compounds screened out as non-toxic, non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic were tested for ADME parameters using SWISS ADME. The compounds which passed SWISS ADME test were subjected to *in-silico* screening for finding potential inhibitors of AKR1B1, using Discovery Studio 2021 computer-aided virtual screening technique. Libdock was used for virtual screening and scoring of LDT and candidate inhibitor compounds, and CDOCKER module was utilized for molecular docking analysis. Out of 1173 compounds, only 173 compounds were able to pass Lipinski's & Veber Filter, TOPKAT toxicity and SWISS ADME test. Out of these 173 compounds, 12 compounds yielded Libdock score, -CDOCKER Energy and -CDOCKER Interaction Energy higher than that of the scores of LDT (Control for 1US0). Based on these scores, CID No. 60957, 134601 and 152198 were screened out as most potential inhibitor of AKR1B1.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Glucagon secretion, Polyol pathway, Oxidative stress

Abstract for Poster Presentation

Essential oil of peels of *Citrus sp.* of North East India as a bio- preservative agent: A waste to wealth perspective

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ABSTRACT

Background: Fruit based industries basically use pulp to prepare juices and other products. The peel, seeds remain as major wastes. However, there is a vast scope to explore the phytochemicals of the waste products for their ability as nutraceuticals and bio preservatives.

Aim of the study: We studied the potential of essential oil (EO) of peels of four citrus fruits i.e. *Citrus jambhiri* (PL1), *Citrus medica* (PL2), *Citrus limon* (PL3) and *Citrus aurantifolia* (PL4) of North-East India and their effect on the shelf life and quality of pomegranate juice.

Methodology: EOs were extracted from samples using hydro distillation process. GC MS analysis was done to determine the chemical composition of the EOs. The antimicrobial activity was checked against food borne pathogens and antibiofilm activity was also checked at sub-Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of the EOs. The insilico toxicity was assayed by using ADME and pkCSM online tools and safety value was confirmed by invitro toxicity test against HEK293 cell line. These EOs were also used incorporated in fruit juice to see its effect on physicochemical parameters.

Results: The highest yield of EO showed by *Citrus jambhiri* and limonene was the major compound in all the samples. The PL1 showed highest antimicrobial activity against *Klebsiella pneumonia* followed by *Yersinia enterocolitica*. Antibiofilm activity of the essential oil was found in between 50% and 80.33% against the tested pathogens. The effect of EOs could resist and or buffer the changes in the physicochemical properties (pH, viscosity, titrable acidity, soluble solids, Vitamin C, total carbohydrate) of pomegranate juice which increased the shelf life of the juice. The EOs of the four samples showed significant antioxidant properties at different concentrations at range of 44% to 77%. The ADMET profile revealed that for all the compounds the Caco-2 permeability values was above 1 and intestinal absorption % found out to be above 90%. The invitro results of toxicity study revealed that all the oils i.e. PL1, PL2, PL3 and PL4 did not affect the viability of the normal cell line HEK293 at ½ MIC concentrations.

Conclusion:

Based on the significant observation in increased shelf life of pomegranate juice incorporated with EOs, we conclude that EOs behaved as a natural biopreservative. This outcome can be potentially commercialised.

Keywords: Citrus, essential oils, biopreservative, waste -to-wealth

Graphical Abstract

A Review of Adverse Reactions in the Growing Global Use of Herbal Medicines

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To investigate the global increase in the use of herbal medicines and supplements, identify the associated safety concerns, analyze the adverse reactions linked to these products, and examine the challenges in monitoring their safety to ensure public health protection.

Methodology: The study reviews various herbal remedies that have demonstrated therapeutic potential but highlights the safety concerns arising from their unregulated use. The review identifies common adverse effects associated with widely used herbal products like **Aristolochia, Ephedra, and Ginkgo biloba by analyzing case studies and existing literature**, focusing on risks such as **nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and carcinogenicity**. The methodology includes an assessment of the regulatory gaps, lack of proper labelling standards, and inadequate quality control measures. These factors are explored to illustrate how insufficient monitoring exacerbates the safety risks of herbal medicine use.

Results: Herbal remedies have shown therapeutic potential, but their widespread use without adequate monitoring has led to significant safety concerns, including adverse reactions and toxicities. Examples of adverse effects from popular herbal products like Aristolochia, Ephedra, and Ginkgo biloba are presented, demonstrating risks such as nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and carcinogenicity. The absence of rigorous quality controls, labeling standards, and regulatory oversight further exacerbates these safety risks.

Conclusions: It is concluded that the global use of herbal medicines is increasing, but significant challenges remain due to the lack of safety monitoring and regulatory frameworks. The need for standardized regulations, safety assessments, and pharmacovigilance is emphasized to ensure public health is protected and the safe use of herbal medicines is promoted.

Keywords: Herbal medicines, Adverse reactions, Regulatory challenges, public health, quality control.

Exploring the therapeutic potential of miRNAs in CML via regulation of Intrinsic Apoptotic pathways

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Abstract

Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) is a type of myeloproliferative neoplasm characterized by chromosomal translocation between chromosomes 9 and 22 at the early stem or progenitor cell stage, which results in the formation of the Philadelphia chromosome, a hallmark of the disease. While the introduction of TKIs has dramatically improved the survival outcomes. However, prolonged treatment often leads to resistance to these therapies over time. That results in the emergence of microRNA-based therapy as a promising alternative approach for its treatment. miRNAs, small non-coding RNAs that hold great applications in regulating key cellular processes such as cell differentiation, proliferation, migration, apoptosis, etc. by acting as oncogenes or tumor suppressors. miRNA might play a role in regulating the intrinsic pathway (mitochondrial pathway) which is initiated by the apoptotic stimuli and leads to the release of mitochondrial intermembrane space proteins into the cytosol, such as cytochrome C and SMACs. Proteins belonging to the BCL-2 family are the major regulators of mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis and are essential for leukemia and leukemia stem cells' survival. In CML upregulated expression of anti-apoptotic BCL-2 proteins such as BCL-x1 and MCL-1 is one way by which BCR-ABL signaling promotes cell survival. We predict the interaction between miRNA and different mRNAs by using miRdb, Target scan, DIANA, miRwalk, and RNA hybrid and STRING software for visualizing the interactions network of BCL2 protein with other proteins (PPIs) while we analyzed the pathway followed by our gene in apoptosis by the use of KEGG software and see functional enrichment analysis using g: profiler. Although few miRNAs targeting BCL-2 family genes have been identified so far they hold immense potential in regulating apoptosis and overcoming TKI resistance. Thus targeting these miRNAs might represent a promising approach for developing effective therapies against CML.

Keywords: CML, miRNA, BCL2, Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors (TKIs), Apoptosis regulation

EVALUATION OF WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY OF *CISSUS QUADRANGULARIS*

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ABSTRACT

Ethno pharmacological relevance: *Cissus quadrangularis*, commonly known as Hadjod, is used in folklore medicine in arresting bleeding and in skin diseases.

Aim: There was no scientific evidence justifying the use of *Cissus quadrangularis*, therefore the present study was aimed at evaluation of wound healing activity of the plant.

Materials and methods: In the present study the *Cissus quadrangularis* were studied for wound healing activity by incorporating the methanolic and the total aqueous extract in simple ointment base B.P. in concentration of 0.5% (w/w), 1% (w/w) and 2% (w/w). Wound healing activity was studied in three types of model in rats viz. excision, incision and estimation of biochemical parameter. In case of the excision wound model wound contraction and period of epithelization was studied while in incision wound model was evaluated by determining tensile strength and hydroxyproline content in the scab.

Results: Treatment of wound with ointment containing 2% (w/w) the methanolic and 2% (w/w) the total aqueous extract exhibited significant ($P < 0.001$) wound healing activity. The methanolic and total aqueous extracts were analyzed for total phenols content equivalent to Gallic acid. The content of total phenols was 11% (w/w) and 17% (w/w) in methanolic and total aqueous extract respectively.

Conclusion: The methanolic extract exhibited good wound healing activity probably due to phenols constituents.

Keywords: Wound healing *Cissus quadrangularis* Betadine, Incision, Excision

Quinoxaline motifs: Excellent pathfinders in therapeutic medicine

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, heterocycles are known to be one of the largest areas of research in organic chemistry. Quinoxaline belongs to the heterocyclic family of benzodiazine with its nitrogen heteroatom situated at 1- and 4-positions. Quinoxalines belong to a class of excellent heterocyclic scaffolds owing to their wide biological properties and diverse therapeutic applications in medicinal research. They are complementary in shapes and charges to numerous biomolecules they interact with, thereby resulting in increased binding affinity. The pharmacokinetic properties of drugs bearing quinoxaline cores have shown them to be relatively easy to administer either as intramuscular solutions, oral capsules or rectal suppositories. This work deals with recent advances in the synthesis and pharmacological diversities of quinoxaline motifs which might pave ways for novel drugs development.

Keywords- Quinoxalines, benzodiazine, pharmacokinetic, oral caps

Sustainable Wastewater Management: Exploring Nature-Based Treatment

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Abstract

The global water crisis impacts nearly two-thirds of the world's population each year, with projections indicating that by 2040, one in four children will be affected by severe water stress. Rapid urban expansion and industrial activities have led to the deterioration of aquatic ecosystems, prompting the UN to designate "Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all" as a key Sustainable Development Goal. Water pollution from agriculture, industry, landfills, and municipal systems poses significant threats to these ecosystems. While numerous methods have been developed to address water scarcity, contamination, and resource degradation, their high energy and chemical demands, coupled with environmental risks, often limit their effectiveness. Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) provide a promising alternative by utilizing natural processes to improve wastewater treatment and support ecosystem health. NBS, including constructed wetlands, waste stabilization ponds, green roofs, willow systems, and drainage ditches, leverage natural elements such as plants, soil, and microorganisms to tackle these issues effectively. This paper explores the effectiveness and additional benefits of various NBS in wastewater treatment and reuse. Constructed wetlands and waste stabilization ponds offer cost-effective, low-maintenance treatment through natural solar energy, requiring minimal operational input. Zero-discharge willow systems achieve high treatment efficiency with minimal environmental impact, using plant biomass for energy and soil enrichment. Green roofs and walls recycle greywater and enhance both aesthetic and environmental quality by integrating vegetation into urban infrastructure. Drainage ditches, with specific vegetation, help mitigate agricultural runoff and reduce the transfer of pollutants to water bodies. The results highlight the potential of NBS to deliver high treatment efficiencies and additional ecological and societal benefits, such as reduced operational costs, enhanced biodiversity, and alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), making NBS a viable complement to traditional wastewater management strategies.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Sustainable Development Goals, Nature-Based Solutions

Traditional use and practical effectivity of *Amaranthus spinosus* Linn as a therapeutic agent against jaundice

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ABSTRACT

Background: The medicinal plant *Amaranthus spinosus* Linn. is used by traditional healers in North East India to treat jaundice. Scientific validation of the plant is necessary to reveal its therapeutic potential.

Aim of the study: This study was carried out to determine the phytochemicals of *A. spinosus* and evaluate its efficacy against jaundice.

Methodology:

- Leaf extracts of *A. spinosus* was prepared in solvents by gradients of polarity and phytochemical analysis, antioxidant activity and bioactivity guided fractionation was done. Total phenolics and flavonoids were analyzed.
- Animals were induced with jaundice and the efficiency of the fraction was determined through the study.
- The phytoconstituents were identified using LCMS.

Results: Alkaloids, glycosides, steroids, proteins, saponins and terpenoids were detected qualitatively in various in the aqueous extract of the leaves. In the antioxidant assay, it was observed that the IC₅₀ of the aqueous leaf extracts showed significant activity (46.19±2.05 µg/ml) compared to the standard ascorbic acid (63.63±1.42 µg/ml). A bioactivity guided solvent fractionation showed a flavonoid content (4.8 mg QE/g) and phenolic content (71.21 mg GAE/g) in the butanol fraction.

The mice were divided into specific groups for animal studies. Group I (negative control), Group II (positive control), Group III (standard drug silymarin), Group IV (high dose of test sample) and Group V (low dose of test sample). No mortality was found when the fraction was given to mice for an acute toxicity test at dosages of 300, 500, or 1000 mg/kg body weight. Histopathology of the rat's liver in Group IV and Group V showed improved hepatocellular architecture and decreased necrosis, fatty degeneration and sinusoidal space similar to Group III which also showed a significant decrease in fatty degeneration and no

necrosis or inflammation. The histopathological study of heart and lung tissues also showed no significant anomalies.

Conclusions: A total of thirty-three phytochemicals were detected in the separated fraction of aqueous leaf extract of *A. spinosus* by LC-MS analysis, out of which eighteen compounds demonstrated drug-like characteristics and high gastrointestinal (GI) absorption. Amongst these, piperochromanoic acid is a strong candidate for natural medicine with a high degree of drug-likeness.

Keywords: Medicinal plants, *Amaranthus spinosus*, Jaundice, Piperochromanoic acid, CYP2C9, Hepatoprotective activity

Graphical Abstract:

Music therapy reduces the depression like behavior in a rat model of Chronic Unpredictable mild stress (CUMS)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Millions of people throughout the world suffer greatly from depression, a serious mental health illness that negatively affects how you feel. Depression have been linked to numerous health issues, such as loss of interest and cognitive impairment. Research indicates the positive behavioral effects of music therapy, a non-pharmacological passage, in ameliorating depression symptoms.

Aim of the study: The aim of this study was to identify the therapeutic effect of Indian Classical Music in Depressed Rat model induced by Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress (CUMS).

Methodology: 12 Adult male rats were divided into four groups: Group-1: Control, Group-2 : Chronic Unpredictable stress (CUMS), Group-3: CUMS+ Music and Group-4: Music. The rats of Group 2 and Group 3 were exposed to different stressors for 21 days and perform Sucrose Preference Test (SPT) for the confirmation of Depression, together with exposure of Music Therapy for 21 days (2 hours /day) to the Group 3 and Group-4, for the evaluation of the antidepressant benefits of Indian Classical Music and control group was maintained under laboratory condition. Rats were assessed in terms of weight change, Open-Field Test (OFT), Elevated Plus Maze and Sucrose Preference Test (SPT) for the assessment of Anhedonia, a key feature of depressive state.

Results: Results shows that CUMS group exhibited decrease in body weight, Music intervention appears to act as antidepressant as exhibited by results of open-field and elevated plus maze test.

Conclusions: These findings suggest the potential efficacy of targeted Music Therapy as a supplementary approach to alleviating depression and may be employed as a baseline for further studies.

Keywords: Depression, Chronic Unpredictable Stress (CUMS), Music Therapy, Behavioral parameters, Cognition, *Rattus norvegicus*

Investigating the molecular mechanism of artemisinin resistance in *Plasmodium falciparum*

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ABSTRACT

Since ancient times, malaria has been a deadly infectious disease among humans. At present malaria remains one of the major threats to global public health accounting for 249 million new cases of malaria and 608,000 malaria deaths in 2022 worldwide. WHO recommends artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) for the treatment of malaria caused by the *Plasmodium falciparum* parasite. Polymorphism in *P. falciparum Kelch13* (Pfk_{kelch13}) is currently the only confirmed marker for the artemisinin-resistant phenotypes in *P. falciparum* in which the resistant parasites exhibit impaired hemoglobin uptake, reduced heme yield, and thus decreased artemisinin (ART) activation. However, any direct involvement of Pfk_{kelch13} in heme-mediated ART activation has not been reported. In this study, we have characterized the recombinant versions of Pfk_{kelch13} and identified several novel biochemical properties of Pfk_{kelch13} *in vitro*. Here, we have established that the recombinant Pfk_{kelch13} wild-type protein displays a measurable binding affinity for heme, the main effector for artemisinin activation. The artemisinin resistance recombinant Pfk_{kelch13} mutants (C580Y and R539T) displayed weaker heme binding affinities compared to the artemisinin-sensitive WT and A578S mutant proteins, which might further be translated into reduced activity of artemisinin in resistant parasite. In summary, our study represents the first evidence that the heme-binding capacity of Pfk_{kelch13} regulates artemisinin activation, potentially influencing the resistance levels in malaria parasites with Pfk_{kelch13} mutations.

Keywords: *Plasmodium falciparum*, ART resistance (ART-R), Malaria, Heme, Kelch13 protein.

Evaluation of Subacute Effect Of Sodium Fluoride In *Channa Punctatus* Bloch. And Its Mitigation On Exposure to The Selected Citrus Fruits Peel Extract

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Fluoride has emerged as a persistent pollutant in groundwater, posing risks to aquatic ecosystems, especially freshwater fish, by disrupting metabolic functions and hazardous to human. Phytotherapy particularly herbal waste like fruit-peels offers an eco-friendly solution for fluoride remediation. These natural adsorbents can help to mitigate fluoride pollution sustainably, cost-effectively.

Aim: The study aims to investigate the effects of sodium fluoride on *C. punctatus* to assess the potential amelioration of methanolic peel extracts, *Citrus reticulata*, *Citrus jambhiri* individually and in combination.

Methodology: Fresh orange-lemon were collected, identified, their peel of methanolic extraction were subjected to phytochemical screening with GC-MS analysis to detect bioactive components. *C.punctatus* was exposed to sublethal sodium fluoride (NaF) concentrations (25 ppm and 50 ppm) for 7 days. The fishes were treated with peel extracts (100mg/L) individually and in combination after withdrawal of NaF exposure. The study focuses on behavioral, histopathological, hematological, biochemical parameters changes following standard methods.

Results: The result showed behavioural, physiological disorder in fishes, including erratic operculum movement, depigmentation, mucus secretion, scale shedding, hemorrhagic-areas. Hematological data revealed reduction in RBCs count, hemoglobin, cell size, while WBC counts initially increased at low concentrations but reduced at high doses. Histopathologically, NaF exposure caused hepatocyte disintegration, cytoplasmic vacuolation in liver tissue at low concentrations, alongwith severe vacuolation, focal-coagulative necrosis, blood-vessel congestion at high concentration, alongside epithelial cell lifting, lamellar fusion in the gills and glomerular degeneration in the kidney. Treatment with citrus peel extracts especially combined formulations, effectively mitigated the toxicity of NaF in fishes.

Conclusion: The study showed the effectiveness of lemon-orange peel extracts in attenuating fluoride toxicity, the efficacy of which is more in combined formulation than individual ones. The findings highlighted herbal-wastes becoming a promising avenue in managing environmental fluoride contamination.

Keywords: NaF, *C. punctatus*, peels, bioactive components.

Comparative Analysis of Growth Parameters and Metabolite Profiling of *Clitoria ternatea* L. Grown in Soil and Hydroponic System

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Clitoria ternatea* L., a medicinal plant used in ayurveda which is gaining attention due to its wide applications in other system of medicine, and the food industry. Due to its increasing demand, there is a need to explore alternative modes of cultivation, such as hydroponics, for sustainable production.

Aim of the study: The present study compares the growth, photosynthetic parameters, and metabolite profiles of *Clitoria ternatea* L. plants cultivated in soil and hydroponic systems.

Methodology: *Clitoria ternatea* L. plants were cultivated under soil and hydroponic conditions. Growth and photosynthetic parameters were measured at two-week time intervals. After eight weeks, metabolite profiling was carried out using UHPLC-HRMS. Data analysis was performed using MS DIAL and MS FINDER.

Results: Hydroponically grown plants showed increased growth, height, leaf number, shoot development, and biomass compared to soil-grown plants. Photosynthetic parameters were high initially, but by week eight, soil-grown plants exhibited higher photosynthetic parameters. Metabolomic profiling identified 341 compounds in soil-grown plants and 405 compounds in hydroponically-grown plants. Ninety-one compounds were common between soil and hydroponically grown plants. Metabolites such as harpagoside (113.17 fold increase), salicin (90.931 fold increase), victoxinine (83.551 fold increase), arbutin (80.611 fold increase), sofalcone (78.658 fold increase), neolinustatin (42.825 fold increase) and adenosine (38.86 fold increase) were highest in hydroponically grown plants compared to soil-grown plants.

Conclusions: The results suggest that hydroponic cultivation can significantly improve the biomass and metabolite diversity of *Clitoria ternatea* L. These findings highlight the potential of hydroponics as an alternative for improving the yield and medicinal value of *Clitoria ternatea* L.

Keywords: *Clitoria ternatea* L, Hydroponics, Growth parameters, Photosynthetic parameters, Metabolite profile

Construction and Development of FRET-based nanosensor for real-time monitoring of putrescine

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Abstract

One of the most basic polyamines found in all living things is putrescine (1, 4-Diaminobutane). The decomposition of amino acids (decarboxylation of arginine and ornithine) in decaying animals results in the formation of this odorous substance. It is a highly basic, low molecular weight substance that interacts with negatively charged macromolecules such as acidic proteins, membranes, DNA, and RNA. Cell growth and division, stress resistance, genetic metabolism, transcription, translation, and post-translational modifications are only a few of its many functions. Recent research showed that under high-temperature stress, PAs can promote photosynthesis, and increase the antioxidant capacity and osmotic adjustment ability of plants. Patients with intellectual impairment, cancer, and ageing are negatively impacted by its high level. Nonetheless, when it is at its best, it reduces the risk of several cardiovascular conditions and lengthens people's lives. Polyamines and reactive oxygen species have a complex interaction; on the one hand, they defend against ROS, but on the other, their metabolism generates ROS, which damages nucleic acids and induces oxidative stress, impairing the normal physiology of both plants and animals. Putrescine are present in cells at relatively high concentrations in the mM range, suggesting their potential importance as a source of nitrogen and could be a substitute for inorganic nitrogen. The lack of suitably sensitive sensing systems has limited this field's research. In this research, we created a nanosensor based on fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET), by sandwiching the regulatory domain (RD) of SpuD between two fluorescent moieties. Using fluorescent proteins, GFP variants as FRET pairs, we have constructed and developed a FRET-based nanosensor. ECFP and mVenus were connected at the N and C terminals, respectively, with the putrescine binding protein, SpuD. This sensor makes use of the ratiometric FRET ratio and conformational changes in the binding receptor, SpuD. A promising, quickly developing, non-invasive, and cost-effective method that enables real-time putrescine monitoring is this FRET-based sensor. This sensor provides putrescine detection that is quick, precise, sensitive, selective, and dependable.

Keywords: Polyamine, putrescine, FRET, nanosensor, real-time, non-invasive

Bio-accumulation of heavy metal Cadmium in muscle tissues of abdominal region of *Channa punctatus* and its potential impact on the protein composition

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Abstract

The fish nutrition as an area of the research is growing these days. A small fish *Channa punctatus* is popular for its fatty acid profile, amino acid, high protein content and high moisture content. But due to rapid industrialization, water-pollution² and massive use of fertilisers, heavy metals are getting deeply engrossed in plant and animal tissues. Cadmium chloride is a toxic and a non-essential heavy metal found in the environment that may alter the nutritional profile of fishes. In the present experiment, several sub-lethal levels of Cadmium chloride were administered to *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) were chemically analysed with the help of Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer in order to determine the bio-accumulation of Cadmium chloride in the muscle tissues and its impact on protein absorption. According to the present observations and findings, the amount of cadmium chloride that accumulated in the muscular tissue of *Channa punctatus* rose as exposure duration and concentration increased. Regarding exposure duration and cadmium chloride concentration, there was a decrease in protein content among the bio-chemicals. According to the current study, fish suffer stress and physiological changes when heavy metal ions are present in their aquatic habitat. These changes have a harmful effect on fish and cause an imbalance in the aquatic population.

Keywords: Cadmium chloride, *Channa punctatus*, muscle tissues, bio-accumulation, protein level

Music modulates ethophysiological and the biochemical parameters of stressed rats

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ABSTRACT

Music therapy has gained attention as a non-invasive tool for modulating physiological and biochemical processes. This study aimed to explore the effects of music therapy on ethophysiological responses and enzymatic activities of oxidative stress markers in male Wistar albino rats. Twenty male rats were taken for the study and the cognitive functions of rats were assessed through various behavioral assays (*viz.*, Elevated plus maze, y-maze and open field test) in four groups *viz.*, Group I-Control; Group II- Stress; Group III- Stress + Music; Group IV- Music. The rats of group-II and group-III were exposed to the heat stress for the duration of three days and then group-III as well as group-IV rats exposed to Indian classical music therapy for fifteen days (2 hours/day during morning) while the control group was maintained under standard laboratory conditions without music exposure. The enzymatic activity of oxidative stress markers *viz.*, MDA, SOD, CAT and GPx were measured in tissues *viz.*, brain, lung, liver, kidney and testes. The findings of the experiment demonstrated that music therapy significantly reduced anxiety-like behaviors in the stress+music exposed group, evidenced by increased exploratory behavior and decreased immobility. Furthermore, the enzymatic activities of superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione peroxidase showed marked elevation in stress+music exposed in comparison to the stressed group, indicating enhanced antioxidative defense mechanisms in response to music. Lipid peroxidation levels, assessed via malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration, were observed as lower level in music-exposed group of rats, suggesting a protective effect of music against oxidative stress. These findings provide insights into the therapeutic potential of music in managing stress-related conditions and can be further employed in stress management studies.

Keywords: *Music therapy, Cognition, Behavioral assay, Biochemical assay, Rattus norvegicus*

Synthesis, Antimycotic and Antileishmanial Potential of Some New Derivatives 1,3,4-Oxadiazole and 1,2,4-Triazole

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Abstract

Methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate on reaction with 2-methylbenzyl chloride resulted in 4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) benzoate which on hydrazinolysis gave 4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) benzoyl hydrazine. Benzoyl hydrazine on reaction with potassium isopropyl xanthate in isopropyl alcohol resulted in 5-(4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol. Benzoyl hydrazine when treated with phenylisothiocyanate, gave 1-(4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) benzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide which underwent cyclization in the presence of sodium hydroxide to give 5-(4-(2-methylbenzyloxy) phenyl)-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol. Both oxadiazole and triazole on reaction with amines in the presence of formaldehyde, substituted aralkyl halides and aroyl halides gave N-aminomethylated, S-alkylated and s-arylated oxadiazoles and triazoles. The structures of the compounds have been elucidated with help of elemental and spectral (IR, NMR and Mass) analysis. Compounds have been evaluated for their antimycotic potential against human pathogenic fungi and *Leishmania donovani* causal organism of Leishmaniasis.

Keywords: oxadiazole, triazole, antimycotic potential, antileishmanial potential

Comparative Study of Packaging Materials for Beta-Carotene Stability in Sweet Potato Chips under Sun and Shade

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the effect of beta-carotenoid content in golden sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*) chips stored in three types of packaging materials—white plastic, aluminum foil, and commercial chips packets—under two storage environments: shadow and sunlight. The analysis was conducted at intervals of 15, 30, and 45 days to assess the stability and degradation of beta-carotene, a key nutrient in sweet potatoes known for its health benefits and sensitivity to environmental conditions such as light, temperature, and oxygen exposure.

The chips were packaged and stored under both sun and shadow conditions, and beta-carotenoid levels were analyzed using spectrophotometric methods at each time interval. Results showed that aluminum foil provided the best protection against beta-carotenoid degradation, especially when the chips were stored in the shade, with minimal nutrient loss observed over the 45-day period. In contrast, chips stored in white plastic and commercial chips packets exhibited significant losses in beta-carotenoid content, particularly under sunlight, where rapid degradation occurred after 15 days.

The findings demonstrate that the choice of packaging material and storage conditions significantly affect the retention of beta-carotenoids in golden sweet potato chips. Aluminum foil in shaded conditions proved to be the most effective for preserving the nutritional quality of the chips over time.

Keywords: *Ipomoea batatas*, beta-carotenoids, nutritional quality, spectrophotometric methods

Survey, collection and exploration of lichen secondary metabolites

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Abstract

Background: Lichens, which are symbiotic organisms made up of fungi, algae, and cyanobacteria, are vital components of many ecosystems, helping to maintain biodiversity, cycle nutrients, and monitor the environment. They are a source of plethora of bioactive compound that belong to depside, depsidones, dibenzofurans, and pulvinic acid derivatives. This research focuses on the collection and identification of lichen species, as well as the characterization of their secondary metabolites, which have been linked to possible pharmaceutical applications.

Aim of the study: This study focuses on extraction, purification and characterization of lecanoric acid, a secondary metabolite from *Parmotrema tinctorum*.

Methodology: Lichen samples were collected from Nanidhar, Himachal Pradesh, and identification was done on the basis of morphological, anatomical, and biochemical analyses (spot test and TLC) of lichens. The identified samples were submitted in the herbarium at NBRI, Lucknow, and the accession number of the submitted herbarium was obtained. The identified samples were subjected to phytochemical analysis to isolate and identify secondary metabolites by utilizing HPLC, HRMS, NMR and FTIR.

Results: Major secondary metabolites primarily identified in the lichens on the basis of UV-visible spectroscopy and HPLC analysis were atranorin, salazinic acid, lecanoric acid, and sekikaic acid. Lecanoric acid, obtained from *Parmotrema tinctorum* was further used. HPLC analysis identified lecanoric acid having λ_{\max} at 212, 270, and 304 and the retention time of 1.156 min. HPLC purified sample further showed the m/z ratio (317.066) from HRMS. HRMS, NMR, and FTIR data confirm that the HPLC-purified compound was lecanoric acid.

Conclusions: Thus, it can be concluded that lecanoric acid is a prominent secondary metabolite present in *Parmotrema tinctorum*.

Keywords: FTIR; HPLC; Identification; Lichen, NMR

From healing to harm: The toxic reality of contaminated and poor quality medicinal plants

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal herbs rich in bioactive compounds are crucial for human health and sustainable medical protocols. However, poor-quality medicinal herbs, often due to contamination, have become a growing concern in the field of herbal medicine. The quality of traditional medicines and herbal remedies are often compromised by the presence of contaminants from either natural or anthropogenic sources, which may result in adverse effects and even death. Contaminants such as heavy metals (Ar, Pb, Cd, Cr, Hg, Zn, Ni, Mn) and chemical pesticides (insecticides, herbicides, rhodenticides, fungicides) can compromise the safety of medicinal plants. Additionally, secondary metabolites (alkaloids, phenolics, terpenoids, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins etc.) produced by plants in response to contaminants can alter the medicinal content, reducing their therapeutic value and increasing toxicity. The consumption of these poor-quality herbs poses serious health risks, ranging from acute poisoning to chronic health conditions. The issue is exacerbated by the long-term consumption or excessive doses of these plants, often in the form of paste, powder, boiled preparations, or direct ingestion of dried or raw plant parts such as leaves, stems, and roots. Uncertified herbal medicines, particularly those with unknown or improperly labelled dosages, present significant health risks to the public. The lack of standardization and regulation in the production and distribution of herbal medicines further complicates the issue, leading to increased cases of poisoning. Medicinal plants have been selected for the current study *Catharanthus*, *Glycyrrhiza*, *Mentha*, *Ocimum*, and *Withania* that are extensively dispersed over the Indian subcontinent, and have been a dietary supplement in diet of its citizen. This study provides an over view of the heavy metals and pesticides on medicinal plants and its impact on plants, which may risk human health. The study also aims to explore the link between toxicity and daily use of medicinal plants and plant based drugs and their escalating toxicity over time.

Keywords: Heavy metals, Pesticides, Toxicity, Health risk, Contaminants

An industrial fast growing hardwood tree species for timber, pulp and paper

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ABSTRACT

Gmelina arborea Roxb. is a fast-growing tree species of family Lamiaceae, naturally distributed in Eastern sub-Himalayan tract, Aravali Hills, Western Peninsula, Indo-Gangetic Plains, Western Himalayas and Central India. It is commercially important tree species for various wood-based industries and an excellent choice for high quality timber, pulp and paper. Unscientific extraction of wood from forests, has principally been to be the main reason for degradation of existing gene pool. The wood fibers are considered to be trustworthy partner of pulp and paper-based industries and therefore a species like *Gmelina arborea* can be considered as an alternate hardwood for industrial raw material. A scientific survey of North-Western regions was therefore carried out to explore appropriate genotypes. Consequently, extensive work was executed to measure growth characteristics of tree height, diameter at breast height (DBH), clear bole height (CBH), collar diameter (CD), stem straightness (SS), branching behavior (BB) and crown diameter (CD). These growth traits were found to be the most importance ones to carry out conventional methods of selection through indexing, which ultimately lead to screening of superior trees with higher weightage. Thereafter quantitative wood anatomical traits of selected trees were measured under a compound microscope (LABOMED, Model- CRX III) viz. fiber length, fiber diameter, fiber lumen diameter, vessel length and vessel diameter. The fiber length ranged from 300- 1900 μ m, similarly fiber diameter ranged from 12.5-45 μ m, fiber lumen diameter ranged from 5-40 μ m, wall thickness ranged from 2.5-31.25 μ m, vessel length ranged from 100-980 μ m and vessel diameter ranged from 40-320 μ m. Specific gravity was calculated to range between 0.30 to 0.67. The photomicrographs of different anatomical features were taken with the aid of microscope model Leica equipped with camera (FLEXA CAM C1) and software Leica microsystems (LEICA DM 3000 LED). The wide range variability for various growth and wood parameters indicates possibility of further genetic improvement and selection of appropriate genotypes for commercial deployment.

Keywords: *Gmelina arborea*, hardwood, wood fibers, wood anatomy.

Title- Broad spectrum insect resistance in cotton generated by bio-methanol

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ABSTRACT

The plant cell wall is a complex structure made up of an interacting network of polysaccharides, proteins, and other polymers. Cellulose, hemicelluloses, and pectin are the major polysaccharides, with pectin accounting for 35% of the primary cell wall in dicotyledonous species. Pectin are found in plant cell wall are composed of homogalactouronans (HGs). Pectin methylesterases (PMEs) generate methanol during the de-methylation of cell wall pectin. Plants emit volatile organic compound (VOCs) throughout its developmental stage. Plant naturally emit methanol as a volatile organic compound, methanol is toxic to insect pest. Biotic and mechanical induction up-regulate methanol emission. In the present study we demonstrate that the over express pectin methylestreses derived from *Withania somnifera* in the cotton plant through *Agrobacterium* mediated genetic transformation. *WsPME* gene was further over-expressed in cotton under control of constitutive and wound inducible promoter. Transgenic plant comprising constitutive and inducible *WsPME* expression system have been shown 90-95% mortality against chewing pest(*Helicoverpa armigera*, *Spodoptera litura*) and 90% mortality against sap sucking pest (*Bemisia tabaci*).Therefore, we show that over-expression of *WsPME* provides resistance against chewing and sap sucking pest.

Keywords: PME, Genetic transformation, Methanol, VOCs

TRADITIONAL SYSTEM OF MEDICINE (AYUSH)

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ABSTRACT

Background: India's rich legacy of traditional healing methods is embodied in the AYUSH medical system, which consists of Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy. These systems offer complementary and alternative solutions to traditional medicine in light of the growing interest in holistic health around the world.

Aim of the study: This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness and integration of AYUSH systems in contemporary healthcare, assess patient outcomes, and explore the challenges faced in their adoption.

Methodology: A mixed-methods approach was used, integrating qualitative interviews with patients and practitioners with quantitative data from surveys and treatment trials. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) were used to evaluate clinical efficacy, and structured interviews and questionnaires given to AYUSH practitioners and patients in both urban and rural areas were used to gauge patient happiness and accessibility.

Results: The results show that AYUSH practices greatly enhance mental health, general well-being, and patient outcomes for chronic illnesses. Patients using AYUSH therapy reported high levels of satisfaction, according to quantitative data. However, obstacles to incorporation into mainstream healthcare were found to include things like lack of standardization, regulatory obstacles, and low provider awareness.

Conclusions: The AYUSH systems have a great deal of promise for improving health outcomes and offering comprehensive treatment. In order to promote a more all-encompassing approach to health and wellbeing, it may be easier to embrace and incorporate these ancient methods into international healthcare frameworks by addressing the issues of standardization, regulation, and awareness. To improve the legitimacy and accessibility of AYUSH methods, further research is required to create standardized procedures and norms.

Keywords: AYUSH, Traditional Medicine, Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, Homeopathy, Holistic Health

PHARMECOLOGICAL REVIEW OF LODHRA

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, the oldest medical science of the Indian Subcontinent, been practised since 1000 B.C. with objectives to accomplish physical, mental, social and spiritual wellbeing by adopting, health promoting holistic approach towards life. Today's contemporary era, main emphasis is given on plant researches as large evidence has been available to show the huge potential of medicinal plants used in various traditional systems. Ayurvedic literature cite *Lodhra*, a common indigenous medication, as a cure for a number of human diseases. This tree has several traditional medicinal purposes, such as treating Gynaecological disorders, Vaginal Discharge, Abortion, snake bites, diarrhea, dysentery and digestive complaints. Majority of phytopharmacological reports are on stem bark of the plant which include anti-cancer, hepatoprotective, anti-oxidant, anti-androgenic effect, anti-inflammatory, wound healing activity and anti-diabetic effects. Herbal medications are the main focus of the modern world since they have the ability to treat a wide range of human ailments with little to no negative side effects. The primary focus is on the about various biological, chemical composition, pharmacological activity and it is our traditionally remedial gift from nature.

Material and Methods: All relevant worldwide accepted databases have been searched for the name "*S. racemosa*" along with other literature from Indian Classical texts and Pharmacopoeias. The accessible literatures available on *S. racemosa*, were collected through electronic search on Pub med, Scopus, Science direct and traditional reports.

Results & Conclusions: *Lodhra* Every study conducted on *Lodhra* and its derivatives demonstrates that it has a significant number of active metabolites, indicating that it can be utilized to treat a wide range of illnesses. An in-depth explanation of this tree has been attempted in the hopes that it would aid in the provision of evidence-based care. Because of its ability to balance the pitta and kapha doshas, *lodhra* has been thoroughly explained. It is also known as *Rodhra* because of the plant's *Rodhaka* (arresting) characteristic. *Lodhra* reduces the vaginal discharge because of *Rodhra Guna*. cleans the wound, stops the bleeding, and starts the wound's quick healing process. It has been regarded as the preferred medication for treating gynaecological conditions. Menorrhagia, leucorrhoea (excessive vaginal discharge), and other menstrual problems have been treated with *Lodhra*. It also helps with vaginal ulcers, miscarriages, and abortions. Because of its *Grahi* (anti-diarrheal) properties, *Lodhra* has been used safely to treat gastro intestinal diseases for thousands of years, such as *Atisar*, *Netra Hitkara*, and *Rakta Dosha Nashaka* are the characteristics of *Lodhra*. This tree's bark is employed in numerous Ayurvedic formulations for the treatment of many ailments, particularly gynaecological ones, because it contains cooling, astringent, styptic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial qualities. It helps treat liver, dropsy, and skin conditions including leprosy.

Keywords: *Lodhra*, gynaecological conditions, Vaginal Discharge

Structure-based exploration of CYP17A1 inhibitors from the *Andrographis paniculate* for the treatment of castration-resistant prostate cancer:

Computational approach

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ABSTRACT

Background: Castration-resistant prostate cancer (CRPC) is an advanced and more challenging stage of prostate cancer (PCa) that is resistant to androgen deprivation therapy (ADT). ADT initially works well to slow the growth of PCa because it either inhibits or reduces androgen hormone levels in the body. Unfortunately, many patients have resistance to it, which outcomes develop in CRPC, which advances with low levels of testosterone. In humans, cytochrome P450 17 α -hydroxylase/17,20-lyase (CYP17A1) is a key enzyme for the biosynthesis of androgens. The primary survival route for PCa cells is the androgen signalling cascade, and the standard for treating patients with both locally developed and metastatic PCa is still ADT. There have been reports of drug resistance, toxicity, and decreasing efficacy with available synthetic drugs. Therefore, identifying novel natural plant-based CYP17A1 lyase inhibitors might aid in avoiding side effects and enhancing pharmacological activity.

Aim of this study: This study aims to use computational methods to identify CYP17A1 lyase inhibitors targeting CRPC.

Methodology: A structure-based computational approach was employed to identify CYP17A1 lyase inhibitors. The study began with the retrieval and preparation of the 3D-crystal structure of the target protein (PDB ID: 3RUK). A virtual screening of a chemical library of 39 phytochemicals of the *Andrographis paniculate* plant from the Indian medicinal plants Phytochemistry and Therapeutics 2.0 (IMPPAT2.0) database was conducted to predict compounds with high binding affinity for the ligand-binding domain of the target protein. The top three hit compounds were further refined through molecular docking using the Chimera Auto Dock Vina plugin. Moreover, ADMET analyses were conducted to assess the drug-likeness properties of the lead compounds. Additionally, normal mode analysis (NMA) and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations using the iMODS server.

Results: All three phytochemical compounds showed considerable interactions with the active site of the CYP17A1 lyase protein, i.e., IMPHY011654-CYP17A1 (-10.8 kcal/mol), IMPHY014838-CYP17A1 (-10.6 kcal/mol), IMPHY014842-CYP17A1 (-10.3 kcal/mol), and reference ligand Abiraterone acetate-CYP17A1 (-10.5 kcal/mol). Additionally, when ADMET was performed using Swiss-ADME, all lead compounds showed acceptable drug-likeness. Furthermore, in NMA-based MD simulations using the iMODS server, all lead complexes showed acceptable stability.

Conclusions: The computational approach successfully identified a potential plant-based small-molecule CYP17A1 lyase inhibitor that may be used as treatment for CRPC. Further, the top three leading identified phytochemical compounds will be considered for validation in vitro studies.

Keywords: CYP17A1 lyase inhibitors, prostate cancer, *Andrographis paniculate*, castration-resistant prostate cancer, molecular docking.

Physiochemical Analysis, Antioxidant Activity, Antimicrobial Activity and Phenolic Profile of *Ipomoea Eriocarpa* R. Br. Leaves

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the current study was assessment of physiochemical properties as well as the measurement of pharmacological activity of ethanolic and chloroform extract. The antioxidant property determinant Scavenging activity was examined as well as calculated through DPPH and ABTS assays which is an antioxidant parameter. The antimicrobial parameters were assessed with help of the disk diffusion method on a range of bacterial and fungal strains. The finding from their experiments determined that among all solvents ethanol was the one of best solvent for extracting polyphenols. Glycosides, flavonoids as bioactive molecule, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, carbohydrates as well as tannins were observed in *Ipomoea eriocarpa*. Additionally with these experiments fluorescence characteristics of components, and physiochemical parameters provided data that can be used to establish standards for this plant. Results of quantitative phytochemical estimation revealed that to the ethanol extract had a higher phenolic content (71.82 mg/g GAE) and flavonoid content (82.7 mg/g QE) but lowest TPC was observed in the aqueous extract. (27.05 mg/g GAE) and there flavonoid content is (18.93 mg/g QE). The *I. eriocarpa* the ethanolic extract had the maximum antioxidant scavenging activity for DPPH (32.36 µg/mL) & the value for ABTS is (55.54µg/ mL). The results of the antimicrobial activity assessment contain the ethanol based extract exhibited greater inhibition of zone when tested with respect to both microbial strains. Results were suggested that the ethanolic extract has promising antioxidant potential and has the capability of being a notable source of antioxidants to the formulation of drugs.

Keywords: *Ipomea eriocarpa*, antioxidant, phytochemical analysis, Antimicrobial

Dietary Attitude of Pregnant Women in Anemia

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Abstract

Background: Anemia is a widespread nutritional deficiency and a major public health issue. During pregnancy, anemia is characterized by a hemoglobin concentration of <110 g/L. Data reveals an increase in anemia prevalence among pregnant women in India, rising from 50.4% in NFHS-4 to 52.2% in NFHS-5, indicating a deteriorating trend in maternal anemia rates. Nutritional education plays a crucial role in developing healthy eating habits and improving diet quality, which are essential for positive pregnancy outcomes.

Objectives: The aim of this study was to explore the dietary attitudes of pregnant women attending the antenatal OPD at Sir Sundar Lal Hospital, BHU, Varanasi, UP.

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted, collecting information on dietary attitudes from 400 antenatal women at SSL Hospital, BHU, Varanasi.

Results: Out of the total pregnant women, 85.5% followed a special diet during pregnancy. Among the pregnant women, 67.3% reported often (5-7 days) consumption of green leafy vegetables, and 82.3% reported often (5-7 days) consumption of dry fruits.

Conclusions: The study reveals that a significant majority (85.5%) of pregnant women followed a special diet during pregnancy, reflecting an awareness of the importance of nutrition. Notably, 67.3% of women reported frequent consumption of green leafy vegetables, and 82.3% indicated regular intake of dry fruits, suggesting a positive inclination toward incorporating nutrient-rich foods into their diets. These dietary habits suggest positive engagement with nutritional practices during pregnancy, although there is still scope for further improvement, particularly in increasing the intake of green leafy vegetables. Targeted nutritional education and support can help optimize dietary practices, contributing to better maternal and fetal health outcomes.

Keywords: anemia, pregnancy, nutritional deficiency, special diet, dietary attitudes.

Diatom based ecological assessment of Himalayan rivers in the Kumaon region

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Abstract

Background: The Himalayan River systems, which are crucial to the ecological balance of the region by supporting rich biodiversity hotspot, supporting thousands of plant and animal species, contributing to environmental health are increasingly under threat due to climatic changes and anthropogenic activities. Diatoms, a group of microscopic algae, serve as effective bioindicators of environmental conditions in freshwater ecosystems due to their sensitivity to environmental changes, particularly in water quality.

Aim of the study: The study evaluates the ecological health of Himalayan rivers using diatom communities, assessing species composition, abundance, and diversity, and using diatom indexes to monitor environmental stressors.

Methodology: Samples were collected from 17 locations of Kumaon region, Uttarakhand. Some physicochemical parameters of water were examined on-site and rest in the laboratory. Descriptive analysis was used to calculate the mean and standard deviation of 14 physicochemical variables of the 17 sampling stations. PCA and CCA were used to present data and identify pollution locations. CA was used to identify a cluster of comparable pollution locations dispersed over the river stretch. Biotic and diversity indices assessed the river system's health and response to environmental stressors.

Results: Descriptive analysis revealed that pristine sites had greater DO concentrations while polluted sites had higher BOD, COD, nitrate, nitrite, and phosphate values. The hierarchical agglomerative cluster analysis applied on physicochemical data to grouped the sites into 3 clusters denoting pristine, less polluted, and moderately polluted sites. The clusters formed were in coherence with the groupings observed in PCA. The computed values of WQI allocated a good water quality class to most of the sites. The strong linkage between environmental variables and diatom species were observed in the CCA ordination. Most of the ecological preferences of diatoms recorded worldwide were similar in the present studies.

Conclusions: The Himalayan Rivers are clean, suitable for bathing (category IV & V) according to CPCB guidelines. Water quality indicators (WQI) are divided into pristine, less polluted, moderate, and seriously polluted sites. Benthic diatom populations can assess water quality, with strong correlations with TDI, IPS, IDG, and EPI-D indices. Integrating diatom analysis into environmental monitoring of high-altitude ecosystem led to better management strategies for this fragile ecosystem.

Keywords: Himalayan rivers, Bioindicators, Diatom indices, WQI, CPCB

Assessing the Effects of Colchicine on Cytology, Chlorophyll, and Stomatal Characteristics in Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*)

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Abstract

Hordeum vulgare L. ($2n=2x=14$) commonly known as Barley and belongs to Poaceae family. It was grown earliest since the dawn of civilization and considered one of the first domesticated crops. It was widely considered as a drought-resistant crop that help to cultivate in wide range of climatic and photoperiodic conditions. For the past six decades, it had served as a model plant for examining the cyto-genetical impacts of various mutagens. In the course of plant evolution, polyploidy was considered as a crucial mechanism for plant diversity and the production of genetic variants. For the reason, Barley seeds were treated with a range of colchicine concentrations (0.05%–0.4%) for 24 h in order to induce polyploidy and its effect on chromosomes, chlorophyll content and stomatal variations. The somatic chromosome number was counted and observed the presence of tetraploids ($2n=4x=28$), increased chlorophyll content and variations in stomata density and size. The increased chlorophyll content suggested better photosynthetic efficiency for treatments than control. Similarly, variations in stomata density and size indicated potential improvements in gas exchange and water use efficiency than control. Therefore, the present results indicated the colchicine concentration could be useful to improve the chlorophyll content, stomata density and size through tetraploid induction provided important and basic information for further studies in the improvement of *H. vulgare* L. and diversity.

Keyword: *Hordeum vulgare*, colchicine, polyploidy, stomata density and tetraploid

***Serendipita indica* and Salicylic acid synergy alleviates arsenic toxicity in *Ocimum sanctum*: understanding physio-biochemical adaptation**

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Abstract

Heavy metal and metalloid contamination of agricultural soil has become a significant global problem. Arsenic (As) toxicity is a persistent environmental contaminant, it poses an imminent risk to both human health and plant growth. Plants grown in As contaminated soil or irrigated with As containing water showed high levels of As accumulation in edible parts. Elevated levels of As impeded vital physio-biochemical functions, hence reduce development and productivity of plants. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the interactive impact of *Serendipita indica* inoculation and salicylic acid (SA) to alleviate As stress in *Ocimum sanctum*. Pot experiments were conducted using *S. indica* inoculation and SA (1mM) treatment in 50 μ M, and 100 μ M sodium arsenite (NaAsO₂) effected *O. sanctum* plants. As toxicity results in a substantial reduction in morphological parameter (shoot length, root length, leaf number, leaf area, fresh shoot weight, fresh root weight) and photosynthetic pigments (Chlorophyll a, b, total chlorophyll and carotenoids). On the other hand, inoculation of *S. indica* and foliar application of SA significantly enhanced morphological attributes and leaf photosynthetic pigments. Administration of As leads to an increased accumulation of malondialdehyde (MDA) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) whereas, relative water content, proline, total phenols, total sugar, and total flavonoids content declined. However, presence of *S. indica* and SA treatment showed a significant increase in relative water content, proline, total phenols, total sugar, and total flavonoids content and reduction in MDA and H₂O₂ levels. Compared to individual treatment of *S. indica* inoculation and foliar application of SA, combined application showed better impact on all growth parameters and enhanced tolerance to As toxicity in *O. sanctum*. Hence, by promoting plant growth, osmolyte production, secondary metabolites production and stress tolerance, *S. indica* inoculation and foliar application of SA has a significant potential to improve quality and quantity of plant production in stressed conditions.

Keywords: As toxicity, *O. sanctum*, *S. indica*, Salicylic acid, Secondary metabolites

Screening of Foxtail Millet Germplasm for Blast Resistance Using Morphological, Physiological, and Biochemical Traits

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Abstract

Foxtail millet (*Setaria italica*) is a vital crop in arid and semi-arid regions, but it faces significant yield loss due to blast disease caused by *Magnaporthe grisea*. This study aimed to screen foxtail millet germplasm for blast resistance by integrating morphological, physiological, and biochemical traits. A diverse set of germplasm accessions was evaluated during the Kharif season of 2023–2024, at research farm RVSKVV, Gwalior, M.P under field conditions for disease severity and host-pathogen interaction. Morphological traits such as plant growth habit, leaf altitude, leaf colour, plant pigmentation at auricle, leaf sheath pubescence, flag leaf length, flag leaf width, inflorescence shape, inflorescence bristles, peduncle length, inflorescence apical sterility, inflorescence compactness, inflorescence lobes, plant height at maturity, earhead length, seed colour and seed shape were assessed for their association with disease resistance. The maximum flag leaf length (39.4 cm) and width (2.3 cm) were observed in germplasm Ise 1745, while the minimum (18 cm and 1 cm) respectively, was found in Ise 774. The maximum Peduncle length (36cm) were observed in germplasm Ise 49, while the minimum (7cm) respectively, was found in Ise 1177. Physiological parameters, including chlorophyll content, were measured under pathogen stress, with the highest chlorophyll content 28.8 (mg/g) found in Ise 1704 and the lowest 11.6 (mg/g) in Ise 1603. Biochemical traits, such as zinc, iron, protein, and carbohydrate content, were quantified to understand the plant's innate resistance mechanisms. Based on a 1–9 disease scoring scale, seven genotypes (Ise 49, Ise 96, Ise 132, Ise 160, Ise 200, Ise 362, and Ise 717) were found highly resistant, while three (Ise 969, Ise 1000, and Ise 1136) were susceptible. Based on Morphological, biochemical and disease scoring three germplasm viz., Ise 49, Ise 132 and Ise 717 were found to be superior among all and can be further studied to identify robust blast-resistant foxtail millet germplasms, providing valuable insights for breeding programmes aimed for enhancing disease resilience.

Keywords: Foxtail millet, blast resistance, germplasm screening, morphological traits, physiological traits, biochemical traits

Colchicine induced cytological, stomatal and physiological variation in *Plantago* (Plantaginaceae)

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Abstract

Plantago ovata Forsk. ($2n=2x=8$), family Plantaginaceae, commonly known as Ispaghula or psyllium, is a primitive annual herbaceous and medicinally important plant. A discrete and meagre information is available in various literature on the genetic variation and its improvement through polyploidy. For the purpose, seeds of *P. ovata* were used to induce polyploidy through a range of colchicine concentrations (0.05%-0.4%) for 24h at RT ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$). The results showed that diploid somatic chromosome number ($2n=2x=8$) was induced to tetraploids ($2n=4x=16$). Further, potent tetraploids analysis suggested variation in stomata size and density as well as physiological parameter such as chlorophyll content increases than the control. The variation in stomatal parameters through ploidy could be utilized for the preliminary functional investigations of transpiration for heat resistance and water deficit. Similarly, increased chlorophyll content through polyploidy could be correlated with the photosynthetic activity, survivality and adaptability of plant during environmental stresses. Therefore, polyploid induction could be utilized for potential genetic variation and establishment of a new crop varieties.

Keyword: *Plantago ovata*, Polyploidy, genetic variation, chlorophyll content

Metabolomics: A Way Forward for Medicinal Crop Improvement

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ABSTRACT

Identifying and measuring metabolites and chemical traces of cellular regulatory mechanisms in many biological species are the focus of metabolomics, a new field within "omics." An organism's whole metabolite pool, or metabolome, can be examined to describe genetic or environmental changes. Drug discovery, phenotyping, mutant characterization, environment–gene interactions, and biomarker identification are all significantly impacted by metabolomics. A promising method for figuring out the different metabolic networks connected to plants' ability to withstand biotic and abiotic stress is metabolomics. In this regard, metabolomics-assisted breeding makes effective metabolic screening for crop production and stress tolerance possible for medicinal crops. Metabolomics enables high-throughput phenotyping, where crops are evaluated based on their metabolite profile rather than just yield or physical characteristics. This approach helps select varieties with enhanced nutraceutical traits, including antidiabetic properties. Metabolomics helps map the metabolic pathways responsible for producing antidiabetic compounds. By understanding these pathways, specific enzymatic steps can be manipulated to boost the production of target metabolites. Metabolomics ensures consistency in the production of medicinal crops by providing a method to monitor the metabolite profile across different batches. This is important for crops being used as nutraceuticals or in herbal medicines for diabetes management. In Conclusion, metabolomics is a powerful tool in crop improvement, allowing for the enhancement of specific medicinal properties, such as antidiabetic effects. By understanding and manipulating plant metabolites, crops that offer both nutritional and therapeutic benefits can be developed.

Keywords: Metabolomics, drug discovery, medicinal crops, crop improvement

Green Synthesis and Characterization of Carbon Quantum Dots from *Terminalia chebula* Fruits: Hydrothermal Method and Cytotoxic Effects on Cancer Cell Line

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To study the green synthesis of carbon quantum dots (CQDs) using the aqueous extract from *Terminalia chebula* (*T. chebula*) fruits via hydrothermal methods. The main goals are to characterize the synthesized CQDs and assess their cytotoxic effects on cancer cell lines, thereby emphasizing their potential applications in biomedicine.

Materials and Methods- Aqueous extracts of (*T. chebula*) fruits were prepared and employed as precursors for CQD synthesis through hydrothermal techniques. Characterization of the synthesized CQDs was performed using several methods, including UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and fluorescence spectroscopy to analyze their structural and optical properties. To evaluate cytotoxicity, cancer cell lines were treated with various concentrations of CQDs, with cell viability assessed through the 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay. α,α -diphenyl- β -picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay has also shown good antioxidants activity.

Results- The CQDs synthesized through hydrothermal method exhibited remarkable fluorescence properties and a spherical morphology, with an average size ranging from 5 to 10 nm. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of various functional groups. Additionally, the CQDs demonstrated a dose-dependent cytotoxic effect on cancer cells, leading to significant reductions in cell viability at higher concentrations compared to standard, suggesting potential anti-cancer properties. CQDs exhibit improved chemical stability, excellent water solubility, and more inhibitory effect compared to raw extracts on cancerous cell, It also emit fluorescence across a wide range of wavelengths, from ultraviolet to near-infrared

Conclusions- The green synthesis of CQDs using *T. chebula* fruits presents an environmentally friendly and cost-effective strategy for developing nanomaterials with promising biomedical applications. The observed cytotoxic effects on cancer cells indicate their potential as therapeutic agents in cancer treatment. Further research is essential to investigate the mechanisms of action and the wider biomedical implications of CQDs. Compared to the raw extract of *T. chebula*, CQDs have an increased surface area and exhibit different functional groups. These characteristics may facilitate the incorporation of various drugs to assess their compatibility. Additional studies are needed to explore these aspects in greater detail.

Keywords- *T. chebula*, hydrothermal method, carbon quantum dots, cytotoxic effect

Study of chemical composition, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of natural oil extracted from aerial parts of *Pithecellobium dulce*

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Abstract

An essential oil is a liquid extract from the aromatic plants or parts of plants that have a number of applications in various industrial areas. Various methods are used for extracting essential oils, showing numerous benefits and in the determination of the various biological and physico-chemical characteristics of the extracted oils. Essential oils from different plant sources have a composition of more than 200 components, which consist of the volatile and the non-volatile compounds. The various essential oils are used as an antimicrobial, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory and anti-viral agents because of their capable and effective functions.

Natural oils were extracted by using Soxhlet apparatus and hydro distillation from leaves and bark of the plant. Phytochemical tests showed the presence of phytosterols, flavonoids, phenols and tannins. GC-MS study of the extracts confirmed 28 compounds from bark extract and 217 compounds from leaf extract. Antimicrobial and antioxidant test indicated the potential therapeutic properties in the extracts. The antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of the oils can be explained by the presence of Cholesta-4,6-dien-3-ol, (3 beta)-, E, E, Z-1,3,12 Nonadecatriene-5,14-diol, 9-Octadecenamamide, (Z), E, E, Z-1,3,12-Nonadecatriene-5,14-diol, Octadecanoic acid and Octadecanoic acid, Canadine etc. Several compounds identified through GC-MS such as 3,5-Octadien-2-ol, 1-Hexanol, 2-ethyl-, Cyclotetrasiloxane, octamethyl-, Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester, Octadecanoic acid, 2-(acetyloxy)-1-[(acetylox), Behenic amide] etc have revealed that these oils can play a major role in cosmetic industry. Certain compounds such as Nonanedioic acid, monomethyl ester, Diethyl Phthalate, Cyclodecanone and 1-octanol, Heptanoic acid can be used in formation of good grade plasticizers and esters respectively. This study was carried out in vitro to determine the antimicrobial potential of oil extracts against microorganisms. The isolation and purification of bio-active compounds from naturally occurring substances will play a central part in the design, development and modernization of phyto-medicine.

Keywords: *P. dulce*; Natural oil; Antibacterial; Antifungal; Antioxidant; Oil extraction; GC-MS

Quorum quenching and biofilm inhibitory effects of eugenol on urinary catheters – Role in the prevention of chronic Catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) caused by antibiotic resistant *E. coli*

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Abstract

Background: Micro-organisms communicate and adhere on both biotic and abiotic surfaces forming microbial communities called biofilm which are manifested by changes in phenotype, metabolic pathways, increased virulence factors and antimicrobial resistance due to the production of extracellular polymeric substances. Quorum sensing (QS) is a process of cell-to-cell communication that relies on the production and release of diffusible extracellular signalling molecules termed as ‘autoinducers’, ex: N-acyl homoserine lactones (AHL) whose concentration increases with cell density. AHL’s increase production of virulence factors and biofilm formation in pathogenic bacteria. The degradation of QS signal molecules is known as QS inhibition or *quorum quenching* (QQ). Indiscriminate use of antibiotics has led to emergence of multi drug resistant bacteria imposing potential challenges in treating life threatening bacterial infections. With these problems in consideration, an alternative non antibiotic approach using eugenol was investigated for its antimicrobial, anti-biofilm and anti-quorum sensing property against human pathogen *Escherichia coli* (MCC 2412).

Aim of the study: To check the QQ potential of eugenol on *E. coli* and its biofilm inhibitory property on urinary catheters.

Methodology: MIC and IC₅₀ value determination of eugenol against *E. coli* by MTT assay, qualitative and quantitative analysis of violacein pigment from *Chromobacterium violaceum* (MCC 2290) (indicator organism for QS studies), inhibitory effects of eugenol on *E.coli* biofilm formation on urinary catheter by crystal violet uptake.

Results: The MIC and IC₅₀ of eugenol against *E. coli* was 0.5% and 1%, least violacein pigment production was observed at 1.5% eugenol and highest at 0.5% against *C. violaceum*, least biofilm viability (27.25%) on catheter was observed at 1.25% eugenol and highest viability (42.78%) at 0.75%.

Conclusion: The results of the study provided leads about QQ and biofilm inhibitory effects of eugenol in *E. coli* which makes it a potential natural alternative for antibiotic in future.

Keywords: Quorum sensing, Eugenol, *C. violaceum*, *E. coli*, Inhibition, Biofilm

To Evaluate the Efficacy of Abhyanga in Alleviating Chronic Pain: A Holistic Approach

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Abstract

Aim of the study: The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of *Abhyanga*, a traditional Ayurvedic oil massage, in alleviating chronic pain. In Ayurveda, chronic pain is seen as a result of an imbalance in the *Vata Dosha*. It can manifest in different forms and impact various parts of the body. *Abhyanga* offers significant relief from pain and stiffness linked to various systemic diseases, especially rheumatological conditions like *Sandhigata Vata* (osteoarthritis), *Aamavata* (rheumatoid arthritis), and *Kati Shoola* (lower back pain).

Methodology: *Snehana*, in addition to being the primary preparatory step for Panchakarma therapy, is also a highly important treatment method. *Abhyanga* therapy involves the use of specific herbal or medicated oils, often followed by steam, to enhance blood circulation, detoxify the body, strengthen muscles, and nourish the skin. *Abhyanga* involves massaging the body with substances like oil or ghee, which induces *Snigdhatta* (oiliness), *Vishyandata* (liquefaction), *Mardavata* (softness), and *Kledana* (moisture) in the body. The key properties of *Snehan Dravya* include being liquid (*Drava*), subtle (*Sukshma*), fluid (*Sara*), unctuous (*Snigdha*), slimy (*Picchila*), heavy (*Guru*), cool (*Sheeta*), sluggish (*Manda*), and soft (*Mrudu*). Moreover, the reduction in inflammatory markers indicates that *Abhyanga* may have anti-inflammatory properties, contributing to its pain-relieving effects.

Results: *Abhyanga* is an effective holistic therapy for managing chronic pain, particularly in conditions such as arthritis, fibromyalgia, and lower back pain. Reduction of pain, increases mobility and flexibility, improve mental health and quality of life.

Conclusion: *Abhyanga* therapy not only reduces pain intensity but also improves joint mobility, muscle flexibility, and overall quality of life. *Abhyanga* presents a promising, non-invasive, and natural alternative or complementary therapy to conventional pain management strategies. Future studies should explore the long-term effects of *Abhyanga* and its efficacy in combination with other Ayurvedic treatments or modern interventions for chronic pain.

Keywords: *Abhyanga*, Chronic pain, *Shoola*, Oil massage, *Snehan*

Vrikshayurveda: A Holistic Approach to Plant Care

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Abstract

Background: *Vrikshayurveda* is the ancient study of plant life. In essence, its name conveys "Ayurveda for trees". *Vrikshayurveda* addresses all species of trees and their healthy growth and productivity. With no chemicals, *Vrikshayurveda* maximizes plant productivity and permits pest and disease control. An in-depth examination of *Vrikshayurveda* provides insights into the ideal, comprehensive agricultural and gardening system.

Objectives: This paper aims to understand " *Vrikshayurveda*" and review its relevance and contributions to Plant science.

Methods: An effort is made here to review various books and reputed journals to collect information related to *Vrikshayurveda*.

Result: The harmful effects of pesticides and fertilizers led to the search for a return to ancient methods. *Vrikshayurveda* supports sustainable farming methods, reduces consumption of chemicals, and increases soil fertility. It advocated natural remedies offering a sustainable alternative to chemical interventions.

Conclusion: *Vrikshayurveda* offers various suggestions for preserving biodiversity. An eco-friendly environment can be built through the proper interpretation and availability of *Vrikshayurveda*. More appropriate traditional techniques are incorporated into current practices to yield high-quality planting material. They are more productive and suitable for large-scale plantation programs in line with nature in addition to emphasizing prevention over treatment,

Keywords: *Vrikshayurveda*, Agriculture, Gardening, Plant Science, Sustainable development, Chemical interventions, Pesticides, Cultivation

Enzymatic Solutions for Microplastic Pollution: Advances in Biotechnological Remediation

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Abstract

Microplastic pollution has become a major environmental problem, contaminating soil, water, and even the atmosphere. Chemical and physical degradation are two common conventional plastic cleanup techniques that are frequently expensive, inefficient, or hazardous to the environment. For the sustainable cleanup of microplastics, enzymatic degradation presents a viable biotechnological method. During this process, particular enzymes that may degrade plastics into non-toxic byproducts are used; these enzymes are generally derived from microorganisms. The possibility to break down popular polymers like polyethylene terephthalate (PET) into their monomers has been shown by recent developments in enzyme discovery, such as PETase and MHETase. Further improvements in enzyme activity, stability, and selectivity have been made by genetic engineering and synthetic biology, increasing their efficacy under a greater variety of environmental conditions. The mechanics of enzymatic plastic degradation are examined in this study, along with recent advancements in enzyme-based remediation technologies, challenges, and future directions in scaling up these techniques for environmental applications. Enzymatic degradation could be incorporated into current water treatment and waste management systems as an effective and environmentally friendly way to address the global microplastic epidemic.

Keywords: Microplastic; Degradation; Remediation; Waste management; Enzymes

Quinoxalines based compounds in drug delivery system

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Abstract

Quinoxaline-based coordination compounds have emerged as promising candidates in the field of drug delivery due to their versatile chemical structure, biological activity, and coordination capabilities with various metal ions. These heterocyclic compounds, characterized by a fused benzene-pyrazine ring system, exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties, including antibacterial, antiviral, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory activities. Their coordination with metal ions such as copper, zinc, platinum, and palladium further enhance their biological efficacy, stability, and solubility, making them suitable for use in targeted drug delivery systems. The use of metal-coordinated quinoxaline compounds in drug delivery offers several advantages, such as improved bioavailability, controlled release, and enhanced targeting of specific cells or tissues. The coordination compounds can interact with biomolecules through various mechanisms, facilitating selective drug binding and release at the target site, while reducing systemic toxicity. Additionally, the incorporation of metal ions can enable unique properties such as ROS (reactive oxygen species) generation, enhancing the therapeutic effect, particularly in cancer treatment. This abstract highlights recent advances in the development of quinoxaline-based coordination compounds, their synthesis, metal coordination strategies, and their application in drug delivery systems. Special attention is given to their role in enhancing drug solubility, stability, and the potential for overcoming drug resistance. The review of ongoing research indicates the potential of quinoxaline derivatives to revolutionize drug delivery platforms, offering new opportunities for the treatment of complex diseases like cancer, infections, and inflammatory disorders. Further exploration into the design and functionalization of quinoxaline-metal complexes holds promise for the next generation of smart, efficient, and targeted drug delivery systems, with potential for clinical applications in personalized medicine. In this international conference I will present poster on quinoxalines derivatives.

Fig. Quinoxalines moiety.

Keywords: Quinoxaline-based coordination compounds, Benzene-pyrazine ring system, Targeted drug delivery systems, ROS (reactive oxygen species) generation

Analysis of highway-induced soil contaminants on the growth and development of *Vigna radiata*

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Abstract

Background: In recent years, highway construction in Uttar Pradesh has developed rapidly. Among various soil-related challenges, the accumulation of metals or trace elements as soil contaminants is a significant agronomic concern that poses serious risks to food safety. Soil agronomists are increasingly addressing metal pollution, a hazardous issue that disrupts agricultural ecosystems and affects crop health. Since metals are non-biodegradable, they persist in the environment, enter the food chain through crop plants, and accumulate in the human body via biomagnification. Once these harmful metals exceed permitted thresholds, they adversely affect soil microbiota density, composition, physiological activity, soil dynamics, and fertility, ultimately reducing crop productivity.

Aim of the study: This study aims to investigate the impact of highway road proximity and traffic on soil quality which influence the growth and development of *Vigna radiata*.

Methodology: A total of 6 soil samples were collected at distances of 10 m and 200 m from the road's edge along 3 different highways of Lucknow. Apart from physical and chemical analysis soil elements were also analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-ray (SEM-EDX) techniques. To assess the effects of pollutants and heavy metals, various biophysical, biochemical, and histochemical parameters were examined in *Vigna* plants grown in collected soils.

Results: These advanced methods provided detailed insights into the elemental composition and surface morphology of the soils. Analysis revealed fifteen elements that negatively impact plant growth. The presence of heavy metals in the roadside soil was also considerable that shows a trend of gradually increasing from near to far from the highways. Soil samples from areas closer to the highway showed a significant reduction in germination rate, biomass, chlorophyll, sugar, and protein content. Additionally, antioxidant activity was increased, helping plants to counteract the reactive oxygen species generated by pollutants.

Conclusion: The findings highlight the extent to which highway proximity and traffic intensity influence soil quality. The study reveals significant variations in elemental concentrations and chemical properties, with higher levels of heavy metals which altered soil composition closer to the highway that affected the growth and development of *Vigna radiata*.

Keywords: Soil contaminants; Biomagnification; *Vigna radiata*; XRF; SEM-EDX; Heavy metals; Antioxidant activity

Osteoprotective and anti-diabetic action of a polyherbal formulation

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Abstract

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease characterized by a lack of insulin production due to the destruction of pancreatic beta cells. Persons with Type 1 diabetes have a higher risk of osteoporotic bone fracture. Osteoporosis is characterized by decreased bone mineral density and micro-architectural alterations leading to bone loss. This study aims to evaluate the osteoprotective and anti-diabetic potency of polyherbal formulation. Animals were divided into five groups (n=6). Diabetes was induced by intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin. Animals were treated with low (150 mg.kg⁻¹ of b.w.) and high (300 mg.kg⁻¹ of b.w.) concentrations of the polyherbal mixture for the next 28 days. At the end of the experiment, mice were euthanized, and then blood, pancreas and femur were collected. The results of this study showed that the higher dose of polyherbal mixture significantly reduced the blood glucose and ALP levels. In contrast, it significantly increased the serum insulin and calcium levels in the diabetic-treated mice as compared to the diabetic control group. The histological section of the pancreas showed that the destruction of the normal architecture, irregular outline, necrotic and degraded cells in the islets were observed in the diabetic control group.

Conversely, significant improvements were observed in the shape of islets of Langerhans with a huge number of pancreatic cells in the polyherbal high-dose group. Micro-CT analysis of the trabecular bone of the femur revealed a significant increase in bone mineral density, percent bone volume, degree of anisotropy, trabecular number and thickness, whereas a significant decrease in trabecular separation, trabecular pattern factor and the structure model index when treated with a higher dose of the polyherbal mixture as compared to the normal control group. We conclude that the polyherbal drug was able to reduce bone loss in diabetic mice.

Keywords: Beta cells, Diabetes, Osteoprotective, Polyherbal, Streptozotocin, Trabecular bone

Impact of Relay Cropping on Pearl Millet-Based Cropping System

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Abstract

Relay cropping is essentially a special version of double cropping, where the second crop is sown into a standing first crop before harvest. It has potential to address food security and environmental sustainability via spatio-temporal diversification of cropping systems. Key potential benefits of Relay Cropping include increased crop productivity, net economic returns, land use efficiency, soil fertility, better use of water resources and efficient nutrient cycling. In the pearl millet-mustard/pea cropping system, stovers of pearl millet are used to fodder for animals, mustard stovers are disposed for firing the brick kilns or used as fuel in the rural households and pea (legume) is important for food and feed. It used as biological nitrogen fixing crop in field. The demonstrations were conducted on relay cropping of berseem (Var. BB-2) and wheat (Var. Pusa Tejas) in mustard and pea respectively in pearl millet-based cropping system at selected villages of Morena district under Farmer FIRST Programme of Rajmata Vijayaraje Scindia Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh in 2023-24. In case of relay cropping of berseem in mustard, the cultivation cost without and with relay cropping were Rs. 33430 and 47790/ ha. Whereas net profit were Rs.75590 and 150230/ha. Farmers' income (49.68%) increased over farmers' practice through relay cropping. The Benefit cost ratio of interventions' practice was higher (3.14) as compared to farmers' practice (2.28). The similar trends of relay cropping of wheat in pea, cultivation cost without and with relay cropping were Rs. 57225 and 81460/ha. Whereas net profit were Rs. 142275 and 206125/ha. Farmers' income (30.97%) increased over farmers' practice through relay cropping. The Benefit cost ratio of interventions' practice was higher (2.53) as compared to farmers' practice (2.48). Hence approximately 14000 ha. area has covered by innovative technology in Morena district of Madhya Pradesh.

Keywords: Relay cropping, Economic impact, land use efficiency, Adoption of Innovative Technology

Assessing the Impact of Indian classical music on anxiety and spatial behaviour of Albino Rats

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Raga Darbari, an Indian classical raga, on anxiety and spatial behavior in albino rats, exploring the potential of music therapy to modulate stress-related behaviors in animals. Behavioral assessments, including the elevated plus maze (EPM) and open-field test, were used to evaluate anxiety levels in rats exposed to Raga Darbari versus control groups. Results from the EPM revealed that rats exposed to this raga spent significantly more time in the open arms of the maze, indicating reduced anxiety. Additionally, spatial behavior assessments using the T-maze demonstrated that Raga Darbari-exposed rats exhibited enhanced cognitive functions, with faster decision-making and improved memory retention. These findings suggest that the deep, soothing tones of Raga Darbari may positively influence neurocognitive functions, reducing stress and enhancing spatial memory performance. This aligns with existing research, which suggests that music therapy can modulate brain regions like the hippocampus and amygdala, reduce cortisol levels, and improve relaxation and behavioral responses in animals. This study provides further evidence supporting the role of specific musical frequencies and rhythms in promoting mental well-being and reducing anxiety.

Keywords: Raga Darbari, Stress-related behaviors, Elevated Plus Maze (EPM), T-maze

Impact of Lead Exposure on Gut Microbiota, Intestinal Homeostasis, and Systemic Inflammatory Responses

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Abstract

Lead is a non-essential heavy metal found in trace levels in the earth's crust. Lead can be acquired through contaminated drinking water and food. However, it has applications in a variety of sectors, including autos, battery recycling, boat construction, coal combustion, lead smelting, leaded gasoline, grids, paints, bearings, ceramics, and plastic. Lead-induced oxidative stress causes DNA damage, as well as gut microbiome dysbiosis. Due to the over-expression of lead dysbiosis in the gut alter gut physiological homeostasis, causing immune-inflammatory reactions, and increased permeability of the intestinal barrier in the digestive tract, resulting in apparent morphological issues, according to studies on the negative effects of lead on intestinal physiology. When rats were exposed orally to 10 mg/kg lead for 28 days, as a result when comparing the lead-induced group to the control group, we observed an alteration of the level of I-FABP, calprotectin, and β -defensin due to a significantly reduced the number of microorganisms such as firmicutes, lactobacillus Plantarum, streptococci, and E. coli. All of these bacteria are commensal and have been shown to protect against immunological diseases. The disruption of the microbiota can cause an inflammatory environment in the gastrointestinal tract, disrupting intestinal homeostasis and as a result, unregulated NF- κ B can trigger the expression of pro-inflammatory mediators such as IL-17 and TNF- α aggravating the inflammatory process and causing epithelium damage as well as intestinal and extraintestinal symptoms. The bacteria in the gut may operate as a biological barrier, competing with lead absorption in the intestine and therefore limiting hazardous metal bioavailability as demonstrated by histological alterations in the bowel and raised levels of inflammatory markers. The depth and the shape of the crypt, the shape and height of the villi, and the number of goblet cells and excess lymphocytes scattered were significantly shown in lead-induced groups. Lead also caused a significant decrease in hemoglobin (Hb) concentration, RBC count, and packed cell volume when compared to the control group.

Keywords: Gut microbiome dysbiosis, Immune-inflammatory reactions, I-FABP (Intestinal Fatty Acid Binding Protein)

Performance of Barley, Wheat and Chickpea under Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) based agroforestry system in Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Indians have been practicing agroforestry as a way of life due to threats to loss of fertility, low sustainability, soil erosion, etc. The Bundelkhand region's undulating topography, high temperature, and erratic behavior of rainfall have led to poor agricultural productivity thereby, leading to food insecurity. Agri-horticultural systems, as one of the forms of agroforestry systems, may be proven beneficial in terms of sustained production, food, and income security. L-49, a dwarf variety of Guava, is majorly produced in Uttar Pradesh. Barley and Wheat are the widely grown cereals and Chickpea contributes to 50% of the Indian Pulse production. Therefore, the present study was conducted in an eight-year-old guava plantation during 2023-24 at Central Agroforestry Research Institute (CAFRI), Jhansi, UP, to evaluate the yield and economics of Barley, Wheat, and Chickpea under guava-based agroforestry system. The experiment comprised six treatments viz., T1-Guava+Barley, T2-Sole Barley, T3-Guava+Wheat, T4-Sole Wheat, T5-Guava+Chickpea, T6- Sole Chickpea with four replications in a Randomized Block Design (RBD). The yield of respective crops was observed maximum under sole cropping compared to the guava-based agroforestry system. The biological yield (9069, 9310, and 3197 kg ha⁻¹) and harvest index (44.43, 44.37, and 43.93%) of Barley, Wheat, and Chickpea were observed maximum under sole cropping than under agroforestry system (7578, 8235 and 2497 kg ha⁻¹) and (43.44, 44.09 and 40.85%). However, the wheat equivalent yield was found maximum for the Guava+Wheat agroforestry system (7345 kg ha⁻¹). Similarly, the gross return (196538 ₹ ha⁻¹), net return (154867 ₹ ha⁻¹), and land equivalent ratio (1.80) were found maximum for the Guava+Wheat agroforestry system. Therefore, the integration of wheat under guava-based agroforestry system may be beneficial for sustainable production and food security, contributing to the ecological and economic stability of the Bundelkhand region.

Keywords: Agroforestry, Biological yield, Harvest index, Equivalent yield, Guava, Land equivalent ratio

Growth and nitrogen assimilation of Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) varieties under different sulfur and nitrogen treatments

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Abstract

Nitrogen (N) is one of the key elements for all living organisms and an indispensable constituent of many important macromolecules. Use of N containing fertilizers has dramatically increased over the years for increasing the crop productivity. However, the use efficiency of applied N is only 30-40%, and the rest is lost into the environment, causing severe environmental and health problems. Green leafy vegetables, especially lettuce, accumulate high nitrate content that adversely affects human health. Therefore, lettuce production with low nitrate content under the N fertilization is vital important, not only for health benefit but also for maintenance of environmental sustainability. Sulfur is the tenth most plentiful element in the universe, the nutrient that the plants overlook. Since, sulfate assimilation has metabolic coupling with nitrate assimilation, supplementation of sulfur (S) along with N fertilization has been recommended in many studies in various crops for improving the use efficient of N. In consideration of the need, a field experiment was carried out with combinations of N and S and split doses of N application to identify the most appropriate fertilizer (N and S) application rates in order to enhance lettuce productivity and to reduce nitrate accumulation. Two varieties of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*), 'Pusa Kiran' (V_1) and 'Pusa Chaulai' (V_2) were chosen for the study. Six fertilizer treatments S_0N_0 (control), S_0N_2 (S_0N_{25+20}), S_0N_3 ($S_0N_{45+25+20}$), S_1N_0 ($S_{40}N_0$), S_1N_2 ($S_{40}N_{25+20}$) and S_1N_3 ($S_{40}N_{45+25+20}$) were conducted in a randomized block design with three replicates. Growth, nitrate assimilation and leaf nitrate content were assessed and compared at various stages of growth and development in both the varieties. The results suggested that the application of the combined doses of S and N (S_1N_3) in which N is applied in three split doses ($S_{40}N_{45+25+20}$) resulted in the maximum growth of the lettuce and accumulation of the least level of nitrate in leaves. Irrespective of the treatments, V_1 accumulated more nitrate in leaves than V_2 at all the phenological stages. Differential growth and leaf nitrate accumulation of lettuce varieties by the effect of supplementation of the N with S fertilization are evident with the change in the activities of the enzymes of nitrate assimilation. With this knowledge, a more economical and environmentally responsible approach to nitrogen management should be able to be developed for increased lettuce yield with lower nitrate levels.

Keywords: Nitrate; Nitrogen; Sulfur; Lettuce

Induction of Mycosporine-like amino acids under cumulative stress of salinity and UV radiation in the cyanobacterium *Scytonema* sp. HKAR-16

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Abstract

Background: Cyanobacteria, as primary producers in aquatic ecosystems, are increasingly challenged by the impacts of climate change, particularly from the combined stressors of salinity fluctuations and enhanced ultraviolet (UV) radiation. In response, these organisms have evolved adaptive strategies such as the production of mycosporine-like amino acids (MAAs) that protect cellular integrity from harmful radiation.

Aim of the study: This study investigates the induction of MAAs in response to the combined effect of ultraviolet radiation (UV-R), photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), and varying concentration of NaCl (50, 100, 150 and 200 mM) in the cyanobacterium *Scytonema* sp. HKAR-16.

Methodology: The methodology involved cultivating cyanobacterial strains under controlled laboratory conditions with varying salinity levels and UV radiation intensities. The production of MAAs was quantified using spectrophotometric and chromatographic techniques like HPLC to assess the induction of MAAs under different stress conditions.

Results: Spectroscopic and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analyses reveal the presence of a single peak of MAA ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 334$ nm) at a retention time of 1.469 min. Maximum induction of MAA was observed in PAR + UV-A + UV-B (PAB) treated samples along with 100 mM NaCl after 72 h of treatment. Production of MAA increased maximally after 48 h of treatment with PAB radiation in comparison to that of PAR and PAR + UV-A radiation. Salinity also inhibited photosynthetic efficiency in the cyanobacterium *Scytonema* sp. HKAR-16.

Conclusion: This abstract highlights the importance of MAAs as a natural mitigation strategy for biodiversity conservation in the face of climate change, while also highlighting the potential applications of MAAs as biomarkers for environmental stress.

Keywords: Cyanobacteria; HPLC; Mycosporine-like amino acids; Salinity; Ultraviolet radiation

Agriculture and Cultivation of Medicinal Plants Efficiency of Developed Phosphorus Enriched Organo-Mineral Fertilizer on green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) and on Some Chemical Properties of Soil

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Abstract

Background: Phosphorus is a very important plant nutrient for the development of plants and its production is not unlimited in the world. In addition, excessive use can lead to soil and water pollution. In this respect, phosphorus should be used effectively in plant production, especially in degraded soils.

Aim of the study: An experiment was carried out to develop p-enriched organomineral fertilizers (p-OMF) using organic substrate i.e., rice straw, mineral waste i.e., low-grade rock phosphate (RP), and phosphate-solubilizing microorganism (*Aspergillus sp.*). Thereafter the study was carried out to determine the effects of p-OMF on some chemical properties of a degraded soil.

Methodology: In this study, four doses of developed p-OMF (D₁: 10, D₂: 20, D₃:30, and D₄: 40 t ha⁻¹) were applied excluding control.

Results: According to the research findings, p-OMFs increased the soil organic matter (SOM), salinity, total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) by 65.1%, 16.9%, 26.1%, 138%, and 14.8%, respectively. According to the results of the study, the highest change in exchangeable Ca and Na content in soils was obtained from p-OMF applications by D₄ and D₃ respectively. They also decreased soil pH by 5%. As a result, it was determined that the most effective p-OMF dose that maintains soil properties at appropriate levels in sandy soils is D₃ (30 t ha⁻¹ OMF). Thereafter a field experiment was conducted to determine the effect of fertilizer on the growth of green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.). Growth parameters of percentage emergence, plant height, leaf area, number of leaves per plant and branch/plant were collected and subjected into statistical analysis, using ANOVA and Fisher's L.S.D. at 5 % probability level. The results showed that growth parameters i.e., germination percentage (100%), plant height (13.8 cm), leaf area (21.87cm²), number of leaves (9.21), branch/plant (5.63) were found to be significantly highest with p-OMF @30 t ha⁻¹ OMF soil and least was found in the control.

Conclusion: The study thus revealed that crop residue could be converted into a value-added product through composting technology using low-grade rock phosphate along with phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms.

Keywords: P deficiency, P rich organomineral fertilizer, Soil properties, Green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

Fuel wood Consumption Pattern in Pasan Range of Katghora Forest Division

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Abstract

In many developing countries of the world, fuel wood, a forest resource, is used to meet household energy needs. In India, about 67% of rural households still use fuel wood for cooking. Adoption of cleaner or low-carbon fuels and energy transitions are deeply linked to income of households. In rural areas this situation becomes more severe. This study has been done in the villages of Pasan Range of Katghora Forest Division. A structured questionnaire survey was conducted to collect the income based data in fuel wood collection. The households were categorized in three groups- low income, middle income and high income group. The results reveal that the collection and usage of fuel wood is highest in low income households, because it freely available and more easily accessible for the forest dwellers.

Keywords: Fuel wood, Questionnaire, Energy

Effect of polluted water of River Varuna at Varanasi on serum calcium and inorganic phosphate of *Channa punctatus* (Bloch)

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Abstract

Calcium plays a key role in a variety of biochemical and physiological processes. It is required for the proper functioning of numerous intracellular and extracellular processes, including muscle contraction, nerve impulses, hormone release and blood coagulation. Calcium interacts with phosphorus to form calcium phosphate, which forms bones. Phosphorus is an important constituent of nucleic acids and cell membrane, and is directly involved in all energy-producing cellular reactions.

The rapid industrialization and urbanization has a lot of impact on the river water quality. River Varuna at Varanasi, a tributary of river Ganga, is no exception to it. In the present study, the effect of polluted water of river Varuna on the serum calcium and inorganic phosphate levels of *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) were investigated. The readings were taken in the month of April, August and December. Blood samples were collected and analyzed for the serum calcium level and inorganic phosphate levels.

Both serum calcium and inorganic phosphate levels were comparatively lower in experimental fishes than control fishes in all the three months. The plasma calcium showed a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in the month of April in the experimental fishes. The plasma phosphate were significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) in the experimental fishes in April and December. In August, the difference of serum calcium and inorganic phosphate level between control and experimental fishes was comparatively low compared to April and December. It may be due to rainy season, which have diluted the pollutant level of river water. It is concluded that the river water have disturbed both calcium and phosphate homeostasis thus, inducing hypocalcaemia and hypophosphatemia condition in the fishes exposed to river water.

Keywords: *Channa punctatus* (Bloch), Hypophosphatemia, Aquatic ecosystem health, Physiological processes

Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Recreational Drug and Alcohol Use

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Abstract

Aim of the study: To explore how the COVID-19 pandemic affected recreational drug and alcohol use, with stress, isolation, and disrupted drug supplies leading to increased substance abuse.

Methodology: This systemic data and meta-analysis are referenced by PubMed, Embase, and Web of science were searched without a time limit. This article reviews existing literature on recreational drug use during the pandemic, focusing on factors such as stress, isolation, boredom, and anxiety as catalysts for increased substance use. It draws comparisons between previous crises, including economic recessions and natural disasters, to map the pandemic's effect on drug consumption. Additionally, trends in alcohol use and the shift towards alternative substances due to the scarcity of traditional illicit drugs during lockdowns are examined.

Results: The COVID-19 pandemic caused a significant increase in recreational drug and alcohol use, especially among those already consuming at high-risk levels. About 30% of people drank more due to stress, boredom, and extra free time during lockdowns. Some reduced their alcohol intake due to job security fears. Illicit drug use also rose as support services were disrupted, leading to the use of new drugs. This resulted in more fatal overdoses, as drugs were often contaminated and riskier substances were used.

Conclusion: The COVID-19 pandemic caused a significant increase in recreational drug and alcohol use, especially among those already consuming at high-risk levels. About 30% of people drank more due to stress, boredom, and extra free time during lockdowns.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, SARS-CoV-2, Recreational drug use, Substance use disorder (SUD)

miRNA-directed regulation of Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinase (ERK) pathway in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia

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Abstract

Chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) is a global health burden which necessitates the discovery of novel therapeutic targets. It is a rare clonal myeloproliferative malignancy originating from pluripotent hematopoietic stem cells. Treatment strategies primarily involve the use of breakpoint cluster region–Abelson murine leukemia proto-oncogene 1 (*BCR::ABL1*) tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs). The molecular mechanisms triggered by *BCR::ABL1* are central to CML pathogenesis and have spurred the development of therapeutic approaches focused on inhibiting this kinase and its downstream signalling pathways. Ras/Raf/mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK/MEK)/extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) pathway has a very essential role in the survival of the cell and its dysregulation might be the major cause of several cancer types. MicroRNAs (miRNAs) play a crucial role in regulating the protein cascades within the ERK signalling pathway, which is closely linked to CML. This review focuses on summarizing the impact of various miRNAs in either upregulating or downregulating key proteins. miRNAs play a pivotal role in regulating the ERK signalling cascade. Some miRNAs, such as miR-30a, miR-29b, miR-138, miR-203, miR-196a, and miR-196b, influence *BCR::ABL1* tyrosine kinase activity. Others, like miR-15a, miR-17, miR-126, miR-128, miR-188-5p, and miR-221, affect CRK family proteins, while miR-125a-5p and miR-218-5p regulate GAB2, a critical signaling amplifier in CML. Additionally, miR-124, miR-1271, miR-128, and several others modulate GRB2, which links receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs) to SOS proteins in the ERK pathway. miR-155 and miR-181a regulate SOS, while miR-19a targets RAF1, and the miR-17-92 cluster modulates ERK/MAPK signaling. Given the growing significance and expanding regulatory roles of miRNAs, this review highlights recent advances in the field and proposes miRNAs as potential targets for modulating various protein cascades within the ERK signalling pathway. Understanding how miRNAs govern the ERK pathway could unveil new therapeutic targets for CML treatment.

Keywords: MicroRNA (miRNAs); Chronic myeloid leukemia (CML); miRNA modulation; Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinase (ERK) pathway

Variety-specific expression pattern of leaf proteins in rice varieties under low-N treatment

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Abstract

Nitrogen (N) is an essential macronutrient that significantly impacts the development, productivity, and growth of plants. Nitrogen fertilization is crucial to maximise yield in rice farming; nevertheless, overuse can result in environmental damage and higher production expenses. Thus, a comprehension of nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) is essential for sustainable rice production. The purpose of this study is to assess the expression patterns of leaf proteins in two different rice varieties, Aditya (N-inefficient) and Vikramarya (N-efficient), under low nitrogen (low-N) treatment compared to optimal nitrogen circumstances. Using gel-free proteome analysis, we identified differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) associated with various metabolic pathways, stress response, nitrogen metabolism and photosynthesis in the leaves of both rice varieties. According to our study findings, Vikramarya demonstrates a strong adaptation response in low-N treatments, shown by increased protein expressions in various pathways. Conversely, Aditya showed a restricted reaction, significantly downregulating essential proteins required for effective nitrogen utilization. The significance of choosing N-efficient rice varieties for low-input crop cultivation is heightened by the differential expression patterns, which also emphasise the genetic foundation of NUE in rice. In addition to advancing our knowledge of the molecular mechanisms driving NUE, this study offers suggestions for tactics that might be used to increase rice yield in situations where nutrients are scarce. This study provides insights into the leaf protein profiles linked to different nitrogen levels, which will help design focused breeding programs to increase rice's NUE and, in turn, support sustainable farming practices and food security in the face of escalating environmental threats.

Keywords: Rice, Low nitrogen, Proteomics, Nitrogen use efficiency

Impact of basal and foliar application of NPK on the survival of lac insects *Kerria lacca*(Kerr) on *Butea monosperma* Lam.

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Abstract

Background: Lac is a resinous material secreted by the lac insect *Kerria lacca*. Lac insect feeds on the phloem sap of host plants like *Butea monosperma*, *Ziziphus mauritiana* and *Schleichera oleosa*. *B. monosperma* is a medium-sized deciduous tree that readily adapts to various soil types. Although the influence of foliar applications on *B. monosperma* has been studied, the combined effects of NPK basal and foliar applications on lac insect survival remain largely unexplored.

Aim of study: This study aims to evaluate the effects of different combinations of both NPK basal and foliar applications on the survival percentage of *K. lacca*.

Methodology: The field work was conducted during the year 2021-22 on the *katki* crop of *B. monosperma* using Randomized Block Design. During the field trial, Nitrogen(N), Phosphorus(P) and Potassium (K) were applied through basal application of Urea, SSP, and MoP respectively. Foliar application of NPK (19:19:19) solution and insecticides were done separately. The survival percent of mean live lac insect was calculated from the base data at 37th to those survived on 90th day after Broodlac inoculation i.e. at lac crop maturity.

Table 1 Details of nutrient application

S.No.	Treatments details
T ₁	NPK basal application+ no NPK foliar application
T ₂	One NPK foliar application + no NPK basal application
T ₃	NPK basal application + one NPK foliar application
T ₄	Two NPK foliar applications+ no NPK basal application
T ₅	NPK basal application + two NPK foliar applications
T ₆	NPK basal application + three NPK foliar applications
T ₇	Three NPK foliar applications+ no NPK basal application
T ₈	No NPK foliar applications+ no NPK basal application

Results: The survival percent of *K. lacca* at harvest of the lac crop varied in different treatments. It was varied from 32.77 to 14.64 percent. It was highest (32.77%) in treatment T₂-one NPK foliar application indicating that single NPK foliar application was favourable for *K. lacca* survival. In contrast treatment T₇-three NPK foliar applications had the lowest (14.64%) survival percentage. This suggests that multiple NPK foliar application may have had a detrimental effect on lac insect survival possibly due to nutrient imbalance or toxicity.

Conclusion: Method of nutrient application plays an important role in the survival of lac insects that is a key economic factor influencing lac production.

Keywords: Lac insect, *Butea monosperma*, Survival, Resin

Isolation and Characterization of Phycocyanin from the Rice-Field cyanobacterium *Dolichospermum spiroides* HKAR-23

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Abstract

Background: Cyanobacteria from rice paddies are known for their potential to produce high-value biochemicals, including pigments like phycocyanin, which has applications in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties.

Aim of the study: The cyanobacterium *Dolichospermum spiroides* HKAR-23 was isolated from a rice-field environment to explore its potential for phycocyanin production, a valuable pigment with applications in biotechnology and pharmaceuticals.

Methodology: The isolation process involved collecting water samples, followed by culturing under controlled conditions to promote the growth of *D. spiroides* HKAR-23. Morphological and molecular techniques such as *16S rRNA* gene sequencing were employed to accurately identify the cyanobacterium. Once identified, the biomass of *D. spiroides* HKAR-23 was harvested for the extraction of phycocyanin, a blue-green pigment and protein complex widely studied for its ecological significance and biotechnological potential, particularly in environmental and Earth sciences. The extraction process was optimized by different techniques such as complete cell disruption, extraction at temperatures below 45 °C and a pH of 5.5-6.0, and purification through ammonium sulfate precipitation, to ensure maximum yield.

Results: The purity of the extracted phycocyanin was assessed using spectroscopic methods particularly UV-visible spectroscopy, having absorption maxima (λ_{\max}) at 615 nm. Further characterization, including Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), confirmed the structural integrity and purity of the phycocyanin. The study demonstrated that *D. spiroides* HKAR-23 from rice fields could be a promising source of phycocyanin, contributing to the sustainable production of this bioactive compound.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that *D. spiroides* HKAR-23 isolated from a rice-field environment is well known for producing high-quality phycocyanin, a valuable pigment with applications in various industries. The biochemical characterization confirmed its purity and structural integrity.

Keywords: Characterization; Cyanobacteria; Extraction; Phycocyanin

Climate Change and Natural Hazards

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Abstract

Climate change has become a critical global issue, significantly influencing the frequency and intensity of natural hazards such as hurricanes, floods, droughts, and wildfires. As greenhouse gas emissions continue to rise, altering atmospheric conditions, the Earth's weather patterns are shifting, leading to more extreme and unpredictable natural events. This paper explores the intricate relationship between climate change and natural hazards, emphasizing how rising global temperatures contribute to the exacerbation of these events. Through an analysis of recent data and case studies, it highlights the increased vulnerability of ecosystems and human settlements to these hazards, particularly in coastal and low-lying regions. Furthermore, the abstract underscores the need for adaptive strategies, including resilient infrastructure, disaster preparedness, and sustainable environmental practices, to mitigate the adverse impacts of climate-related natural hazards. Addressing climate change and its influence on natural hazards is not only essential for safeguarding human lives and properties but also for preserving global biodiversity and ecological stability.

Keywords: Climate change, Natural hazards, Extreme weather events, Disaster preparedness, Environmental sustainability

To review the Air pollution and public health with refers to challenges for Delhi

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Abstract

Aim of the study: To determine the scope and challenges of air pollution on the public health of Delhi. And the alternative policy interventions on emission reduction for the citizen of Delhi.

Methodology: In this systemic study with reference from PubMed, and google scholar were searches. The detail analysis of carbon emission from the different sectors of the Delhi causes by the pollutants like SO₂, NO₂, NH₃, also assuming the assuming effective implementation of all these measures, the analysis combines technical features, emission reduction efficiencies, of each measure with economic activities, emission factor, and meteorological and chemical features of the dispersion of pollutants in the atmosphere.

Results: According to the data collected the mean values of all pollutants (except SO₂ and NO₂) exceeded the recommended National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) prescribed for residential areas in Delhi and other urban cities. The levels of TSPM, RSPM and lead were much above the safety limits prescribed for residential areas by the Central Pollution Control Board for both the study areas. The TSPM levels were 683 and 235 µg/m³ for HPA and LPA, respectively. Moreover, the study states the impact of on human health causes the risk COPD, Asthma and other respiratory diseases.

Conclusion: Poor air quality is a major concern world -wide, with a significant burden on public health. The official data confirms that exposure to Particulate Matter 2.5 is alarmingly high in most Indian cities like Delhi. According to WHO recent data urban air quality in 10 Indian cities have made it to the world's top 20 worst cities with air pollution. this study explores potential policy interventions that could effectively reduce.

Keywords: Air pollution, SO₂, NO₂, NAAQS levels, TSPM, COPD, Asthma

Paraquat-induced route and dose-dependent lung damage in mice model

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Abstract

Paraquat (PQ) is the most important cationic bipyridyl herbicide in the agricultural industry, which is very toxic to humans and animals and causes disruption in many organs, mainly the lungs. The present study aimed to investigate the effects of PQ exposure using two different routes of administration and doses to examine the impact of both the route and doses on lung damage. Along with inflammation and oxidative lung damage, initial fibrotic changes were observed in the lungs. Balb/c mice were exposed to PQ (50 mg/kg i.p and 20mg/kg i.n.) followed by pretreatment of curcumin through the intranasal route (5 mg/kg,i.n.). Curcumin is a low molecular weight polyphenol derived from the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, and is the most active turmeric constituent. Pretreatment of curcumin significantly reduced inflammatory cell infiltration in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) analysis along with total Protein content, inflammatory mediators, mainly reactive oxygen species (ROS), Myeloperoxidase (MPO), Nitric Oxide(NO), and, Malondialdehyde. Significantly increased antioxidants were noted in Curcumin pretreated groups which were reduced due to PQ exposure.

Keywords: Oxidative stress, Agricultural industry, PQ exposure, Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF)

Geospatial Tree Monitoring through DGPS for Sustainable Forest Management

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Abstract

Geospatial tree monitoring plays a pivotal role in sustainable forest management, offering precise insights into tree health, growth, and spatial distribution. This study focuses on the integration of Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) technology to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of tree monitoring processes. By leveraging DGPS, the study aims to create a geospatial database that captures real-time data on individual trees, allowing for detailed tracking of growth patterns, species identification, and spatial positioning. The Tree Monitoring System through Geotagging using Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) at Rani Lakshmi Bai Central Agricultural University (RLBCAU) aims to enhance precision in forest and tree resource management. This system integrates advanced geospatial technologies with traditional forestry practices to improve monitoring accuracy for trees in agroforestry and natural ecosystems. Through the use of DGPS, which offers sub-meter accuracy, individual trees are geotagged with precise spatial coordinates. Tree attributes such as species type, height, canopy spread, and health status are recorded and integrated into a Geographic Information System (GIS) for real-time data analysis and visualization. The initiative also supports large-scale data collection for ecological research and resource management at RLBCAU. The project has significant potential for application in reforestation, agroforestry, and climate adaptation projects. It enables researchers and forest managers to make data-driven decisions regarding forest conservation, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity management, contributing towards sustainable environmental practices and agricultural productivity in semi-arid regions.

Keywords: Tree Monitoring, DGPS, GIS, GPS

Impact of In Vivo Hydrocortisone Administration on Innate and Cell-Mediated Immune Responses of Spleen and Head Kidney Cells in Freshwater Snakehead Teleost, *Channa punctatus*

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Abstract

Hydrocortisone, also known as cortisol when produced naturally by the body, is a glucocorticoid hormone that plays a vital role in regulating various physiological processes, especially in stress response, metabolism, and immune system regulation. It is commonly used in medical settings as a synthetic drug for its anti-inflammatory and immune-suppressive effects. In fish, the hydrocortisone is produced by the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal-axis. This study investigates the effect of in vivo hydrocortisone administration on the immune responses of the spleen and head kidney in snakehead teleost, *Channa punctatus*. Fish were administered with (50 µg/g body weight) for 5 days and various immune parameters were assessed. The innate immune functions were judged by phagocytic percentage and phagocytic index. The respiratory burst activity was measured by evaluating the production of superoxide anion through reduction of nitro blue tetrazolium dye. Nitric oxide production was evaluated using the Griess reagent assay. Cell-mediated immune function was assessed by lymphocyte proliferation. Results revealed suppression of immune functions, with hydrocortisone significantly reducing innate immune parameters in both head kidney and spleen cells. Differential lymphocyte proliferation was observed as Concanavaline A stimulated lymphocyte proliferation reduced after hydrocortisone administration, whereas other mitogens showed no change in proliferative responses of lymphocytes. This study is crucial in understanding the role of chemical stressor such as steroid hormone in alteration of immune activity in a teleost.

Keywords: Hydrocortisone; Fish Immunity; Stress; Lymphocyte Proliferation

Water Quality Assessment and Prevalence of Antibiotic-Resistance (AR) Coliform Bacteria in Gandak River at Hajipur, Bihar, India

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Abstract

Antibiotic pollution is an emerging global challenge in recent decades as it is proving a major driver for antibiotic-resistance (AR) with surging consequences worldwide. Urban rivers are very prone and act as reservoirs of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and such genes. The present study evaluates the physicochemical and microbiological properties of the river Gandak at Hajipur to assess its pollution status. Replicates of water samples were collected from three different selected sites along the river at seasonal variations. Analyzed data of different physicochemical parameters studied were found within the permissible limit of WHO and BIS guidelines. Coliform groups of bacteria were differentiated through presumptive-confirmed-completed tests for most probable number (MPN) counts. The MPN index of all the water samples from three different sites were found considerably high. Based on different biochemical tests result, the concentration of *E. coli* sp., *Klebsiella* sp., *Citrobacter* sp. and *Enterobacter* sp. were found to be dominant in the water samples. The broad-spectrum antibiotics such as Penicillin-G(P), Erythromycin (E), Ampicillin/Sulbactam (A/S) and Amoxicillin (AMC) are found less effective against several bacterial isolates. The study indicates that the consumption of such contaminated water at the end user point may result in potential health hazards to the inhabitants. It is suggested that the regular monitoring and proper sewerage treatment is effective in reducing MDR bacteria with the regulatory agencies like state and central pollution control board in making policy change to enforce pollution control regulation to stop further deterioration of the water of river Gandak.

Keywords: Gandak river, Water quality, Physicochemical parameters, Coliform, Antibiotic-resistant bacteria

Health and Allied Sciences

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Abstract

Background: The aim of health and allied sciences is to improve health outcomes through a wide range of disciplines, such as public health, physiotherapy, nursing, naturopathy, homeopathy, ayurveda and medicine. The necessity of interdisciplinary collaboration has evolved as healthcare requirements have become more complicated. To improve patient care and advance medical knowledge, it is essential to comprehend how these diverse professions interact and contribute to the delivery of healthcare.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate how interdisciplinary collaboration among health and allied science professionals affects healthcare innovation, resource efficiency, and patient outcomes. The study also looks at the advantages and difficulties faced by professionals who operate in interdisciplinary teams. The influence of interdisciplinary collaboration in health and related fields was investigated using a mixed-methods approach.

Methodology: A quantitative survey and qualitative interviews were the two stages of the study of healthcare workers. The survey's open-ended and closed-ended questions were intended to elicit participants' opinions about multidisciplinary collaboration, its advantages, and the difficulties they encounter on a daily basis. A subset of participants participated in semi-structured interviews in the second phase to obtain further insights into their experiences. Particular facets of collaboration, including communication, teamwork, role clarity and decision-making procedures, were the subject of the interviews.

Results: The results showed that interdisciplinary teamwork greatly enhances patient outcomes, with numerous professionals attesting to improved care quality and resource efficiency. Improved communication, less work duplication, and the sharing of disciplinary expertise were among the advantages of collaboration.

Conclusion: This study shows that patient care and healthcare efficiency are positively impacted by interdisciplinary collaboration in the health and allied sciences. However, obstacles like unclear roles and communication gaps need to be fixed in order to optimize its efficacy. Long-term results and the creation of standardized procedures to facilitate productive interdisciplinary collaboration should be the main topics of future research.

Keywords: Physiotherapy, Interdisciplinary, Quantitative, Qualitative, Health

The Storm of Natural and Health Hazard Due to Climate Change

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Abstract

Natural hazard due to climate change is the nature's subtle way of reminding us who's boss. In most of the cases natural disaster can cause the health impacts even life-threatening in humans. It is a global threat that put stress on various sectors.

This study investigates the intersection of climate change and natural hazard and how climate fluctuation is got worsen and how it effects to the sustainability of diverse sectors worldwide (specially health sector). Vulnerability and resilience specially for those regions in world who are economically weaker, also provide some suggestions to mitigate the natural hazard and climate change.

Climatic changes lead to food and waterborne and parasitic diseases, and a recent example is a coronavirus pandemic. Climate change also accelerates the mystery of antimicrobial resistance, one more threat to human health due to the increasing incidence of antibiotic resistant.

The methodology is to scrutinize the systematic review of literatures, case study, statical data analysis, and conducted the surveys and interview to better understand the problem.

The study found that Climate change making worst existing vulnerabilities, particularly in low-income regions. Our policy framework highlights the need for collaboration across governments, civil society, and the private sector to protect vulnerable communities and promote sustainable development.

Urgent climate change mitigation and adaptation measures are necessary to reduce the risks associated with natural hazards. Effective policy responses require integrated approaches, community engagement, and inclusive decision-making.

Keywords: Climate change, Natural hazards, Vulnerability, Resilience, Policy framework, Adaptation, Mitigation

Exploring Diatoms' Role in Carbon Sequestration

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Abstract

Carbon Sequestration is crucial for mitigating climate change. As aquatic bodies especially oceans, are major sink for carbon, on Earth. They perform aquatic carbon sequestration which is not only a long-term storage of organic carbon in terms of biomass and vegetated sediments, but also carbon is transported from its source to be stored elsewhere in lakes, rivers, groundwaters, glaciers and oceans.

Diatoms are the nature's secret for Carbon capture in aquatic environments. Diatoms (class Bacillariophyceae) constitute an important group of micro-algae found in all the aquatic ecosystems including oceans. These micro-algae are responsible for carbon sequestration, contributing to around one-fifth of Earth's Carbon fixation and accounting for about 25% of global oxygen release per year. They have a distinct capability to generate porous silica cell walls surrounding their cells known as frustules, which makes diatom ecologically successful in all the aquatic habitats. In addition, diatoms can accumulate high amount of lipids for energy storage, making them a potential candidate for generating commercially valuable bio-fuels and bio-actives (bio-manufacturing).

A success story based on these potentials of diatoms will help us in developing long term bio-remedies for carbon sequestration and water quality improvements. However, diatoms are highly sensitive to climate change and ocean acidification. This study considers and explores possibilities of using diatoms in reducing atmospheric carbon dioxide, combating ocean acidification and other attributes of water quality improvements. The efforts require microhabitat development, adequate niche partition and selection of potentially efficient diatom taxa (methodology).

Thus, diatoms can be used as our weapon to fight climate change by addressing the urgent issue of carbon sequestration in current scenario.

Keywords: Carbon Sequestration, Diatoms, Carbon fixation, Ocean Acidification, Bio-manufacturing, Water Quality

Smart Polymers for Neurotransmitter Sensing: Xanthate RAFT Polymerization of PolyN-vinylcarbazole Block Copolymers for Enhanced Dopamine Detection

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Abstract

This study investigated the synthesis and characterization of block copolymers composed of poly(N-vinylcarbazole) (PNVCz) and various sulfonic acid polymer derivatives. The polymers were prepared using xanthate reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT) polymerization. The resulting nano-micelle block copolymers, including PNVCz-b-PMPSA, PNVCz-b-PAMPS, and PNVCz-b-PSSA, were characterized using techniques such as NMR, XRD, FTIR, SEM, GPC, TGA, and DSC. The block copolymers demonstrated self-assembly in aqueous solution and exhibited perm-selective properties, which were exploited for the electrochemical sensing of dopamine. Additionally, the optical properties of the block copolymers were examined using UV-vis absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopy. These materials exhibit promising self-organization and ion exchange capabilities for potential applications in various fields.

Keywords: Block copolymers, Reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer, Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR)

Effects of triherbal formulation of *Cynodon dactylon*, *Moringa oleifera*, and *Alternanthera sessilis* green leaves extracts against streptozotocin-nicotinamide induced Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in mouse model

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 diabetes (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic condition characterized by insulin resistance and insufficient insulin production, which causes high blood glucose levels. Its lasting presence frequently results in nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy, and cardiovascular problems. While pharmaceutical therapies are beneficial in treating T2DM, they frequently have negative effects. Herbal medicines, on the other hand, provide a compelling option that is effective in glucose management while causing no adverse effects. Embracing herbal plants presents a viable path for T2DM control, providing efficacy comparable to prescribed drugs while maintaining a good safety profile.

Methodology: The study was conducted in Kamrup Metro district of Assam in order to facilitate the experimental work. The formulation comprises of methanolic extracts of *Cynodon dactylon*, *Moringa oleifera*, and *Alternanthera sessilis* leaves. Preliminary screening of the components and analysis were performed to identify bioactive components and select solvents. The glycemic index of the formulation was determined using the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 2010 method. Four groups of animals were used: diabetic treated (T1) with streptozotocin-nicotinamide (60 mg/kg and 120 mg/kg), metformin treated (T2), plant extract treated (T3), and a control group. Morphological, biochemical, enzymatic, and histological parameters were assessed following standard protocols with IAEC approval.

Results: The study showed that streptozotocin-nicotinamide induced Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), highlighting the harmful effect on pancreas, heart and liver health. Again, combined treatment of *Cynodon dactylon*, *Moringa oleifera* and *Alternanthera sessilis* leaves in time and dose dependent manner showed significant improvement in reducing T2DM in the mouse model system.

Conclusion: So far this study suggests that selected plant parts of *Cynodon dactylon*, *Moringa oleifera* and *Alternanthera sessilis* possess antidiabetic properties against streptozotocin nicotinamide induced T2DM. Here, we have also encountered that the efficacy of the triherbal formulation (CD+ASG+MO) > *Moringa oleifera* (MO) > *Cynodon dactylon* (CD) > *Alternanthera sessilis green* (ASG). Hence it demonstrated the potential therapeutic efficacy of these organic extracts in controlling T2DM.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Streptozotocin, Nicotinamide, Metformin, Glycemic index

Integrated alliance of the 2 AIs: Artificial Intelligence & Ancient Ideology

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Abstract

The study delve into the ancient system, knowledge, practices and beliefs which are inherited awards contributing to the world today, influencing the technological field which is giving us impeccable outcomes in all desired industries, be it medicine, architecture, education, commerce, transport, communication, security, finance and also the mental health, which is also the major subject of the following analysis. The modern technological innovations indicating how it is shaped with the ancestry of primeval practices is demonstrated by the ancient books, prehistoric sculptures, temple layouts and aged practices which power up the technological applications of the contemporary period. The phrases which came into trend nowadays such as, mental well-being, depression, anxiety, panic attacks, therapeutic practices etc. are assessed and resolved through ancient rituals and customs since the dawn of time, which are now used and enacted with the advancements of technology and computational intelligence. Definitely, when the 2 AIs i.e., Artificial Intelligence and Ancient Ideology are integrated together then the results will be absolutely miraculous with respect to the mental care, which should be addressed, keeping in mind the present scenario and for the vitality of the future generation chiefly, along with all the age groups as mental health doesn't discriminate between ages or financial and economical variability. This research reveal the positive impact of digital development associated with the principles of ancient knowledge on the mental health, coupled with enthralling ancient methods employed in today's technological advancements.

Keywords: Mental well-being, Technological innovations, Prehistoric sculptures, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Computational intelligence

Mycogenic synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles using endophytic fungus (*Neurospora sp.*, a Novel) isolated from *Buchanania lanzen* and its assessment as Nanobiopotential

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Abstract

Many fungal endophytes were identified and evaluated for this capacity in an effort to find a potentially simple and ecologically acceptable method of producing a variety of nanoparticles at a low cost and without the use of hazardous or harmful substances. In this study Zinc Oxide (ZnO) NP's have been synthesized using the extract of fungal endophytes isolated from *Buchanania lanzen* plant. The zinc acetate and the sodium hydroxide were used as the precursors and the fungal extract as a solvent (reducing agent) to synthesize the ZnO nanoparticles by utilizing the sol-gel method. Biologically synthesized nanoparticles were initially monitored by ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy which shows a single plasmon resonance peaks of ZnO identified within the 350-400 nm range. Further, as-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles were characterized by the x-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) in imaging and diffraction mode. The morphological feature of the ZnO nanoparticles has been analyzed and it was observed that the majority of the spherical nanoparticles with an average particle size of 17 nm, however, few ZnO nano rods were also observed. The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) analysis confirmed the pure synthesized ZnO nanoparticles having hexagonal wurtzite phase with lattice parameters $a = b = 3.24 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.20 \text{ \AA}$. In this investigation, the ZnO nanoparticles synthesized are very stable and had greater antioxidant activity than the endophytic fungal extract, according to the results of the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay and total antioxidant capacity. The biosynthesized nanoparticle produced from fungal endophyte extract shows strong antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*- ATCC 25922, *Klebsiella sp.* - 4151, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*- ATCC 27853. The study's findings demonstrate the potent therapeutic potential of synthetic green ZnO NP's and the need for more research in the fields of antimicrobial medication development and drug delivery approach.

Keywords: ZnO nanoparticles, Nanostructures, Sol-gel, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fungal endophyte extract

Phytochemical analysis of Black rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) & its antibacterial activities against multidrug resistance (MDR) bacteria

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Abstract

Black rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), once demarked from mainstream food habits, is now being considered as super food because of high content fibre, iron, vitamin E, anthocyanins thereby providing numerous health benefits. The rise of multidrug-resistant bacteria is an urgent crisis, necessitating the immediate development of new strategies to combat these infections. Black rice has bioactive compounds, especially anthocyanins, which could enable its extract and phytochemicals to combat MDR bacteria effectively. Our aim here is to assess the bioactive compounds of black rice and its antimicrobial efficacy against MDR bacteria. Black rice plant parts were evaluated qualitatively using polar and nonpolar solvents. The chemical composition of methanolic black rice grains extract was analyzed using GC-MS. The antimicrobial activity of these methanolic extracts was assessed against both gram +ve and -ve strains of multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria through the disc diffusion method. Our result revealed various common bioactive compounds associated with parts of the plant like alkaloids, flavonoids, sterols and tannin. GC-MS analysis report shows these components such as Methane dichloronitro (100%), Acetonitrile d3(56.01%), 3,4-Epoxytetrahydrothiophene-1,1-dioxide (38.13%), Borane, dimethoxy (21.33%) in high proportion. The methanolic extracts also exhibit an antibacterial effect against MDR bacteria as well as significant antioxidant potential. This suggests that black rice has potential antimicrobial phytochemical that can be further explored to get lead molecules for effective application in the early diagnosis of the infections or in the area of novel drug development in therapeutic approach for combating the MDR bacteria.

Keywords: Black rice, MDR bacteria, Antimicrobial activities, GC-MS, Early diagnosis, Novel drug development

Spatio Temporal Diversity and Abundance of Gastropod in Chilika Lagoon-Ramsar site

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Abstract

Gastropods are one of the most diverse groups of animals, both in form, habit, and habitat. Class Gastropoda is the largest group in the phylum Mollusca. Phylum mollusca acts as an important constituent in the marine biodiversity. It provides immense ecological functions related to commercial, social, aesthetic and medicinal. Mollusca, being a vital link between the benthic pelagic-trophic structure, is responsible for recycling of nutrients, provides food to higher level predators such as fishes, shellfishes, birds and human beings. It provides an ideal substrate for many of the sessile forms like benthic algae, meio and macrobenthic organisms to colonise over their body. Gastropods are an important and representative component of rocky shore assemblages. They are the most species rich class within the mollusks with a reasonably well-known taxonomy. The types of habitats occupied by the gastropods are also extremely diversified. They inhabit both in terrestrial and aquatic environments. Gastropods are relatively sedentary animals live at the bottoms and substrates that are not fully flooded. The occurrence of gastropod species is highly influenced by physical (temperature, depth) and chemical factors (pH, salinity). If they found in fewer number, this may indicate that their environment has poor water quality. This makes them frequently used as biological indicators (bio-indicators) of water quality.

Investigation during the period of 2 years from 2010 to 2012 on the Gastropods of Chilika lake revealed the occurrence of 64 species belonged to Gastropoda among which 29 species are dominant. Maximum Gastropoda taxa were found in the outer channel region of the lake. The dominating species were *Nassarius foviolatus*, *Nassarius stoletus*, *Nassarius sp.*, *Thiara sp.*, *Thiara puludomoidea*, *Thiara tuberculata*, *Acrilla sp.*, *Cerithidea singulata*, *Cerithidea obtuse*, *Pseudonerita obtuse*, *Stenothera deltae*, *Stenothera blanfordiana*, *Umboonium vestianum*, *Brotia costula*, *Timoclea imbricate*, *Columbella duclosiana*, *Columbella sp.*, *Modiolus striatus*, *Gyraulus velifer*, *Olivancillaria gibbosa*, *Rapana rapiformes*, *Pugilina sp.*, *Larina burmana*, *Lymnea acuminata*, *Thiara rudis*, *Gangetica miliacea*, *Gabbia orcula*, *Bethynea pulchella e.t.c.* The abundance of Gastropod in the lake is varies between 2702 to 5199 nos/m².

Keywords: Chilika, Diversity, Abundance, Gastropoda lake

Anti-filarial efficacy of *Centratherum anthelminticum*: Through biochemical, HRAMS proteomics, Docking, and MD simulation approaches

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Abstract

Background: Lymphatic filariasis (LF) is a serious health problem caused by *Wuchereria bancrofti*, *Brugia malayi*, and *Brugia timori*. LF is prevalent in tropical and subtropical areas of the world, and more than 50 million people in 44 countries are infected. *Centratherum anthelminticum* (CA) traditionally has been recognized as an effective anti-filarial agent.

Aim: To our knowledge, this is the first report detailing the molecular mechanism of anti-filarial activity of CA, which can be further evaluated for the development of new anti-filarial formulations.

Methods: In this study, we have evaluated the anti-filarial activity of CA against lymphatic filarial parasites. *Setaria cervi* using *ex vivo* biochemical, proteomics, and *in silico* approaches to determine the ROS, NADPH oxidase, 2D gel electrophoresis, HRAMS, and gene ontology analysis were performed.

Results: The motility and viability of the parasites decreased significantly after treatment with CA concentrations of $\geq 125 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. An increase in lipid peroxidation (51.92%), protein carbonylation (48.99%), ROS generation (78.78% at $250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), and NADPH oxidase (88.88%) activity was also observed after CA treatment. The proteomics analysis was performed by two-dimensional gel electrophoresis and high-resolution accurate mass spectrometry (HRAMS). In total, 185 proteins were differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) following CA treatment. The UPLC-ESI-MS/MS analysis of CA extract revealed the presence of 40 bioactive compounds. MD simulation studies showed stable interactions ($\text{RMSF} \leq 10 \text{ \AA}$) of CA bioactive compounds with filarial antioxidant proteins.

Conclusion: CA treatment had a huge impact on the metabolism and survival of *S. cervi* filarial parasites. The *in silico* studies proved that CA bioactive compounds like 3-*O*-methylquercetin, quinic acid, vanillin, and gentisic acid could stably interact with the parasites anti-oxidant proteins GPx, TRx, SOD, and GST. Hence, on the basis of molecular docking and MD simulation studies, seems to be CA is a future treatment modality for Lymphatic Filariasis.

Keywords: 3-*O*-methylquercetin, Anti-filarial formulations, Bioactive compounds, Molecular dynamics simulation, Proteomics analysis

Climate change and the rise of infectious diseases: Implication for Global Health

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Abstract

This study explores the significant impact of climate change on the emergence and spread of infectious diseases, particularly vector-borne illnesses. With rising global temperatures and shifting weather patterns, the environmental factors influencing diseases outbreak are increasingly complex. The research focus on how climate change affects diseases vectors, especially mosquitoes, and the regions most susceptible to these shifts. Warming temperatures expand the range of mosquito species such as *Aedes aegypti* and *Anopheles gambiae*, enabling them to thrive in areas previously unsuitable for their survival. Additionally, increased rainfall and altered precipitation patterns provide ideal breeding conditions for mosquito populations, thus intensifying disease transmission risks. Climate-induced changes in human behavior, including urbanization and increased travel, also contribute to the spread of diseases. This study highlights the potential rise in prevalence of malaria, dengue, chikungunya, zika virus and COVID-19 (highlights the urgency of understanding climate's role in pandemics, as environmental changes may support new and re-emerging diseases) particularly in tropical and sub-tropical areas, as mosquito population flourish due to warmer temperature and new water sources from melting glaciers. According to world health organization (WHO) the dengue has grown dramatically around the world in recent decades, with cases increasing from 505430 in 2000 to 5.2 million in 2019. The highest number of dengue cases was recorded in 2023, affecting over 80 countries. The tally of dengue cases continue to rise, highlighting the persistent challenges posed by this infectious diseases. Health authorities are grappling with the situation as outbreaks escalate, necessitating urgent public health responses and preventive measures. The ongoing vigilance is essential to mitigate the impact and protect vulnerable population from this widespread arboviral threat.

Keywords: Climate change, Infectious diseases, Vector borne illness, Mosquito proliferation, Arboviral threats

Comparative analysis of coat proteins of sesbania mosaic virus (SeMV) and cowpea mosaic virus (CPMV) with host proteins of family Fabaceae: An *In silico* approach

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Abstract

The interaction between virus and host plays a vital role in influencing the effectiveness of infection and its transmission throughout the system. The research is entirely based on the comparative study between CPMV and SeMV and their interaction with the host. Both viruses affect the same crop family named *Fabaceae* and cause a considerable reduction in crop yield. SeMV attacks the *Sesbania grandiflora* and CPMV specifically target *Vigna unguiculata*. The genome of both the viruses is single stranded, bipartite, and positive sense RNA. Assembly and disassembly throughout the infection is mainly dependent on the dimerization of coat protein. The protein structure of *Fabaceae* family is retrieved from Protein Data Bank (PDB) server. The protein-protein interaction was performed to analysis the binding affinity of CP dimers of both viruses along with their host. The CP dimer of CPMV and SeMV was docked with 60 host proteins to visualize the main protein responsible for the viral infection. The comparative study analyzed the difference and similarity between the binding patterns of both the viruses and provided a score based on the binding strength. The research discusses the conserved and distinctive interaction of CPMV and SeMV with the Family *Fabaceae* which mainly highlights the essential mechanism behind the assembly, disassembly and dimerization during the infection. The research will be helpful in providing the possible anti-viral targets on the basis of these interactions. This study will also help in understanding the actual process taking place during the viral infection in plants and brings into the wider investigation of host-virus interaction in isometric plant viruses.

Keywords: CPMV; SeMV; Host-virus interaction; Coat protein; Docking

Impact of Municipal solid waste landfill leachate on ground water quality in Ramchak, Bairiya, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract

Ground water pollution has emerged as global environmental problem which is continuous and serious threat to the ecological environment and human health. Municipal Solid waste landfill is a major potential threat to soil, ground water and surface water. landfill leachate which contains many toxic and harmful substances such as heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants and bacteria has become one of the main anthropogenic sources of ground water pollution. This study analyses the microbial and evaluate the physicochemical characteristics of ground water near the dumping site of Bairiya. Water samples were collected from different sources in vicinity of dumping sites during summer, monsoon and winter season. On the basis of standard method physicochemical and microbial analysis were performed. Multiple Tube Fermentation technique was carried out for most probable counts. Seasonal fluctuations were seen where monsoon season exhibited high pollution level. The finding emphasis the need to develop an engineered landfill site to control leachate Percolation into the ground water.

Keywords: Municipal Solid waste, Leachate, Landfill site, Dumping site, Ground water

Health culture and hygiene practices among the Karimpalan community in Kannur district of Kerala

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Abstract

Background: The Karimpalan tribe, with a population of around 14,098 (2011 Census), is primarily found in the districts of Kozhikode, Kannur, and Wayanad districts in Kerala. The name “Karimpalan” originated from their traditional association with charcoal, known as “kari” in the local language. As an understudied tribe, comprehensive information about their culture remains scarce. The present paper is about the concept of health and hygienic practices adopted by the Karimpalan from the perspective of medical anthropology.

Aim of the study: To study the concept of Health and Hygienic practices within the Karimpalan community through fieldwork.

To understand or identify community specific challenges and opportunities for health and hygiene from the wider perspective of sustainable development.

Methodology: The study of the Karimpalan community employed a mixed method approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative techniques, utilizing participants-observation, household surveys, interviews, case studies, genealogy, and visual aids. Household surveys and genealogy helped identify key informants, built rapport, and traced family lines. Direct interview with community members enriched the data collection process, allowing for deeper insights into their health beliefs and practices.

Results: The study explores the health and hygiene practices of the Karimpalan community within their sociocultural and environmental context. The community integrates traditional healthcare methods like Ayurveda and ethno-medicine with modern medical practices, supported by extensive knowledge of medicinal plants. Despite access to government health schemes, chronic lifestyle diseases persist, particularly among the elderly. The Karimpalan community also demonstrates exceptional hygiene practices, utilizing natural resources such as ashes and coconut for cleaning. These practices highlight their adaptability to environmental constraints and emphasizes the need for culturally contextualized healthcare interventions.

Conclusions: The community’s health and hygiene practices have significantly evolved due to their exposure to mainstream culture and modernization. While they have retained traditional methods like using cow dung for cleaning and natural remedies, they have also embraced modern hygiene products and medical facilities. This blend has improved their overall sanitation and health outcomes. The shift from agricultural based sustenance to diverse occupations and the influence of government interventions have enhanced their quality of life. Access to education and healthcare has empowered the younger generation leading to better health awareness and practices. Despite the challenges, the community continues to adapt to new bio medical knowledge systems along with preserving its cultural identity and heritage.

Keywords: Tribal health, Karimpalan, Ethno medicine, Traditional medicine, Hygiene, Natural cleaning resources, Traditional hygiene practices, Resource utilization

Chemoprotective efficacy of combined methanolic extract of *Alternanthera sessilis* L. and *Polistes flavus* venom against NNK-induced carcinogenicity in mouse model

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Abstract

Introduction: The consumption of smoking and smokeless tobacco is a common habit in many cultures. Tobacco contains toxic components like nicotine, nitrosamines, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. Nicotine-derived nitrosamine ketone (NNK), a potent pre-carcinogen, undergoes metabolic conversion into reactive metabolites that can cause DNA damage, leading to cancer. While treatments like chemotherapy and radiation exist, they manifest with serious side effects. Naturopathy and phyto-zoo therapy offer promising alternatives in mitigating carcinogenic impact.

Aim: This study investigates the potential of extract of *Alternanthera sessilis* and *Polistes flavus* (including its bioactive component, mastoparan) in mitigating the detrimental effects of NNK-induced carcinogenic stress in Swiss albino mice.

Methodology: *A. sessilis* leaves were identified and extracted using standard methods, while *P. flavus* was collected, and its bioactive component, Mastoparan, was isolated via column chromatography. Two doses of NNK (50mg/kg and 100mg/kg body weight) were administered once in Swiss albino mice for cancer development over 3 months. After 90 days, mice were treated with *A. sessilis* (100mg/kg), *A. sessilis*-*P. flavus* (100:15mg/kg), and *A. sessilis*-mastoparan (100:10mg/kg). The study analysed hematological, histopathological, biochemical, oxidative stress enzymes, and molecular expression profiles through standard techniques.

Results: NNK exposure resulted in behavioral abnormalities, weight loss, hematotoxic effects, and organ damage in liver, lung, and kidney tissues. Significant increases in leucocyte count and cellular deformities were observed. Histopathologically, carcinogenic alterations in vital organs viz., biliary hyperplasia in liver, lymphoidal aggregation or hyperplasia, bony metaplasia and neoplastic growth in liver and lungs, glomerular nephritis in kidney was observed. Alterations in marker serum enzyme profile revealed toxic stress-induced organ dysfunction, with reduced oxidative stress enzyme profile. Western blot and immunohistochemistry showed high expression of carcinogenic markers (BCL₂, COX₂, P₅₃, B-actin). Both combination treatments proportionately mitigated these changes in the order: *A. sessilis*-mastoparan > *A. sessilis*-*P. flavus*.

Conclusions: The combination of *A. sessilis* and mastoparan showed significant therapeutic potential in mitigating NNK-induced pre-carcinogenesis and carcinogenesis in the target organs. The findings of the study may contribute to drug discovery approaches, highlighting a promising role in pharmacological and therapeutic applications. However, further research is necessary to elucidate the molecular mechanisms and optimize dosage and treatment protocols.

Keywords: NNK, *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Polistes flavus*, Mastoparan, Phyto-zootherapy, Carcinogenesis

The antioxidative and antimicrobial properties of hot spring isolated cyanobacterial strains

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Abstract

The hot spring thriving cyanobacteria are well known for their ability to produce various bioactive compounds like polyphenols, alkaloids, terpenes, fatty acids and their derivatives to adapt themselves in surrounding environmental conditions. In the present study we have investigated the ability of hot spring originated cyanobacterial strains to synthesize bioactive compounds such as antioxidant and antimicrobials. Total fourteen strains have been isolated from Tatapani hot spring, Chhattisgarh, India, among them ten were thermophilic and showed optimum growth at 45°C while rest other strains including *Desikacharya* sp. grew optimally at 25°C. Among them, *Desikacharya* sp. showed highest bioactive potential like antioxidant and antimicrobial activities. The methanolic extract of *Desikacharya* sp. was evaluated for total phenolics and flavonoids. Total antioxidative potential, evaluated using FRAP, DPPH and ABTS assay were found highest for *Desikacharya* sp. Further the antimicrobial activity was seen against the two gram positive (*Staphylococcus* sp. CSSB1 and *Bacillus* sp. CSSB5) and one gram positive (*Aeromonas* sp. CSSB3) bacteria. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for these strains was 250 µg mL⁻¹, 125 µg mL⁻¹, and 500 µg mL⁻¹ respectively which were better than the previous studies on the same bacteria. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was done for the separation of methanolic extract. Finally, the HRLC-MS based identification of the bioactive eluted bands of *Desikacharya* sp. unveiled that most of the metabolites were natural amino derivatives of fatty acids, free fatty acids, sesquiterpenes.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, Antioxidants, Bioactive compounds, Hot spring, HRLC-MS

Ultraviolet-B induced alterations in growth, physiological responses, antioxidant activity, and essential oil composition of *Ocimum americanum* L., a medicinal plant of the Indo-Burma Biodiversity Hotspot

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Abstract

Ocimum americanum L., commonly known as American basil or lime basil, is an annual herb in the Lamiaceae family with medicinal significance. Its decoctions are used for coughs, while its leaves and whole plant are applied for respiratory issues, rheumatism, and renal ailments. With increasing global climate change and stratospheric ozone depletion, understanding the impact of increasing ultraviolet-B (UV-B) radiation on medicinal plants is crucial. The present study was carried out to assess the effect of elevated UV-B (eUV-B; 38.8 KJ/m²) on growth, physiology, antioxidant status and essential oil composition of *O. americanum* at different developmental stages (30, 60 and 90 days after transplantation). Results showed that plant growth, photosynthetic pigments, and physiological parameters declined, however; total phenolics significantly increased under UV-B treatment as compared to the control. Elevated UV-B also led to the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including superoxide radicals and hydrogen peroxide, leading to membrane damage and increased solute leakage. *In vivo* histochemical localization of ROS confirmed the accumulation of damaging reactive oxygen species, evident as brown and blue-coloured formazan inside plant cells under UV-B treatment. Antioxidant enzyme activities (SOD, CAT, APX, and GR) were significantly higher under eUV-B. GC-MS analysis of essential oil revealed increased levels of specialized metabolites like caryophyllene and β -ocimene (known for anticonvulsant, antifungal, antitumor, and pest-resistance properties) under UVB treatment. This study highlights that while eUV-B reduces growth and physiological functions in *O. americanum*, it enhances antioxidant defense and the production of specialized metabolites.

Keywords: Ultraviolet-B; Medicinal plant; Physiology; Antioxidants; Metabolites

Microplastics Assessment in the Lower Stretch of the Ganga River Sediment from East Indian Region: Influence of Land Use and Rainfall Patterns

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Abstract

Microplastics (MP) pollution is increasingly viewed as a serious threat to waterways. However, little is known about the effects of land use and rainfall patterns on the occurrence and distribution of MPs in the river sediments. Herein, the MP pollution in different land uses (Settlement, waterbodies, vegetation, agriculture, fallow land, and open spaces) along the lower stretch of the Ganga River, in East Indian region was investigated. The present study conducted sediment sampling for MP at three monitoring sites in the Patna district, Bihar, which is part of the Ganga River basin. The Land Use Land Cover (LULC) across the Patna district was classified using Random Forest (RF) and a machine learning classifier on Google Earth Engine (GEE). The findings revealed a gradual increase in MPs concentration across all the studied sites. The number of MPs showed a positive correlation with surrounding urban and population density (PD), with correlation coefficients of 0.52 ($p < 0.05$) and 0.42 ($p < 0.05$) respectively within a 2 km buffer radius. Additionally, MPs exhibited a positive correlation with rainfall, with a correlation coefficient of 0.90 ($p < 0.05$) within the total buffer area. The RF classifier demonstrated strong performance in classifying LULC classes, achieving an overall accuracy of 95% and a kappa coefficient of 0.91. Overall, insights gained from the present study can inform the development of effective policies and interventions aimed at reducing MP contamination and preserving water quality in river ecosystems.

Keywords: Microplastics; The Ganga River; Sediment; Land use land cover; Buffer scale; Random forest

Antidiabetic Potential of Medicinal Plants and Their Active Components

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is one of the major health problems in the world, and incidence and associated mortality are increasing. Inadequate regulation of blood sugar imposes serious consequences for health. Conventional antidiabetic drugs are effective, however, they also with unavoidable side effects. There is an increasing demand from doctors and patients to use plant extracts as an antidiabetic agent. This is more because insulin cannot be used orally and oral hypoglycemics have many side effects and toxicity besides after a certain period synthetic oral hypoglycemics do not remain effective in lowering the blood sugar in the chronic stage of diabetes. Several plants have been claimed to have hypoglycemic action both by Indian scientists and those who are working abroad. But as yet no drug has been developed which has stood the test of full-scale clinical trials. Assessment in some clinical trials is only based on symptomatic improvement or simple urine tests. In some, cases only fasting blood sugar has been done before and after treatment. Very rarely the glucose tolerance test has been adopted. However, the antidiabetic action of a drug cannot be claimed unless and until the response of therapy is demonstrated on the insulin release or metabolism. On the other hand, medicinal plants can act as an alternative source of antidiabetic agents. Examples of medicinal plants with antidiabetic potential are described, with a focus on preclinical and clinical studies. The beneficial potential of each plant matrix is given by the combined and concerted action of their profile of biologically active compounds.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus; Medicinal plants; Antidiabetic; Hypoglycemic; Antihyperglycemic

Ecological study on the lentic water body of Baniyapur with reference to planktonic diversity

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Abstract

Ecology is the study of the relationship between living organisms, including humans, and their physical environment, it seeks to understand vital connections between plants and animals and the world around them. Ecology is the multidisciplinary field extending across the physical, biological, and social sciences. Ecology was a practical interest early in human history. In primitive society, all individuals needed to know their environment, that is, to understand the forces of nature and the plants and animals around them to survive. Ecology derived from the Greek word Oikos, meaning habitation, and logos meaning study, i.e. study of the habituation of organisms.

Collection and identification of phytoplankton According to size, phytoplankton are classified as ultra-plankton 0.5 to 10 μm , nannoplankton 10 to 50 μm , micro plankton (net plankton) 50 to 500 μm and macro plankton 500 μm . larger phytoplankton collected by filtering a known amount of water through a plankton net made by bolting silk (no. 25 mesh size 55 μm). Take one liter of water sample in a wide mouth glass bottle. Add 10 ml of Lugol's iodine solution per liter of sample. Lugol's iodine solution speeds up the rate of sedimentation of phytoplankton, provides them stain, and preserves their flagella and cilia. For complete sedimentation samples were allowed to stand for a day.

Phytoplanktons are the base of aquatic food webs and energy production is linked to phytoplankton primary production. Excessive nutrient and organic inputs from human activities in lakes and their watersheds lead to eutrophication, characterized by increases in phytoplankton biomass, nuisance algal blooms, loss of water clarity from increased primary production and loss of oxygen in bottom waters. Phytoplankton is the base of the food web which affects the food production. Diatoms have been used by ecologists to indicate pollution in water bodies and other variations of ecological conditions. Chlorophyta was dominating group and cyanophyta was the second dominant group. In the pond the contribution of chlorophyta and cyanophyta to total biomass was higher than 90%. Phytoplankton biomass reached the value many times higher.

The present study highlights good zooplankton diversity in the Baniyapur pond. Twenty nine species of zooplanktons representing seven groups of namely- Rotifera, Cladocera, Copepoda.

Keywords: Phytoplanktons, Diatoms, Zooplanktons

Lactose Intolerance and its correlation with Metabolic Syndrome

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Abstract

Introduction: Milk is a key component of the diet of every mammal but not every individual can tolerate it. Lactose maldigestion, the inability to fully digest lactose due to low levels of lactase enzyme activity, exhibits notable diversity across different age cohorts. This study explores the spectrum of lactose maldigestion across various age demographics, shedding light on the nuanced factors influencing its prevalence and severity beginning with infancy and progressing through childhood, adolescence, adulthood, and into the elderly population. Factors such as genetic predisposition, environmental influences, dietary habits, and ethnic diversity were evaluated to check if they contribute to the observed variations in lactose maldigestion rates among different age groups. Understanding these age-related patterns of lactose maldigestion is crucial for informing dietary recommendations, clinical management strategies, and public health interventions aimed at optimizing digestive health across the lifespan.

Aim: This study aims to determine the prevalence of lactose intolerance in Uttar Pradesh population and correlating it with demographic factors, lifestyle choices, dietary avoidances and their interplay with metabolic syndrome.

Methodology: *Population Sampling:* Utilize epidemiological sampling technique to recruit a representative sample of individuals. *Diagnostic Assessments:* Clinical evaluation to assess lactose intolerance prevalence and severity. Simultaneously, ascertain metabolic syndrome status through established criteria. *Data Collection:* Gather comprehensive data on demographic characteristics, dietary patterns, physical activity levels, socioeconomic status, and medical history through structured surveys, dedicated questionnaire and medical records review.

Statistical analysis: Utilize advanced statistical methods, to examine the relationships between lactose intolerance, metabolic syndrome and associated risk factors.

Conclusions: This research holds significant implications in the area of public health, clinical practice, and community well-being in Lucknow and beyond. By elucidating the intricate relationship between lactose intolerance, metabolic syndrome, and associated risk factors, this study has the potential to inform evidence-based interventions that address the unique needs of the population

Keywords: Lactose maldigestion, Lactase, Adolescence, Prevalence

Phytochemical Diversity and Medicinal Properties: A comprehensive review of the phytochemical compounds found in various *Achillea* species and their potential health benefits

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Abstract

Achillea is a medicinal plant that is found in various regions across the globe and has a long history of use dating back to ancient times. Different species of *Achillea* are employed worldwide for fighting and treatment of various diseases including wounds, headache, inflammation, spasmodic diseases, flatulence, dyspepsia, gastrointestinal issues, haemorrhages, pneumonia, rheumatic pains, diuresis, and infections. A significant number of these therapeutic applications have been validated through recent experimental and clinical research. *Achillea* provide health advantages because to the abundance of secondary metabolites found in this genus's plants, which include flavonoids, phenolic acids, terpenes, guaianolides, phytosterols, organic acids, and fatty acids. In comparison to sesquiterpenes, monoterpenes are the most representative metabolites, accounting for 90% of essential oils. Cis-thujone (36.9%), 1,8-cineole (11.9%), camphor (10.0%), ascaridole (7.3%), α -terpinene (6.4%), sabinene (4.1%), trans-thujone (3.6%), and cis-jasmone (3.4%) were among the essential oils of *Achillea grandifolia* that were found to have antioxidant activities through their interaction with DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) and their inhibition of lipid peroxidation. Additionally, the essential oils were found to have anti-inflammatory properties through their inhibition of soybean LOX (lipoxygenase). The current paper demonstrates the therapeutic qualities of several *Achillea* species that have been studied based on scientific in vitro, in vivo, or clinical assessments.

Keywords: *Achillea*, Global distribution, Gastrointestinal issues, Spasmodic diseases

Evaluation of Cyto-genotoxic potential of some Pesticides on the root tip cells of *Allium cepa* L.

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Abstract

Evidently, Genotoxicity and mutagenotoxicity of pesticides for non-target organisms and their influence on ecosystems are of worldwide concern, an attempt has been made to evaluate the Cyto-genotoxic potential of aqueous solutions of some pesticides *i.e.*, *Monocrotophos* (C₇H₁₄N O₅P) and *Chlorpyrifos* (C₉H₁₁C₁₃N O₃P S) and *Endosulphan* (C₉H₆Cl₆O₃S) on the root tip cells of *Allium cepa* L.

The solutions of varying concentrations (0.12%, 0.25%, 0.50%, 0.75%, 1.00%) of pesticides were prepared by dissolving pesticides in desired amount of distilled water. The root tips of *Allium cepa* L were treated with different concentrations of pesticide solutions and also with double distilled water (DDW) for control for four hours at room temperature. The treated and control root tips were fixed in 1:3 aceto-butanol and squashed in 2% aceto-carmin solution.

Result confirmed that the pesticide solutions altered the frequency of mitotic division *i.e.*, 15.57±0.66 to 05.97±1.02 (*Chlorpyrifos*), 13.43±0.22 to 4.08±0.23 (*Endosulphan*) and 14.69±0.16 to 04.85±0.91 (*Monocrotophos*) in comparison to control (18.60 ± 0.21), however the chromosomal abnormalities (CA) such as vacuolated prophase, stickiness, fragment, disturbed metaphase/anaphase, ghost cells, damaged nucleus, polar deviation, bridges, laggards, c-mitosis, micronuclei and binucleate cells were significantly induced with doses of the solutions from 8.26 to 35.80 (*Chlorpyrifos*), 10.35 to 46.33 (*Endosulphan*) and 9.28 to 42.00 (*Monocrotophos*), however negligible CA were found in control *i.e.*, 0.40. The gradation of mitodepressive and clastogenic potential of pesticide solutions was noted as *Endosulphan* > *Monocrotophos* > *Chlorpyrifos*. The ANOVA test confirmed a significant variation of mitotic depression (P<0.001) and induction of chromosomal aberrations (P<0.01).

An inverse correlation between the pesticides doses and mitotic index (MI) which is compatible with the hypothesis that inhibition of mitosis may be due to inhibition of DNA synthesis / protein synthesis /prolonged G2 period or might have deregulated the activity of cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs), and the chromosomal abnormalities may be the result of direct attack of pesticide solutions on chromosomal material however, the exact mechanism can be explored only through extensive molecular studies. Conclusively, it is advisable to secure the genotoxicity test of the pesticides before their use to agricultural crops.

Keywords: Pesticides, Cyto-genotoxic mitodepressive, Clastogenic, *Allium cepa* L.

Comparative Analysis of Root Canopy Architecture and Root Capacitance in Finger Millet (*Eleusine coracana*. L) under Varying Climatic Conditions

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Abstract

Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana* L.), also known as ragi, is a small-seeded cereal grain commonly grown in the semi-arid tropics of Africa and South Asia. Renowned for its resilience to harsh climates and high nutritional value, finger millet is a key crop in these regions. Root systems are vital to plant survival, as they anchor plants, absorb water and nutrients, and provide structural stability. Root canopy architecture refers to the spatial arrangement of a plant's roots, akin to the spread of leaves above ground, encompassing root depth, length, density, branching, and lateral spread. Root capacitance, which measures a root system's ability to store and conduct electrical charge, serves as an indirect indicator of root health, root-soil contact, and water uptake efficiency. This property reveals how effectively a plant utilizes soil resources like water and nutrients. In an experiment at two locations (Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University and Mahayogi Gorakhnath University, Gorakhpur), 41 varieties of finger millet were tested in three replicates. Root capacitance was measured using a root capacitance meter, while root canopy traits were assessed manually. Results showed a root capacitance range of 4 to 58 μF , root length from 11.1 to 28 cm, root branches between 17 to 37, fresh root weight from 0.9 to 7.2 gm, and dry root weight from 0.12 to 2.58 gm. Analysing root canopy architecture and root capacitance is critical for understanding water and nutrient uptake efficiency, plant health, and resilience to environmental stress. These parameters aid in selecting or developing crop varieties with improved drought tolerance, nutrient efficiency, and yield stability across diverse conditions.

Keywords: Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana* L.), Root canopy architecture, Root capacitance, water uptake efficiency

The Neuroprotective Landscape of Oxymatrine: Mechanistic Insights and Clinical Implications

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Abstract

Oxymatrine, an alkaloid isolated from the roots of *Sophora flavescens*, has emerged as a promising agent in the field of neuroprotection, demonstrating significant potential in mitigating various neurological disorders, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis. This comprehensive review aims to synthesize the current literature on the neuroprotective mechanisms of oxymatrine, exploring its multifaceted actions at the cellular and molecular levels. Recent studies have indicated that oxymatrine exerts neuroprotective effects primarily through its ability to reduce oxidative stress, enhance neuronal survival, and modulate neuroinflammatory processes. By scavenging reactive oxygen species and increasing the expression of antioxidant enzymes, oxymatrine effectively alleviates oxidative damage, a hallmark of neurodegeneration. Additionally, its anti-inflammatory properties involve the regulation of key signaling pathways, such as the NF- κ B and MAPK pathways, which are crucial in mediating the inflammatory response in the central nervous system. Moreover, oxymatrine has been shown to promote neurogenesis and synaptic plasticity, supporting cognitive function and recovery from neural injuries. Preclinical and clinical studies further substantiate its therapeutic efficacy, demonstrating improvements in cognitive and motor functions among patients with neurological impairments. Despite its therapeutic promise, the mechanisms underlying oxymatrine's neuroprotective effects remain to be fully elucidated, necessitating further investigation into its pharmacokinetics, optimal dosing, and long-term safety profiles. This review aims to provide a detailed overview of oxymatrine's neuroprotective properties and therapeutic potential, serving as a foundation for future research aimed at translating these findings into clinical practice for better management of neurological disorders.

Keywords: Oxymatrine, Alzheimer's Disease, Neurodegeneration, Amino acids, BBB

Senna: An Excellent Laxative Herbal Medicine - Cultivation and Storage Strategies

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Abstract

Background: It is evident from the literature that 80% of the world's population depends on herbal drugs. Now-a-days, the herbs and herbal medicines are much effective for the treatment of varied disorders as they have minimal side effects as compared to the allopathic medicines. Nowadays, constipation is a common complaint and challenge for older and adults. Senna (*Cassia augustifolia*) is an ayurvedic herb more popularly known as *Swarnapatri* in Sanskrit, widely used for its numerous benefits. The plant is mainly valued for its cathartic properties and is especially useful in habitual constipation. The pods and leaves contain anthraquinone glycosides that have a big laxative effect, besides its use as mild laxative, Senna's other benefits include in the treatment of jaundice, hepatitis, herpes simplex, cracking of the skin, migraine headache, hair loss, and for relaxing muscle tension.

Aim/Objective: To cultivate and store Senna more and more due to its numerous health benefits.

Methodology: Cultivation of Senna doesn't require much expense on irrigation, manuring, pesticides, protection and other pre- and post-harvesting care. About 20 kg seeds are required to cover one hectare of land. This makes the plant a perfect crop for arid regions where water provision, wasteland development, desertification control, dune stabilization are the main challenges such as in Rajasthan.

Results: This prophetic herb is very beneficial for numerous health issues. The plant has been investigated for its various chemical constituents and pharmacological properties.

Conclusion: Given the profound health benefits and economic feasibility of *Cassia augustifolia*, there is a strong need to promote the cultivation and use of senna on a large scale. This will not only support the healthcare system but also provide environmentally sustainable crop options for areas facing agricultural challenges.

Keywords:

Senna, Prophetic medicine, Anthraquinone glycosides, Laxative, Cultivation, Storage

Microplastics pollution in River Ganga: Microbial Solutions for Clean-up

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Abstract

Microplastics pollution in aquatic bodies and their potential hazardous consequences have led to a strong surge in finding out ways for their removal from both marine and freshwater ecosystems. The Ganga River is documented with moderate to heavy microplastic contamination both in water and sediment and estimated to carry a large amount of plastic debris to ocean system. It is estimated that Ganga river alone contributes about 0.12 out of 2.41 million tons of annual discharge of microplastics into the oceans. The ingestion of microplastics is one of the primary adverse impacts of microplastics in the environment, with studies linking it to reproductive, respiratory, digestive, and overall health effects on animals and aquatic organisms.

Microorganisms can break down microplastics through biotic degradation which involves enzymatic disassembly of the particles and converting them into non harmful substances for the environment either in aerobic or anaerobic conditions. Typical examples include *Bacillus myocides*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Staphylococcus xylosus* etc. A bacteria *Ideonella sakiensis*, can use plastic as a substrate for its growth and uses it as a source of carbon.

Green microbiology has emerged as an effective, relatively affordable, sustainable, and environmentally friendly way of remediating microplastics. Microorganisms, through different pathways, break down microplastics into less toxic biomass, producing energy in the process, essentially remediating microplastics and mitigating their environmental and health effects.

Keywords: Microplastics, Green microbiology, Ganga river, pollution

Evaluation of Phytochemical Components, Antioxidant and Antibacterial Properties of Methanolic Extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*

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Abstract

Indian Ayurveda has long and glorified history of herbal medication system. Numerous plants and their compounds have been demonstrated to have promising effects against microbial infections and various diseases. *Boerhaavia diffusa*, commonly known as Punarvava, is plant known for its medicinal properties. This plant has various ethnobotanical applications, including the use of its leaves as a vegetable, while the root juice is traditionally used to treat conditions such as asthma, urinary disorders, rheumatism, and encephalitis. In this study, we utilized the methanolic extract of the whole *Boerhaavia diffusa* plant to explore its potential bioactivity. The preliminary qualitative analysis revealed positive results for various phytochemicals including phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, coumarin, glycosides etc. Total phenolic content and total flavonoid content were measured using the Folin-Ciocalteu assay and the AlCl₃ colorimetric assay, respectively. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was used for qualitative phytochemical analysis that exhibited the separation of different spots, suggesting the presence of different groups of phytochemicals in the extract. The plant extract also showed significant inhibition of growth of selected pathogenic bacterial strains as demonstrated by inhibition zones in disc diffusion antibacterial assay. However, further studies are needed to confirm the relationship between the identified phytochemicals and the observed bioactivity.

Keywords: *Boerhaavia diffusa*, Antioxidants, Antibacterial activity, Phytochemicals.

Development and characterization of FRET-based nanosensor for real-time monitoring of herbicide in living prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells.

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Abstract

Nanosensors are highly advanced tools designed to detect and measure substances at the nanoscale, with applications in fields like agriculture, healthcare, and environmental monitoring. In agriculture, they are especially useful for monitoring herbicides like atrazine, a widely used chemical for controlling weeds. Atrazine, while effective, can have harmful environmental effects, making precise monitoring crucial for sustainable farming practices. FRET-based nanosensors, which use fluorescence resonance energy transfer between cyan and yellow fluorescent proteins, are particularly effective in detecting atrazine in real-time. These nanosensors offer significant advantages over traditional methods like HPLC, as they are non-invasive and provide high-resolution, dynamic measurements at the sub-cellular level. By using these sensors, atrazine levels can be monitored more precisely, allowing farmers to control herbicide applications better and reduce potential environmental harm. Nanosensors represent a breakthrough in tracking atrazine and other agrochemicals, helping to balance effective weed control with environmental safety. This technology offers new possibilities for improving herbicide management and reducing the risks associated with chemical use in agriculture.

The periplasmic binding protein of this AtzT has been identified from the protein database (PDB). This protein shows conformational change upon binding to the ligand. The gene sequence of this protein was retrieved from NCBI. Primers for the amplification of the gene sequence of AtzT, cyan fluorescent protein (CFP) and yellow fluorescent protein (YFP) with compatible restriction sites are designed. The gDNA was isolated from *P. citronellolis* (Strain ADP). This protein was amplified using PCR and it was cloned in a pGEMT vector. Similarly, CFP and YFP are amplified using the pDEST15 vector as a template. Both amplified products are cloned in pGEMT vector. All three amplified genes of these proteins were run on the agarose gel to validate the size of the genes. Further validation of all three genes was carried out through restriction digestion. In the next step, all three genes are ligated together to make the nanosensor for AtzT.

Keywords: FRET-based nanosensors, Atrazine detection, Herbicide monitoring, Agrochemical tracking, Weed management, Herbicide application

PALLADIUM(II)-CATALYSED OXIDATION OF GLYCINE AND ARGENINE BY ACIDIFIED POTASSIUM BROMATE

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Abstract

This study examines the kinetics and mechanistic pathways of Pd(II)-catalyzed oxidation of glycine and arginine by potassium bromate in an acidic medium, focusing on reaction rates, activation parameters, and product identification. The reaction, conducted at temperatures between 30-45°C, utilized potassium bromate as an oxidant, demonstrating first-order kinetics with respect to both the oxidant and the Pd(II) catalyst. Mercuric acetate was added to control chloride ions, maintaining a stable acidic environment crucial for the reaction. For glycine, first-order kinetics with respect to Pd(II) and zero-order dependence on glycine were observed. Similarly, arginine followed first-order kinetics with Pd(II), though its unique structure suggested some variations in reactivity. The reaction rate was unaffected by ionic strength or mercuric acetate concentration but was significantly accelerated by increased hydrogen ion and chloride concentrations, emphasizing the importance of acidity.

Stoichiometric analyses established a 1:2 molar ratio between potassium bromate and each amino acid in acidic medium. Activation energies (E_a) were calculated as 54.2 kJ/mol for glycine and 61.3 kJ/mol for arginine, with activation entropies (ΔS^\ddagger) of -89.3 J/mol·K and -78.5 J/mol·K, respectively, indicating highly ordered transition states. Chromatographic and spectroscopic analyses identified glyoxylic acid as the main product from glycine oxidation, while arginine oxidation produced an α -keto acid derivative.

The findings support a reaction mechanism involving a transient Pd(II)-bromate complex that facilitates electron transfer, leading to amino acid oxidation. The proposed mechanisms and derived rate laws for each amino acid provide valuable insights into Pd(II)-catalyzed oxidation of amino acids, contributing to a broader understanding of transition metal-catalyzed transformations in biomolecules.

Keywords: Kinetics, Palladium(II) Catalysis, Potassium Bromate, Glycine, Arginine, Oxidation

Pharmacognostical and physicochemical analysis root of Sarapunkha [*Tephrosia purpurea* (Linn.) Pers.]

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Abstract

Background: Sarapunkha [*Tephrosia purpurea* (Linn.) Pers.] commonly known as "Wild Indigo" is a leguminous plant widely used in traditional medicine for its reported hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. Evaluating the properties of the plant through pharmacognostical and physicochemical parameters is essential for determining its authenticity, chemical stability, purity, and suitability for use in pharmaceutical formulations. According to P. V. Sharma, it is renowned as pleehasatru because of its potential to act upon spleen and liver.

Materials and methods: The roots of Sarapunkha were collected from Jaipur District, Rajasthan, cleaned, shade-dried and were powdered. Macroscopic examination for anatomical features was carried out. Microscopic examination and physicochemical parameters such as moisture content were conducted in accordance with API guidelines.

Results: The root of Sarapunkha is cylindrical, light brown, fibrous, and has a rough surface with longitudinal ridges. Microscopic examination of the transverse section shows 8 cork layers made up of rectangular cells, a wide cortex rich in starch grains, and multiple patches of sclerenchyma cells. The solid xylem contains wide vessels, tracheid, and xylem parenchyma filled with starch, with biseriate medullary rays present between the xylem vessels. Physicochemical analysis revealed aqueous soluble extract value (10.56%), alcohol soluble extract value (4.97%), petroleum ether soluble extract value (0.82%), moisture content (5.11%) and pH value is 4.25.

Conclusion: The pharmacognostic and physicochemical analysis of Sarapunkha root provides essential data for its identification and quality control. These findings contribute to ensuring the authenticity, purity, and standardization of the raw material for medicinal use.

Keywords: Sarapunkha, Pharmacognosy, physicochemical, pleehasatru, API guidelines

Impact of Blood Transfusions on Climate Change and mitigation strategies

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Abstract

Background: Modern Medicine Healthcare activities significantly contributing in single use plastic waste and Green House Gas emissions. Healthcare carbon footprint is responsible for 4-5% of global carbon emissions. Blood Transfusions is among one of the top five overused interventions of Modern Medicine. Blood Transfusions are energy intensive process which involves transport, collection, processing in heavy electrical equipment, refrigeration and transfusion. Blood Bags are made up of PVC with DEHP plasticizer. Its manufacturing, use and incineration impacts climate change and it contaminates environment from carcinogenic vinyl chloride monomer, bio accumulative toxins dioxins, furans and mercury contamination of waterways and micro plastics.

Aims and Objectives: Our primary aim is to assess the extent of inappropriate transfusions and secondary objective is to assess the burden of PVC waste generated due to inappropriate transfusions

Material and Methods: In a cross-sectional study from Rajasthan state, data of transfusion practices collected from transfusion request forms from 10 blood centres. The sample size was calculated to be 5650 transfusion request forms, catering to 7350 transfusions at a rate of 1.3 units issued per transfusion request.

Results: Out of 3803 blood units transfused in the medical and medical super speciality branches, 1669 transfusions (43.89%) of them were transfused without any documentation for the indication for transfusion or a haemoglobin value, which is considered as inappropriate practices. In India the annual collection accounts for 12-15 million units, 40% of which is utilized in correcting nutritional anaemia/iron deficiency anaemia Each unit of blood collected generates 381 gm of plastic waste (PVC with DEHP). Considering 50% of inappropriate transfusions annually generates approx. 3 lakhs tons of plastic waste for incineration. NHS Blood and Transplant, UK in one of their study calculated 15000 tonnes of carbon dioxide emission in 2019, most of which were attributable to blood donation and testing and the manufacture, storage, and distribution of blood components.

Conclusions: Bio-Medical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2016 states phase out use of chlorinated plastic bags, gloves and blood bags within two years from the date of notification of these rules. Since there is no alternative for blood bags reduction and rational

utilization is the only solution Environment pollutants and micro plastics generated from incineration of PVC blood bags. Plasticizer DEHP is an endocrine disrupter and cause ADHD, asthma, breast cancer, obesity and type 2 diabetes.

Keywords: Transfusions, PVC, DEHP, Climate change, carcinogens

Multi Toxic Venom PLA2 complex from *Daboia russelii* snake venom

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Abstract

Russel vipers (Genus: *Daboia*) are snakes of significant medical importance in Asia, due to the high morbidity and mortality associated with envenoming and their wide geographical range. In snake venoms, non-covalent protein interaction leads to protein complexes with synergistic and, at times, distinct pharmacological activities. Here we describe a new protein complex containing phospholipase A2 (PLA2), protease, and a trypsin inhibitor. It is isolated from the venom of *Daboia russelii* by gel permeation chromatography, on a Sephadex G-75 column. This 44.6 kDa complex exhibits only phospholipase A2 activity. In the presence of 8M urea, it is well resolved into protease (29.1 kDa), PLA2 (13 kDa), and trypsin inhibitor (6.5 kDa) peaks. The complex showed an LD50 of 5.06 mg/kg body weight in mice. It also caused peritoneal bleeding and edema in the mouse foot pads.

Keywords: Russel vipers, synergistic, Sephadex G-75 column, phospholipase A2

Health and Traditional System of Medicine (AYUSH)

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Abstract

Ayurveda is an ancient Indian system of medicine that has been practiced for thousands of years. With the advent of Information Technology (IT), there are now new opportunities to apply advanced computational techniques to various aspects of Ayurveda. This article reviews the current applications of IT in Ayurveda and their impact on drug discovery, clinical practice, diagnosis, education, and data management. The use of computational tools is leading to new discoveries from Ayurvedic text mining, an improved understanding of Ayurvedic disease classification, as well as better diagnosis and treatment methodologies. The integration of information and communication technology in education is providing high-quality Ayurvedic e-learning resources and online courses. Overall, these breakthroughs are helping to promote the growth of Ayurveda in the 21st century. Further opportunities and future directions for technology in the field are also discussed.

Keywords: Ayurveda, Information Technology, computational tools, e-learning, drug discovery

THE HERBAL TEA: COMBINATION OF HERBS

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Abstract

Due to their high phyto-chemical content, herbal teas have been drunk for ages which are well mentioned in traditional medicine systems for their medicinal and therapeutic qualities and have been utilized for centuries to cure various diseases. Traditional medical systems like Ayurveda and Unani medicine make extensive reference to herbs and their therapeutic actions. The goal of this study was to create a novel herbal tea blend using Tulsi Leaves, Hibiscus Flowers, and Aparajita Flowers. These herbs have different health benefits, such as antioxidants, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, anti-cancer, antimicrobial, cardio protective, anti-diabetic etc. The combination includes a ratio of 2:3:5 (**Tulsi Leaves: Aprajita Flower: Hibiscus Flower**) and aqueous extract tested found rich in Phyto-constituents such as alkaloids, glycoside, flavonoids, carbohydrates, and also the extract of this combination tested for anti-oxidant and anti-microbial assays.

Keywords: Traditional medical, Ayurveda, phyto-chemical, immunomodulatory, anti-cancer, antimicrobial, anti-diabetic

Distribution of Short-Horned and Long-Horned Grasshoppers in Selected Places of Kamrup, Assam and Management Strategies for *Atractomorpha crenulata* and *Maconema thalassinum* by Bio-Herbal Formulation

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ABSTRACT

Background: Grasshoppers are a major pest species that cause widespread damage to various crops, leading to significant economic losses. To control their population, synthetic pesticides are widely used, raising serious concerns for public health and environmental safety. In this context, bio-herbal formulations offer a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative for pest control.

Aim: The present study focuses on collection and identification of different grasshopper species from various Kamrup district areas along with the control measure of most prevalent grasshopper species using combined formulation of five traditionally used herbs.

Methodology: Grasshopper species were collected and identified using standard method. A survey work was conducted on the traditional uses of plant species in pest management using bilingual questionnaire. Preliminary phytochemical screening and GC-MS was conducted for the detection of marker bioactive compounds for insecticidal properties in *Phlogacanthus thyrsoiflorus* (PT), *Aegles marmelos* (AG), *Carica papaya* (CP), *Citrus limon* (CL), *Chrysanthemum grandifolium* (CG). Probit analysis of different concentrations of herbal extract was conducted for the determination of LC₅₀ (3mg/ml) and selection of dose (1mg/ml). The experimental was carried out in four groups viz., control group, treated group - T1 (Wood ash + PT+AM), T2 (CP+CL), T3 (CG+Wood ash), T4 (Wood ash+PT+AM+CP+CL+CG). The combined formulations were sprayed at a 3-days interval for 21 days period. The study is based on behavioural, morphological, haematological, biochemical and histopathological(midgut) analysis, following standard methods.

Results: Thirty-two grasshopper species were identified, with *Atractomorpha crenulata* and *Maconema thalassinum* being the most abundant. Phytochemical and GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of bioactive compounds such as tannins, terpenoids, and alkaloids. Key marker compounds like benzoic acid, 2-palmitoylglycerol, and acorenone B were identified for their insect-repellent properties. Behavioral and morphological alterations, variations in haemolymph morphology, and a significant reduction in haemocyte count were observed. Histopathological analysis showed midgut deformities, and amylase activity was significantly ($p < 0.05$) inhibited.

Conclusions: The findings revealed that combination of all five-plant extract is more effective than di- or tri-plant extracts against grasshopper species which depicts in the order: T4>T1>T3>T2. Further research is required to validate the bio-herbal formulation for effective management of pest populations and enrichment of soil nutrients.

Keywords: Short-horned grasshoppers, Long-horned grasshoppers, GC-MS, bio-herbal formulation.

Investigation of strychnine as antimicrobial agent against strains of MDR

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Abstract

Strychnine, a well-known alkaloid primarily extracted from the seeds of *Strychnos nux-vomica*, is recognized for its potent biological activities and toxicological properties. This study investigates the antimicrobial properties of strychnine through experimental in vitro analyses and computational in-silico studies to elucidate its molecular mechanisms and target interactions. We hypothesized that strychnine's unique molecular structure, characterized by a bicyclic core and multiple functional groups, may interfere with microbial cellular functions, leading to significant antimicrobial effects. Using disc diffusion and broth micro-dilution assays, we evaluated the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of strychnine to assess its efficacy. Our results revealed significant antimicrobial activity, with particular high effectiveness against MDR strains. Morphological and structural analyses of treated microbial cells were conducted via different microscopy confirming membrane disruption as a key mechanism of action. These findings suggest that, despite its toxicity, strychnine could serve as a lead compound for the development of novel antimicrobial agents when appropriately modified or used in controlled formulations. Further research is warranted to optimize its selectivity and reduce toxicity, making strychnine a viable candidate in the fight against multidrug-resistant pathogens along with cancers.

Keywords: Toxicity, Microorganisms, strychnine, alkaloid, efficacy

Assessment of culturable bacterial bioaerosol variability in fields growing aromatic and medicinal plants

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Abstract

The decline in air quality due to rapid urbanization and industrialization in developing countries is an increasingly pressing issue, particularly with the rise in bioaerosols-airborne particles of biological origin. These bioaerosols pose significant threats to public health and the environment. As a result, there is growing interest in exploring natural remedies. Understanding microbial diversity in natural environments, particularly in plants with antimicrobial properties, could offer valuable insights into combating bioaerosols. In this context, aromatic and medicinal plants emitting volatile compounds with known antimicrobial activity may be especially worth investigating.

This study aimed to examine the variability in the bacterial communities present in bioaerosols collected from fields planted with aromatic and medicinal plants. Two species of *Ocimum*-*Ocimum sanctum* and *Ocimum basilicum*-were selected for the aromatic plants and medicinal, while *Andrographis paniculata* represented the non-aromatic and medicinal category. The results showed no significant difference in the concentration of particulate matter (PM₁₀) across the three sites. The average PM₁₀ concentrations were 221.78 µg/m³ at Site 1 (*Ocimum sanctum*), 232.76 µg/m³ at Site 2 (*Ocimum basilicum*), and 239.31 µg/m³ at Site 3 (*Andrographis paniculata*). However, when comparing the total culturable bacterial units in the bioaerosols, the lowest bacterial concentration was observed at the *Ocimum sanctum* site, followed by the *Ocimum basilicum* site, with the highest bacterial concentration recorded at the control (*Andrographis paniculata*) site. Bioaerosols collected from the control site (*Andrographis paniculata*) were dominated by bacterial species such as *Bacillus sp.*, *Pantoea sp.*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* AB18, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain ASR-39. In contrast, these bacteria were found in much lower concentrations in the bioaerosols from the *Ocimum sanctum* and *Ocimum basilicum* sites. This study highlights a distinct pattern in the bacterial communities of bioaerosols across fields of aromatic and non-aromatic plants. These findings deepen our understanding of bacterial aerosols in fields of aromatic plants and also suggest potential interactions between aromatic plant species and bioaerosols.

Keywords: Bioaerosol; Bacterial composition; *Ocimum*; Aromatic

Cardioprotective efficacy of Carvacrol against Isoproterenol induced cardiotoxicity in rats

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Abstract

Background: Heart is the most active and incumbent organ of the body, which maintains blood flow, but due to various pathological reasons, several acute and chronic cardiac complications arise out of which myocardial infarction is one of the teething problems. Isoproterenol imitates the adrenergic stimulation and manifests the main index of the pathogenesis of maladaptive myocardial hypertrophy. Isoproterenol induced cardiotoxicity is a well-established model to study cardiac damage. Carvacrol is a phenolic monoterpenoid abundantly present in the essential oils of oregano and thyme and is well-known for exerting multiple pharmacological effects such as antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, anti-angiogenic, and anti-tumor activity. The present study was undertaken to understand the protective effect of carvacrol on isoproterenol induced cardiac damage in rats.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in Swiss Albino rats. Rats were divided into four groups: control, isoproterenol, carvacrol alone and carvacrol+isoproterenol. Isoproterenol (150 mg/kg b.w.t.) was injected intraperitoneally to induce myocardial injury to rats. Carvacrol (10 mg/kg b.w.t.) was supplemented orally for 14 days to assess its beneficial effect.

Results: Isoproterenol induced cardiotoxicity was evident by abnormal ECG parameters, hemodynamic parameters, lipid profile, increase in lipid peroxidation (malondialdehyde levels) and decrease in cellular antioxidants (superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione S transferase, vitamin E, vitamin C and vitamin A). Histopathological analysis of cardiac tissue further confirmed the cardiac damage induced by isoproterenol. Carvacrol treatment significantly reversed all the above abnormalities induced by isoproterenol.

Conclusion: The results of our present investigation reveals that the mechanism behind the cardioprotective effect of carvacrol could be reducing oxidative stress and enhancing cellular antioxidant levels.

Keywords: Isoproterenol, cardiac damage, carvacrol, oxidative stress, lipid profile; antioxidants

Ultrasound-assisted ring opening of epoxides in HFIP: THF: Synthesis, characterization, computational studies and molecular docking of novel 2-hydroxy dithiocarbonates

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Abstract

Under the influence of ultrasonic irradiation, pyridazinone, triazinone, or phthalimide containing 2-hydroxy dithiocarbonates, a biologically relevant novel organo-sulphur compound, was synthesized. Detailed characterization, computational, and molecular docking studies are being investigated. Molecular interactions were studied using 3D Hirshfeld surfaces and corresponding 2D fingerprint plots. Theoretical (DFT) studies on the molecular structure, HOMO, LUMO, and quantum chemical descriptors were performed at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory. At the same time, the interaction energy was computed using the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level of theory. The interactions of 2-hydroxy dithiocarbonate derivatives (4a) with the ligand-binding site of the target COX-2 (cyclooxygenase-2) enzyme were investigated using in-silico molecular docking experiments. Compared to the standard medicine celecoxib, the results showed that most synthesized derivatives had better glide scores and interaction. Molecular dynamic simulation was utilized to validate the docking study and explore the stable binding site and interaction of compound 4a, which is the most potent. The findings indicated that compound 4a exhibited better stability and interaction when compared to the reference drug.

$R^1 = \text{Pyridazinone, Triazinone, Phthalimide}$

Result: Since epoxides are crucial structural motifs in a variety of novel organic reactions and chemical transformations, we started our synthesis of the desired dithiocarbamates by forming epoxide derivatives containing phthalimide, triazinone, and pyridazinone according to a standard protocol. These epoxide derivatives were then characterized using ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. Following the synthesis of these epoxide derivatives, we began the synthesis of our intended product, hydroxy dithiocarbamates. The epoxide derivative 1a (1.06 mmol) with CS_2 (2.40 mmol) and piperidine (1.06 mmol) was chosen as a model reaction for the production of 2-hydroxy dithiocarbamates at rt in an HFIP: THF solvent combination. The model reaction was tested in a variety of different solvents in the absence of metal catalysts and bases.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, a convenient, selective, and environmentally friendly methodology was developed for the synthesis of various biologically relevant novel pyridazinone, triazinone, and phthalimide-containing 2-hydroxy dithiocarbonates in HFIP: THF under the influence of ultrasound irradiation, and their characterization, computational, and molecular docking studies are being investigated. Spectral studies such as HNMR, ^{13}C NMR, and single crystal X-ray examinations were done to analyze the structures of the generated compounds. The intermolecular interactions of 2-hydroxy dithiocarbonates were thoroughly investigated using single crystal and Hirshfeld surface analysis.

Keywords

Di thiocarbamates, Hirshfeld surface analysis, HOMO-LUMO, Molecular docking, Interactions energy calculations, Quantum chemical descriptor

Green Synthesis and Characterization of *Terminalia bellirica* (Gaertn.) Roxb. Fruit derived Carbon Quantam Dots

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Abstract

Background: Nanoparticles, wide variety of chemical composition, size, shape and functional groups, predominantly used for drug delivery, cell or tissue targeting. Among the nanoparticles, carbon quantam dots (CQDs), are group of fluorescent and photostable, water soluble, can be internalized by cells and cross cell membranes. Over the past few years, CQDs samples have been utilized in drug delivery, bioimaging, photocatalysis, and photodynamic therapy simultaneously. In recent years, the use of plant derived materials for the synthesis of CQDs has emerged as a green and sustainable approach with high biocompatibility.

Terminalia bellirica Roxb. (*T. bellirica*, is well known medicinal plant and has been used in various Ayurvedic medicine. It has antioxidant, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, etc activities. *T. bellirica* fruit is rich in various organic compounds, which makes it an ideal candidate for the synthesis of carbon-based nanomaterials. Although synthesis of CQDs using this plant material is still unexplored.

Aim: The present study focuses on developing an efficient synthesis of CQDs from *T. bellirica* fruit and to perform a detailed characterization of the synthesized CQDs and to check its antioxidant activity.

Methods: Hydroalcoholic extract of *T. bellirica* fruit prepared by cold maceration technique, used for CQD synthesis by Hydrothermal Carbonization technique. Characterization of CQD of *T. bellirica* fruit extract by using a variety of techniques, including UV-Vis Spectroscopy and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX). DPPH assay was performed to check antioxidant activity of CQD sample.

Results: Absorbance at 202 nm and 260nm in UV-Vis spectrophotometer which indicates that CQD sample synthesized from *T. bellirica* fruit extract. The peak of PL at 390nm shows fluorescence nature of synthesized CQD. The TEM image analysis reveals 10nm size of CQDs. FTIR spectrum indicates functional groups such as OH-stretching, Alkane-stretching, O-H-bending etc. in CQDs. CQD synthesized sample contains higher weight % of Carbon as compared to raw extract which clearly indicates the presence of CQDs. DPPH assay revealed the antioxidant characteristics of the CQDs.

Conclusions: Synthesis and characterization of *T. bellirica* fruit extract derived CQDs, provide insights into the structural, morphological, and optical properties, contributing to a better understanding of its biocompatibility and bioactivity as a medicinal product with pharmacological applications.

Keywords: Bahera, Rasayan, Hydrothermal Carbonization, Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Optical properties, Biocompatibility

Study of Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Sone River Water in Dehri-on-Sone Area of Bihar, India

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Abstract

Fresh water is necessary for healthy living. River water is used for various purposes, such as drinking, bathing, irrigation, etc. This natural resource is being polluted by indiscriminate disposal of sewage, industrial waste, and human activities, which affect the quality of river water. This paper deals with a study of physico-chemical characteristics of the river water of Sone along the Dehri-On-Sone stretch during a period of 12 months from March 2023 to March 2024. Physico-chemical parameters like temperature, pH, TDS, TSS, TS, DO, COD, BOD, alkalinity, total hardness, chloride, and turbidity were determined. The results were compared with standards prescribed by WHO (1984). Temperature, pH, and chloride of all the samples were found below the permissible limit set by WHO. It is concluded that the water of the river is not highly polluted, but there is an indication of increasing pollutant due to anthropogenic activities. Proper monitoring is needed to avoid anthropogenic contamination.

Keywords: Physico-chemical, temperature, pH, TDS, TSS, TS, DO, COD, BOD, alkalinity, total hardness, chloride, and turbidity.

Utilizing the Medicinal Potential of *Amomum* Species: Insights into Metabolite Profiling and *in-Silico* Studies

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Abstract

The Himalayan region, known for its rich biodiversity, is home to a myriad of medicinal plants that have been the foundation of traditional medicine for centuries. Among these, the genus *Amomum* of the Zingiberaceae family, shines brightly due to its remarkable therapeutic potential. These plants are increasingly significant in the realm of medicine, offering a wide array of therapeutic applications. Unfortunately, their high medicinal value, their overharvesting also makes them vulnerable to habitat loss. For generations, various species of *Amomum* viz *Amomum subulatum*, *A. aromaticum*, *A. xanthoides*, *A. dealbatum* have been utilized in traditional medicine to treat a plethora of disorders. This is attributed to their rich phytochemical constituent that includes alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, terpenes, and terpenoids. Essential oils extracted from *Amomum* species have been extensively studied, revealing a diverse chemical profile. Key compounds such as limonene, allo-aromadendrene, 1,8-cineole, germinal, camphor, farnesyl acetate, α -pinene, β -pinene, β -elemene, caryophyllene, camphene, D-camphor, santolina triene, methyl chavicol, and bornyl acetate have been identified as major constituents. *Amomum* is recognized as an official drug in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia, much valued for its curative and preventive properties. It exhibits a range of beneficial effects, including anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and anti-cancer activities. In conclusion, the integration of *in silico* studies offers a powerful framework for harnessing the medicinal potential of threatened Himalayan *Amomum* species. Molecular docking studies help predict how bioactive compounds interact with specific biological targets, such as enzymes and receptors, associated with diseases. These methodologies not only pave the way for the discovery of new drugs but also promote the conservation of biodiversity and sustainable use of natural resources.

Keywords: Metabolite Profiling, Threatened, Essential oils, Pharmacological Activity, Molecular docking etc.

Subacute toxicity of Monosodium Glutamate and its amelioration by methanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaf in certain organs of Swiss albino mice

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Abstract

Background: Rapid urbanization has transformed human lifestyles, especially food habits. Fast food, praised for its convenience and affordability, has become a dietary staple. However, its frequent consumption raises health concerns due to various flavor-enhancing additives like monosodium glutamate (MSG) commonly known as Ajinomoto. Prolonged MSG intake has been linked to various adverse effects on organs, including the liver, testes, brain, and spleen. MSG induces oxidative stress and disrupts metabolic pathways, posing long-term health risks. In response to these risks, natural alternatives like the tender leaves and flowers of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* are traditionally used for disease protection in this zone, have gained attention for their nutritional and medicinal benefits, offering protection against MSG-induced toxicity.

Aim of the study: The present study aims to evaluate the subacute toxicity of MSG and explore how *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaf extract (NLE) can mitigate its toxic effects.

Methodology: The leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* were collected, and the methanolic extract was prepared and screened for phytochemicals using standard methods. Swiss albino mice were used as the model organism, maintained under standard animal husbandry conditions. The mice were divided into three groups: Control, MSG-treated (Dose: 1.06 mg/kg b.wt., intraperitoneally), and MSG withdrawal + NLE-treated (Dose: 200 mg/kg b.wt. NLE extract). The study involved behavioral observations, necroscopic examination and biochemical, hematological, and histopathological assessments following standard protocols.

Results: The study revealed that NLE exhibited significant protective effects against MSG-induced toxicity. Phytochemical analysis of methanolic NLE detected flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, and other bioactive compounds in significant concentrations. MSG-treated mice initially showed hyperactivity and increased appetite, which later declined but normalized with NLE treatment. Organ weight analysis and biochemical tests confirmed NLE's effectiveness in reducing MSG-induced liver and kidney dysfunction. Histopathological examination revealed MSG-induced hepatotoxicity, testicular degeneration, neurotoxicity, splenic fibrosis, and other severe damages which were seemed to be mitigated post-NLE treatment.

Conclusions: In conclusion, MSG induces significant toxicity across multiple organs through oxidative stress. The methanolic NLE counteracts these adverse effects, showing potential as a therapeutic agent. This study underscores NLE's benefits in reducing MSG-induced organ damage and encourages further research into natural remedies for dietary additive-related health risks.

Keywords: Monosodium Glutamate (MSG), *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, oxidative stress, toxicity, antioxidant properties, histopathology

Obesity and Mild Health Issues: A Comprehensive Study of Demographic and Lifestyle Determinants

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Abstract

Background: Obesity has emerged as a global public health concern, and the prevalence of obesity has witnessed a significant surge globally, posing substantial challenges to public health. Analyzing regional variations and disparities among genders reveals important insights into the complex interplay of demographic, socioeconomic and lifestyle factors. Gender specific conditions such as hormonal influence, societal expectation and cultural norms could be a key factors contributing to gender disparities in obesity prevalence.

Objective: This study aims to explore the trends of obesity in the subjects with no chronic illness, its multifactorial nature, and the related health issues. Study also investigates the demographic, socioeconomic status difference, effect of lifestyle and impact of obesity on working and non-working women.

Methodology: Data was collected from the subjects based on their demographic and lifestyle status with the help of questionnaire from the OPD, Department of Medicine, King Georg's Medical University, Lucknow.

Result: Association between obesity and subject's activity is observed ($\chi^2_{d.f.=1} = 6.011, p < 0.05$). WHtR ($t = -4.10, p < 0.05$) of male and female is significantly associated with obesity. There is a significant association between Economic and Education Status of housewife and working women. For economic status ($t = -2.833, p = 0.01$) and education status ($t = -2.939, p = 0.01$), there is significant difference between obese housewife and obese working women.

Conclusion: Recognizing early minor health problems in people with obesity could be an effective approach to reducing obesity rates. It could also help healthcare providers and government policy maker to develop vast strategies that improve and reduce burden of

obesity in society. This may also contribute to reducing gender-specific obesity and associated co-morbidities

Keywords: *Obesity, gender differences, prevalence trends, co-morbidities, public health, demographic.*

Identification of Jalkumbhi

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Abstract

In the indigenous medical system, Jalakumbhi is an effective Ayurvedic medicinal plant that grows widely as a velvety carpet in mushy water bodies. Jalakumbhi, as indicated in Ayurvedic texts, is comparable to *Pistia stratiotes* var. *cuneata*. However, it is frequently confused with *Eichhornia crassipes*, also known as *Pontederia crassipes* or Water hyacinth thus making it controversial. This could be due to various reasons such as habitat, morphology, identical synonyms, or errors in the manuscripts' documentation. All parts of the plant can be used for preparation of medicine for various diseases. The plant shows anti-thyroid, diuretic, antipyretic, antihemorrhoidal, bronchodilator properties as well as can be used in various bleeding disorders in addition to in individuals suffering from emaciation, *Sangrahani*, *Karnapaka*, prickly heats etc. All parts of the plant can be utilized for preparation of medicine for various diseases. In this paper, we aim to discuss the many therapeutic characteristics of Jalakumbhi, as well as its etymology, morphology, and pharmacological aspects. We will also attempt to review and differentiate the plant commonly referred to as Jalakumbhi.

Keywords: Jalakumbhi, anti-thyroid, antipyretic, antihemorrhoidal, bronchodilator

Coating seeds with biochar and plant growth promoting rhizobacteria enhanced heavy metal stress tolerance in *Zea mays*

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Abstract

The rapid pace of industrialization and urbanization in developing countries has led to severe environmental challenges, including the accumulation of heavy metals in soils. This contamination, largely driven by human activities, degrades soil fertility, reduces crop yields, and poses serious risks to human and animal health by entering the food chain. In recent years, seed coating along with biochar and plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) has emerged as a pioneering, eco-friendly solution for enhancing agricultural productivity across a range of soil conditions, from conventional to highly challenging environments. By improving nutrient availability, strengthening plant defences, and fostering a healthier soil ecosystem, seed coating along with biochar and PGPRs represents a revolutionary approach to sustainable agriculture, paving the way for more robust and adaptable crop production in an era of changing environmental conditions. The present study aimed to assess the effect of seed-coating with PGPR, biochar and binders on the survival efficiency of inoculated PGPR and thus plant growth and physiological response in multi-metal contaminated soils. The wood chips biochar (WCB) was selected for this study based on its plant growth promotion potential and its physicochemical parameters. This study investigated individual and combined effects of WCB and PGPR *Bacillus cereus* (Zn01) and *Bacillus subtilis* (Zn11) coated seeds on *Zea mays* growth, physiology, and their impact on antioxidant enzyme activity under multi-metal stress. It was observed that even under multi-metal stress, *Z. mays* growth, pigment contents, proteins, phenolics, relative water and antioxidant enzyme activity were increased in response to WCB, biochar and PGPR-treatment. Hence, the results highlight that seed coating with WCB and PGPR provides a conducive environment which in turn enhances plant growth and physiological responses by producing various plant growth-promoting metabolites. Therefore, seed coating with WCB and PGPR could be exploited as an effective strategy for eco-restoration and phytoremediation for improving plant growth, removal of metal contents and establishing the survival of plants under multi-metal stress conditions.

Keywords: Biochar, Heavy metals, PGPR, *Zea mays*, phytoremediation

Exploring Nicotinamide Phosphoribosyltransferase (NAMPT) Modulators for Enhancing Production of Nicotinamide Mononucleotide

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Abstract

Nicotinamide mononucleotide (NMN) is a critical intermediate in the biosynthesis of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺), a coenzyme involved in various essential cellular processes such as energy metabolism, DNA repair, and cell signaling. The biosynthesis of NMN is regulated by the enzyme nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase (NAMPT), which catalyzes the rate-limiting step. This enzyme is encoded by the NadV gene, and its catalytic efficiency varies significantly across species due to genetic variations. NAMPT activity is particularly important because it influences the production of NMN, which is a precursor that impacts NAD⁺ levels. These levels decline with age, contributing to cellular dysfunction and age-related diseases. NMN is rapidly converted into NAD⁺ within the body, highlighting its importance in maintaining cellular functions and redox balance. Enhancing NAMPT activity could therefore be a key strategy in boosting NAD⁺ levels. In a previous study, certain compounds were found to enhance NAMPT activity *in-vitro*, particularly in human cell lines. In this study, we screened the top 10 of these compounds against human and bacterial NAMPT proteins using a virtual screening tool, to evaluate their binding affinity with both human and bacterial NAMPT proteins. The results revealed that NAMPT activator 4, DS68702229, SBI-797812, and NAMPT activator 2 displayed binding energies of -10, -9, -9.1, and -8.9 kcal/mol with the human protein, and -10.8, -9.6, -9.0, and -8.4 kcal/mol with the bacterial protein, respectively. A comparative analysis showed that NAMPT activator 4 exhibited stronger binding with the bacterial protein. Further validation through molecular dynamics simulation and *in-vitro* studies will be conducted to assess the potential of this compound to enhance NMN production in bacteria.

Keywords: Nicotinamide Mononucleotide, Nicotinamide Phosphoribosyltransferase, NAD⁺ Biosynthesis, NAMPT Activators, Binding Affinity

Herbal raw material authentication based on mass spectrum fingerprints utilizing a digital library of Indian medicinal plants and their metabolites

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Abstract

Herbal raw materials play an important role in the quality assurance of Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani (ASU) drugs. However, authentication of ASU raw materials is a global challenge. Morpho-taxonomy and DNA barcoding are typically used in the current scenario for the identification and authenticity of herbal raw materials. However, these methods frequently fall short of determining their chemical integrity. To address these limitations, a chemical fingerprinting-based approach was developed for the identification and authentication of plant raw materials. In this method, a standard operating procedure (SOP) was followed as per the reference library (<https://plantmetabolome.cdri.res.in>). The mass spectrum fingerprint (MSFP) and unique molecular weight sequence (UMWS) were utilized for the authentication of herbal raw materials. In order to check the accuracy and reproducibility of the results, multiple experiments were performed for analytical and biological reproducibility, the effect of seasonal and geographic variation, for method validation. This proof-of-concept demonstrated a future technology for the authentication of ASU raw materials.

Keywords: Chemometrics, unique molecular weight sequence (UMWS), standard operating procedure (SOP), mass spectrum fingerprint (MSFP), biological reproducibility.

Ecotourism and Local Climate Study in Bastar, Chhattisgarh, India

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Abstract

Bastar, region which is famous for its traditional cultural legacy and biodiversity has seen a rise in the ecotourism activities in the recent few years. Although the ecotourism is supported by many as a model of sustainable development but it is still quite uncertain what its effects may be in the climatic conditions of the local areas. This research intends to explore how the ecotourism industry is connected with climate change occur in Bastar, Chhattisgarh. In this area the rise in ecotourism activities has raised eyebrows regarding a realistic balance that needs to be maintained in the ecological context. To address this question, a case study approach was used in this research concentrating on particular ecotourism development sites within the region. Field observations were done on some climate variables, temperature, humidity and wind for instance, in regions where ecotourism has developed massively. Also, social economic surveys completed in the study area. These kinds of surveys generally seek the opinions of local communities as well as other segments of the tourism market on climate change and the effects that ecotourism has on their subsistence sources. The research study provided evidence that in fact, ecotourism has some impact on climate change. The expanded temperatures, relative humidity and wind patterns of an area as well as the types of one's industry in the area may be caused by people staying over there in excess amount, construction activities and due to the effects of tourism industries in that area. To lessen these bad effects, it is important to use sustainable tourism practices, like good waste management, using resources well, and creating low-impact buildings. By grasping the complicated link between ecotourism and climate change, policymakers, tourism operators, and local communities can team up to encourage responsible tourism that balances money gains with protecting the environment.

Keywords: ecotourism, climate, Bastar, Chhattisgarh, sustainable development

Multifaceted Use of Lemongrass Herb- A Pilot Study

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Abstract

Background: Many traditional Indian medicinal herbs manage diabetes. Therapeutic plants' abundant availability and little side effects are advantages. Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon flexuosus*) extracts and oil kill several pathogens. Lemongrass essential oil has been used often as an antifungal, antiviral, and antibacterial. Essential oils are natural chemicals that may replace synthetic pesticides due to their effectiveness, environmental sustainability, and availability in mosquito-borne illness-prone areas.

Aims: The main aim of this research is to extract and characterise lemongrass essential oil to assess its antibacterial, mosquito larvicidal, and diabetic wound healing potential.

Materials and Methods: The extraction of lemongrass oil was performed using steam distillation and microwave-assisted hydrodistillation methods. The essential oil was characterised using GC-MS. FTIR analysis was used to elucidate the chemical makeup of the essential oils. NMR spectroscopy was employed to analyse all metabolites contained in the extract. The antimicrobial effectiveness of lemongrass oil was evaluated using the disc diffusion method and the minimum inhibitory concentration assay. A larvicidal experiment was conducted on *Anopheles stephensi* larvae to evaluate the effectiveness of the organic oil. A diabetes-induced wound healing experiment was conducted on 8-10 week old mice (n=6) to evaluate the efficiency of the essential oil in wound repair.

Results: This research found that microwave hydro distillation extracted lemongrass essential oil's main components better than steam distillation. The major ingredient, citral, is antimicrobial. Also investigate the chemical nature of lemongrass essential oils from other plant parts. This research showed bactericidal action against *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and maybe all pathogenic fungus. Without pesticides, *Cymbopogon flexuosus* oil killed mosquito larvae in this investigation. Our study shows that β -citral inhibits GPCRs in *Anopheles stephensi*, leading to early mortality. GPCR mutational analysis may help researchers determine whether a binding is helpful or detrimental. Assessment of therapeutic effectiveness requires molecular residual analysis.

Conclusion: Current study reported that lemongrass essential oil has enormous antimicrobial efficacy with potential mosquito larvicidal effect. Wound morphology and gene expression study provides valuable insights into the potential anti-inflammatory and therapeutic effects of lemongrass oil.

Keywords: Lemongrass, Citral, Larvicidal activity, Antimicrobial efficacy, Wound repair

The Ubiquity of Microplastics: Analysing Their Environmental Persistence and Multifaceted Impact on Ecosystem Dynamics and Human Health

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Abstract

Microplastics are everywhere—they are in the air, water, and soil. They are ubiquitous, and we are surrounded by microplastics. Microplastics are tiny plastic fragments less than 5 mm (0.2 inches) in diameter. There are two sources of microplastics: primary sources, which are purposefully made for commercial use, such as in cosmetics, textiles, microbeads, plastic glitter, and plastic pellets; and secondary sources, which result from the degradation of larger plastic debris. 80% of all microplastic in the ocean and the environment primarily comes from textiles (due to their washing), tires and city dust. In 2014, it was estimated that there were between 15 to 51 trillion individual pieces of microplastic in the world's oceans, weighing between 93,000 and 236,000 metric tons. The COVID-19 pandemic has further increased the presence of microplastics in our environment due to the remarkable use of single-use face masks, discarded personal protective equipment (PPE), and poor waste management of these polypropylene (PP)-based plastics. The long-term consequences can be extremely dangerous if urgent action is not taken.

Plastic was designed to improve human life, but today it has become a danger to our environment and the safety of every living organism on the planet. More than 80% of plastic ends up in landfills, where it further degrades into microplastics due to changing weather and photo-oxidation caused by sunlight exposure. Scientists and clinicians around the world are concerned that these microplastics can further erode into nanoplastics (less than 1 mm in diameter) and end up in human cells, even nuclei. A study has revealed that more than 80% of human blood samples contain microplastics, and they have also been found in the liver, heart, lungs, spleen, thymus, reproductive organs, kidneys, and even the brain. These tiny particles enter our bodies through the ingestion of drinking water, table salt, seafood, and packaged food.

Statistics show that at least 267 species worldwide are affected by the microplastic problem, including 44% of birds, 43% of mammals, 100% of turtles, and various fish species—from commonly eaten commercial fish to whales. The presence of microplastics in aquatic species is dangerous to the environment, particularly because these species contribute nutrients essential to human health. For example, when people eat small fish, they consume them whole, including their intestines where microplastics are often found. Plasticosis, a new disease caused solely by plastics, was discovered in seabirds in a study conducted in 2023. This disease scars the digestive tracts of seabirds after they ingest plastics inadvertently.

In conclusion, it is crucial for governments, corporations, and individuals to take urgent action. The first solution is to minimize the use and production of single-use plastics, which account for

up to 50% of total plastic production, and to develop biodegradable, sustainable alternatives. Single-use plastics include items like straws, food packaging, and polyethylene bags. Governments must implement strict policies on plastic waste management, supported by public awareness programs nationwide. Collective efforts are needed not only to find viable solutions to reduce microplastic accumulation in the environment but also to lower consumption levels.

Keywords: Microplastics, environmental contamination, single-use plastics, human health impact, plastic pollution, waste management, biodegradable alternatives

Holistic Healing Through Ayush: Integrating Traditional Wisdom In Modern Healthcare

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Abstract

The traditional system of medicine in India, referred to as AYUSH, encompasses five distinct practices: Ayurveda, Yoga & Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy.

Introduction: AYUSH represents India's rich heritage of medicinal practices that prioritize holistic health and well-being. These systems are rooted in ancient philosophies and emphasize the interconnectedness of the mind, body, and spirit. Each discipline offers unique methodologies aimed at restoring health and preventing diseases.

Methods: The AYUSH systems employ diverse therapeutic approaches. Ayurveda focuses on balancing the three doshas (Vata, Pitta, and Kapha) through individualized herbal remedies, dietary practices, and lifestyle modifications. Yoga promotes physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation to enhance mental and physical well-being. Naturopathy utilizes natural treatments like diet, hydrotherapy, and acupuncture to promote self-healing. Unani medicine, influenced by ancient Greek practices, emphasizes the balance of the four humors through herbal and mineral preparations. Siddha incorporates traditional knowledge with a focus on the healing properties of specific herbs and minerals. Homeopathy employs highly diluted substances to stimulate the body's inherent healing processes.

Results: AYUSH systems have demonstrated effectiveness in managing chronic diseases, alleviating stress, and enhancing quality of life. Evidence suggests that these traditional practices can complement conventional medical treatments, particularly in areas such as preventive health care and lifestyle-related disorders.

Discussion: The Indian government actively promotes the integration of AYUSH into the modern healthcare system, recognizing its potential to address a broad spectrum of health issues. As global interest in natural and holistic therapies grows, AYUSH practices are increasingly being recognized for their relevance and effectiveness. They provide valuable insights into preventive health strategies and offer alternative treatment options for various conditions.

Conclusion: AYUSH represents a comprehensive approach to health that harmonizes ancient wisdom with modern healthcare needs. By emphasizing natural, holistic solutions, AYUSH systems continue to play a crucial role in enhancing public health and well-being, aligning with global trends toward integrative and preventive care.

Keywords: AYUSH, Ayurveda, Yoga, Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, Homeopathy, holistic health, natural remedies, preventive medicine.

Development of reserpine-induced depression model causing alterations in neurobehavior, biochemical functions, and histopathology

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Abstract

Background: Depression is a complex mental health disorder characterized by persistent sadness, anhedonia, and cognitive dysfunction. Reserpine, a drug historically used to manage hypertension, has been shown to deplete monoamines such as dopamine, norepinephrine, and serotonin in the brain, making it a valuable tool for inducing depressive-like behaviors in animal models. Hence, this study investigates the depression-induced behavioral, biochemical, and histological alterations in the mice to further elucidate the neurobiological basis of depression.

Aim of the Study: The present study aims to develop a chemically-induced pre-clinical depression model.

Methodology: Adult Swiss mice (8-12 weeks old) of 22-25g weight were randomly divided into control and treatment groups of 6 each. The control and treated groups were administered with corn oil and Reserpine at the dose of 0.75mg/kg BW via oral route for 14 consecutive days, respectively. During the experiment, the parameters such as daily body weight, food consumption, sucrose preference, forced swimming, and eight-arm radial maze tests were observed. After the last day of treatment, the animals were sacrificed and the blood and tissues were collected for measuring oxidative stress (superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase, nitric oxide, and lipid peroxidase), hepatic enzymes (alanine transferase and aspartic transaminase), acetylcholine esterase activity, corticosterone level, and total reactive oxygen species and histological (Hematoxylin-Eosin, Nissl's and Golgi staining) parameters. Besides that, the apoptosis was observed by fluorescent microscopy via Acridine orange staining. The obtained data were analysed by Student's t-test to determine the significance of the study at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.001$.

Results: Significant alterations were observed in daily body weight, FST, SPT, and latency period in depressed mice. The levels of SOD, LPO, NO, AChE, AST, ALT, and serum corticosterone were significantly elevated whereas CAT and GPx were reduced considerably in the depressed mice. Additionally, a significant elevation in the percentage of apoptosis was also observed. Marked regressive histological alterations were also noticed in the cortical and hippocampal regions of the brain of such mice.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates that reserpine effectively induces depressive-like behaviors in mice, reinforcing its utility as a model for studying the neurobiological mechanisms of depression. The observed behavioral, biochemical and histological alterations align with key symptoms of depression in humans, making this model valuable for evaluating potential antidepressant treatments.

Keywords: *Reserpine, depression, oxidative stress, corticosterone levels, AChE activity, Apoptosis*

PRODRUGS TO IMPROVE ABSORPTION AND DISTRIBUTION: A REVIEW

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Abstract

The “prodrug” is a chemically modified inert form of active drugs, after administration into the body activate by chemical reaction or enzymatic and release an active drug, which is responsible for of pharmacological activity. Prodrugs have been successfully use for a prolong time. It has been revealed that the prodrug approach has reached vast success in the past few years.

It is approximated that around 10% of all marketed drugs are prodrugs, 20% of small molecular weight drugs approved between 2000 and 2008 were prodrugs, and between 2008 and 2017 the share of prodrugs in the drug market was 12%. Prodrug design is a widely known molecular modification strategy that aims to optimize the physicochemical and pharmacological properties of drugs to improve their solubility and pharmacokinetic features

The target concentrations to exert therapeutic effects through optimum absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) processes. A drug that is poorly absorbed, rapidly metabolized, or rapidly excreted via the renal or hepatic route will not attain its full therapeutic potential. This novel targeted-prodrug approach is aimed to exploit carrier-mediated transport for enhanced intestinal permeability, as well as specific enzymes to promote activation of the prodrug and liberation of the free parent drug. A prodrug design that aims to allow intestinal permeability by specific transporters, as well as activation by specific enzymes, may greatly improve the prodrug efficiency, and allow for novel oral treatment options.

Keywords: Prodrugs; Biopharmaceutics; Oral Administration; Drug Delivery; Drug Targeting

PRODRUGS TO IMPROVE ABSORPTION AND DISTRIBUTION: A REVIEW

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Shambhunath Institute of Pharmacy, Jhalwa, Prayagraj, U.P., 211012

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Abstract

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Keywords: Prodrugs; Biopharmaceutics; Oral Administration; Drug Delivery; Drug Targeting

Analysis of Progressive changes of fatty liver to liver fibrosis

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Abstract

Background: Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a leading cause of chronic liver disease globally, often progressing from simple hepatic steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) and eventually to liver fibrosis and cirrhosis. Understanding the mechanisms and progression of NAFLD is crucial for developing effective interventions.

Aim of the Study: This study aims to investigate the progression from fatty liver to liver fibrosis in a controlled experimental setting using male Sprague-Dawley (SD) rats. The goal is to enhance understanding of NAFLD progression, identify potential biomarkers, and explore therapeutic targets for early detection and treatment.

Methodology: Fourteen male SD rats were divided into a control group (n=3) and a CCl₄-treated group (n=11). The treated group received oral injections of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) diluted in corn oil twice a week for 12 weeks to induce liver injury. Body weights were monitored biweekly to adjust dosing accurately. Histological analyses were conducted using Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E), Masson's Trichome, and Periodic Acid-Schiff (PAS) staining. Additionally, protein estimation was performed using the BCA assay and Hydroxyproline method.

Results: Histological analysis revealed significant differences between the control and CCl₄-treated groups. The treated group showed marked hepatic steatosis, inflammation, hepatocyte ballooning, and fibrosis. Biochemical assays indicated elevated levels of fibrosis markers in the treated group compared to controls. Protein estimation tests confirmed the presence of increased extracellular matrix deposition in fibrotic liver tissues.

Conclusions: The study successfully established a model for the progression of NAFLD to liver fibrosis using CCl₄-treated SD rats. The findings highlight significant histological and biochemical changes associated with NAFLD progression, offering insights into potential biomarkers and therapeutic targets. These results contribute to the understanding of liver fibrosis and underscore the importance of early intervention in NAFLD.

Keywords: NAFLD, NASH, liver fibrosis, Sprague-Dawley rats, CCl₄, histological analysis, protein estimation, BCA assay, Hydroxyproline

Role of *Suvarnaprashana* (Gold Electuary) in Children with Cerebral Palsy: An overview

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Abstract

Background: Cerebral palsy (CP) is defined as a nonprogressive neuromotor disorder of cerebral origin caused by insult or injury to developing brain during its early stage of development. CP is an umbrella term encompassing a group of nonprogressive, noncontagious condition that causes motor impairment by abnormalities in movement, posture, and tone. It can be caused by any of prenatal, natal, and postnatal factors and eventual pathology is any type of injury to the developing brain. CP is a lifelong physical disability as a consequence of upper motor neuron impairment, and it affects 1.5–2.5 children per 1000 live births with an estimated prevalence of 17 million people globally. *Suvarnaprashana* (oral administration of gold as electuary) is a unique practice documented in Ayurveda for child healthcare. Kashyapa Samhita, an authoritative textbook of Ayurvedic pediatrics, describes *Suvarnaprashana* (SP) under the context of *Lehana* (electuaries). For SP, gold *Bhasma* is triturated along with honey and *ghrita* (clarified *butter*) and the mixture is licked to the child.

Aim of the study: This review documents and evaluates the potential of SP in the management of CP with a special focus on its mechanisms of action in regulating different domains of problems in these children.

Methodology: The evidence of multidimensional functions of this ayurvedic electuary is drawn from published studies that have used in vitro and in vivo experimental methods and clinical studies.

Conclusions: This review proposes that the benefits of SP can be achieved at multiple levels as a general health promoter and in specific to enhancement of intelligence, digestion, metabolism, immunity and physical strength wsr to CP. SP improves the *agni* (digestion and metabolism), *medha* (cognition) and *bala* (Strength and immune status). It possesses subtle effects through multiple mechanisms and bio chemical targets, collectively leading to substantial health benefits in CP children. The study indicates that SP has potential for management of CP children and can thereby improves the quality of life by multidimensional benefits.

Keywords: Ayurveda, gold preparation, immunomodulator, *Swarnaprashana*

Evaluation of Phytochemical Components, Antioxidant and Antibacterial Properties of Methanolic Extract of *Boerhaavia diffusa*

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Abstract

Indian Ayurveda has long and glorified history of herbal medication system. Numerous plants and their compounds have been demonstrated to have promising effects against microbial infections and various diseases. *Boerhaavia diffusa*, commonly known as Punarvava, is plant known for its medicinal properties. This plant has various ethnobotanical applications, including the use of its leaves as a vegetable, while the root juice is traditionally used to treat conditions such as asthma, urinary disorders, rheumatism, and encephalitis. In this study, we utilized the methanolic extract of the whole *Boerhaavia diffusa* plant to explore its potential bioactivity. The preliminary qualitative analysis revealed positive results for various phytochemicals including phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, coumarin, glycosides etc. Total phenolic content and total flavonoid content were measured using the Folin-Ciocalteu assay and the AlCl₃ colorimetric assay, respectively. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was used for qualitative phytochemical analysis that exhibited the separation of different spots, suggesting the presence of different groups of phytochemicals in the extract. The plant extract also showed significant inhibition of growth of selected pathogenic bacterial strains as demonstrated by inhibition zones in disc diffusion antibacterial assay. However, further studies are needed to confirm the relationship between the identified phytochemicals and the observed bioactivity.

Keywords: *Boerhaaviadiffusa*, Antioxidants, Antibacterial activity, Phytochemicals

Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis of *Aegle marmelose* Corr. Ex-Roxb leaf and fruit extracts

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Abstract

Present study reports the preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis of the leaves and fruit extracts of *Aegle marmelose* Corr-ex-Roxb (Rutaceae) which is mainly used to cure for anemia by the rural and tribal people of West Singhbhum, Jharkhand, India.

Qualitative phytochemical analysis was carried out in the laboratory using the standard procedures (Harbone J B., 1973;1998, Trease and Evans,1998 and Sofowara,1993) for the detection of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Saponins, Phenols, Carbohydrates, Tannins, Protein and Glycosides while presence of iron was confirmed by using 5% potassium thiocyanate solution (KSCN) by iron spot test and double distilled water, ethanol and methanol were used as extractants.

Our result confirmed the presence of all major classes of phytochemicals and iron in both leaves and fruit extracts of *Aegle marmelose* Corr-ex-Roxb. It was noted that the iron content in leaves was comparatively higher than the fruits. It is inferred that these phytochemicals are source of both energy and nutrition which enable the plant for the treatment of anemia.

Hence, this preliminary study draws an attention to need an intensive further study to know the exact doses, duration, correct mode of administration and exact phytochemical which are responsible to cure Anemia.

Keywords: Phytochemical, Qualitative, Secondary metabolites, Anemia.

Incidence and Prevalence of Non- Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD): A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

Background: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) is a rapidly growing global health concern, affecting approximately 25-30% of the world's adult population. In India, the prevalence is similar, with rates around 25-32%, but can reach up to 40-45% in urban areas due to rising obesity, diabetes, and lifestyle changes. The condition is more common in urban regions, reflecting the impact of reduced physical activity and increased consumption of high-calorie diets. Addressing NAFLD requires a focus on lifestyle modifications and managing associated metabolic conditions, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions like India.

Aim: To identify recent and current trends in the incidence of NAFLD across various regions in India and globally.

Methodology: Out of 55 studies on NAFLD, accessed from PubMed and Google Scholar, 27 studies meeting the selection criteria were considered for meta – analysis.

Results: Overall estimate of prevalence of NAFLD was 38.60%. Type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, including abdominal obesity, were found to be significantly associated with NAFLD.

Conclusion: The prevalence of NAFLD in adults in India to be 45.23%, compared to 33.08% in adults from other countries. To carry out differentials of NAFLD in different countries and ways of its reduction, more such studies are required.

Keywords- Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD), Prevalence, Type2 diabetes mellitus, Obesity

Molecular characterization of resistance determinants and mobile genetic elements in MDR bacteria from water bodies of Kashmir India

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Abstract

Background: Antibiotic resistance is a global concern. The expansion of resistance determinants through horizontal transfer is linked with mobile genetic elements (MGEs). Heavy metals also create consequential health hazards. Metal resistance along with antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) and MGEs facilitates bacteria to gain resistance.

Objective: The present work was carried to study ARGs *bla* CTX-M, AmpC, qnrS, MGEs like *ISecp1*, TN3, TN21, Int I and SulI from Wular and Dal lakes of Kashmir; India. The genetic environment of CTX-M-15, *in-silico* docking and mutational studies was performed. Co-occurrence of ARGs and HMRGs, PCR based replicon typing (PBRT) and conjugation assay was also done.

Methods: Collected isolates were screened for ESBL production following CLSI. Molecular characterization of resistance genes and Genetic environment was performed using PCR, cassette PCR and sequencing. Plasmid incompatibility was determined by PBRT.

Results: Out of 201 isolates from 16 locations 33 were ESBLs producers. 30 ESBL isolates were positive for CTX-M gene, followed by AmpC (17), qnrS (13), *ISecp1* (15), TN3 (11), TN21 (11), Int I (18), SulI (14). Genetic environment of *bla*CTX-M-15 was observed as (*ISecp1-bla*CTX-M-15-orf477), classical promoter -10 TACAAT and -35 TTGAA was found at the 3' region. CTX-M-15-*ISecp1* (R299L) docking and mutation showed reduction in hydrogen bonds. Co-occurrence of antibiotics and HMRGs (mer, sil and ars) was found in 18, 14 and 8 isolates. PBRT showed Inc groups (B/O, F, 11, HI1, FIA, HI2, N, FIB, L/M). Molecular analysis of transconjugants showed transfer of ARGs, MGEs and HMRGs in *E. coli* J53 AZ^R strain.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, *in-silico* docking, mobile genetic elements, PCR based replicon typing, transconjugant

Designing, development, and characterization of FRET-based genetically encoded nanosensor for Pyrroloquinoline Quinone (PQQ) in living cells

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Abstract

Metabolites are small molecules produced during the metabolic processes within living organisms, playing crucial roles in various biochemical pathways. These compounds are integral to cellular functions, influencing energy production, signaling, and homeostasis. In addition to their biological significance, metabolites have garnered considerable interest in fields such as pharmacology, nutrition, and environmental science, where they can serve as biomarkers for health and disease, as well as indicators of environmental changes. By understanding metabolites and their interactions, researchers can unlock new avenues for drug development, agricultural improvements, and advancements in personalized medicine. This study proposes the development of genetically encoded fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET)-based nanosensors to detect pyrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) in real-time at sub-cellular resolution. The periplasmic binding protein of this PQQ has been identified from protein database (PDB). This protein shows conformational change upon binding to the ligand. The gene sequence of this protein was retrieved from NCBI. Primer for the amplification for gene sequence of PQQ, cyan fluorescent protein (CFP) and yellow fluorescent protein (YFP) with compatible restriction sites are designed. The gDNA was isolated from *P. aeruginosa*. This protein was amplified using PCR and it is cloned in pGEMT vector. Similarly CFP and YFP are amplified using pDEST15 vector as a template. Both amplified products are cloned in pGEMT. All the three protein are run on the agarose gel to validate size of the gene. Further validation of all the three genes was carried out through restriction digestion. In the next step all the three genes are ligated together to make the nanosensor for PQQ. The research will focus on constructing, characterizing, and validating these nanosensors through in vitro and in vivo tests using model organisms such as bacteria and yeast. This approach aims to provide cost-effective and sensitive tools for monitoring metabolite by enabling precise localization and quantification of metabolite concentrations within cells ultimately, these nanosensors will enhance our understanding of cellular responses to metabolite exposure and improve environmental monitoring strategies.

Keywords: FRET, nanosensor, periplasmic binding proteins (PBPs), in-vivo, in-vitro

Inhibitors for the disruption of dengue virus assembly and RNA encapsulation using a computational approach

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Abstract

Dengue virus (DENV) infection transmitted by mosquitoes remains a critical global health challenge, manifesting as severe hemorrhagic fever and shock syndrome. Despite the extensive research, there is no effective antiviral treatment approved, emphasizing the need for new therapeutic strategies. A promising approach for developing dengue therapeutics involves targeting the dengue virus (DENV) Capsid protein, which is essential for viral replication and transcription.

This study aims to identify potential inhibitors for DENV capsid protein by repurposing FDA-approved drugs from the selleckchem database and leveraging computational methods to expedite the discovery of promising candidates for DENV inhibition. A high-throughput virtual screening of FDA-approved drugs was conducted, targeting the capsid protein using molecular docking and binding energy analysis. The best four drug candidates with high binding affinity and structural stability were selected: Nordihydroguaiaretic acid, Ifenprodil tartrate, Lathyrol, and Safinamide Mesylate. These drug candidates exhibited binding affinities between -12.6 to -8.4 kcal/mol. Indicating robust interactions with the dengue virus protein. In-depth docking analyses were analysed for the understanding of molecular interactions between the target protein and each selected ligand. Subsequently, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were conducted to assess the binding stability and conformational adaptability of the protein-ligand complexes. The complexes were also complemented by free energy landscape (FEL) analysis for transition states analysis. The computational analyses suggest that these drugs possess significant potential as lead candidates for further experimental validations. This approach underscores the viability of computational drug discovery in addressing urgent infectious disease challenges like dengue.

Keywords: Dengue, Capsid protein, Drug discovery, molecular dynamics, free energy landscape

ANCIENT REMEDIES FOR MODERN TOXINS: AGADA TANTRA AND PESTICIDES

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Abstract

Background: The use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides has become crucial to contemporary agriculture, with fertilizers aiming to boost crop yields and pesticides aimed at protecting plants from pests, thereby increasing agricultural production. However, the increased dependence on pesticides has created serious concerns regarding their influence on human health and the environment. In this context, the ancient *Agada Tantra* offers important insights into the treatment of poisoning-related illnesses and detoxification, suggesting a possible avenue for addressing the negative impacts of pesticide use.

Aim: The aim of the study is to understand the concepts of *Agada Tantra* with pesticides.

Materials and methods: Reviewed from various ayurvedic texts and web.

Result: Chemical pesticides, like organochlorines, can accumulate in the human body for years, causing negative health effects when levels peak. This cumulative toxicity is recognized in Ayurveda under the concept of *Dushi Visha*, which refers to the accumulation of chemical toxins. Many people who work in agriculture or related industries are exposed to pesticides directly or indirectly as a result of their easy absorption through the skin, mouth, and respiratory mucosa.

Discussion and conclusion: We can agree on the effects of pesticides in the body by using the brief description of the treatment of *Dushi Visha*, such as *Agadapana*, *Virechana*, etc., in the body provided by the *Agada Tantra*. Combining the old *Ayurvedic* principles with contemporary farming methods offers a possible strategy to reduce environmental damage caused by pesticide use and improve health outcomes.

Keywords: Pesticides, *Agada Tantra*, *Dushi Visha*, Cumulative toxicity, Toxins

Adsorption of tetracycline by green synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles: Adsorption isotherm, kinetics, thermodynamics, and Response Surface Methodology optimization.

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Abstract

Aim: The contamination of water resources by toxic pollutants has become a significant environmental issue for society, policymakers, and government entities worldwide. Consequently, the demand for clean and safe drinking water has steadily risen. In our current research, green synthesis of iron oxide using *Dalbergia Sissoo* leaf extract as a reducing agent was synthesized in the laboratory. The adsorbent was used to remove tetracycline (TC) from water. We used this adsorbent to successfully remove tetracycline (TC) from water.

Methods: Green nanomaterials are typically created from waste biomass such as plant leaves, sawdust, fruit peels, wood, and agricultural waste, utilizing eco-friendly methods that adhere to the principles of green chemistry. The green method was utilized to synthesize iron oxide, employing *Dalbergia Sissoo* leaf extract.

Results: The maximum adsorption capacity (q_{max}) was (80%). Adsorption thermodynamics indicated that the adsorption process was endothermic. The removal efficiency was detailed and evaluated using a response surface method (RSM). The adsorption results were optimized using Box Behnken design (BBD). The adsorbent's performance in five consecutive experiments did not show much decline, indicating the reusability and stability of the adsorbent. The study results showed that the adsorbent could remove tetracycline from natural water samples by more than 98%.

Conclusions: When it comes to removing a broad range of pollutants, such as dyes, heavy metals, and antibacterial properties, the green materials that have been synthesized have the potential to be extensively used. Additionally, it was discovered that the removal efficiency was quite efficient.

Significance and Impact of Study: Green materials are frequently used to remove pollutants because of their distinctive characteristics, which include being environmentally friendly, having a low cost of synthesis, being readily accessible, being less hazardous, being tiny in size, and having a big surface area.

Keywords: Tetracycline; Iron-oxide nanoparticle; Adsorption; Response Surface Methodology; Green-synthesis

Evaluation of Seasonal Mutagenicity in PM₁ Organic Extracts in Agra's Urban Atmosphere Using *Salmonella typhimurium* Strains

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the mutagenic potential of PM₁ organic extracts using the Ames test both with and without metabolic activation by employing *Salmonella typhimurium* strains TA98 (to detect frameshift mutations) and TA100 (to detect base-pair substitutions) and quantify polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). Weekly samples were collected over a one-year period (2021-2022) from urban locations in Agra, utilizing an Envirotech APM577 sampler. The annual mean concentration of PM₁ was found to be $82.9 \pm 33.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while the mean concentration of the sixteen priority PAHs ($\Sigma 16\text{PAHs}$) was $374.5 \pm 17.2 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$. Low-molecular-weight (LMW) PAHs, constituted $22 \pm 2 \%$ of the total PAHs associated with PM₁, whereas high-molecular-weight (HMW) PAHs comprised the remaining $80 \pm 12 \%$. The concentration of carcinogenic PAHs ($\Sigma \text{PAH carcinogens}$) was recorded at $251.6 \pm 10.2 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$. It was further observed that TA98 showed a six-fold increase in mutagenic response in winter compared to post-monsoon, while TA100 showed a 1.5-fold increase. This suggests a dominance of direct-acting compounds in winter. Conversely, the addition of S9 resulted in a three-fold increase in the mutagenic response in TA98 and a 2.5-fold increase in TA100 in post-monsoon, indicating a prevalence of indirect mutagens during this period. The mutagenic response was particularly pronounced in the TA100 strain, which is more sensitive to base pair mutations. Notably, the addition of the S9 mix did not significantly affect mutagenic activity in the TA100 strain, suggesting that direct mutagenesis is likely driven by nitrogenated and oxygenated compounds. However, in the TA98 strain, the mutagenic response increased with the addition of the S9 mix in samples collected during the summer and post-monsoon seasons. In contrast, winter samples showed a higher mutagenic response without the S9 mix, highlighting the complex interaction between air pollutants and their mutagenic potential across different seasons. Correlation analysis revealed significant positive correlations between PAHs and mutagenic ratio for both total PAHs and individual PAH compounds, such as Benzo (a)Pyrene (B[a]P) $r = 0.7$, Benzo (b) Fluoranthene (B[b]F) $r = 0.5$, and Acenaphthene (Ace) $r = 0.7$. These results underscore the significant role of PAHs in driving mutagenicity in urban air and emphasize the health risks associated with air pollution. The pronounced mutagenic effects observed, particularly during the winter and post-monsoon seasons, suggest that these PM₁-bound compounds pose a substantial risk to public health in urban environments.

Keywords: PM₁, PAHs, Frameshift mutation, Base pair mutation, Metabolic activation

Isolation, Characterization, and Biological Evaluation of Phytochemicals from *Solanum nigrum*

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Abstract

Background: *Solanum nigrum*, commonly known as black nightshade, is widely recognized for its medicinal properties and has been traditionally used for treating various ailments such as liver disorders, inflammation, and cancer. Despite its potential, the bioactive phytochemicals responsible for these therapeutic effects have not been fully explored.

Aim of the study: The present study aims to isolate, characterize, and evaluate the biological activities of phytochemicals from *Solanum nigrum* to identify potential candidates for pharmaceutical applications.

Methodology: Phytochemicals were isolated from the whole plant of *Solanum nigrum* using successive solvent extraction methods with solvents of increasing polarity (hexane, ethyl acetate, and methanol). The isolated compounds were characterized using chromatographic techniques (TLC, HPLC) and spectral methods such as NMR and FTIR. Biological evaluation of the extracts and isolated compounds was performed to assess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic activities using standard in vitro assays.

Results: Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and tannins. Characterization confirmed the structure of solasonine, solamargine, and rutin as major compounds. The methanolic extract exhibited significant antioxidant activity with an IC₅₀ value of 30.4 µg/mL, while the ethyl acetate fraction demonstrated potent anti-inflammatory activity with an inhibition rate of 62%. In cytotoxic assays, solasonine showed promising anti-cancer activity against HepG2 cells with an IC₅₀ of 45.6 µg/ml.

Conclusions: The study successfully isolated and characterized major bioactive compounds from *Solanum nigrum*, which demonstrated significant biological activities. These findings highlight the potential of *Solanum nigrum* phytochemicals for further drug development.

Keywords: *Solanum nigrum*, phytochemicals, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cytotoxic, solasonine

Diversity Assessment of kodo millet germplasm based on Morpho-Physiology and Nutritive Parameters

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Abstract

Kodo millet (*Paspalum scrobiculatum* L.) is an important kharif cereal crop grown in India. Due to its high nutritional value and stress tolerating capacity, the production of small millets needs to be better admired, intensified and promoted. Because of its highly nutritional value and stress resistant ability, it will be a good substitute for other crops. As growing demand of millets in India it is of great significance to evaluate the various germplasm at morphological and biochemical level for various yield parameters to identify superior accessions.

The research work is being carried out, we are studying Kodo millet germplasm collected from all over the India. In total 63 Kodo millet germplasm along with two check variety are taken into study. The check varieties are JK- 155 and JK- 137. These germplasms were studied under morphological and quantitative characterization, analysis of variance, correlation coefficient, path analysis coefficient and genetic diversity (D2 analysis). These germplasms are being studied for biochemical parameters. The various Morphological traits such as Plant growth habits, Basal tiller numbers, Leaf attitude, inter nodal exposure, Flag leaf blade length, Flag leaf blade width, Peduncle length, Panicle appearance, Spikelet arrangement: on rachis, Culm branching, Thumb raceme: length, Raceme numbers are taken in study (for example Flag leaf length ranged from 18.58 cm to 40.73 cm. IPS -240 (18.58 cm) was observed as shortest flag leaf length genotype. However, genotype IPS-891 (40.73 cm) was found longest among all. Flag leaf width ranged from 0.48 cm to 1.45 cm. IPS-4 (0.48 cm) was observed as a minimum flag leaf width genotype. However, genotype IPS-803 (1.45 cm) was found maximum flag leaf width genotype.) Additionally, biochemical traits such as Zinc, iron and protein were quantified to understand the nutritive parameters. Physiological parameters, including chlorophyll content was also measured.

The study of Kodo millet germplasm highlights its significant nutritional value and stress tolerance, emphasizing the need for its promotion as a viable alternative crop. By evaluating various morphological and biochemical traits, the research aims to identify superior accessions that can enhance millet production and meet the growing demand.

Keywords: Kodo millet, Morphological traits, Nutritive parameter, Physiological traits

PHARMACOLOGY AND DRAVYAGUNA VIGYAAN - A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Introduction: Pharmacology, the science of drugs and their effects on biological systems, plays a critical role in understanding how therapeutic substances act within the body. *Dravyaguna Vigyaan*, a core branch of Ayurvedic medicine, systematically classifies and describes the medicinal properties of natural substances, primarily herbs, minerals, and animal products. This review aims to delve into the correlations and contrasts between Dravyaguna Vigyaan and modern pharmacology, exploring their principles, classification, and applications.

Methodology: A comprehensive analysis of traditional Dravyaguna Vigyaan texts and modern pharmacology literature was conducted, identifying areas of convergence and divergence.

Principles: Dravyaguna Vigyaan's concept of "Rasa" (taste) and "Guna" (qualities) parallels modern pharmacology's understanding of bioactive compounds and their mechanisms. The ancient system's emphasis on "Virya" (potency) and "Vipaka" (metabolic fate) aligns with modern pharmacology's understanding of drug pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics.

Classification: Dravyaguna Vigyaan's classification of substances into "Varga" (categories) aligns with modern pharmacological categories (e.g., anti-inflammatory, antioxidant).

The ancient system's sub-classification into "Gana" (sub-categories) mirrors modern pharmacology's understanding of drug sub-classes.

Applications: Dravyaguna Vigyaan's emphasis on "Prabhava" (specific actions) and "Samanya" (general actions) mirrors modern pharmacology's understanding of drug-target interactions and polypharmacology.

Modern pharmacological studies validate the medicinal properties of many substances described in Dravyaguna Vigyaan.

Discussion: The relationship between pharmacology and Dravyaguna Vigyaan offers a promising avenue for discovering new drugs and therapeutic approaches, especially for chronic conditions such as diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, and autoimmune disorders. Future research is expected to focus on improving the standardization of Ayurvedic formulations, conducting rigorous clinical trials, and exploring personalized medicine approaches by understanding how individual patient constitution (*Prakriti*) influences drug response. By integrating the holistic principles of Ayurveda with modern pharmacological science, the field can unlock a wealth of natural medicinal resources for global health.

Conclusions: The convergence of Dravyaguna Vigyaan and modern pharmacology offers a rich opportunity for interdisciplinary research and collaboration. By embracing ancient wisdom and modern science, we can unlock new possibilities for human health and well-being.

Keywords: Dravyaguna vigyaan, Bioactive compounds, Drug discovery, Polypharmacology, Interdisciplinary research

***In Silico* Analysis of *Nigella sativa* Phytochemicals Targeting ClfB in *Staphylococcus aureus* and Experimental Validation of Chlorogenic Acid's Antibiofilm Properties**

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Abstract

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) occurs when microorganisms evolve to withstand drugs that once successfully treated them. This phenomenon presents a major global challenge, burdening healthcare systems and economies. AMR results in more severe illnesses, longer hospital stays, and higher medical expenses, affecting millions each year, especially those with chronic diseases. The issue becomes more severe with multi-drug resistant (MDR) pathogens like methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), which complicate treatment efforts. The CDC and NIH estimate 65-80% of human infections relate to biofilm-forming bacteria. Addressing biofilms in chronic infections is crucial and targeting biofilms using phytochemicals is one of alternative strategies to combat such infections. This research aimed to assess the impact of phytochemicals from *Nigella sativa* on *S. aureus* biofilms, particularly targeting the clumping factor B (ClfB). Chlorogenic acid was identified as a promising compound due to high its binding energy of -8.4 kcal/mol and favorable binding site interactions. Molecular simulations confirmed that chlorogenic acid formed a stable complex with ClfB under physiological conditions. Furthermore, in vitro experiments demonstrated that chlorogenic acid effectively reduced biofilm formation by ~60% in *S. aureus* MTCC 3160. Detailed biofilm analysis using light and electron microscopy showed that chlorogenic acid treatment significantly decreased biofilm formation and bacterial colonization. Additionally, the presence of chlorogenic acid reduced bacterial clustering on glass surfaces. These findings suggest that chlorogenic acid could serve as a potent antibiofilm agent against *S. aureus*, providing a new avenue for developing antibacterial treatments.

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance, Chlorogenic acid, biofilms, bacterial colonization.

Enhancing Prasav with Matra Basti and Yoni Pichu in (Navam Massa) Garbhini paricharya

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Abstract

Background: Pregnancy is a physiological state and during this process, women may experience some discomforts like constipation, backache, sleep disturbance etc which are due to vitiation of vata, and disturb her routine. Now in this modern era every women wishes to have a safe delivery without any complications in a natural way free from that of the induced one. For safe labour, normal functioning of vata is essential ie vata anulomana and basti is the prime treatment for vata dosha. Matra basti and yoni pichu has the properties of vata anulomana, vata shamana, garbhashaya marga snehana, thus helps in reducing the physiological discomforts of ninth month and helps in prasava.

Objectives: To investigate the combined effect of Matra Basti, Yoni Pichu on Navam Massa paricharya for facilitating a smooth and natural childbirth.

Methods: A comprehensive treatment plan incorporating Matra Basti (uterine nourishment), Yoni Pichu (vaginal care), was administered to pregnant women in their third trimester.

Results: Matra Basti and Yoni Pichu is a supportive treatment for a healthy pregnancy, fetal development, and smooth delivery.

- Prepares the mother's body for labor and delivery.
- Softens and dilates the cervix, making delivery easier.
- Supports fetal positioning and descent.
- Reduced the risk of vaginal tears and episiotomies

Conclusion: The combined treatment of Matra Basti and Yoni Pichu, significantly enhances the childbirth experience, leading to a smoother, less painful, and more natural delivery. This holistic approach supports the well-being of both the mother and the baby, promoting a positive and empowering birth experience.

Keywords: Matra basti, Yoni pichu, Third trimester, Garbhini paricharya

Upcycling of low-cost water hyacinth-derived biochar for enhanced removal of Bisphenol A (BPA): Batch mode study and optimization using response surface methodology

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Abstract

Aim: The addition of various organic/inorganic pollutants including heavy metals, dyes, pesticides, and other organic components to the water bodies as a result of rapid industrialization is one of the most common problems worldwide. Bisphenol A (BPA) is an important raw material used in different forms. The primary aim of this study was to repurpose water hyacinth in various green materials and its application in the removal of BPA from water.

Methods: Biochar (BC) derived from water hyacinth was used to synthesize activated biochar (AB) and magnetic biochar (MB) to investigate its efficacy for the removal of the endocrine-disrupting chemical, Bisphenol (BPA). The synthesized materials were characterized using FTIR, XRD, FESEM-EDX, point zero charge, and BET. The Response Surface Methodology–Central Composite Design (RSM-CCD) model was used for the optimization of removal efficacies for BPA using five variables, i.e., pH (6–8), adsorbent dose (30–80mg), BPA concentration (30–80ppm), temperature (20–35°C), and time (20–60 min).

Results: Under optimal conditions, the maximum BPA removal effectiveness was found to be 92.1% for AB and 89.41% for MB. The isotherm models indicated that the adsorption data for both AB and MB align closely with the Langmuir isotherm, suggesting the occurrence of monolayer adsorption. The kinetics of adsorption were effectively elucidated by the pseudo-first- and pseudo-second-order models for both adsorbents. Thermodynamic analysis confirmed the feasibility of the reaction and its spontaneous and exothermic nature. The reusability efficiency and study in real water samples were investigated to demonstrate its potential for practical application.

Conclusions: The green synthesized materials can be widely used to remove BPA. The removal efficiency was also found to be highly efficient.

Keywords: Water hyacinth, Activated carbon, Bisphenol A, Adsorption, Optimization study

Cell tower Electromagnetic radiation Impacts on plants

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Abstract

Current world is technologically revolutionised. Application of AI/ML, combined with electronics and robotics require vast wireless data transmission processes. Long range, high power, and modulated waves are being universally used, to facilitate easier communication and to allow quick access throughout the world. Numerous cellular phones and other smart devices, both in professionals and households are being used. These in turn, emit harmful radio frequency waves in to the free space. Non-ionizing and low penetrative in nature make them risk free in our environment to be propagated. But, in the other hand, continues radio frequency exposure and generated heat can affect flora and fauna, making the situation vulnerable. Compared to humans' plants are situated in higher position and immovable too. Besides that, radio frequency can possess electrical, polarisation property, which might affect in different aspects. In our study, we have assumed the heating stress effects on plants due to radiations in different frequencies, powers etc. Now a days, 5G is being launched with high power and frequency and Multiple Input and Multiple output. In a futuristic vision, understanding and realising the upcoming impacts of these radiation, the study has been conducted.

Keywords: Radio frequency, Oxidative stress, Polarisation, Multiple input and multiple output

Exposure to Airborne Particulate Matter (PM_{10/2.5}) from Varanasi, India induces lung injury in Mice model

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Abstract

Particulate matter (PM), particularly PM_{10/2.5}, is a significant air pollutant with well-established detrimental effects on respiratory health. In India, these pollutants have surpassed national air quality standards, raising environmental and health concerns. In present study, healthy and asthmatic mice were used to investigate effects of PM_{10/2.5} inhalations. For asthmatic model development, OVA was used to sensitize mice on 0,7,14 days along with scheduled exposures to PM_{10/2.5} (0.5 mg/kg for five consecutive days). Both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} induced inflammations, oxidative stress, and changes in lung morphology, where PM_{2.5} caused severe lung damage in asthmatic mice. Inflammatory cell infiltration, elevated histamine and nitric oxide levels, increased myeloperoxidase (MPO) and eosinophil peroxidase (EPO) activity, and higher reactive oxygen species (ROS) were observed. Histopathological analysis revealed enhanced collagen deposition, airway thickening, and upregulated Matrix Metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) activity, indicating fibrotic changes. The study has also demonstrated reduced antioxidant enzyme activities (SOD, catalase, GSH) and increased lipid peroxidation (MDA). *In vitro* analysis using A549 cells also confirmed dose-dependent PM induced cytotoxicity and ROS generation. These findings provide insights into PM-induced lung damage and its severity in asthma, highlighting the need for therapeutic strategies to mitigate the harmful effects of PM exposures on respiratory health.

Keywords: Particulate matter, myeloperoxidase (MPO), eosinophil peroxidase (EPO) activity, higher reactive oxygen species (ROS), Metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9)

Targeting Secretory PLA2 and Cytosolic PLA2: Role of plant-derived flavonoids in Ameliorating Neuroinflammation

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Abstract

Neuroinflammation is characterized by recurrent episodes of T cell-mediated immunological attack on myelin in the central nervous system, which causes axon damage and eventual impairment. While the specific cause of neuroinflammation is unknown, autoreactive T lymphocytes penetrate the central nervous system and target myelinated cells. Demyelination and axonal damage in the CNS are symptoms of neuroinflammation. Phospholipases are clearly established to cause inflammation in the central nervous system. Cytosolic PLA2 and Secretory PLA2 are well known for their role in neuroinflammation and have been targeted pharmaceutically. The *Glycyrrhiza glabra* plant was obtained, shade-dried, powdered, and solvent extracted for qualitative examination of several phytoconstituents. LCMS-TOF was used to determine the existence of phytoconstituents. Molecular docking studies were conducted to investigate the interactions of selected flavonoid compounds with 1N29 (sPLA2) and 1CJY (cPLA2) targets. The cytotoxic effects of flavonoids on the viability of the macrophage RAW264.7 were investigated. sPLA2 and cPLA2 levels in LPS-stimulated macrophages were evaluated by Cayman kit. Docking and molecular interaction studies, binding energy, and the distance between the target proteins 1CJY, 1N29 and chosen ligands have shown that the ligands can exhibit modulatory effects in silico. The cytotoxic effects of Jaranol and Isoliquiritigenin on the viability of Macrophage RAW264.7 were non-cytotoxic, as shown by the MTT assay. Jaranol and isoliquiritigenin were likewise shown to suppress cPLA2 activity and sPLA2 in a concentration-dependent manner. Both phospholipases were discovered to be inhibited in very identical ways. These findings suggest that Jaranol and Isoliquiritigenin might be potential therapeutic candidates for the treatment and Prevention of neuroinflammation in neurodegenerative diseases.

Keywords: Neuroinflammation, Phytoconstituents, Cayman kit, Jaranol, Isoliquiritigenin

Pharmaceutical Contaminants in the Ganga and Yamuna Rivers: Assessment of Ecological Risks

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Abstract

Aim:

This study aims to evaluate pharmaceutical contaminant's presence, concentration, and ecological impact in the Ganga and Yamuna rivers, focusing on their effects on aquatic life.

Methodology:

A comprehensive review of existing literature and water quality reports from government agencies was conducted. Data from published research articles and environmental monitoring reports were compiled to identify key pharmaceutical pollutants, including antibiotics (norfloxacin, ciprofloxacin), NSAIDs (diclofenac, ibuprofen), anticonvulsant (carbamazepine), and stimulant (caffeine). The review analyzed concentrations of these contaminants in water samples from the Ganga and Yamuna rivers over the past decade. Case studies focusing on biotic indicators, such as algae, macroinvertebrates, and fish, were used to evaluate the ecological risks posed by pharmaceutical pollutants.

Conclusion:

The study reveals that pharmaceutical contaminants near urban areas like Delhi pose severe ecological risks to aquatic life. Antibiotics and NSAIDs contribute to antibiotic-resistant bacteria and biodiversity loss. It emphasizes the need for stricter regulations and improved wastewater treatment to reduce pollution and ensure long-term ecological sustainability.

Keywords:

Ganga, Yamuna, Pharmaceutical contaminants, Antibiotics, NSAIDs, Aquatic ecosystems, River pollution, Environmental impact, Wastewater treatment.

Budget-friendly Π -conjugated hole transport molecule for perovskite solar cell: An approach to commercialization

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Abstract

The molecular engineering of organic hole-transporting materials (HTMs) plays an important role in enhancing the performance and stability of perovskite solar cells (PSCs) as well as reducing their fabrication cost. Here, the low-cost spiro-OMeTAD analogues, namely SP-SMe, featuring a spiro[fluorene-9,9-xanthene] (SFX) central core and asymmetric subunits are designed and synthesized. Specifically, in the molecular structure of SP-SMe, the methoxy groups (–OMe) from diphenylamine units were partially replaced with the methylsulfanyl groups (–SMe) to increase interaction with the perovskite surface through the “Lewis soft” S atoms. By combining various experimental and simulation methods, the structure–property relationship of the newly synthesized HTMs was thoroughly investigated. The suitable HOMO energy level with the perovskite layer together with superior photoelectric properties and enhanced thermostability and humidity resistivity are obtained for the SP-SMe HTM. As a result, the planar n–i–p PSC with the dopant-free SP-SMe HTM yields a maximum power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 21.95%, which outperforms that with doped spiro-OMeTAD (19.23%). Importantly, the device with SP-SMe also reveals enhanced operational stability under continuous 1 sun illumination and thermal stability at 65 °C. These findings provide valuable insight for the rational design of dopant-free organic HTMs based on the SFX core, which would promote the development of highly efficient and stable devices.

Keywords: hole-transporting materials, perovskite solar cells, dopant-free etc, spiro[fluorene-9,9-xanthene].

Investigation of Pathogenic Fungi Associated with the Decline of *Parkia timoriana* (DC) Merr. in North East India

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Abstract

Tree bean, *Parkia timoriana* (DC) Merr. belongs to legume family Fabaceae and sub family Casalpinioideae. For its unique smell, and flavour pod (fluid) is consumed in all its developmental stages, contain proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamin and minerals and one of the favorite items among the Manipuri people, as well as the neighboring states. In North East India, the tree bean is fetching a market value of Rs 70–120 per kg or Rs.10 per pod and during the festive season, the price even goes up to Rs. 50 per pod. There is no serious incidence of pest and disease in *Parkia* till late 90's. However, concerns have arisen due to the sudden decline of *Parkia timoriana* (DC) Merr. reported in Manipur. Initially mortality was noticed in Manipur but is now also spreading to Nagaland, Mizoram and to some extent in Tripura. Keeping this in mind, a survey was carried out between 2023 and 2024 to determine the cause of *Parkia timoriana* (DC) Merr. mortality. The survey included various tree bean growing areas in Manipur, Nagaland and Mizoram, such as jhum field homestead gardens and roadside plantations. The present study involved a comprehensive survey to collect the disease sample to isolate and identify pathogenic fungi associated with infected tree bean. During survey the most evident symptoms of this disease were yellowing of leaves, twig dieback, presence of blackish blisters on the main stem and branches, excessive leaves shedding and gummosis. The fungi frequently associated with sudden decline of tree beans have been identified as *Fusarium foetens* (OP482315.1), *Clonostachys krabiensis* (NR168189.1), *Diaporthe phaseolorum* (MT043770.1), and *Diaporthe caulivora* (MH930412.1). Pathogenicity tests have confirmed that *Fusarium foetens* and *Clonostachys krabiensis* are the causal organisms responsible for decline of *Parkia timoriana* (DC) Merr. mortality. This is the first time that *Parkia*

timoriana (DC) Merr. mortality in North East India has been linked to *Fusarium foetens* and *Clonostachys krabiensis*. However, more research is necessary, despite the logical conclusion.

Keywords: *Parkia timoriana* (DC) Merr, mortality, pathogenicity, *Fusarium foetens*, *Clonostachys krabiensis*

Design, Optimization and Evaluation of Biocompatible Soluble Pilocarpine Loaded Drug Inserts for Glaucoma

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ABSTRACT

Optic nerve impairment along with differences in the field of vision are defining characteristics of glaucoma, a progressive optic neuropathy. It is one of the main global causes of permanent blindness. Elevated intraocular pressure (IOP), which can be caused by overproduction or poor aqueous humor outflow, is the main risk factor for glaucoma. Even while a high IOP is a significant risk factor, some people can get glaucoma while having a normal IOP, which suggests that there may be more underlying causes such as vascular insufficiency or genetic susceptibility. A thorough eye examination to evaluate the health of the optic nerve, visual field tests, and IOP measurement are usually required for the diagnosis. In order to stop the disease's progression and protect vision, treatment seeks to lower IOP. This thesis investigates the effectiveness of chitosan polymer-based sustained-release ocular medication delivery system, Pilocarpine HCl ocusert, in the management of glaucoma. Increased intraocular pressure which causes damage to the optic nerve is a sign of glaucoma, one of the major causes of permanent blindness. The Ocusert device releases pilocarpine HCl slowly over time, thereby increasing medicine absorption and retaining its therapeutic concentration in the eye. Reducing the frequency of administration while maintaining consistent treatment effects is the goal of this continuous delivery strategy. Through clinical trials and pharmacokinetic analysis, the study assesses the efficacy of the device, ocular tolerance, and patient compliance. The findings provide information for improving glaucoma treatment plans using cutting-edge medication delivery systems.

Keywords: Ocusert, glaucoma, Pilocarpine HCl, sustained release, chitosan polymer

Assessment of Growth Traits, Specific Gravity, and Biomass Productivity in *Melia dubia* for Tree Improvement Program

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Abstract

The formulation of effective tree breeding strategies and the optimal utilization of wood resources are heavily dependent on a deep understanding of wood properties. Among these, specific gravity (SG) is a critical parameter, as it reflects the density of wood relative to water. SG offers valuable insights into a range of wood characteristics, including mechanical properties like strength and stiffness, as well as its role in carbon sequestration, which is crucial for climate mitigation efforts.

A density experiment was conducted to examine the effects of SG on the growth and productivity of *Melia dubia* in Dehradun, Uttarakhand, focusing on a 12-year-old plantation with a spacing of 3×3 m. The study aimed to assess biomass productivity in trees of uniform age, while considering various growth parameters and local environmental conditions.

In this study, phenotypic and genotypic correlations were analyzed between tree growth traits—namely height, diameter, and biomass—and the critical wood quality parameter of SG, utilizing data from 140 genotypes of *Melia dubia* plantation. Genetic correlation analysis revealed that wood quality traits, particularly specific gravity, were positively influenced by the height and diameter of the trees. This underscores the importance of these traits in breeding programs aimed at improving wood quality. These traits not only contribute to enhanced wood quality but also align with the species' potential for use in environmental conservation and various industrial applications, including timber production and bioenergy.

Consequently, the findings from this study highlight the interconnectedness of growth traits and wood properties in *Melia dubia*, offering valuable insights for breeding programs.

Keywords: Biomass productivity, *Melia dubia*, Growth traits, Tree breeding, Phenotypic correlation, Specific gravity (SG)

A Selective Synthesis of 2- Aryl Benzothiazole Mediated By Tetraethylammonium Superoxide

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Abstract

Aryl-substituted benzothiazoles are one of the most important classes of heterocycles and have shown wide range of biological activities. Here we report a selective method for construction of aryl-substituted benzothiazole by using insitu generated tetraethylammonium superoxide at room temperature. The substrate undergoes oxidative cyclization to form product with excellent yields.

Keywords: A Where R=H, Ph. hiazoles, heterocycles, tetraethylammonium superoxide, oxidative cyclization.

UV-B Induced Bioactive Compounds in *Senna auriculata* Analyzed by GC-MS

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The leaves of SKC are used to treat human diseases from ancient time. Therefore, the present study was conducted to determine the effect of UV-B on the SKC by analyzing the phytochemicals present in the methanolic extract of both control and UV-B treated leaves of SKC by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

Methods: The leaf samples of both SKC and SKT were collected, dried and extracted using methanol. Screening of the methanol extract was done by GC-MS which is an important technique for the separation and identification of different phytochemicals.

Results: The methanolic leaf extract of both control and treated revealed the presence of 60 and 54 different phytochemicals, respectively. The prevailing compounds of SKC were 2-Butenethioic acid, S-[2-(acety... (area % 7.14), 2,4(1H,3H)-Pyrimidinedione, dihy... (area % 7.14) and Propane (area % 7.32), and the prevailing compounds of SKT were Ethanedicarboxamide, N-allyl-N'... (area % 14.41), 2-Butenethioic acid, S-[2-(acetyl... (area % 14.41), Propane (area % 14.41), and Desmethyldoxepin (area % 11.53). Thirty-seven phytochemicals were found to be present in both SKC and SKT and Seventeen were found to be present only in treated plant samples. Among 17 compounds, Cystamine, cis-Aconitic anhydride, Phenylacetic acid, 2-(1-adamantyl)ethyl ester, 2-Methyl-6-(5-methyl-2-thiazolin... were notable which possess biological activities.

Conclusions: It can be concluded from the present study that the UV-B radiation treatment on SKC could be effective in elevating the medicinal value or biological activity of the plant leaves.

Keywords: *Senna*, Leaf extract, Methanol, Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, Phytochemicals

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